

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

Deliverable 1.3 Gender analysis of
research and innovation
ecosystems and reports
from the local R&I

WP1- Analysis of external and internal
conditions for GEPs development and
acceptance

Version: 02

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Executive Summary

The Deliverable has three main components: the first one (chapter 2) constitutes the theoretical and policy background for the CALIPER peculiar approach based on emphasizing linking research organizations to their innovation milieus in promoting institutional change. The second one (chapter 3) reports about a dedicated study to identify good practices as well as experts' views on synergies with external stakeholders in institutional change processes for gender equality. The third one (chapter 4) presents results from the assessment that each CALIPER partner conducted on their national policy framework, the gender dimensions of their own innovation ecosystems and the mapping of existing collaborative projects/actions and their gender dimensions.

Key concepts, such as "innovation ecosystems" and "quadruple helixes approaches" and their gender components are investigated from a gender perspective, pointing out how, within Gender in Research policies and interventions, institutional change processes for gender equality are seen as in need of involving, and being grounded in, the economic sectors and society at large. It is acknowledged how new structures and units are set up to manage external relations more formally, while scientists and other similar figures are expected to assume the role of "institutional entrepreneurs" in a context which is increasingly collaborative and competitive at the same time, and this opens questions on how and to what extent institutional change for gender equality can be anchored in such changes and to what point such dynamics risk to strengthen gender inequalities further. Arguments and interpretative frameworks are offered to enable institutions engaged in institutional change processes for gender equality to interact with the existing policy trends: both approaches that leverage on the business case of gender in innovation and critical studies deconstructing gender bias in innovation conceptions and practices are reviewed, to facilitate and at the same time taking advantage of strategic windows of opportunities and critically being aware of the need for more structural/radical and long term transformation.

The selection of good practices and examples of collaborative actions for gender equality and institutional change presented in chapter 3, distils the experiences and opinions of the numerous change actors and experts involved in the study based on interviews and focus groups. Adoption of collaborative practices for gender equality is found to have numerous positive effects for RPOs and RFOs, such as capacity building, awareness-raising, but also legitimation and leverage for change. Potential obstacles and resistances are also explored, both within and outside the implementing institutions, as well as the most dynamic actors in institutional change actions. Particular attention is given to the role of feminist organisations as representatives of civil society that can contribute to gender equality collaborative practices. The collaborative actions and good practices presented in the chapter explore in a contextualized way many of the ideas and approaches proposed throughout the report.

The analysis of the external assessments conducted by partners RPOs and PFOs, shows how, in general, policies on gender equality exist in all contexts, even though the level of development and concrete application of such policies is different. In some cases, there are also specific provisions concerning the area of Higher Education and Scientific Research & Innovation. The data collected by partners in terms of STEM students, researchers, patent registrations, innovative start-up founders, etc., show - with a few exceptions - a great predominance of males in all categories. The numerous and varied partners' collaborations with external stakeholders in their own regional and national innovation ecosystems show that only in some cases the collaborating organizations have already implemented gender equality measures within their own institutions or have worked on the topic. Nevertheless, the interest in gender equality and the willingness of fostering collaborations with the partners in this area clearly emerged. The assessments' analysis and the results of the Social Network Analysis pictures a different scenario in each partner organisation. Detailed data for each partner point out how on average in RPOs the 42% of the collaborations in place are led by women, while the share of men-led collaborative actions for RFOs is higher (about 54%). The share of collaborations taking into account or focusing on gender issues, for those partners who could track them, is very low, 14% on average.

Overall, the analysis leads to the conclusion that the external promotion of gender equality will be crucial for the next project phases, starting by selecting a few strategic alliances with those entities which are already active on the topic, and, as emerges also from chapters 2 and 3, keeping a close and strong connection between the desired internal change in a given area of intervention and the synergies which will be leveraged with the respective innovation ecosystems.

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Table of contents

1	Introduction.....	11
1.1	Purpose & Scope	11
1.2	Structure of the deliverable	11
1.3	Relation to other WPs & Tasks.....	11
2	Theoretical frameworks and policy background	12
2.1	A changing landscape for increasingly interconnected EU policies on Research and Innovation... 12	
2.2	‘Innovation ecosystems’: what and how?.....	13
2.3	Changing roles for research organisations and related institutional change processes	14
2.4	Gender dimensions of the issues at stake	17
2.4.1	Feminist institutional change: positioning external factors and actors between risks and opportunities 18	
2.4.2	Gender (and bias) in innovation	20
2.5	Concluding remarks.....	24
3	Collaborative actions for gender equality and institutional change: good practices and examples 25	
3.1	Research methodology.....	25
3.2	Expert views and experiences by change agents and researchers	28
3.2.1	Positive consequences of involving external stakeholders	28
3.2.2	Potential obstacles.....	30
3.2.3	What actions can be done? With what partners?	31
3.3	Good practices: contextualized examples	39
3.3.1	RPOs: Attracting women in STEM.....	40
3.3.2	RPOs: collaborating for gender-sensitive innovation	47
3.3.3	RPOs: changing internal practices	56
3.3.4	RFOs: enhancing gender equality and inclusion	62
3.4	Concluding remarks.....	73
4	External assessment.....	74
4.1	External assessment methodology at CALIPER partner organizations	74
4.2	External assessment of UZG	77
4.2.1	The Croatian national legal and policy framework.....	77
4.2.2	The innovation ecosystem context analysis at UZG	81
4.2.3	UZG Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA	84
4.2.4	Final remarks on the external assessment of UZG	89
4.3	External assessment of STU BA.....	91
4.3.1	The Slovakian national legal and policy framework	91

4.3.2	The innovation ecosystem context analysis at STU BA	97
4.3.3	STU BA Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA.....	102
4.3.4	Final remarks on the external assessment of STU BA	108
4.4	External assessment of ULB	109
4.4.1	The Belgian national legal and policy framework.....	109
4.4.2	The innovation ecosystem context analysis at ULB.....	115
4.4.3	ULB Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA	118
4.4.4	Final remarks on the external assessment of ULB.....	124
4.5	External assessment of NTUA	125
4.5.1	The Greek national legal and policy framework.....	125
4.5.2	The innovation ecosystem context analysis at NTUA.....	131
4.5.3	NTUA Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA.....	135
4.5.4	Final remarks on the external assessment of NTUA.....	141
4.6	External assessment of YASAR	143
4.6.1	The Turkish national legal and policy framework.....	143
4.6.2	The innovation ecosystem context analysis at YASAR.....	150
4.6.3	YASAR Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA.....	153
4.6.4	Final remarks on the external assessment of YASAR.....	159
4.7	External assessment of IRB	161
4.7.1	The Spanish national legal and policy framework	161
4.7.2	The innovation ecosystem context analysis at IRB.....	169
4.7.3	IRB Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA	176
4.7.4	Final remarks on the external assessment of IRB.....	182
4.8	External assessment of UNILE	183
4.8.1	The Italian national legal and policy framework	183
4.8.2	The innovation ecosystem context analysis at UNILE	189
4.8.3	UNILE Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA.....	193
4.8.4	Final remarks on the external assessment of UNILE	197
4.9	External assessment of SRNSFG	198
4.9.1	The Georgian national legal and policy framework.....	198
4.9.2	The innovation ecosystem context analysis at SRNSFG	203
4.9.3	SRNSFG Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA.....	207
4.9.4	Final remarks on the external assessment of SRNSFG	212
4.10	External assessment of UEFISCDI	213
4.10.1	The Romanian national legal and policy framework	213

4.10.2	The UEFISCDI national and regional innovation ecosystem	219
4.10.3	UEFISCDI Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA	221
4.10.4	Final remarks on the external assessment of UEFISCDI	226
4.11	Concluding remarks on the CALIPER partners' external assessments	227
5	References (Chapters 2 and 3)	228
5.1	Books, articles, and reports.....	228
5.2	Websites.....	232
	Annex I: Semi-structured interview template	233
	Annex II: Focus group template	234
	Annex III: Survey template	236
	Annex IV: Infographics of the results of the survey	239
	Annex V: External assessment reporting template	240
	Annex VI: ULB's survey's questions.....	254

Table of Figures

Figure 1 the institutional change process lifecycle for GE	31
Figure 2: mind map of the potential actions for gender equality in scientific careers/promoting women participation	33
Figure 3 mind map of the potential actions for promoting gender balance in decision making	35
Figure 4 mind map of the potential actions for promoting gender in scientific research content	36
Figure 5_UNIZG_FER collaborations with "Academia & university" stakeholders	88
Figure 6_UNIZG-FER collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders	88
Figure 7_UNIZG-FER collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders	88
Figure 8_UNIZG-FER collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders	88
Figure 9_UNIZG-FER collaborations with schools	89
Figure 10_MTF STU BA collaborations with "Academia & University" stakeholders	107
Figure 11_MTF STU BA collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders	107
Figure 12_MTF STU BA collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders	107
Figure 13_MTF STU BA collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders	107
Figure 14_ULB collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholder	122
Figure 15_ULB collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders.....	123
Figure 165_ULB collaborations with "Academia & university" stakeholders	123
Figure 17_ECE-NTUA collaborations with "Academia & universities" stakeholders	140
Figure 18_ECE-NTUA collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders	140
Figure 19_Yasar collaborations with "Academia & universities" stakeholders	157
Figure 20_Yasar collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders	158
Figure 21_Yasar collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders	158
Figure 22_Yasar collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders	158
Figure 23_Yasar collaborations with "Schools"	158
Figure 24_IRB collaborations with "Academia & Universities" stakeholders	181
Figure 25_IRB collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders.....	181
Figure 26_IRB collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders.....	181
Figure 27_IRB collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders	181
Figure 28_IRB collaborations with "others" stakeholders	181
Figure 29_UNILE collaborations with "Academia & Universities" stakeholders	195
Figure 30_UNILE collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders	196
Figure 31_UNILE collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders	196
Figure 32_UNILE collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders	196
Figure 33_UNILE collaborations with "Schools"	196
Figure 34_SRNSFG collaborations with "Academia & universities" stakeholders	210
Figure 35_SRNSFG collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders	211
Figure 36_SRNSFG collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders	211
Figure 37_SRNSFG collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders	211

Figure 38_SRNSFG collaborations with "others"	211
Figure 39_UEFISCDI collaborations with "Academy & Universities" stakeholders	224
Figure 40_UEFISCDI collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders	225
Figure 410_UEFISCDI collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders	225
Figure 421_UEFISCDI collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders	225
Figure 43_UEFISCDI collaborations with "others"	225

Table of Tables

Table 1 List of participants to the semistructured interviews	26
Table 2 List of participants to the focus groups	27
<i>Table 3 Collaborative projects for cultural change towards gender equality funded by the "Inclusion Matters" call</i>	64
Table 4_Interactive index of CALIPER partners' external assessments	76
Table 5_Results of the context analysis conducted by UZG	83
Table 6_Results of the context analysis conducted by STU BA	101
Table 7_Results of the context analysis conducted by ULB	117
Table 8_Results of the context analysis conducted by NTUA	134
Table 9_Results of the context analysis conducted by YASAR	152
Table 10_Results of the context analysis conducted by IRB	175
Table 11 Results of the context analysis conducted by UNILE	192
Table 12_Results of the context analysis conducted by SRNSFG	206
Table 13_Results of the context analysis conducted by UEFISCDI	220

List of acronyms / abbreviations used in this document

BES	Business enterprise sector
EEA	European Education Area
EIT	European Institute of Innovation & Technology
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GE	Gender Equality
GEI	Gender Equality Index
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
HE	Higher Education
HEI	Higher Education Institution
HR	Human Resources
IT	Information Technology
MS	Member States
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PI	Principal Investigators
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
SNA	Social Network Analysis
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
STS	Science Technology and Society
SWGR	Standing Working Group on Gender in Research

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

The purpose of this document is threefold. First of all, it aims at providing the research ground of the CALIPER methodology, characterized by linking research and innovation, in terms of policy developments and theoretical approaches. Secondly, it presents a selection of good practices of implementing institutional gender equality policies leveraging on collaborations and alignment with other actors within innovation ecosystems. Finally, it displays the results of the external assessment conducted by each partner RPO/RFO, which, together with D1.2, will represent the basis for both the design of the GEPs and the set up of the CALIPER Research & Innovation Hubs (WP2).

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

After this introductory first chapter, the deliverable's Chapter 2 provides with the policy developments and theoretical approaches related to the interconnections between HE Institutions and innovation ecosystems. It also presents the theoretical background for the research questions of the qualitative study presented in Chapter 3.

Indeed, Chapter 3 presents a selection of good practices and examples of collaborative actions for gender equality and institutional change. Moreover, it reports the experiences and opinions of numerous change actors involved in the study with diverse roles: from researchers/scientists, to project managers, to consultants for gender equality.

Finally, Chapter 4 provides with the results of the external assessments carried out by each partner organisation by focusing on the national legal and policy framework on gender equality and the ecosystem context. Moreover, it provides with a mapping of the existing collaborations with external stakeholders which are in place at each partner organisation.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

D1.3 is based on D1.1 and the CALIPER assessment methodology, which the partners implemented to carry out their local studies on their legislative frameworks, the features of their external innovation ecosystems, and their external collaborations. Results from D1.3 will be used throughout WP2 for the creation of the CALIPER R&I Hubs and to involve them in the GEPs creation (T2.2 and T2.3) and further strategic actions. Results will be summarized and communicated internally and externally in each partner contexts through WP5 in tasks related to engaging with the innovation ecosystem and awareness-raising activities (T5.2 and T5.3).

2 Theoretical frameworks and policy background

2.1 A changing landscape for increasingly interconnected EU policies on Research and Innovation

The new ERA Communication published in September 2020 emphasizes the need for strengthening interlinkages between scientific research and the economy, confirming the 3% of GDP target for R&D investment for European Member States (currently, on average, 2.19%). The transfer to market of the results of scientific research is seen as one of the most important means to boost economic growth, particularly after the crisis generated by the COVID-19 pandemic. All forms of interconnections and exchange between the world of research and the economy, and society as large as well, are fostered in the form of citizens engagement/citizen science. Moreover, ERA is anticipated to be increasingly interconnected with the European Education Area to promote synergies with the three main components of the EEA and the multifold missions of universities (education, research, service to society). Changes along these lines are rooted in policy development from the last 20 years and are destined to grow in the next EU programming period. For example, the European Institute of Innovation & Technology is going to support 750 higher education institutions with funding, expertise and coaching: such action is meant to enable them to develop economic activities within their area of interest¹ also by building on policy initiatives such as the HEInnovate tool², allowing universities to self-assess the extent to which they foster innovation in their own regions.

The gender component of such policy developments has been fostered by the [ERA SWGR \(Standing Working Group on Gender in Research, former Helsinki Group\)](#) which is also linked to the [H2020 GENDERACTION project](#), providing ERA with research and policy briefs leveraging on an EU wide community of gender experts and advocates of gender equality in research.

In this framework, the well-known ERA priorities on gender in research, such as facilitating women researchers' careers in science and technology (including leadership positions) as well as integrating a gender dimension in research content, are increasingly seen to be achievable only if the entire research and innovation pipeline is addressed: in fact, for example, the above mentioned new ERA communication stresses out how intersectoral circulation of researchers (from academia to industrial R&D) shall be enhanced and gender gaps shall be tackled across the entire pipelines, with the re-focused objective of increasing the number of female researchers in STEM and favouring the transition of female researchers to entrepreneurship.

These recent directions have been accompanied during the last few years by a continued debate on expanding ERA objectives on gender equality to the private sector and on better connecting Research policies and Innovation. This is reflected in one of the recent GENDERACTION Policy Briefs (GENDERACTION, 2019),³ where a series of actions are proposed, which stresses that efforts from RPOs/RFOs to pursue gender equality in research would not be enough without commitment and clear-cut goals for the wider private sector implicated in the commercialization of research results and as potential STEM (female) researchers' employers.

¹ <https://eit.europa.eu/who-we-are/eit-glance/eit-strategy-2021-2027>

² <https://heinnovate.eu/en>

³ GENDERACTION. (2019a). The future of gender equality in European research and innovation, Briefing Paper, No. 11

These recent developments in the specific realm of Gender in Research Policies at the EU level are strengthened by the recent public commitment by the European Commission to link the access to Horizon Europe funds to those public research institutions that can demonstrate to have gender equality policies and plans in place⁴. Given the announced increasing integration between Horizon Europe, European Regional Development Funds and Erasmus+, such changes can be expected to have an impact beyond the realm of Universities and public research organisations only. Such policy trends are rooted into broader debates on the nature of knowledge production, the role of HEIs and RPOs in innovation, and the institutional reforms of the academic sector, which are the subject of the following paragraph.

Gender Action Recommendations: expand gender equality policies from research to innovation

- Stimulate the BES (Business Enterprise Sector) to take their corporate social responsibility seriously, promoting institutional changes for equality and diversity internally and addressing the gender dimension in the research and innovation solutions they develop
- Make public funds allocated to the BES contingent upon gender and diversity measures in place
- Make specific funding available for tech companies and start-ups led by women and minorities
- Make sure that funding lines for innovation at the EU and MS levels address the gender and diversity dimensions in innovation, so that gender and other forms of bias are not built into new technologies and innovations
- Promote the EU Prize for Women Innovators more widely, to strengthen the brand and awareness in the EU.
- Engage Members States to join the Commission and incentivise the unique role of women as social innovators and entrepreneurs in driving smart specialisation, by establishing funding schemes.

2.2 ‘Innovation ecosystems’: what and how?

The spatial regional and national dimension of innovation is highlighted by the widespread concept of “innovation ecosystems” and of multi-actor, co-creation-based innovation, where RPOs (Academia) have a prominent role as knowledge producers and capacities builders, and RFOs as well, as part of the Public Sector and as research funders. In CALIPER, we make use of such terminology, although it is important to raise awareness about how it is positioned in current debates and the risk of “innovation ecosystems” becoming a “buzzword”.

Innovation “ecosystem” has been in use as a concept since the last 15 years and has gradually replaced innovation “systems” in policy-oriented debates: such nature-based metaphor, according to some scholars, implies a greater emphasis on collaboration and complementarities than on competition (Gomes et al., 2018). A recent study has put forward a definition based on thorough literature review from innovation and history of economy studies. This definition tends to balance the two aspects and to consider actors, activities and artefacts, as components of innovation ecosystems, linked in **competitive** (substitution) and **complementary** (collaborative) **relations**, with “institutions”, meant as rules/regulatory frameworks:

“An innovation ecosystem is the evolving set of actors, activities, and artefacts, and the institutions and relations, including complementary and substitute relations, that are important for the innovative performance of an actor or a population of actors” (Grandstrand & Holgersson, 2019).

In terms of ecosystems’ actors, there is also a variety of conceptions:

Komorowski (2019) shaped a typology based on four types of stakeholders: (1) industry actors (companies, large enterprises, freelancers, etc.), (2) academia (universities, colleges, tech transfer offices, labs,

⁴ Recordings from the [“Get Ready: a new ERA for Equality is calling” session \(25/09/2020\)](#) are available online.

technology parks, etc.), (3) public bodies (municipalities, regional authorities, public agencies, etc.), (4) finance (banks, venture capital, business angels, etc.), and (5) other actors (media, formal and informal networks, trade organisations, cluster organisations, etc.), integrated with additional actors such as associations, chambers of commerce, research and technology organisations (RTOs), accelerators, incubators.

Since the beginning, the CALIPER project has adopted a so-called “quadruple helix” approach to identify actors within ecosystems. It considers it as a promising approach in terms of opening to a gender sensitive vision thanks to its inclusion of civil society organisations, which are typically not taken into account as players in innovation also due to biased interpretations of “innovation”.

In fact, this concept represents a gradual critical evolution of early definitions of “innovation systems”, which were initially depicted as formed by industry and academic/research organisations only, and expanded to ‘triple’ models to include governmental actors afterwards. The further opening to a fourth dimension of the helix encompassed civil society organisations/citizens/consumers-users, as a way to take into account bottom-up social dimensions and dynamics, instead of reducing innovation to economic and regulatory/governance aspects only. **The 4th Helix is often presented as playing a bridging role to connect marginalized groups/stakeholders to the other helixes and to foster a more inclusive and less biased approach to innovation policies.** Even if the Quadruple Helix represents a promising approach to avoid excluding women’s organisations from innovation milieus, it is not free from critical aspects and constraints, highlighted in the text box.

Power imbalances are to be taken into account when representing the different stakeholder groups in the Quadruple (or ‘Ntuple’) Helix models: differences between often economically ‘fragile’ third-sector’s actors (and women’s and/or gender expert organizations are often of such type) and the other ‘harder’ and way more structured components of innovation ecosystems should be observed and taken into account without giving it for granted that they operate on similar grounds.

Distinctions between voluntary entities or social entrepreneurs have also found to be useful for a more granular understanding of the fourth helix. In a similar way, beyond gender issues, the fourth helix was spotted for being as at risk of exclusionary/elitist interpretations and phenomena by other scholars as well (Carayannis & Campbell,

2010).

The debate on these aspects has further evolved into adding more helixes (the natural environment as Quintuple Helix) or by dividing the fourth helix into the voluntary sector and individual societal entrepreneurs (Penta Helix)⁵.

2.3 Changing roles for research organisations and related institutional change processes

Management models for research and knowledge production are evolving and rapidly changing along with the above-referred policy trends: universities are acknowledged increased autonomy from central

⁵ Carayannis EG, Campbell, D. (2010) Triple Helix, Quadruple Helix and Quintuple Helix and how do knowledge, innovation and the environment relate to each other? A proposed framework for a trans-disciplinary analysis of sustainable development and social ecology. *Int J Soc Ecol Sustain Dev* 1(1):41–69. Leyerdorff, L. (2012), The Triple Helix, Quadruple Helix, ..., and an N-Tuple of Helices: Explanatory Models for Analyzing the Knowledge-Based Economy? *Journal of the Knowledge Economy* volume 3, pages25–35(2012).

governments/the Public Administration sector, and research is increasingly funded on a grant-based and competitive system, both at the national and EU level (Esterman & Nokkala, 2011⁶).

In parallel, augmented harmonization efforts in HE (such as the Bologna Process and Quality Assurance mechanisms) are taking place. Such efforts are often received with criticisms within the academic world as implying a bureaucratic burden, distracting from core missions and/or forcing corporate-like models on research institutions (Whilborg & Teelken, 2014⁷). All this has been happening in a prolonged period of economic stagnation, now turning in a covid-19 generated crisis, with increasing competition among research organisations at the national and transnational levels, across Europe and beyond⁸.

An important EU level stakeholder such as European University Association (EUA) has recently investigated the role of Universities as essential nodes facilitating collaboration within their innovation ecosystems: the study builds on acknowledging a series of **paradigm shifts** in the conception of innovation and positioning the role of Universities as strategic in such a changing scenario, where research organisations and universities tend to operate in synergies with industrial players, SMEs, civil society organisations and the media at large. Ideas and practices of innovation have been shifting from linear, closed, tech-driven, individual, spontaneous, exchange and project-based paradigms to reiterative, open, systemic change-driven, interdisciplinary, systematic, co-created and based on common culture ones. In such frameworks, not only technology transfer projects, industry-funded research programmes, and research spin outs are seen as strategic assets for the University, but also science communication and citizen science activities become widespread areas where academic and research organisations invest efforts to position themselves. The regional dimension of innovation ecosystems appears to be more and more strategic, as Regions shape their so-called “smart-specialization strategies” and fund them with ERDF resources, although many innovation ecosystems are centrally initiated and supported by national governments (Komorowski, 2019⁹). Also, with the objective to attract prospective students to STEM disciplines in particular, Universities tend to collaborate more with schools to raise the interest towards their Undergraduate courses’ offer.

Research Funding Organisations are also touched by the highlighted processes. Beside funding academic research/universities, they have been and they are funding R&D in the private sector: this means that there is a familiarity from such organisations in dealing with multi-stakeholders settings, and funding both blue-skies and applied research or technology transfer/innovation projects. Research Funding organisations are increasingly active on issues related to the societal impacts of research, such as Responsible Research and Innovation, interdisciplinarity (Lyll et al. 2013; Science Europe, 2018a¹⁰), and citizen science (and 2018b)¹¹. Also, RFOs tend to be increasingly present in engagement and reach out activities with schools and educators, funding educational projects, and in setting up or playing a role in national/regional innovation Hubs.

In fact, several studies have demonstrated how in general **organisational boundaries of research institutions tend to expand and become more “porous”**: even if most of the research is funded via national or transnational public money, there is an increased need for research organisations to rely on multiple channels and external stakeholders to get resources. Not only financial resources, but also students,

⁶ Estermann, T., – Nokkala, T. – Steinel, M. (2011): University Autonomy in Europe II. The Scorecard. European University Association, Brussels.

⁷ Whilborg, M. & Teelken, K. (2014). Striving for Uniformity, Hoping for Innovation and Diversification: A Critical Review concerning the Bologna Process-Providing an Overview and Reflecting on the Criticism, Policy Futures in Education, 12, 8, pp. 1084-1100.

⁸ <https://www.eua.eu/resources/publications/927:the-impact-of-the-covid-19-crisis-on-university-funding-in-europe.html>

⁹ Komorowski (2019). INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPE: First outline of an innovation ecosystem index, SMIT_VUB on behalf of the Digital Transition Partnership.

¹⁰ Lyll, C., Bruce, A., Marsden, W., & Meagher, L. (2013). The role of funding agencies in creating interdisciplinary knowledge. *Science and Public Policy*, 40(1), 62–71. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scs121>. *Science Europe (2018a). Symposium Report. Interdisciplinarity* <https://www.scienceeurope.org/our-resources/science-europe-symposium-on-interdisciplinarity/>.

¹¹ Science Europe (2018b). Symposium Report. Interdisciplinarity. www.scienceeurope.org/our-resources/science-europe-symposium-on-interdisciplinarity/

legitimacy and reputation are at stake: such changes, it has been said, are transforming universities from “republic of scholars” to “stakeholders organisations” (Huisman & Fumasoli, 2014¹²).

In such a context, universities are seen as playing an important role precisely due to their being positioned as less dependent on markets and economic forces, and for being “responsive, adaptable, interlinked” (EUA, 2019). Indeed, Universities are often found to play a role even as leading actors in innovation ecosystems (Komorowski, 2019). Interestingly, it is stressed how **Universities need to undergo internal institutional change to be able to fully take advantage of these evolving scenarios**, including “changes in research organisation, teaching methods, personnel development, internal governance and financial incentives, as well as an expanded support service portfolio” (EUA, 2019, p.47).

In fact, such initiatives are increasingly seeking to reinforce exchanges with external stakeholders **establishing “structured relations” and “formalized interactions” with non-academic organisations** (Brostrom, Feldman & Kaulio, 2019). Although in the past years research organisations were obviously already active in commercialization of research outputs and patenting, the scope of external relations has been broadened to support networking opportunities and collaboration platforms fostering joint research projects and educational activities with economic and societal actors. **Dedicated organisational units** are set up for this purpose by Research Organisations, **mergers** are put forward and/or **external stakeholders are appointed in managing or advisory boards** to foster partnerships. It has been noted how what was happening in a spontaneous way and totally under the initiative and autonomous control by individual academics, is now implying institutional change, as it is increasingly taking place in a centralized fashion, and this is not free from tensions and criticism within research organisations themselves.

Hiring practices are also affected by institutional changes that are driven by the opening to external stakeholders. For example, different departments and **external stakeholders happen to be included in recruitment panels**, especially in technical universities, and more emphasis is placed on broader selection criteria than “research productivity”, assessing the readiness of candidates to go beyond the familiar comfort zones of the area of specialization, and coupling scientific research with an entrepreneurial spirit (EUA, 2019, Huisman & Fumasoli, 2014). The already mentioned “porosity” of the boundaries of research organisations has also other features, as mobility/double affiliation of researchers and academic staff tends to increase as it is also fostered by grant-based research funding models, and as the “casualisation” of research and teaching activities increase (ibid.). This clearly poses issues of identity/membership as **Universities and Research Organisations face increased competition in attracting talented researchers, both among each other’s and with industry**, as academia-to-industry career paths become more frequent.

In analogy between the “institutional entrepreneurs”, the “change agents” engaged in gender equality projects (and CALIPER itself) could also operate under similar dynamics when leveraging on synergies with external stakeholders to promote internal institutional change.

The role of internal actors (scientists and research managers) within research organisations has been found to be crucial together with the **impact of exogenous events in driving institutional change** (Fortune, 2013¹³): exogenous factors such as technological advancements, political/policy factors, social and cultural norms can both provide impetus to

¹² Huisman, J. and T. Fumasoli (2014). Organisational boundaries and institutional change in higher education, Paper prepared for the 27th CHER (Consortium of Higher Education Researchers) Annual Conference, Rome 8-10 September 2014.

¹³ Fortune, A. (2013). The Interaction of Embedded Actors and Exogenous Events: The Emergence of Proteomics, American International Journal of Social Science, 2, 8, pp.45-59.

institutional change and exert an ongoing influence as organisational boundaries become more and more permeable.

Studies proved that internal actors who have an interest in specific institutional arrangements can build on such exogenous factors and the new institutional logics they bring about to leverage resources, often starting from internal contradictions. Drawing on social network resources and “spanning institutional boundaries”, such so-called “**institutional entrepreneurs**”¹⁴ manage to plug into alternative logics and incorporate them into their efforts towards change. So, coalition building and access to resources come as results of the increased legitimacy they get across a wide range of internal/external stakeholders.

Beside the opportunities at stake in a changing scenarios, the increasing interconnectedness of academic and publicly funded research/knowledge production with economic/societal forces presents some **risks to be taken into account**: if the share of industry-funded research becomes predominant over publicly funded ‘curiosity-driven’ research, the risk of dismissing the more radical forms of innovation becomes high (EUA, 2019). In other terms, the societal and economic impact of research is more and more under the radar of public funders of research looking to maximize their ROI (Return on Investment) so that the way such impact is measured should avoid privileging short-term impact over the long-term pursuit of breakthrough contributions to knowledge, and policymakers should balance between the support offered to practical innovation and ‘blue skies’ research (Gunn & Mintrom 2016)¹⁵.

2.4 Gender dimensions of the issues at stake

The CALIPER approach to leverage on existing dynamics such as those illustrated in the previous paragraphs builds upon feminist debates on the current changes in academic and research governance. Several scholars have stressed how the whole set of European Higher Education policies, focused on strengthening the links between research, the economy and society, bring about loss of academic freedom and autonomy in favour of increased dependency from market forces. This, coherently with concerns on shrinking State-level investments on HE and research, is seen as shaping the agency of researchers and scientist as (often precarious) “neoliberal academic subjects” (Morrissey, 2015¹⁶) conditioned via “regimes of performance”, as they engage in practices of “normalization” (ibid.), such as self-monitoring, flexibility, and adopting new forms of auditing (Gill, 2009¹⁷).

For example, a small-scale qualitative study with PI (Principal Investigators) in social sciences from the UK, Finland, the US and Australia, all of whom are doing feminist-oriented research, described their concerns with changing university practices and the pressures experienced by researchers to secure external funding, combined with the need to satisfy funding bodies’ preferences or supposed preferences (Acker & Wagner, 2019)¹⁸. Forms of accountability that over-simplify and over-measure accomplishments were also seen as an unpleasant feature of contemporary university life, and still different **adaptation and resistances strategies**

¹⁴ Change agents for gender equality were already framed as ‘institutional entrepreneurs’ to study issues of embedded agency in institutional change, in a study of the NSF Advance project at one US University back in 1999 (Meyerson & Tompkins, *Tempered radicals as institutional changed agents: the case of advancing gender equity at the University of Michigan*, *Harvard Women’s Law Journal*, 30, 2, 303-322).

¹⁵ Gunn, A. and M. Mintrom (2016) Higher Education Policy Change in Europe: Academic Research Funding and the Impact Agenda, *European Education*, 48:4, 241-257.

¹⁶ Morrissey, J. (2015). Regimes of performance: Practices of the normalised self in the neoliberal university. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 36(4), 614–634. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01425692.2013.838515>

¹⁷ Gill, R. (2010). Breaking the Silence: The Hidden Injuries of the Neoliberal University’ in Flood, R.R. and R. Gill (eds.), *Secrecy and Silence in the Research Process: Feminist Reflections*, London: Routledge, pp.228-244.

¹⁸ Acker, S. & A. Wagner (2017). Feminist scholars working around the neoliberal university, *Gender and Education*, 31, 1, pp. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2017.1296117

were put in place by the researchers taking part to the study to cope with the ongoing changes and preserve the transformative agendas of their research programmes.

There's increasing evidence that certain features of rapidly changing research organisations and the working conditions they shape precisely due the highlighted policy trends, risk to be in sheer contrast with change strategies for gender equality, and this has to be taken into account.

On a similar line, a study based on two STEM research centres, organised in newly established flat Pls'-centred structures and highly connected with their external ecosystems, showed how both female and male participants were working under

pressure to secure external funding, and had to cope with the feeling of having to meet the preferences of funding agencies to progress in their careers. Their working experience was featured by requests for over-simplifying and over-measuring their achievements in a permanent- audit organisational culture. The authors de-constructed the researchers' narratives with a methodology grounded and inspired by Foucauldian studies. They detected one common trait of scientific subjectivities, or the way both men and women working at the institutes reflexively accounted about their experience. Such trait was the "turn to one-self" and the incorporation of individualism in one's definition, leading to self-exploitation under the illusion of freedom and autonomy. Only women featured a "gendered turn-to-oneself" that added a feeling of guiltiness and self-blame for not adhering to the prevailing image of the successful and entrepreneurial scientist. Both traits, the scholars argued, are preventing resistances and absorbing the energy to be put in changing the system and the institution by keeping the attention of individuals focused on "the self" (Vayreda et al., 2019)¹⁹

Nevertheless, it is important to underline and acknowledge how even if the new research policies and new forms of HEIs management are driven by economic forces, they have been going hand in hand with gender-oriented policy developments in research, higher education and innovation. In fact, projects and policies to mainstream gender equality in these fields at the EU level date back to 1998 already, with the aim of challenging existing power structures within research organisations to make them more gender equal and inclusive (Marx Ferree & Zippel, 2015)²⁰. In such contested terrain, the CALIPER approach prioritises the pragmatic aim of envisaging a strategic framing for the project's partners' efforts within existing discursive windows of opportunities (the entrepreneurial University/Research Organisation, active in its innovation ecosystem).

Aspects underlined by critical gender studies and gender in research projects are valuable to foster a transformative approach and make sure that the collaborative actions set in place do not end up reinforcing existing inequalities and/or remain at a superficial level of intervention .

2.4.1 Feminist institutional change: positioning external factors and actors between risks and opportunities

Feminist institutionalism has been focusing on the gender dimensions of change in institutions, mostly by looking at the institutions of democratic representation. This field of study has been featured by a variety of approaches taking into account history and path dependency, rational choice theories, organisational studies, and discursive structures. Different change dynamics have been observed, stressing how, even if

¹⁹ Vayreda, A., Conesa, E., Revelles-Benavente, B., and A. M. González Ramos (2019). Subjectivation processes and gender in a neoliberal model of science in three Spanish research centres, *Gender Work and Organization*, 26, pp. 430–447.

²⁰ Ferree, M. M., & Zippel, K. (2015). Gender Equality in the Age of Academic Capitalism: Cassandra and Pollyanna Interpret University Restructuring. *Social Politics*, 22(4), 561–584. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxv039>

institutions tend to have self-reproductive properties and resistances to change, they have moments of openness where even abrupt and rapid institutional innovations can be initiated, both thanks to endogenous and exogenous drivers encompassing structural factors and agency from institutional and external subjects. Due to the specific subject of studies, democratic institutions and public policies, “external subjects” have been framed as parties and feminist/social movements (Mackay, Kenny & Chappell, 2010)²¹.

Relying on both organisational and political studies, another stream of studies has looked at organisational change for gender equality: change has been theorised as a dynamic and contextual process where multiple interests and actors are at play to address both structural and individual levels. Collaborative aspects between gender experts and institutional change agents have been also considered as important: emphasis is placed on dialogue and negotiation to set up change processes which are flexible, participatory and based on negotiation, also to avoid the pitfalls of managerialism. (Beschop & Verloo; 2011).

In such accounts of organisational/institutional changes, the **external subjects and entities that were** taken into account were mostly **gender experts**. And still, the knowledge generated from the field (H2020 institutional change projects on gender equality and research conducted in individual RPOs) is pointing at **different opportunities** in terms of the role of external stakeholders.

- Within the GENOVATE project, Lulea University of Technology has adopted a **co-creation and collaborative approach to develop** their **Gender Equality Plan**, involving industry players and local authorities mostly (Reported in Sangiuliano, 2019.²² see also the good practice in chapter 3.3.2) with several co-managed actions and the University as provider of gender expertise to local-regional stakeholders.
- In the STAGES Project, the University of Milano has successfully implemented actions on Gender Medicine thanks to synergies with Regional Authorities and Hospitals (ibid).
- Some of the partners of the EQUAL-IST project have experienced the **role of external stakeholders as important to foster internal consensus towards GEP measures** (especially governmental and regional authorities) **and to ensure the sustainability** of some of the actions **by providing financial and human resources to activities of joint interest** (Sangiuliano, Moutzi & Vontas, 2019²³).
- INTEGER project partners experimented how briefing from influential external gender equality champions was facilitating buy-in from internal decision-makers (Bailey & Drew, 2021²⁴)
- Interventions from entities such ministries or funding bodies can work as ‘galvanizing events’ and be deliberately used to create an internal change culture, in the first “establish a sense of urgency” step of the Kotter’s Eight Steps Change model²⁵, elaborated by Bailey and Drew within their Change Management Model for Gender Equality (ibid.)

Different **risks** have also been pointed out and are important to be taken into account, when promoting collaborative efforts/synergies with external stakeholders:

- As already noted, the increasing amount of **externally funded research projects** is one of the features of the changing scenario in which Research Organisations operate. Still, it was found how it often happens that institutions in such projects are allowed to hire temporary professorships under **closed recruitment procedures**, and if the projects at stake are large, these can even result to be permanent

²¹ Mackay, F., Kenny, M. and L. Chappell (2010). New Institutionalism Through a Gender Lens: Towards a Feminist Institutionalism? *International Political Science Review* 31(5) 573–58

²² Sangiuliano, M. (2019). Planning Institutional Change for Gender Equality. Reflections from a study on GEPs implementation in Europe, in Sangiuliano, M. & A. Cortesi (eds.), *Institutional Change for Gender Equality in Research*, Edizioni Ca’ Foscari, Venezia, pp.179-234.

²³ Sangiuliano, M., Moutzi, V. and A. Vontas (2019). Sustaining and Expanding Gender Equality Plans in RPOs from Faculty to Institution Level, in Sangiuliano, M. & A. Cortesi (eds.), *Institutional Change for Gender Equality in Research*, Edizioni Ca’ Foscari, Venezia, pp.156-175.

²⁴ Bailey, J. And E. Drew (2021). *Change Management for Gender Equality*, in Drew, E. and S. Canavan, *The Gender-Sensitive University; A Contradiction in Terms?*, pp. 124-139, Abingdon, Oxon; New York, Routledge.

²⁵ Kotter, J. (2012) *Leading change*, Harvard Business Review Press, Cambridge, MA

positions, and closed procedures serve to attract partners and donors especially from private sectors. Such ‘exemption’ cases from normal procedures, **can be detrimental for gender equality** as in these circumstances what is needed from candidates is to have close ties and informal networks with decision-makers, which tend to have gender homophilic traits, especially in horizontally and vertically segregated contexts such as STEM research fields (Wullum Nielsen, 2021²⁶).

- An interesting study on two science research institutes in a Dutch University has conceptualized “systemic gender knowledge” as a crucial condition for transformational change, namely knowledge on the interaction of gender inequality processes and endogenous thinking. The focus on the organisations is considered to be the distinguishing trait of such a gender knowledge, and the phenomenon of “**scapegoating external processes**” is widespread as **exogenous causes are easily used as arguments to resist internal change** (Lansu, Bleijenbergh & Benschop, 2019²⁷). Framing the influence of societal or individual processes as interacting with organisational processes in bi-directional ways, and not as causes of the internal gender inequalities, is seen by the authors as a sign that participants to the institutional change process are developing systemic gender knowledge.
- It can be also stressed how in a time when **backsliding, conservative and regressive trends** and constructs such as the ‘anti-gender ideology’ are increasingly influencing politics and policies (Kriszan & Roggeband, 2019²⁸), also in Higher Education (starting with attacks against gender studies and gender related interventions²⁹), **external ecosystems and actors can be subject to such influence and become inhospitable contexts for synergies to promote institutional change**. Nevertheless, the selection of like-minded allies (individuals, social movements, and organisations) becomes even more important to overcome isolation and to contrast and lobby against such developments.

2.4.2 Gender (and bias) in innovation

Research institutions working on institutional change for gender equality with a collaborative approach can leverage on strategic windows of opportunities opened by their enhanced roles within broader innovation ecosystems. It is important to build on results from studies by gender scholars and practitioners on gender in innovation. This section will present key findings from selected studies, divided into two main blocks: more “mainstream” oriented ones, which typically highlight the value or “business case” of gender equality approaches to innovation, and the most critical/radical ones dissecting the inherent bias in prevailing conceptions of innovation. The former ones can be useful to identify discursive frameworks to present gender equality actions and strategies to key decision-makers and those external and internal players more sensitive to economic/efficiency-related arguments. The latter are of great importance to make sure that actions for gender equality keep transformative features.

The business/quality/excellence case of gender & innovation

A widespread set of analytical approaches and studies on gender and innovation relies on a framework which presents gender as factoring quality, and/or excellence, and/or economic value into existing innovation dynamics. Some examples are reported below:

- A recent study, soon to be published, from the ERA Standing Working Group on Gender, showed a **high empirical correlation level between the Innovation Scoreboard (IS, 2018) and the Gender Equality Index (2017)**. Countries which are high achievers in the GEI are also classified among the

²⁶ Wullum Nielsen, M. (2021). Gender in academic recruitment and selection, in Drew, E. and S. Canavan, *The Gender-Sensitive University; A Contradiction in Terms? The Gender-Sensitive University. A Contradiction in Terms?*, pp. 28-40, Abingdon, Oxon; New York, Routledge.

²⁷ Lansu, M. Bleijenbergh and Y. Benschop (2019). Seeing the system: Systemic gender knowledge to support transformational change towards gender equality in science, *Gender Work Organ.* 2019; 26:1589–1605.

²⁸ Kriszan, A. and C. Roggeband (eds.) (2019). *Gendering democratic backsliding in Central and Eastern Europe. A comparative agenda*. Centre for Policy Studies, Central European University Press.

²⁹ Redden, E. (2018). *Global attack on Gender Studies*, *Inside Higher Education*, [Online article](#) accessed 28th October 2020.

so called ‘Innovation leaders’ or ‘strong innovators’ in the IS. Vice versa, countries with a low GEI result to position among ‘moderate and ‘modest Innovators’. Most of old EU members states clustered higher and more centrally on the graph where both Indexes relatively high, contrary to newer EU Member States. In addition to higher achievements in innovation and gender equality, “Innovation leaders” and “strong innovators” have more measures for gender equality in place than moderate or modest innovators do. Most of the countries defined as “strong innovators” or “innovation leaders” offer incentives to research organisations to implement Gender Equality Plans. 4 countries among “strong innovators” (Austria, Iceland, Ireland and Norway) are the only ones with national target quotas to achieve gender balance among university professors. Only 2 countries among the 9 moderate innovators (Cyprus and Spain) have similar national measures.

- A wide range of arguments is presented as **“the innovation case” for gender equality, framing gender as functional to competitiveness in the knowledge economy**, in a book based on the experience of Swedish Industrial clusters from different sectors the steel industry, food production chain, maritime industry, development of products and services based on optic fibre, automated manufacturing and lightweight materials (Vinnova, 2011³⁰). It is highlighted how gender equality can support innovation players in competing for well-educated employees, enabling better decisions and enhancing creativity through more diverse teams; Moreover, gender equality can provide increased market traction through user-driven and gender-sensitive product and service design. Finally, embracing gender sensitiveness can shape a positive brand identity for institutions and companies increasing their reputation.
- On a similar note, **gender equality measures** are seen as **generating quality of innovation**, as real-life innovations can often result in different quality of outcomes for women and men and as socioeconomic empowerment of women has become a driver of market needs (Pollitzer and Schraudner, 2015). Shaping **gender sensitive innovation ecosystems** implies bringing the knowledge side and the market side closer together by using gender as the shared, enabling element. On one hand, the gender dimension becomes central in scientific knowledge production only if there is an understanding of sex and gender differences as dimensions of research content: as the **Gendered Innovations**³¹ project promoted by Stanford University and the European Commission has proved, applied STEM research provides an ideal ground for demonstrating the relevance of including gender as a dimension in defining research questions and determining the research methodologies. On the other hand, product design can be improved by inclusive and gender sensitive design practices, and ‘women’s buying power’ can be untapped. Finally, employers’ branding as ensuring equality in career progression, mobility and work-life balance to their employees becomes crucial in attracting and retaining the best talents, as these are features highly valued by young and educated workforce.³²
- Collaboration and co-creation across sectors can help leverage a diverse set of stakeholders to advance gender equality (IDIA, 2018³³). Such approaches are found helpful also in the framework of international development cooperation, to unpack a broad set of unconscious biases as well as to collect the needed information to nourish innovative solutions. Coordination of scientific, technical, social, and business innovations is needed to achieve gender equality outcomes, and also to leverage intellectual, financial, and social resources from all (ibid.).

Deconstructing gender biased innovation narratives and practices

³⁰ Danilda, I. & J. Granat Thorslund (2011). Innovation and Gender, Stockholm, Vinnova.

³¹ www.genderedinnovations.stanford.eu

³² Pollitzer, E. and M. Schraudner (2015). Integrating Gender Dynamics into Innovation Ecosystems, *Sociology & Anthropology*, 3, 11, pp. 617-626.

³³ The International Development Innovation Alliance (IDIA). (2018). Toward Bridging Gender Equality and Innovation. Retrieved from www.idiainnovation.org.

Another stream of investigation points at emphasizing a deconstructing role for gender and the need to reconsider the very essence of how innovation policies and practices are conceived, defined, and implemented.

Gender and feminist scholars have demonstrated how **definitions of innovation are biased**, and typically built around subjects and values that are traditionally ascribed to men as the norm. As mentioned above, changes are ongoing and shifting when it comes to the new innovation paradigms, but innovation has been traditionally (and partly is still) mostly **identified with technological and product innovation**. Considering how rooted horizontal and vertical gender segregation in STEM disciplines are, innovation's conceptions and the way innovators' are conceived have, not surprisingly, **masculine traits** (Nahlinder, Tillmar and Wigren 2015; Blake & Hanson³⁴). Furthermore, the absence of a gender perspective (and therefore the presence of a gender bias) in tech products' design has been widely demonstrated by Science Technology and Society (STS) studies (Rommes et al. 2004, Draude, 1017).³⁵

- To **overcome the predominant tech-orientation of the mainstream definitions of innovation**, critical gender and feminist scholars have started **considering the social economy, welfare and creative industries as drivers and part of innovation**, also in consideration of the fact that in these sectors women's presence is typically higher (Lindberg, Forsberg & Karlberg, 2015, Lindberg, 2018³⁶). The interconnections between tech/digital and social components of innovation are increasingly, although gradually, being taken into account beyond the gender studies community, and even within research funding programmes³⁷.
- It has also been demonstrated how **an 'exceptionalism' bias** is implied in most common definitions of (often implicitly meant as radical) innovations. On the opposite, innovations can also gradually emerge from everyday life practices and stem from behaviors different from invention, such as proceeding by mimicking, or re-interpretation, or re-configuration of already existing practices to different uses and different contexts (Lindberg & Uden, 2010)³⁸.
- Beyond advocating for more (gender) inclusive growth and innovation discourses and policies, gender scholars and practitioners have also pinpointed at the pitfalls of those (not numerous) efforts which have attempted to mainstream gender in regional or national innovation policies: for example, studies from Sweden have found out that when women's organisations were actively engaged in regional innovation milieus, the predominant discourses and expectations about their role tended to reproduce images of women as either subjects lacking skills/competences or as 'resources' to be put at work to benefit the existing system. **Including entities 'representing' excluded or marginalized subjects doesn't ensure per se that their voices will be heard and have the power to actually influence or set the agenda** or determine the use of resources made available for innovation. Also, power unbalances are at stake and influence whatever attempts to open up fora where power and access to resources are negotiated (Lindberg, Ronnblom, 2005).³⁹

³⁴ Nahlinder, J., Tillmar, M., & Wigren, C. (2015). Towards a Gender-Aware understanding of innovation: A three-dimensional route. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 7(1), 66–86. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJGE-09-2012-005>; Blake, M. K., & Hanson, S. (2005). Rethinking innovation: Context and gender. *Environment and Planning A*, 37(4), 681–701. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a3710>

³⁵ Rommes, E., Slooten, I., Oost, E., & Oudshoorn, N. (2004). Designing Inclusion: The development of ICT products to include women in the Information Society. Draude, C. (2017). *Computing Bodies. Gender Codes and Anthropomorphic Design at the Human-Computer Interface*. Springer

³⁶ Lindberg, M., Forsberg, L. and H. Karlberg (2015). Gendered social innovation. A theoretical lens for analyzing structural transformation in organisations and society. *International Journal of Social Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 472, 3 (6). Lindberg, M. (2018). *Relating inclusiveness and innovativeness in inclusive innovation*. *International Journal of Innovation and Regional Development*, Vol. 8, 2, pp.103-119.

³⁷ www.digitalsocial.eu

³⁸ Lindberg, M., & Udén, M. (2010). Women, reindeer herding and the internet: An innovative process in northern Sweden. *Innovation*, 23(2), 169–177. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13511610.2010.512441>

³⁹ Ronnblom (2005). Letting Women in? Gender Mainstreaming in Regional Policies, *NORA - Nordic Journal of Feminist and Gender Research* 13(3):164-174.

- **Intersectional approaches to gender equality** in innovation challenge binary and universalistic views and meanings attributed to gender, male/female, man/woman categories. Looking at how gender intersects with other axes of differentiation and discrimination grounds (class, different gender identities, sexual orientation, ethnicity, disability, age etc.) enables a more nuanced and view on innovation dynamics, an related multiple and interconnected exclusionary practices and inequalities. This is relevant at various levels, both when analysing and intervening on innovative entrepreneurship (Martinez Dy, Marlow & Martin, 2016),⁴⁰ inclusive technology design (Shivers- Mc Nair et al. 2019)⁴¹, integration of a gender and intersectional approach in research content more broadly (European Commission, 2020a⁴²). Even if, especially in Europe, theory on intersectionality is much more developed than implementation and operationalization in Higher Education, and Institutional change in R&I policies in particular, it is important to recall how the new EU Strategy on Gender Equality (European Commission, 2020b⁴³) has embraced an intersectional approach which was also advocated by the EU level communities of Gender experts and scholars connected to the ERA Standing Working Group on Gender in Research (GenderAction 2019⁴⁴). As far as their impacts on collaborative actions between Research Organisations and external stakeholders are concerned, these aspects are further explored in chapter 3.2.3.

It is worth concluding this introductory chapter by referring to the only study available so far, which reflects on results from an action research project that tried to address gender inequalities in innovation by experimenting with an approach blending internal organisational change and outward change. Funded by Vinnova, the Swedish Innovation Agency, the project addressed the Triple Helix Network organisation/HUB facilitating and coordinating the Food Innovation System in the Skane Region with the goal of addressing internal gender issues and at the same time “leaking” gender change outward and promoting change at the level of the food industry ecosystem (Scholten & al, 2012)⁴⁵.

Different levels of actions were pursued to bring change about internally at the organisational level and towards member organisations/companies in the ecosystem. The project’s goal and ambition was to address gender in a crosscutting way in dialogue with all stakeholders from the food system. This scope met several resistances, resulting in attempts to narrow down the scope of the proposed change process to the issue of the low representation of women in the food industry. In spite of the challenges, the researchers confirmed that the twofold approach, based on stimulating inward and outward actions and learning processes at the same time, was a productive and promising one (ibid.).

⁴⁰ Martinez Dy, A., Marlow, S. and L. Martin (2016). A Web of opportunity or the same old story? Women digital entrepreneurs and intersectionality theory, *Human Relations*, , 3, pp. 286-311.

⁴¹ Shivers-McNair, A., Gonzales, L., & Zhyvotovska, T. (2019). An Intersectional Technofeminist Framework for Community-Driven Technology Innovation. *Computers and Composition*, 51, 43–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compcop.2018.11.005>

⁴² European Commission (2020a). GENDERED INNOVATIONS 2: How Inclusive Analysis Contributes to Research and Innovation Policy Review Research and Innovation. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2020.

⁴³ European Commission. (2020b). A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/4ed128c0-5ec5-11ea-b735-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-119579348>

⁴⁴ GENDERACTION. (2019a). The future of gender equality in European research and innovation, Briefing Paper, No. 11

⁴⁵ Scholten, C., A. Hansson, K. Stridh & M. Swärdh (2012). Inward and Outward Learning Processes. Reflections on Research Methodology and Learning whilst working with a strong Innovation Network Organisation in an Innovation System, in Andersson, S., Berglund, K., Gunnarsson, E., & Sundin, E. (eds). *Promoting Innovation -Policies, practices and procedures*, pg.- 197-220. VINNOVA, Stockholm.

2.5 Concluding remarks

This Chapter has grounded the CALIPER methodology, characterized by linking research and innovation, in terms of policy developments and theoretical approaches. It highlighted the features of a changing landscape, as far as HEI and Research policies are concerned, which is leading towards greater and more structured interconnections between research organizations and their surrounding so-called innovation ecosystems. Moreover, the report analysed how, within Gender in Research policies and interventions, institutional change processes for gender equality are seen as in need of involving and being grounded in the economic sectors and society at large. (2.1).

Based on recent literature in the fields of higher education management studies and policy reports from relevant EU-level stakeholders, the present shifts towards more open innovation paradigms and views of scientific research connected to societal and economic challenges were accounted for; definitions of concepts, such as innovation ecosystems and quadruple helixes approaches and their gender components, were clarified, as they are shaping the CALIPER methodology throughout the project (2.2).

The current developments have already an impact in terms of institutional change in research organizations: new structures and units are set up to manage external relations more formally and mergers are happening in innovation milieus (third mission units, science communication centres, technology transfer and spin out offices, etc.). Scientists and other similar figures assume/are expected to assume the role of 'institutional entrepreneurs' in a context which is increasingly collaborative and competitive at the same time. It is therefore important to acknowledge risks and tensions connected to such changes, and the gender dimensions/paradoxes they feature, as some studies have started to focus on this (2.4).

Trying to balance a critical awareness of the paradoxes at stake with the willingness to open up spaces for action to favour transformative change for gender equality which can leverage on collaborative efforts with external stakeholders, the chapter also built on feminist studies on institutional change and results from other Horizon2020 sister projects. These have pinpointed how synergy processes, alliances and exogenous change factors can be featured as potential levers, generating exchanges of gender expertise, facilitating internal consensus building and buy-in towards gender equality, as well as promoting sustainability of the internal actions as well.

At the same time, risks are to be taken into account, such as scapegoating external factors not to take full responsibility towards change, and others (2.4.1).

Finally, a review of the key arguments and takeaways from gender and innovation studies and practices was proposed, covering both approaches that frame gender equality as factoring quality, and/or excellence, and/or economic value into existing innovation dynamics, and the stream of research which emphasizes a deconstructing role for gender and the need to reconsider the very essence of how innovation policies and practices are conceived, defined, and implemented (2.4.2).

This chapter constitutes the policy and theoretical background for the research questions of the qualitative study presented in Chapter 3, which was carried out with the involvement of gender experts and research institutions actively engaged in institutional change processes, and which presents a selection of good practices.

3 Collaborative actions for gender equality and institutional change: good practices and examples

3.1 Research methodology

The research for good practices and examples in collaborative actions for institutional change towards gender equality was carried out through different methods: semi-structured interviews, focus groups and a targeted survey for researchers taking part in the Young Academy of Europe (YAE) network.

The main method was that of **semi-structured interviews** with selected representatives of academic and research institutions leading collaborative projects and actions on gender equality. The interviews took around one hour each and were carried out online between August and November 2020.

The interviews flexibly followed a series of questions⁴⁶ that explored:

- The collaborative action's methods and objectives;
- The impact of the action on the institutional change process, the internal actors and dynamics;
- The features and added values of involving external stakeholders;
- The obstacles and resistances faced by the change promoters.

The content of the interviews was summarised and reported in a series of sheets (available in chapter 3.3). These sheets provide contextualised examples of institutional change activities: they present an overview of the actions, reflections on their influence on institutional change, the advantages and disadvantages of their collaborative nature, and key learning points. The names of the interviewees are listed in the following table.

Name of the collaborative action	Institution	Interviewee
Digital Girls Summer Camp	University of Modena and Reggio Emilia	Claudia Canali
Girls Project ADA	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	Line Berg
Inspira STEAM	Deusto University	Mariluz Guenaga
Gender Smart Arena	Luleå University of Technology	Paula Wennberg
Women and Spinouts	Oxford Brookes University	Simonetta Manfredi
Interdisciplinary research platforms – the Gender platform	Deusto University	María López Belloso
WeRin Erasmus+ Project	FH Münster University of Applied Science (MUAS)	Sue Rossano-Rivero
Families Share - Trento City LabCityLab	Bruno Kessler Foundation	Chiara Leonardi Gianluca Schiavo
Collaborative actions in the Gender Equality Plan	Kharkiv National University of Economics	Ganna Plekhanova Iryna Zolotaryova
The Unisalento Medical Center	University of Salento	Anna Maria Cherubini
Gender Equality actions for Research Funding Organisations	Science Foundation Ireland	Rochelle Fritch

⁴⁶ The complete list of interview questions is available as an annex (Annex I).

TeRRItoria (Horizon 2020)	Region of Central Macedonia	Eleni Pappa Kallitsa Pantazzi
Norm Critical Innovation	Vinnova	Sophia Ivarsson

Table 1 List of participants to the semistructured interviews

The second research method consisted in relying on two **focus groups** of around 1.5 hours each, which were held online, on the 2nd and on the 17th of September 2020.

The first focus group was composed of representatives of institutions taking part in CALIPER “sister projects” funded through the SwafS H2020 call of the European Commission. They were invited due to their expertise with institutional change (as implementing RPOs/RFOs, project coordinators, and gender expert organisations). The second focus group involved representatives of institutions which are part of the Communities of Practices (CoPs) promoted by the “[ACT on gender](#)” project. They were selected to reach out to a broader pool of entities engaged in institutional change processes, and because of the collaborative nature of the CoPs, in which best practices for institutional change towards gender equality are routinely shared. The questions⁴⁷ addressed:

- The potential benefits of involving actors from external innovation ecosystem in actions related to the design and/or implementation of the GEPs
- The best moment to involve external actors in the GEP implementation
- The most suitable internal actors for this kind of cooperation
- The potential actions which can support to reach the main priorities for gender equality in research
- The role of feminist organisations in the collaborations
- The role of an intersectional approach towards gender equality
- Potential resistances and obstacles for institutional change
- Potential shortcomings and unexpected effects of collaborative actions

The results of the focus groups are exposed in chapter 3.2, which follows the logic and structure of the focus groups’ list of questions. The contributions of the interviewees are anonymised – nonetheless, there are going to be references to specific practices and examples whenever valuable for the context of the report. The names of the interviewees are listed in the following table.

Focus group	Institution	Project/CoP	Interviewee
1	Vilnius University	SPEAR	Aurelija Novelskaite
1	TU Wien	GEECCO	Brigitte Ratzer
1	Cirad	Gender SMART	Cyndy van der Hyfte
1	Vienna Science and Technology Fund	GEECCO	Elizabeth Nagl
1	University of Southern Denmark SDU	SPEAR	Eva Sophia Myers
1	Yellow Window	GEECCO, SUPERA, GEARING-Roles, Gender-SMART, +	Lut Mergaert
1	CIHEAM IAM	Gender SMART	Maroun El Moujabber
1	Uppsala University	SPEAR	Minna Salminen
1	University of Rijeka	SPEAR	Sanja Bojanic
2	CNRS /Paris Créteil	Strategies CoP	Anne Sophie Godfroy
2	German Federal Environment Agency	GENERA CoP	Arn Sauer

⁴⁷ The complete list of the focus group’s questions is available as an annex (Annex II).

2	FLACSO	LAC CoP	Gloria Bonder
2	ZRC-ZASU	Alt+G CoP	Jovana Mihajlović Trbovc
2	UOC	ACT coordin.	Rachel Palmen
2	Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG)	LifeSciCoP	Sonja Reiland

Table 2 List of participants to the focus groups

Finally, the research used a **short online survey**, co-designed by Smart Venice and YAE, to further broaden the scope and investigate the presence of good and promising practices set up by researchers/scientists who are part of the Young Academy of Europe's network.

The survey targeted researchers in STEM disciplines, and especially those who are European Research Council grant holders. Beyond looking for interesting collaborative practices, it explored if and how gender is taken into consideration as a dimension in scientific research, and if and how different stakeholders are involved. The survey has been shared with the YAE network throughout August, September, and October 2020. It was eventually shared with researchers beyond the YAE network, in October, in order to receive more answers. It had a mixed approach, with qualitative and quantitative questions⁴⁸.

With a total of 31 answers, the survey gives some insight on the individual researchers' point of view on the importance of gender equality in their research, and in how and when they are including external stakeholders in their research. Given the low number of answers, the results of this survey are very limited, and hardly apt to support any kind of generalisation. Nonetheless, the survey has permitted to collect the experience of some promising young researchers.

The summary of the survey's results is available as an infographic (annex IV, accessible through [this link](#)).

Whenever relevant, their experiences and reflections of the surveyed researchers are reported throughout this document as short, in-box quotations.

⁴⁸ The complete list of the survey's questions is available as an annex (Annex III).

3.2 Expert views and experiences by change agents and researchers

In this section, the results of the focus groups are explored and discussed. As the focus groups were formed by experts and representatives of different institutions, the results reflect different experiences and points of view. Where relevant, reflections provided by some of the surveyed young researchers of the YAE network are also included in the discussion.

Key lessons learnt are highlighted throughout the text. While this section collects different experiences, opinions and reflections in a choral and often theoretical way⁴⁹, section 3.3 will instead focus on specific case studies, in which these reflections are contextualised and concretely applied.

3.2.1 Positive consequences of involving external stakeholders

The discussion of the consequences of the involvement of external stakeholders in institutional change processes led to many useful considerations. Overall, the effect of synergies and collaborations was considered widely beneficial – at all levels, and for all the quadruple helix categories.

For example, **collaborations between implementing RPOs as well as between RPOs and RFOs** were considered hugely beneficial, even when institutions are at different stages. In facts, they can be **inspiring** and lead to an **exchange of ideas** about how to tackle difficult situations, as well as about **strategies** that have been used by other organisations to overcome challenges.

“Gender equality measures are not simply a set of values but also have a specific vocabulary” reflects a participant, member of one of the ACT Communities of Practice, *“implementing organisations may need time to “translate” them in a language that is understandable to them”*. For this reason, it is important to share experiences, as some problems repeat themselves in similar contexts. The role of gender expert consultants can be central in that, as they support multiple institutions at different points of GEP implementation, and can facilitate the exchange of good practices.

Synergies can also be used as a way to acquire **legitimisation**: if peer organisations are proceeding with gender equality measures, an institution may be pushed towards achieving certain steps as well. Moreover, in cases of strong resistances minimizing the importance of gender equality themes in the institutional culture, having respected external actors acknowledging and *“taking these concerns seriously”* may be particularly persuasive.

One expert explained that, in their national context, there is a wide collaboration among all the local universities, the public authorities for higher education, and UNESCO, and this produces a **leverage effect**. In facts, *“all organisations want to be represented in an initiative if the others are”*, they explained.

Another expert stressed how collaboration with external stakeholders beyond the consortium has a **capacity building effect**. *“Moreover, it is a way of **benchmarking** the organisation against others and it helps to exercise pressure in the own organisation when there are certain actors which are opposing the process*

⁴⁹ However theoretic in nature, it should be reminded that this section reflects the opinions of institutional change actors who have specific and substantial experience in institutional change for gender equality within and beyond their organisation. Wherever possible, reference will be made to concrete examples and experiences.

towards gender equality”, experts explained. Participants also agreed on the fact that these collaborations give **visibility to the commitment** of one organisation and **enhance the accountability of the management**.

Another participant seconded that in their experience the added value of working, **formally and informally**, with external stakeholders is definitely that of sharing knowledge and **raise awareness** on gender equality. Their organisation organises “power lunches” and several other meetings at the local level with local and national NGOs, joined by different RPOs. They also added that *“when we collaborate with private stakeholders what we appreciate is their pragmatic approach. For us, the engagement of external stakeholders is important to get our own **management’s buy-in**: for example, when we started a cooperation on gender equality and innovation with a major IT company and we invited one of its managers to discuss with our Board of Directors, and this had a powerful impact”*.

The experience of a change actor showed the importance of the role played by both **formal and informal collaborations** with civil society for institutionalising gender equality policies within universities. In their university, the institutionalisation of gender equality practices was influenced by strong bottom up advocacy by researchers and, interestingly, the **student movement**. The expert also highlighted the role of feminist **journalists** as external actors, as they helped to broadcast the need, and the positive impact of, institutionalising Gender Equality in Higher Education⁵⁰.

Connections between academic and non-academic environments is important to promote institutional change, as gender expertise can also come from outside academia, from NGOs or public bodies. *“It is important to create connections between who has the expertise and who doesn’t”*, summarised a participant. On this topic, one expert reported that National Ombudpersons for gender equality are particularly useful for **knowledge sharing and learning**, especially when an RPO is at an initial stage, or policies on gender equality in the country are not in place or not well developed.

The participation of **gender experts as external stakeholders** also helps, especially as they act as **“critical friends”**⁵¹. *“Internally, it is difficult to push for change, so it is good to have this external, trusted person [who follows] the development of institutional change along the whole process, so that also administration trusts their input”*, explained a representative of an institution which took part to the H2020 LIBRA project.

External collaborations with the government and public sector are also important for **promoting policies and directives which support gender equality** “from the top-down”. Having laws, local or institutional legislations which allow for quotas, for example, can be helpful for the institutional change efforts of an organisation. **Funding organisations** can have a central role as they **can make specific gender-related requirements** (i.e. gender balance in the team, integration of gender in research). Funds can **be a strong leverage** for change.

Several examples were raised from the French context, where collaboration and synergies by gender expert RPOs take the form of **policy work, joint engagement and lobbying in policy debates**, or the form of expertise provision. In this context there are several **connections with feminist NGOs** to influence current debates and the national reform of academia and education, which was initially gender blind. In many cases, there is a **double affiliation**, as the same academics may be active members in feminist NGOs and this **facilitates collaboration** especially at the policy design level.

⁵⁰ Journalists interested in gender equality are potentially decisive civil society allies. This can also be seen in the experience of the Italian Regional Authority of Sardinia as an RFO which is collaboratively developing a GEP – please refer to the RAS case study in chapter 3.3.4.

⁵¹ To know more about the “critical friend approach” for evaluation, further information is available in Balthasar, Andreas (2011): Critical Friend Approach. Policy Evaluation Between Methodological Soundness, Practical Relevance, and Transparency of the Evaluation Process. German Policy Studies 7 (3), pp. 187-231 and Rossman, Gretchen (2000): Dialogue for Learning. Evaluator as a Critical Friend. New Directions for Evaluation no. 86

Academic expertise is sometimes requested by local governments, through the organisation of training sessions – for example on gender budgeting, gender equal childcare and work-life balance, and intersectional data collection. due to new regulations and obligations to companies as far as gender equality is concerned, the private sector also asks academics to provide knowledge and expertise on gender equality. Collaborative actions have therefore vast potential to promote gender equality change within and beyond organisations.

These reflections follow the line emerging from studies and experiences presented in chapter 2.4.1 which were more focused on setting up alliances for gender change, and further emphasize “gender expertise/knowledge” aspects as flowing in bi-directional ways, so that expertise can be looked for and/or offered by RPOs/RFOs and other actors within innovation ecosystems.

3.2.2 Potential obstacles

After having considered the positive consequences of collaborative practices, the experts were invited to reflect on potential negative aspects of collaborations. In particular, they have considered both internal obstacles and resistance and possible negative, unexpected consequences of collaborative practices. Reported results complement the risks highlighted by gender scholars and practitioners in chapter 2.4.1 and add new elements for consideration.

Internal obstacles and resistances

One issue which was highlighted is that, in some cases, even the GEP core teams tend to be **reluctant to share shortcomings and weaknesses** of their own organisations with external partners. One interviewee explained this position in this way: *“involving external players when trying to be honest and transparent can be very difficult [...] as there is always this sense of being judged, of “needing to be perfect”; it’s good to have small steps and make mistakes, if one is willing to try and get better. It is difficult with external stakeholders watching you”*.

Another line of reflections was that organisations do not always want to adapt to what other organisations are doing, the opposite of the “legitimation” concept expressed before. Arguments could be raised internally about a **difference in organisational culture and structure** (i.e. *“we have different problems than the private sector, this might be easier to achieve for companies than for public research institutions”*), this could be an obstacle and an internal resistance towards working and dialoguing with actors from different backgrounds.

A central requirement for collaborations, shared an expert, are diplomacy and communication skills by facilitators. Often “we are speaking different languages across sectors”, they warned, and therefore communication must be facilitated carefully. Feminist organisations working together with institutions, in particular, could be perceived as too conflictual by those in position of power. *“Activists usually look for radical change in discourse, not compromise, asking “too much too early”, and it may lead to backlash”*, one of the academics explained. Especially in countries where there are **conservative governments**, feminist academics are aware that **overt activism may provoke a backlash**, with conservative actors bolstered towards stronger resistance by the “provocation” of activism.

Shortcomings and unexpected effects

When asked to identify potential shortcomings or unexpected effects of collaboration with external stakeholders, the main issue which was raised was that of **competition between academia and public institutions for research and the private sector** (a dynamic also recalled in chapter 2.3). One unexpected effect of collaboration, it was explained, could be that the most talented researchers and scientists may end up leaving academia and RPOs to join the private sector, which they might find more attractive. This was recognized as an issue especially in physics and IT sector. One of the experts suggested that in general *“it is*

*important to be aware of how universities, because of the competitiveness approach to research and innovation, can be led to ‘selling themselves’ to the corporate sector”. For sustainable gender equality change in the whole innovation milieu, it is important to focus not only on “bringing more women to the STEM sector”, but also on “what happens to those women once they are working [in the private sector]”, the expert concluded. Cooperative actions should help institutional change for both the implementing RPOs and for the partners, at least in their objectives. An obstacle to this is that the external actors with whom the actions are implemented “might be very motivated to act and change their companies, but with **limited power** in their own organisations”.*

3.2.3 What actions can be done? With what partners?

When to involve external stakeholders

There are different options as to when to involve external stakeholders. Dividing the institutional change process for gender equality lifecycle in four main areas (Assessment/diagnostic, GEP design, Implementation, and Monitoring and Evaluation), the experts shared their opinion as to when it would be better to activate collaborations with external actors, and why.

There was a consensus on the fact that the best approach to external collaborations is to engage external actors **throughout the whole institutional change process**.

The majority of experts agreed that the best moment to involve external stakeholders is “as soon as possible”, during the **assessment/diagnostic stage**. Already at this stage, external actors can provide insight on best practices and help the institution set out their internal change process with stronger foundations. If the institution has little experience, external expertise can help in avoiding repeating the same “starting mistakes” as others.

During the **design** of the Gender Equality Plan, collaborations are particularly relevant because they help in setting priorities, choosing and tailoring actions.

During **implementation**, experts supported the continuation of external collaborations from a practical and a strategic point of view: on one hand, it will be possible to communicate and disseminate externally the work which is being done, improving the actions’ reach out and impact; on the other hand, the increased pressure and support from outside might re-instigate the motivation of the people in charge of the change process in the organisation. Another aspect of external collaborations during implementation promoted by experts is the use of external trainers for the formative activities related to the GEP.

Finally, external actors can be key figures during **monitoring and evaluation**, experts agreed. This is already foreseen and implemented in the way institutional change processes for gender equality are formalized by EIGE and the requirements on evaluation within the thematic Horizon Calls for Proposals. Monitoring and evaluation, they reminded, should be continuous efforts: in such cases, external stakeholders to be engaged are external gender experts as evaluators, who can take the part of the “**critical friend**” since the very beginning of the process, supporting learning through critical questioning and their outside perspective.

Figure 1 the institutional change process lifecycle for GE

Internal staff – who is easier to involve

The experts were asked which staff categories⁵², in their opinion, could be the most interested and ready to participate in a collaborative action for gender equality institutional change – and thus should be involved for a smooth implementation of such actions. They were asked to vote the most collaborative category, and to comment on the difficulties or advantages of involving each.

1. Researchers/Academics

Researchers and academics were voted as the most probably interested in gender equality actions, especially as *“they generally experience gender-based inequalities first-hand”* and may be more aware of that as an issue. For this reason, they should be involved in gender equality efforts from the very beginning. On the other hand, some experts shared how researchers may sometimes be the most difficult to convince on certain topics, such as the importance of a gender perspective in their work. In these cases, these experts agree that external, professional trainers on gender equality can be extremely valuable to convince researchers and overcome their resistances. A respondent suggested that the researchers’ interest in collaborative practices for institutional change for gender equality could be stimulated through publication incentives, or making it part of (extra) paid work. *“Pro bono work”* they explain *“could appeal just as far as it can influence policy or can be seen as a way to fight for a cause”*. Payment is expected for providing expertise, either in the form of research/consultancy work or as funded PhD grants. Such considerations appear to be in line with the literature on the role of ‘institutional entrepreneurs’ and their motivations as change agents in general, reported in chapter 2.3.

2. Middle/High Management

Experts agreed that middle and high management could be best involved and stimulated to work on gender equality change processes through peer pressure. Therefore, collaboration and exchanges with other institutions which are working on institutional change can have a central role in engaging higher management. The interviewees also reminded that middle and high management are key actors for institutional change, as their positive (or negative) approach towards gender equality influences all levels of the organisation. Internal gender equality supporters may in fact feel unwelcome in proposing activities, while resisting actors may feel validated in their positions, by neutral or negative approaches to gender equality. On the other end, a supportive management can be a strong push factor for long term and sustainable change.

3. HR staff

In a respondent’s experience, HR staff doesn’t generally have the motivation to exchange with external actors, but its involvement is essential at later stages of collaborative practices for institutional change, to ensure long term sustainability of organisational changes.

4. Administrative staff

The administrative staff was depicted, in the focus groups’ reflections, as potentially more resistant⁵³, as collaboration with external stakeholders can be seen as implying more work for them. They may be more difficult to engage, as they may not see the benefits of institutional change for aspects which do not directly involve them. At later stages, it will be important to involve them and have them cooperate to share information and experience on administrative technicalities, especially during implementation of GEPs.

One of the conclusions of the focus group was that the GEP team ideally should be composed of people from

⁵² The staff categories proposed in the focus group exercise were: “Researchers/scientists/Academic staff”; “Administrative staff”; “Human Resources staff”; “Middle to High Management”.

⁵³ It is possible that experts automatically assumed that administration entailed only generic, clerical functions: it should be noted that many key and proactive actors for external collaborations are technically administrative (tech transfer research, orientation, etc).

all of the categories above. According to the participants, which profiles should be engaged depends on the nature of the collaboration, on the kind of external stakeholders, and on the structure of the organisation.

Particular importance was finally given to the issue of providing **recognition**. Rewarding internal stakeholders' efforts by bringing added value to the institution and/or to the individual careers was considered as crucial for promoting their engagement in any kind of collaborative practice.

The three main priorities for gender in research. What collaborative actions can be promoted, and with whom

In the European [Horizon 2020 programme](#), three specific objectives have underpinned the strategy on gender equality in academia and research:

- fostering gender balance in research teams and scientific careers
- ensuring gender balance in decision-making
- integrating the gender dimension in research and innovation

The experts participating to the focus groups were asked to brainstorm, for each of these priorities, what potential actors, in their opinion and experience, are the most useful to involve in collaborative practices. They were also asked to share their knowledge and ideas on the potential collaborative practices which would contribute towards the achievement of the three main priorities for the European academic and scientific context.

Promoting women scientific careers in STEM

Figure 2: mind map of the potential actions for gender equality in scientific careers/promoting women participation

The brainstorming session on what actions could be implemented to promote women participation in research and gender equality in scientific careers promoted different ideas and good practices.

It was deemed particularly important to “start from the beginning”, promoting science as a potential career, beyond stereotypes, to young girls and children. In order to do so, the promotion of **positive role models** for girls has been identified as a fundamental good practice. Positive role models can be promoted via **mentoring** by volunteer STEM experts in elementary, middle and high schools, as in the case of Inspira STEAM (see the case study in 3.3.1), but also through media **representation**, which could reach a wider audience. One of the experts has shared how one of the projects they are following, as a member of a feminist group, is a collaboration with local artists to produce a comic book on great female scientists to be promoted around children. Further activities with artists, youth workers, and creative minds of the civil society can be useful for promoting young women's interest in science and **overcoming harmful stereotypes**. An area of action

which was addressed in multiple CALIPER survey answers was that of training on **unconscious bias**, which contributes to *“biased hiring and supervision of students”*. *“We need to encourage young girls to be more self-confident with themselves and make sure that the selection processes are fair”*, a respondent suggested.

Another area of actions which could be promoted is the one related to the **support of women’s scientific career**, especially at their first steps. Examples of such actions are **peer mentoring** initiatives, such as the one promoted by the [LIBRA Career Mentoring Compass](#). Other actions are **collaborations with career centres** and industry for career counselling, training, and support to women’s entrepreneurship; others are activities with **incubators**, business angels, and other industry actors who could support the development of **women’s start ups and spin offs** (such is the case for the research project by OBU on women and spin outs which is further analysed in this report as a case study in 3.3.2). In some cases, experts underlined, it is also a matter of **recognising women’s scientific excellence** and contributions: an example is provided by the [FemTech](#) initiative, spear-headed by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology. This initiative aims at improving women’s visibility in science, with actions such as the FEMtech's database of female experts, which collects the CV of female experts in various areas of research, and especially in STEM. One of the responses to the CALIPER survey also underline the need to recognise women’s scientific results, as *“there is a bias on how scientific results presented by women are received (e.g. taken less seriously, considered less important, etc). There is a “gender barrier” in establishing and maintaining scientific collaborations”*.

Finally, an area of intervention where collaborations can be particularly fruitful is that of **promoting exchanges with peers and with political decision makers** at the local, regional and international level. **Communities of Practice** (such as those promoted by the ACT project) can be effective ways to exchange good practices and information with other RPOs, RFOs, and experts from academia. **Gender equality professional networks** can also provide useful arenas for exchange.

Gender balance in decision making

Figure 3 mind map of the potential actions for promoting gender balance in decision making

On the topic of the promotion of gender balance in decision making, the experts had few, yet strong arguments. A general reflection was that comprehensive **change is needed on a systematic level**, and steps should be taken even “*before processes of decision making*”, for example by ensuring the access to academic careers to women in general: “*if there aren’t enough women at lower levels, there won’t be at the higher*”, synthesised a participant.

Nonetheless, there were also specific actions which were deemed as necessary to overcome the obstacles which women face in order to achieve decision making positions. The onus of such actions was mostly put on the **public authorities**, which have the most power to provide “top down solutions” such as legal requirements for gender equality in RPOs decision making bodies. Research **Funding bodies** were also identified as major actors to promote change through specific requirements and expectations in order to provide funds.

The cooperative actions which were identified by the interviewees were therefore limited, and mostly related to **awareness raising** at the institutional level, **lobbying** at the public level, and the **exchange of good practices** at all levels.

At the institutional level, it would be important to develop actions which illustrate the business case for gender balance in decision making to the higher management; an interviewee suggested that adding external female consultants in decision making bodies could also be an option. According to the experience of another focus group participant, bringing high-level decision makers who resisted gender equality in their organisation together with peers who had already started an institutional change process has helped in smoothening the opposition and lowering resistances. Multilateral talks, the exchange of best practices among institutions can therefore be actionable ways towards supporting gender equality in decision making.

The interviewees underlined the importance of the public institutions and legislative actions which lead to the formulation of legal requirements towards gender equality. These are strictly related to the national and regional contexts in which the RPOs and RFOs operate, and the experts also recognised the importance of lobbying for change at the public level. “*It is important to have the right people in public bodies, where they can influence the overall strategy*” reflects an expert, underlining the importance of having gender equality experts in public commissions, where they can connect, share ideas, and influence governmental decision making. A member of the ACT project shares that a dedicated group in the project is indeed exchanging ideas on how CoPs and academics can lobby to push for policy reforms on gender equality at the national levels.

The importance of strategic collaborations and awareness raising with public authorities is therefore recognized as fundamental, as public policies are strong push factors towards institutional change.

Gender in scientific research content

Figure 4 mind map of the potential actions for promoting gender in scientific research content

Regarding the inclusion of gender in scientific research content, the interviewees have identified two main areas of potential collaborative actions to promote institutional change, which are inextricably linked one to the other. The first is connected to a set of activities which aims at **providing best practices, exchange information and educate institutions and companies** regarding the advantages of such an approach. The second area of potential action is that of **advocacy**, especially towards funding organisations, **to develop policies** which support the integration of a gender approach in research.

Interviewees considered that **education and training** are the basis of any action which aims at promoting gender in research content. *“It is important to have workshops and trainings in the organisations in order for people to understand what this is all about and avoid misunderstandings. Training should happen in a collaborative way as well, therefore involving professionals from different organisations as well as researchers from different disciplines”*, pertinently explains one of the experts. They are seconded by another interviewee, who shared that interdisciplinarity has been central for the success of the training carried out on this topic by their own organisation.

The participants in the focus groups underlined that it is important to **educate scientists and researchers**, also by passing through **university associations** to reach out as many stakeholders as possible and “exercise more pressure”, as one expert put it. **Role models and case studies** were identified as good ways to present the issue, especially to convince members of the scientific community. **Evidence-based training** was universally recognised by the interviewees as a best practice, and the collaboration with external gender experts was recommended as well. Businesses and tech companies, as well, should be taken into consideration as potential partners for educational activities on the topic. One of the surveyed young researchers shared this approach, including gender experts in all phases of their research: *“We try to mitigate [risks] by including gender from the beginning and checking with gender experts each phase of the project.”*

Finally, the focus groups’ interviewees emphasised **the central role of policy makers and funding bodies** in setting out directives and indications on the inclusion of gender in research content for the granting of funds. For such reason, these bodies should also be sensitized towards the importance of the issue, thus promoting the adoption of legal frameworks and incentives to bind RPOs to carry out gender sensitive research. Of course, policies may not be enough – as one interviewee warned, policies *“might generate a sort of lip service attitude”* when they are not accompanied by adequate awareness raising. Therefore, education and exchange of best practices may support change agents in promoting the adoption of gender content in their organisation research work.

A note on GBV and Sexual Harassment

During the discussion in one of the focus groups, some experts raised the importance of considering the fight against gender-based violence and sexual harassment in the context of research and higher education as a priority. For this topic, they have underlined how the collaboration with civil society organisations such as

feminist NGOs is particularly important.

The next section explores why, how, and with what obstacles the interviewed change agents and experts have collaborated with feminist organisations to contribute to institutional change for gender equality.

The role of feminist organisations

The participants to the focus groups shared their experience with working with feminist organisations and women NGOs. While some respondents expressed some difficulties in involving feminist organisations in collaborative activities, others reported that these civil society actors had had a central role in providing **precious critical voices** in their institutional change processes. All interviewees expressed the value and utility of involving feminist organisations and external feminist voices, even though with some reservations.

One expert explained how when gender mainstreaming “comes from outside” as a policy requirement, implementing organisations can interpret it very formalistically and narrowly – without any feminist essence. Institutions may assume the meaning of a “gender perspective” without really engaging with it. They could just “add a woman in the project proposal”, or have essentialist interpretations and no intersectional approach. *“Including feminist activists in the collaborations can provide a much-needed critical voice”* concluded the expert.

Other interviewees reminded, though, that it **is difficult to involve feminist NGOs in issues related to Higher Education and research unless they are specialised in these issues**. One of the experts explained that in her country there already are strong alliances between feminist organisations and academia; the former, though, usually deal with poverty, gender-based violence, and other issues. *“Women’s careers in STEM are not at the forefront for them: they are already struggling with time and resources, adding it to the list of concerns to act upon would take extra effort and attention”*. Another respondent also emphasized how feminist organisations **tend to take “more activist stands, and this can be tricky”** in the context of institutional change, where resistances may be emboldened by direct challenges, as already reported above.

The same respondent also underlined, nonetheless, that in their regional context there are feminist associations with rich libraries and documentation centres with **relevant resources**, which can be an important source for students and schools, who also involve them as speakers (e.g. at teacher training days). Therefore, they suggested, the involvement of such actors would be valuable in the context of multi-stakeholder initiatives. Another expert seconded that suggestion, referring that their institution has solid collaborations an NGO with focus on Women in Science, and that the *“synergy with them can be leveraged at different levels, for all the 3 priorities: we organize exchange sessions, actions to influence policy makers, actions to increase the visibility of gender equality in the media, events to connect with civil society”*.

Finally, in one respondent’s experience, in their organisation there is an informal kind of exchange and collaboration, where literature and knowledge are shared (i.e. by funding online archives managed by the feminist organisations on the topics of scientific research of the organisation). This **informal exchange** indirectly empowers the feminist organisations’ advocacy work at the governmental level - while the respondent’s organisation, as a public institution, must keep a neutral approach to politics. Thanks to this emboldened feminist advocacy, there could be more awareness and support at the political level towards gender equality in the institution’s topic of research, which is essential for long-lasting change at the ecosystem level, beyond the institution itself.

A last observation was provided by an interviewee who observed that the involvement of feminist organisations could be a **facilitating factor for the inclusion of an intersectional approach** in the institutional

change process. Indeed, the majority of respondents shared that intersectionality is an essential approach to take into consideration – in line with the latest European policy guidelines and strategies -, but institutions may have some difficulties in actually applying it.

The role of intersectionality

Some respondents, experienced in supporting other institutions in the creation of their GEPs, were quite wary of the application of an intersectional approach in institutional efforts for gender equality. They considered that such approach *“is **still very new and challenging**, and for many organisations it is too early to work on intersectionality. Gender equality is already a big challenge”*. Others were convinced about its relevance, but admitted that their institutions did not yet have a systematic approach or a methodology to apply it. Most organisations may indeed **lack the expertise specific to intersectionality**, even when they do have some gender expertise. **External stakeholders could actually help in providing such expertise** and knowledge.

The majority of respondents enthusiastically approved the **necessity of an intersectional approach** to gender equality. One expert shared that their university is already **considering various aspects of inequality** in its GEP: *“there is always the need to involve people who have problems not only because they are women but also because they don’t speak the language, wear a hijab, etc. You need to understand that there are intersectional issues”*.

Another responder highlighted the need to deal with concerns about disability and the inclusion of people with mental and physical disabilities. The other lines of inequality which should be looked at in a GEP which cares about an intersectional approach, suggested the experts, are part-time/full-time employment, type of contract, age, hierarchies, care responsibilities and children. *“It is important to **consider different types of differentiations which are relevant for the local environment**, not only gender/race/class”* adds one of the experts, who explains: *“for example, older, higher-level professors in secure positions may not be sensitive for precarious work conditions, and do not understand the difficulties coming from being young, female, and professionally insecure. Or women in administrative staff, they have different needs for work/life balance and may be insensitive to researchers’ needs”*.

It must be noted that race/ethnic background, sexual orientation and gender identity, and religion are sensitive areas which in some legal contexts cannot be collected as data, thus hampering data collection initiatives necessary to implement an intersectional analysis. One of the experts recommended, for this issue, to nonetheless consider these aspects through the **use of the gender+ concept** in the development of GEPs and in the research content.

3.3 Good practices: contextualized examples

The following section presents a series of case studies on good practices of collaborative actions for gender equality institutional change. These serve as examples which explore the issues considered so far in a contextualized manner, thus reflecting on the experience of diverse institutions.

The definition of “good practices” that was adopted in this report is the one proposed by EIGE (available [online](#)). The practices presented in the report have all been conducted in formalized contexts, have been implemented for several years, and have been subject to thorough monitoring and impact assessment. The report does not aim to assess the practices’ cross-context transferability; nonetheless, it highlights their learning potential. Their efficiency, effectiveness, impact and sustainability were explored through desk research and semi-structured interviews with selected representatives.

The collaborative actions have been divided in four separate sections, three of which are dedicated to RPOs and one to RFOs, which deal with different macro objectives.

In the case of RPOs, the actions are categorized as “attracting women in STEM”, “collaborating for gender sensitive innovation”, and “changing internal practices”. These categories are flexible and porous, as often these practices deal with all of these objectives simultaneously. In the case of RFOs, the main objective of the action was to “enhance gender equality and inclusion” in their research and innovation milieus.

The case studies are presented through semi-standardised two-page profiles and are based on the semi-structured interviews described in the methodology in chapter 3.1.

3.3.1 RPOs: Attracting women in STEM

This section explores the experience of three different RPOs with collaborative practices. The common element of these practices is the strong link with the first priority for gender equality in science of the H2020 programme, which is that of closing the gap of the participation of women in scientific research.

The practices explored in this section are:

- **Digital Girls summer camp (University of Modena and Reggio Emilia - UNIMORE)**
- **Girl project ADA (Norwegian University of Science and Technology - NTNU)**
- **Inspira STEAM (Deusto University)**

These innovative actions contribute to the involvement of more women in STEM by fighting stereotypes, educating young girls about science and technology, proposing role models, and ensuring safe and empowering education.

The collaborative nature of such practices was described as definitely positive by all interviewees. The exchange of point of views was considered a great advantage, which nonetheless needs to be balanced by the defence of the project's idea and goals, in the Digital Summer Camp experience. The Girl project ADA's case also underlines how the collaboration has brought to plenty of publicity and awareness-raising to the whole milieu, to the point that local media now routinely ask about the female rate of enrolment of the university. Finally, the Inspira STEAM practice shows that the institution higher management has raised its interest towards gender equality as it has seen that it is taken seriously by other actors, as reported by the interviewee.

Some of the previously discussed themes which appear in the discussion of these three practices are:

- Attracting girls in STEM beyond stereotypes
- Providing role models
- Collaborating with:
 - private companies
 - public bodies
 - academic partners
 - civil society and feminist organisation
- Visibility and awareness-raising

Covid-19 challenges

Digital Girls Summer Camp

University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UniMORE) – Italy

Website

www.ragazedigitali.it

Interviewee

Claudia Canali

Main stakeholders and external actors

- University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE)
- European Women Management and Development (EWMD)
Civil society
- University of Bologna (Cesena branch)
- Modena Foundation
Banking
- Modena Municipality
Public sector
- Reggio Emilia Municipality
Public sector
- Vignola foundation
Banking
- Iren, Kohler, CIS, Club digitale
Private companies
- Regione Emilia Romagna
Public sector

Overview

The “Digital Girls summer camp” is a yearly 4 weeks-long summer camp in ICT dedicated to girls attending the third and fourth year of high school. “Digital Girls” (Ragazze Digitali) is organised by the Engineering Department of the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE) in collaboration with the European Women Management and Development association (EWMD). It has the main objective of attracting girls towards computer science through a learn-by-doing, team-based, creative approach to ICT.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

The action was designed as part of UNIMORE’s GEP implementation under the [EQUAL-IST project](#) and is, therefore, inextricably linked with the university’s internal change process. The contribution of Ragazze Digitali in terms of higher engagement of top management towards gender equality, though, was not immediate. Things have changed after some editions of the summer camp and its recognition by the EQUAL-IST project as a best practice. For example, as a result, now the gender gap is mentioned in all the university’s promotion materials; internal and external communication is more gender-sensitive; and the summer camp is endorsed and promoted as a best practice by the university itself.

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

The network of external stakeholders was built over time, and the choice of actors to include was made on a case by case basis, depending on the project’s developing needs. To this day, the network is increasing year by year. The EWMD, a civil society association, was an important partner since the beginning, as co-designer and coordinator.

During the first year, UNIMORE looked mainly for local public institutions that would give official recognition to the project with their support. The backing from public institutions also facilitated the involvement of high schools as stakeholders. High schools were essential actors as they enabled the project to reach out to young girls and to be promoted thoroughly to its target group. As the work was mostly pro bono, the project eventually needed to ensure financial sustainability. For this reason, UNIMORE started routinely looking for sponsors, which may be different every year, and encompass both public actors and private ICT companies. It also considered the replicability of the project in different cities and reached out for different universities. In particular, the University of Bologna (UNIBO) replicated the camp in Cesena (Italy), after having learned the format and having taken the responsibility to carry it out independently.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Key takeaways from the interview

- *Flexibility is important when looking for stakeholders*
- *The replicability of the action can be a form of long-term sustainability*
- *“if you trust your project, be stubborn and stick with it!”*

From the external stakeholders’ point of view, there are different reasons for this project’s relevance. For the public sector, there is the return of supporting a socially useful project which fights the lack of digital competences in the population. At the municipality level, both the council member on equal opportunities and the one on innovation and smart cities are committed to the project. Private companies also have a long-term interest in providing new generations with digital competences, which are missing in the workforce – and in some cases, they are interested in the project as part of their own internal process for enhancing gender equality. Finally, the schools wish to provide new competences and opportunities for their students. In Claudia Canali’s words, *“it is important for organisers to understand which is the specific interest of each external stakeholder and try to leverage it”*. The project also triggered further changes for gender equality in the external stakeholders and in the university’s ecosystem: other universities in the region had seminars and similar experiences inspired by Ragazze Digitali; in some of the private companies which sponsored the project, it triggered more interest and attention towards gender equality in their own workplace. The project does not explicitly apply an intersectional approach, as no other aspects were considered aside from gender. At the same time, there was an effort to reach the most disadvantaged girls and those who were less likely to join the ICT field. Participation in the camp is free.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

From the institutional change process point of view, the major difficulty was to “change minds”, to convince people in charge of communication to use gender-sensitive communication in promoting the university and its activities. The other issue was the lack of resources, for which they looked for the help of external stakeholders as sponsors. There were some minor differences in the project strategy: for example, there was a discussion as to whether involve boys as well. There was an effort in that sense in Cesena (another city in the Emilia-Romagna Region), but eventually decided to keep the camps open only to girls, as they found that *“if girls are shy or lacking in self-confidence it is better to have them work among only girls”*. Regarding the collaboration with external stakeholders, there were no major conflicts or tensions: *“Probably what helped in this was the fact that since the beginning we had a very clear idea of the camp and its activities. The idea wasn’t really negotiable”*, said Canali. For example, some ICT companies tried to impose the use of certain software for their contribution, but the team resisted that, preferring open source solutions. Finally, the Covid-19 situation has imposed some changes for the 2020 version of the camp. It was migrated online, with shorter sessions. While the girls missed the physical interaction, in this way the camp had fewer difficulties related to its logistics and attracted girls from other cities of Italy, and it was found to be successful and appreciated nonetheless.

Girl Project Ada

Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) – Norway

Overview

The Girl Project Ada is a project that aims to promote the recruitment and retainment of more women in the Faculty of Information Technology and Electrical Engineering (IE) at NTNU. It has been active since 1997, and it was born thanks to political pressure from the Norwegian government, which aimed at augmenting the number of women in STEM education. Ada promotes the university's courses to younger girls through the Technology Week (previously known as Technology Camp and Girls' Day), where high school students are invited to visit the campus. Ada also organises various academic and social events throughout the semester for the university female students; it also provides study spaces for women only. In summary, it aims at preventing women from leaving their STEM studies by providing welcoming solutions. An important aspect of the project, and the most collaborative one, is the Career Network, where companies are invited to the university and students meet them to develop professional and social contacts.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

The project was born as part of the university GEP implementation. Initially, it was a smaller project in which they provided a summer camp for girls to get to know more about the faculty before enrolling. Now there is a full-time project manager directing it, and the resources are provided in equal parts by the Faculty, specific "gender funds" budgeted by the gender equality advisor of the university, and private businesses which sponsor it. Interestingly, now are the private companies that ask the university to cooperate. Line Berg, the project manager, reported that the action "*is a success story, the university is proud and really supports it*". Some study programs have experienced a rise in girls' enrolment, which confirms the validity of the project. There is a positive culture around this action, and also male students are aware of, and support, the project activities. "*I can't say much about the first years [of the project], but now it is quite commonly accepted that gender balance is good for everyone*", said Berg, who also believes that this project has increased the attention towards gender equality in the university environment. To manage the project, she is also supported by 12 students in part-time positions from different academic years, to enhance representativity.

Website

www.ntnu.edu/girls

Interviewee

Line Berg

Main stakeholders and external actors

- Accenture, Cisco, Facebook, and many others
Businesses

- European Centre for Women and Technology (ECWT)
International partnership

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Key takeaways from the interview

- *the involvement of students in the management of the project may enhance sustainability*
- *“The conditions for a successful project are: it has to be a long-term project (3 year is short); you need not only money but motivated and enthusiastic people; support at the managerial level is very important”.*
- *Communication should be accessible for everyone – use clear examples and avoid academic jargon*

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

The collaboration is with private companies: they support the project financially, but also by organising visits to their offices, and providing role models. In return, they get access to career network gatherings, free marketing of open positions, and therefore advantages for their recruitment strategies, which often are oriented towards increasing the number of women in their staff. Berg described it as *“a win-win situation, with hands-on experience and networking for students and good profiling for companies”*. The latter usually send female staff who used to study at NTNU to act as role models, to provide motivation, inspiration, and knowledge to the girls. At the moment the university has a waiting list of companies who want to collaborate (for the symbolic fee of 3000€), and it holds some events for smaller companies and entrepreneurs who could not afford it, in order to show the students a wide diversity of options. Usually, it is the Business development departments of the companies which are involved in this project, but also Human Resources and technical staff. Some companies which collaborate with Ada have shown a developed interest in gender equality, asking for support for their own gender-sensitive communication, or by increasing the number of women in their workforce.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

While the project has not encountered major misalignments in its strategy, there have been some difficulties: once, the university has been reported to the national anti-discrimination office when it invited all girls studying mathematics to attend the technology campus for free. A high school boy filed a discrimination complaint against the university, and the national media widely reported the story. Eventually, the university has been proven not guilty, because the project will be active only as long as equality is not reached. Moreover, in this way the project received plenty of publicity, and a major boost was given by the endorsement of the university’s Board Director, who defended the project in the media. Another critique that the project has faced was that it would focus too much on women, while there are also problems related to the lack of men’s participation in health and social studies. The university has responded to this kind of critiques by showing that in their GEP there actually are other activities which relate to these issues. The project is therefore framed in a context of diverse actions which support gender equality in a concerted manner.

Inspira STEAM

Deusto University – Spain

Overview

The project started in 2015 to address the lack of young women in STEM. While the university outreach activities were routinely oriented to 16-18 years old students, the project targets children between 10 and 11 years old. Maria Luz Guenaga, one of the initiators, explained that *“at that age, girls are still confident, they know they are good at math. During secondary education self-confidence decreases”*. The selected methodology was that of group mentoring. The program consists of 6 sessions of around 1 hour, during school time and every 1-2 weeks. In each, they address obstacles to children’s interest in STEM (from a lack of knowledge to the biased image they may have about these professions because of stereotypes). It also addresses the lack of women role models: the mentors are in fact volunteer, mostly female, STEM professionals.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

The project was designed and led by individual lecturers and university researchers, and started as a bottom-up initiative. Now it is recognised as a good practice by the university: the rector, for example, would talk about it during the start of the year ceremonies. The university also contributes to part of the overall budget. The project has received visibility and dissemination, and has contributed to awareness-raising regarding the issue of the lack of women in STEM courses in the context of the Deusto University and beyond.

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

Most of the initial budget was provided by the Spanish Science and Technology Foundation (FECYT), and the rest from the university. Year by year, new institutions have joined and have contributed to the project’s funding: among them, the regional government of Basque countries, but also private businesses. In many cases, the participation of the latter is part of their CSR (corporate social responsibility) strategies, in all cases they are technology-based, and they are often part of the Basque network of science, technology and innovation. For public institutions such as regional governments, it is gender equity departments who participate, rather than educational departments. The main stakeholders who participate in the project activities are of course the schools, which participate freely, and the volunteer mentors themselves. The mentors are provided with a one-day training, and they are considered as both actors and beneficiaries of

Website

inspirasteam.net

Interviewee

Maria Luz Guenaga

Main stakeholders and external actors

- Innobasque
Basque offices for innovation
- Edenway
Consulting firm
- University of Cádiz,
University of Vigo
- Spanish Science and
Technology Foundation
(FECYT)
Funding institution

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Key takeaways from the interview

- *Mentors are actors but can also be considered beneficiaries*
- *It's important to develop ways to collect feedback and analyse the project's impact*

the project: Inspira STEAM is in fact interested in supporting the female mentors in enhancing their self-confidence, and both male and female mentors in developing their understanding of gender-related issues.

The project started in the Basque area and then it spread: the project's methodology was systematised and disseminated for other institutions to use. The project team receives feedback from all such institutions and the project's beneficiaries, and indeed *"the project is very much alive"*, in Guenaga's words. Mentoring always remained the project's methodology, but the training content changed over time; they also developed several materials, such as information kits for schools, or material for families on what are the children working on and why, and activities they can do at home. The project also developed an intranet to register information and feedback.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

There have not been many obstacles, even though the project team has registered a general lack of confidence from the mentors, who only realise their importance after the end of the project. The project has found some resistance from the schools due to its methodology: the first and last of the mentoring sessions are mixed, while the central ones are separate for boys and girls. This separation may be a problem for some schools who do not want to divide the children; in the project's perspective, though, it is important to tailor the sessions' content to the children's gender and to leave free space for girls to work among only girls. The boys, on the other hand, receive mentoring from both female and male mentors.

An important concern for the project is to measure its impact. Along the years, the project team has used satisfaction surveys, which received plenty of answers and valuable feedback. *"Children are very satisfied, but it is not enough to have their enthusiasm"* reflected Guenaga: they want to have a rigorous impact assessment (with pre-test and post-test evaluation) on various aspects: the children's attitude towards science, their self-perception, and prejudices, for example.

The main difficulty was to collect quality data, as questionnaires were too large, and not all schools would carry them out thoroughly, providing a challengingly low 10% response rate. To overcome these issues, this year the project will select 4-5 schools to carry out a personalised evaluation, with a tailored and rigorous measuring. The impact assessment will also focus on mentors, to measure the project's success in changing their own attitudes towards gender equality in science and technology.

3.3.2 RPOs: collaborating for gender-sensitive innovation

The actions described in this section focus on creativity, innovation, and collaborations with the private sector for gender equality change. The actions are:

- **Gender Smart Arena (Luleå University of Technology)**
- **Women and Spin Outs: a case for action (Oxford Brookes University - OBU)**
- **Interdisciplinary research platforms – The Gender Platform (Deusto University)**
- **WeRin Erasmus+ Project - FH Münster University of Applied Science (MUAS)**

These collaborative practices are very diverse, and each one focuses on a different aspect.

Gender Smart Arena was born out of Luleå University of Technology's GEP implementation, and focuses on providing education on gender equality issues to private businesses and municipalities of the region.

The Women and Spin Outs project is a collaborative research to identify the factors that influence the (lack of) participation of women scientists and engineers in spin out processes and entrepreneurial activities to commercialise research and innovation.

The Gender Platform is an informal structure which was developed in the Deusto university, as one of its interdisciplinary research platforms, which focuses on collaborative activities for gender equality and acts as a driver for institutional change.

WeRin is an Erasmus+ project which ambition is to make entrepreneurship education and support programmes more inclusive for women, through a multi-stakeholder consortium and the involvement of a wide range of external stakeholders.

The collaborative nature of these practices was deemed essential to promote innovation within and beyond the institution. The project manager of the Gender Smart Arena, who has a long experience in gender equality actions, underlined how a multi-stakeholder collaboration raises the creativity and innovation capacity of the projects. For the Oxford Brookes' research project, the interviewee maintained that universities have an important role in improving society – and through this project they have *“now put gender diversity very much into the agenda of the local economy”*. For the Deusto University, collaborations have helped in promoting institutional change to the point that it is now participating in the GEARING ROLES European project and developing their GEP. For the WeRin project the collaboration is considered essential for achieving a change in the entrepreneurial ecosystem with a gender perspective.

Some of the previously discussed themes which appear in the discussion of these three practices are:

- Collaborating with:
 - private companies
 - public bodies
 - academic partners
 - civil society and feminist organisation
- Providing gender expertise to external actors
- Engendering the local innovation ecosystem
- Promoting women's careers in STEM
- Promoting women entrepreneurs
- Promoting institutional internal change
- Promoting the involvement of internal actors
- Recognising valuable bottom-up practices

Website

<https://www.ltu.se/centres/cdt/Projekt/Pagande-projekt/Gender-Smart-Arena-1.184061?l=en>

Interviewee

Paula Wennberg

Main stakeholders and external actors

- Arctic Group, BnearIT, Explizit, Lunet, Metria and Tornado IT companies

- Luleå municipality, Piteå municipality and Skellefteå municipality Public bodies

Gender Smart Arena

Luleå University of Technology– Sweden

Overview

The goals of the Gender Smart Arena project are two: to enhance the collaboration between the university and the surrounding society in the region and to contribute to inclusive growth and employment through gender equality and gender mainstreaming. The coordinator of the project is the Luleå University of Technology and the partners are 6 IT companies and 3 municipalities. The project is funded by the EU Regional Development Fund and co-funded by regions and municipalities. The project carried out more than 40 activities per year: it held seminars, workshops and meetings about different topics, in particular about the development of business and organisational models to support companies and municipalities to become more inclusive and more competitive. Now the project is in its conclusive, dissemination phase. One of the outcomes of the project was a digital **tool** designed for organisations on how to integrate the gender perspective in their processes, structure and routines. The tool defines 6 areas: customer value, capital, collaboration, competences, communication and culture. The tool was built on 12 practical scenarios and can be used to raise awareness on gender equality and on how it can contribute to organisations' processes. The project focused on gender issues since the IT sector is male-dominated: *“since we don't have the research capacity to work also on other [intersectional] issues we had to narrow down our goals and objectives”* states Paula Wennberg, the project manager. However, the project also takes ethnicity and age into account together with gender issues.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

At a government level, in Sweden, all universities and colleges have to gender mainstream their internal operations: Gender Smart Arena contributed to the LTU strategy on gender equality and mainstreaming according to the national policies they had to comply with. The project was at the intersection of the research centre's own interest in enhancing gender equality, the IT sector willingness to include more diversity, national policies for gender equality and inclusion, among which the requirement for the gender perspective to be taken into consideration to receive funding from external funding bodies. The leading entity of the project is the Centre for distance spanning technology of the [Luleå University](#); moreover, all 6 departments of the university are involved in the project, together with the External Funding Office, and the project research team is strongly interdisciplinary. The steering group of the

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Key takeaways from the interview

- *it is never only about one project, it is the sum of many projects and interventions that make a difference.*
- *“We always find it easy to work with recruitment, decision making and communication. These are the three components we offer support to”.*

project is composed by six members, among which many representatives of the higher levels of management of the university: one representative each for the university’s vice chancellors, deans, and heads of department, the CEO of the research centre, a representative of the companies and a representative of the municipalities. The impact of the collaboration at the university level was mostly raising the knowledge and attention on gender equality: *“I think it's only positive because when you get the attention from organisations and companies outside of the university, it also raises the interest of people inside the university”*, said Wennberg.

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

The university had already developed many and long collaborative relationships with companies in their region, and found it easy to include them in the action. The action also included municipalities, making it more innovative, as they were trying to integrate the gender perspective in their operations but lacked concrete examples, and were attracted towards the project. As a further form of reach out, the project has carried out annual conferences, where it presented its work and received input from experts. In these events, many women organisations were involved.

The project impact seems to be positive: all the companies have raised their knowledge about gender equality issues, and their awareness on the need to take action. Some have reached gender parity in their human resources, for example, and most of them are interested in using the tool developed within the project. *“we usually work with people who are motivated to take part to these interventions, who want to gain something and want to raise the gender knowledge, who are willing to come on board”* explains Wennberg.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

The main challenge for the project was time: the project involved 25 people from different areas and that made time management difficult. For bigger companies (at least 40 employees) it would be easier to have the time and resources to allocate to the project, while for the smaller organisations and the university itself that was the main issue. As the project was not focused on enticing collaborations by raising awareness, but rather attracted organisations already interested in the area of diversity and gender equality, a major obstacle was the limited number of people with expertise in gender equality in the external stakeholders. For example, in one of the companies there was only one person who had deeper knowledge on gender equality issues, and when this person left the job, there was no one else to take her place as referent for the project. As Wennberg simply put it, *“if there is only one person who deals with this issue within an organisation, it makes it harder”*.

Women and Spinouts: a case for action

Oxford Brookes University (OBU) – United Kingdom

Website

www.brookes.ac.uk/women-and-spinouts

Interviewee

Simonetta Manfredi

Main stakeholders and external actors

- OxLep
Funding organisation
- Advanced Oxford
business umbrella
organisation
- Elsevier
Publisher
- UKRI
Funding organisation

Overview

The project is carried out by the Centre for Diversity Policy Research and Practice at Oxford Brookes University, and it is funded by the Engineering Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) under their “Inclusion Matters” programme. The expected results of the project concern the production of new research, and knowledge, providing evidence on the fact that women are underrepresented in university spinout companies, and that spinouts founded by women tend to be smaller and to get fewer investments. The aim is to inform institutions to promote change. Findings of the research will be used for developing interventions, tools, practical actions that institutions can adopt in order to increase the number of women in this area. Regarding intersectionality, *“There was the intention [to take an intersectional approach], but it is incredibly difficult to do it [...] because you depend on individuals to disclose the other diversities and in some cases are quite sensitive”*, elucidated Simonetta Manfredi, the founding director of the Centre for Diversity Policy Research and Practice and project director. However, they managed to explore the issue of ethnicity and age. For example, they found that women scientists are often stereotyped with regard to their appearance and what they should wear. Gender stereotypes may intersect with racial profiling and this may exacerbate the issue for women scientists from an ethnic minority background.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

The Women and Spinouts project wasn’t an outcome of an internal change process. It resulted from a research idea by its researchers, and it did not stem from an internal assessment of OBU, since the university is not underrepresented in terms of women in spinouts - it only has one spin out and it is led by a woman. However, the project fits into a tradition of actions towards gender equality and institutional change. OBU has an Athena SWAN bronze status, and it was one of the very first universities in the 90s to establish an Equal Opportunity Action Group, which looked at gender but also at diversity more in general. Some examples of gender equality actions were the improvement of the maternity leave and the introduction of childcare facilities on campus. As far as this specific project is concerned, it has started to make an impact, since it coincides with a renewed interest of the university in spinouts activities and commercialization of research. *“Since there is this renewed interest of the university, we are actually thinking about developing new policies and practices in these areas. Moreover, staff development initiatives based on*

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Key takeaways from the interview

- *The policy framework can be a strong influencing factor for the success of gender equality initiatives*
- *Innovation and entrepreneurship are areas which still have plenty of potential for gender equality actions*
- *A gender-blind understanding of meritocracy is a strong aspect of resistances*

some of the outputs of this project have started to be integrated in the mainstream” confirmed Manfredi.

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

One of the partners is OxLep, a government funding agency, which has the role of supporting the development of the local economy. Advanced Oxford is a business umbrella organisation representing Oxfordshire companies in the area of science and technology. Elsevier is a publisher which often works in the field of gender and research; other partners are UKRI (Research and Innovation Funding Councils), the Royal Academy of Engineers, the Royal Society, the European Space Agency, Taylor Vinters (corporate lawyers). All such partners have an advisor role, and researchers from the University of Oxford also contribute to the research.

The main responsibility of the external stakeholders is to provide guidance and advice to ensure that the project has an impact at the regional and national level. They collaborated from the very beginning through regular meetings and exchanges, but did not participate in the initial project design. All stakeholders have an interest in the project as there is a strong drive in the UK industrial strategy on the topic of equality and diversity. Oxfordshire is a very successful region for innovation companies, but there is also a shortage of high-level skills. The underrepresentation of women has an implication for the economy: *“if women researchers in science can't achieve their full potential, then there is a loss from the economic point of view, in terms of missing out on all that potential talent”* explained Manfredi.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

The project has not met internal resistances as it fits very well with the current effort of the university in terms of gender equality. Rather, there have been **interesting complementarities**, since members of the team have different backgrounds. There may be resistances from external actors, though. The **investor community** has a central role for the success of spinouts, yet it is a male-dominated community which often has a gender-blind consideration of merit and does not engage in conversations on the matter, resisting the conceptualization of merit as gendered and biased. Having to face new resistances can be a source of frustration for gender equality change actors: *“Having worked on gender equality for a long time [...] it is a moving target. After having achieved some balance in certain areas, the focus shifts, and now it is on innovation and entrepreneurship. And these areas are highly male-dominated. It's like going back of 20 years, you feel like you will never win sometimes”* reflects Manfredi. *“But I am very pleased that we have gone into this particular area, this work is very much needed”*, she concluded.

Interdisciplinary research platforms – The Gender Platform

Deusto University – Spain

Overview

The University of Deusto has five flexible and informal interdisciplinary research platforms, that reunite experts, researchers, and external stakeholders from different fields around specific topics. These 5 interdisciplinary platforms are: Ageing and wellbeing; Be Creative-Cultural and Creative Industries and Cities; Gender Equality; Social Justice and Inclusion; and Strengthening participation. The platforms on gender equality and social justice strive to work from an intersectionality perspective, considering gender, race, age, and social class and their intersections as sources of inequality. Within the platforms there are “core groups” where researchers work on different initiatives. These core groups usually form around a research proposal, or at least around [current research topics](#) that are aligned with the European research agenda. In some cases, the outputs are small-scale collaborative activities with few stakeholders (for example, working with local high schools on projects against online sexual harassment) and in other cases there are proposals for European projects with wider, international consortia. For each activity, the platforms always try to have at least a publication so that they can have an output of the work that they have been doing.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

The interdisciplinary platforms emerged as bottom-up informal mechanisms, fostered by the [International Research Project Office \(IRPO\)](#) from 2010. These eventually were integrated into the top-down strategy by the Vice-Rector for Research and Transfer in 2014. “*When the university noticed that these were relevant initiatives to foster interdisciplinary research, they embraced and scaled up these interdisciplinary platforms*” explained María López Belloso, researcher and key promoter of the Gender Platform. The University of Deusto is currently working on its Gender Equality Plan, supported by the European H2020 [GEARING ROLES](#), of which Belloso is the project general manager. The gender interdisciplinary platform is central in the development of the Gender Equality Plan and in mainstreaming a gender perspective in research. The platform compels research groups and other initiatives in order to embed the gender dimension in the different research topics. At the moment, this support is on a case by case basis, but one action the GEP is already implementing is the creation of two pilot groups to develop guidelines to mainstream gender in teaching and research actions.

Website

<https://www.deusto.es/cs/Satellite/deustoresearch/en/home/interdisciplinary-research-platforms-1/gender-1/the-university-of-deusto>

Interviewee

María López Belloso

Main stakeholders and external actors

Depend on the projects. Private organisations, other RPOs, civil society and public bodies are all potential stakeholders.

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Key takeaways from the interview

- *Three elements to overcome resistances: “a lot of kindness, a lot of patience, and a lot of cakes. And yes, many, many hours of interaction with different stakeholders, bringing people together. The informal setting is also very important to foster trust among stakeholders”.*

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

The platforms are one important mechanism to channel the 6i-strategy⁵⁴, a process of change for the internationalisation of research and innovation. This is based on three dimensions that start with an ‘i’; international, interdisciplinary, and intersectoral, that pave the way for collaborative endeavours in conjunction with the three long term vision looking dimensions: innovative, impactful and inclusive. All platforms are highly collaborative, with local, regional, and international stakeholders to achieve [higher social impact](#). The gender equality platform, for example, collaborates with the [Basque Institute for women-Emakunde](#), various women associations, and different NGOs working on gender-related issues.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

When working with interdisciplinary groups, in general, it may be difficult to find the balance between collaboration and competition, between sharing ideas and protecting intellectual property rights. Moreover, there is a tension with conventional recognition systems that are still mainly anchored in disciplinary evaluation panels. In Deusto’s case, another challenge is that the Basque and national governments only acknowledge the research groups. The platforms are overcoming the resistances and fears of the principal investigators who were worried that the platforms would harm the groups. *“It is not the case”* reassures Belloso, *“because it is a way to join forces, it is a win-win. If we produce a publication, it will be an output for both groups, we are joining forces, we are not splitting forces”*. Moreover, it is not always easy to find a common language to foster communication between very diverse areas of research.

When implementing external collaborations, the intersectional approach was often challenged by civil society partners, in the gender equality platform experience – especially in those cases in which a non-binary understanding of gender was proposed. When trying to foster institutional change from a gender perspective, *“resistances are everywhere”* sighed Belloso. The research field was particularly problematic, because they noticed that if people, who are interested in gender, are not engaged in research, then the gender lens is simply missing, and it is not still a priority to include it. This results on “gender fatigue” of the people involved: *“We are all the time relying on the commitment and in the compromise of these researchers who are trying to foster this institutional change and this process of gender mainstreaming in research, but it’s also sometimes a problem because they are tired working in different projects, at different levels. This is something that always comes “on top of”, so it is tiring. But I think it is working well nonetheless”* concludes Belloso.

⁵⁴ See also Caro-Gonzalez, A., 2019. [The “6i research model”](#): evolution of an innovative institutional STI policy framework at the university of Deusto. Fteval Journal for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation vol. 48, pp.105-113 and <http://6i-strategy.com/>

Website

<https://werinproject.eu/>

Interviewee

Sue Rossano-Rivero

Main stakeholders and external actors

In the consortium, there is one non-academic partner per each university. Apart from students and women entrepreneurs also regional experts and professionals were involved.

Key takeaways from the interview

- A change in the ecosystem of entrepreneurship is fundamental. For this reason, “collaborating and engaging external stakeholders” is important.

WeRin (Erasmus+ project)

FH Münster University of Applied Science (MUAS)

Overview

FH Münster University of Applied Science (MUAS) is the coordinator of the WeRin project (Women Entrepreneurs in Regional Inclusive Entrepreneurial Ecosystems) whose ambition is to make entrepreneurship education and support programmes more inclusive for women. The main target of the project are female students in HE, female entrepreneurs and aspiring female entrepreneurs, (even if there is an acknowledgement that it would be important to open the project to other women targets as well). The project is founded on the paradox “*in the global entrepreneurs monitor it is visible that the more women are educated the less they are entrepreneurs*”. The project main activities concern: 1) an extensive research on entrepreneurship to have an overview of entrepreneurial education and support programs with a gender perspective; 2) identification of best practices across Europe; 3) re-design of entrepreneurship programs to make them more inclusive for women; 4) creation of long term regional alliances. At the time the interview was conducted, the project was in its initial phase. The FH Münster University of Applied Science started with the engagement of the target beneficiaries of the project in the frame of ad hoc organized workshops, which were highly participated and had the positive result that participating women started considering becoming entrepreneurs. The main outcome of the workshops was the shared awareness that there is something missing from the side of educational providers, since the offer and the communication were not considered appealing for the women side.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

The synergy among the partner institutions is great, all of them introducing workshops and discussions in their own organizations to implement actions. The interviewee also reported an high involvement of rectors of partner organizations in the project activities, resulting in some cases in an higher engagement towards GE by the top management. All partner organizations have a GEP.

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

Being the change of the entrepreneurial ecosystem with a gender perspective, one of the main purposes of the project, the collaboration with external stakeholders was considered as fundamental. Also, the consortium is multi-stakeholder, since at the time of the proposal preparation each academic partner had to involve a non-academic one. The collaboration in the design phase was high: even non-academic

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partners took part in the co-creation and no particular resistance emerged. One of the first project activities, consisting in conducting interviews for the extensive research, involved around 65-70 stakeholders per partner. Students and women entrepreneurs were among the interviewees, together with regional experts and professors. Among the other stakeholders to be involved in the other project activities, trainers, mentors, coaches, professional associations, representatives of bank, networks and associations working on entrepreneurship were mentioned. The interviewee explained that collaborative actions are interesting because *“other organizations have the same perception of the phenomenon (i.e. the non presence of women in the entrepreneurial field) but they are not fully aware of it and how it operates”*.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

Since the topic is very sensitive, some misalignments emerged. In particular, sometimes consortium’s researchers had different positions on the same topic. In addition, some tensions arose between academics and non-academics of the consortium, this was due to the fact that practitioners and researchers tend to have different perspectives on the different topics. Such tensions were all solved through discussion. However, these misalignments were perceived by the interviewee as an added value of the project. Divergences also emerged with external stakeholders due to disagreements in the way the project is creating tools.

3.3.3 RPOs: changing internal practices

The collaborative actions discussed in this section are linked to institutional change for gender equality from a specific perspective (work-life balance, for the first) and from a general perspective (as it describes the collaborative activities included in the GEP, for the second).

The two collaborative actions are:

- **Trento CityLab – Families Share (Fondazione Bruno Kessler - FBK)**
- **Collaborative actions in the Gender Equality Plan (Kharkiv National University of Economics - KhNUE)**
- **The Unisalento Medical Center – University of Salento**

The Fondazione Bruno Kessler has piloted an innovative action for collaborative childcare practices and for enhancing the work-life balance of its researchers. This pilot action was undertaken in the context of the [Families Share](#) project.

The Kharkiv National University of Economics presents a wide-ranging set of collaborative activities in its GEP design and implementation. It is now at its sustainability phase and it is exploring ways to contribute to sustainable cultural change in their innovation milieu. Their GEP creation and implementation were carried out in the context of the [EQUAL-IST](#) project.

The University of Salento implemented a Medical Center in collaboration with the local medical entity.

Both as a thematically-specific pilot action and as a generalised effort towards gender equality change, the actions have been highly collaborative. In the case of the Trento CityLab, the existence of an already strong collaboration with regional actors has permitted the success of the action, even if hampered by the Covid-19 pandemic and consequent lockdown. For the Kharkiv University GEP, one of the most valuable aspects of the collaborative nature of the GEP has been that of receiving training by external, gender expert actors, which has helped in overcoming internal resistances. For the Unisalento Medical Center the project was jointly developed by Unisalento and the ASL of Lecce.

Some of the previously encountered themes which appear in the discussion of these three practices are:

- Collaborating with:
 - private companies
 - public bodies
 - academic partners
 - civil society and feminist organisation
- Promoting institutional internal change
- Receiving training from external gender experts
- Covid-19 challenges
- Collaborating with civil society and feminist organisations
- Promoting internal synergies and involving internal actors
- Recognising valuable bottom-up practices

Trento CityLab – Families Share

Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) – Italy

Website

families-share.eu/project-citylabs/trento/

Interviewees

Chiara Leonardi
Gianluca Schiavo

Main stakeholders and external actors

- Progetto 92 ,Spazio 100, Kaleidoscopio

Local cooperatives

- Trento Family District

- University of Trento

Overview

The Trento CityLab was a pilot action which involved the Italian RPO Fondazione Bruno Kessler in the context of the EU project Families Share. FBK is part of the Trento Family Audit district, a regional multi-stakeholder agreement for the exchange of best practices on work-life balance. The Family Audit district participated to Families Share with the creation of the Trento CityLab: the action supported collaborative, bottom-up and creative practices of community childcare to support the work-life balance of employees of different organisations. For instance, FBK organised afternoon labs, summer camps and pre-school camps for the employees' children. These activities were managed with the contribution of the employees themselves, as part of their working schedule, and supported by external professional educators. The process was preceded by a need assessment and a co-design of the model, in order to tailor the actions to the target group's needs.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

FBK had previously taken part to the EU project FESTA and had implemented some institutional changes activities for gender equality; nonetheless, it does not yet have a comprehensive, structural GEP, and the Families Share project is one of a series of activities to enhance work-life balance. FBK holds the European Human Resources Strategy for researchers (HRS4R) certification and the Family Audit certifications, a regional certification for work life balance and human resources. The Families Share activities were included in an overall plan connected to the retention of such certifications. The main impact of the project is related to the promotion of childcare activities which resulted in a higher participation of parents/researchers in this kind of events, and stronger involvement of male parents in the care work. According to the HR manager, the Families Share activities contribute to innovate the welfare perspective of FBK in the direction of the "proximity welfare", that is a welfare that wants to be more participative and closer to the employees' needs by activating services not only in the FBK's premises but also in the areas where the employees live.

The top management was very satisfied with the Families Share project: their engagement had grown since they the researchers started to have some tangible results to show, and the entire HR department is now more aware of this type of actions. Moreover, the administrative and HR staff now see a strong connection between the quality of research and

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Key takeaways from the interview

- *Strong collaboration with the HR department is essential for the success of this kind of activities within RPOs*
- *Sharing resources and knowledge between organisations can provide new opportunities for innovating practices on work-life balance*
- *Researchers' active participation in collaborative childcare initiatives can be supported with the involvement of professional educators*

innovative childcare solutions for better worklife balance. Therefore, they are motivated to push this kind of actions, and to promote them even outside the organisation. They also would like to set up a stronger and more continuous collaboration with researchers and create a sort of “living lab”, where the HR department further collaborates with the research department.

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

The main external stakeholders were social cooperatives, the University of Trento, and some small private companies, all actors of the regional ecosystem and parts of the Trento Family Audit district. The social cooperatives supported the concrete implementation of the activities, and Trento University was also active in the organisation. The private companies were instead mostly provided with the Families Share model to tailor to their own context. The head of the research group of FBK tried also to connect with Confindustria, a national business association, but due to the Covid-19 emergency the negotiations stopped. The cooperatives have shown an interest in applying the model within their own context, as they see it as a potential way to enrich their competencies, and also the University of Trento is interested in formulating a tailored version of the project for itself.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

The Covid-19 pandemic was a major obstacle for the project implementation and undermined the public fostering of the activities. The main difficulties were related to the organisation of activities during the summer of 2020, when regional bodies would not provide support to this kind of innovative activities; most of the social cooperatives also decided to do just traditional activities for that uncertain period. The pandemic also prevented the researchers to further involve other company contexts as initially planned, such as health agencies.

A structural difficulty for the functioning of the activities was related to the high turnover of people working at the HR department, which delayed the project implementation as negotiations needed to readjust whenever the key actors would leave the institutions. Moreover, such type of initiatives require a strong collaboration between the HR department and researchers, and a key for sustainability would be that of integrating the action into the HR policies, allocating human and financial resources, to guarantee future community engagement. Indeed, the activities carried out within the Families Share project will become part of a long term plan.

Collaborative actions in the Gender Equality Plan

Kharkiv National University of Economics (KhNUE) – Ukraine

Website

equal-ist.eu/gep-in-simon-kuznets-kharkiv-national-university-ukraine/

Interviewees

Ganna Plekhanova
Iryna Zolotaryova

Main stakeholders and external actors

- IT cluster associations (70+ IT companies)
- Network of University gender centres
- NGOs – es. “Actual Woman”, which works on women empowerment
- Corporate Social responsibility (CSR) centre
- Technological Pact” association of technology organisations

Overview

At the Kharkiv National University of Economics, the GEP design, implementation and evaluation were highly cooperative and were financed through the EQUAL-IST H2020 project. The GEP implementation included a series of events for students and staff inside the university which also involved feminist organisations: there were events, workshops, and trainings to promote gender equality and a feminist approach to equality. Numerous gender experts were contacted to provide their input, and IT professionals were also invited as role models. The GEP also promoted a gender-sensitive language in the institution, and they developed collaboratively, with local NGOs, a methodology to evaluate all teaching material throughout the plan’s implementation. The GEP also included a feasibility study for a childcare facility in the university, which involved other universities’ gender centres by carrying out on-site visits. Finally, the GEP has integrated a specific prize for girls in the programming championship it routinely holds in collaboration with local creative hubs and school teachers. The GEP also included actions aimed at the creation of a University Gender Equality commission.

There is not an entirely intersectional approach, but the university is working for the promotion of a “culture of tolerance”, in general terms. In particular, there are many students from foreign countries and that is considered a “burning issue”.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

During the project there have been two implementation phases which are now complete, and the GEP is currently at its sustainability phase. A Sustainability Plan was drafted and approved, and was focused on 3 main pillars:

- continuing events to recruit more girls to IT and promoted their careers in the field
- carrying out gender-disaggregated data collection and statistics at all levels within the university
- support the Gender Equality Commission of the University

An important objective of the sustainability plan is to promote a change of culture also in the university’s milieu. Some change has already visibly happened: for example, the Trade Union representative at the university

Key takeaways from the interview

- *The university can learn from external stakeholders and absorb their expertise, and then give back to their milieus by sharing their learnings*
- *External stakeholders can help overcome internal resistances as they show that the issue of gender equality is taken seriously*

routinely holds a speech on gender equality and its importance during the university's mid-terms meetings.

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

Internally, the university had created an Equal-IST team, which was the main responsible for the GEP design and implementation. The external actors involved were mostly IT clusters, feminist NGOs, the Gender Museum, and the Network of University gender centres (e.g. the gender centre of the Sumy State University). In some cases, there were "multiple affiliations", as members of the internal Equal-IST team were also members of the NGOs.

There was no contribution from external Ukrainian partners in the design of the GEP, as it was built on the outcomes of a participatory audit process and subsequent internal discussions at different levels. The external stakeholders were mostly involved in implementation, while evaluation was double: it was managed internally by the EQUAL-IST team, and externally by the project's gender expert (Yellow Window Maxime Forest). Thinking about advantages and disadvantages of this approach, Ganna Plekhanova and Iryna Zolotaryova, members of the EQUAL-IST team, reflect on how sometimes the external stakeholders did not have much interest in the "internal stuff" and dynamics of the university. Nonetheless, they were a great source of expertise, information, and human capital – for example when they sent role models for young girls interested in STEM. Moreover, an external opinion gave a strong push for change – in several occasions the team had the impression that external experts made a difference in convincing the top management. It also helped to have collaborative actions as it was a confirmation that these issues are being taken seriously by the community.

On their side, emboldened by these collaborations, the local IT cluster now works more on the involvement of women in IT, also carrying out activities involving secondary level school girls independently. The CSR centre also carries out activities to promote the inclusion of girls in STEM.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

There weren't misalignments with external stakeholders, possibly because their role has primarily been that of experts and advisors. In facts, "*their expertise has shown to the university management that these issues have a common understanding and are considered important by various actors - it was not "just us"*" reflect Plekhanova and Zolotaryova. When first discussing gender equality initiatives at the University Council, the team had encountered some resistances by colleagues, who feared that these would be initiatives "just for women" of which the university had not any need. They eventually changed their mind when they understood, for example, that work-life balance for women and men was an issue intrinsic to gender equality.

UniSalento medical centre

University of Salento - Italy

Website

<https://www.unisalento.it/strutture/presidio-medico>

Interviewee

Annamaria Cherubini

Main stakeholders and external actors

- ASL Lecce
- Lecce municipality

Overview

The medical centre of the University of Salento (Unisalento) was inaugurated in February 2023, with the idea of promoting equality and the construction of a serene work and study environment.

The centre provides an easy way for students and the university staff to access professional first medical assistance and psychological support, including in cases of harassment and GBV.

One of the most requested service is the counselling desk, that is managed by university psychologists, but that works with the ASL psychological service (Regional Public Health Services).

Also it also serves as place for the vaccination campaigns.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

The Center is part of the institution's GEP and represents an absolute novelty for the University. Therefore, it changed the internal equilibrium by adding a service that was inexistent before: students, professors and staff can now access to primary health care with greater easiness.

Responsible of the center are the vice-rector for equal opportunities of Unisalento, a doctor and a psychologist.

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

The Center relies on a collaboration between Unisalento and the local medical entity (ASL- Regional Public Health Services) of the city of Lecce. While Unisalento provided with adapted properly furnished Campus' spaces , while the ALS Lecce provides with personnel: a daily nurse, a daily generic doctor and weekly gynaecologists and andrologists.

Together with ASL also jointly informative events are organized.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

No resistance was found. However, it is worth mentioning that finding suitable spaces and furnishing them required time and much organisational work.

Another problematic was the Covid19 pandemic as the project had to be stopped for a long time.

3.3.4 RFOs: enhancing gender equality and inclusion

This section deals with collaborative practices in the context of RFOs. The main focus⁵⁵ is on the experience of Science Foundation Ireland and its efforts towards enhancing gender equality and inclusion in its regional and national milieu.

The sheet presented in this section are:

- **Gender Equality actions for Research Funding Organisations (Science Foundation Ireland)**
- **Region of Central Macedonia – TeRRItoria (Horizon 2020 project)**
- **Norm Critical Innovation - Vinnova**

Another experience which is discussed in this section is that of the Regional Authority of Sardinia (Italy). This institution's strategy for implementing their GEP has been strongly collaborative, and was presented to the public through the [SUPERA project's series of webinars on RFOs experiences](#) with gender equality and institutional change.

Finally, a good practice which was identified for RFOs is that of formulating specific calls which focus on gender equality and inclusion. In particular, in this section there will be a short overview of the "Inclusion Matters" call by the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council. This call has funded highly collaborative projects (such as the "Women and Spin Outs" project which was presented in this report) which can also be of inspiration for RPOs which wish to integrate their internal institutional change with external collaborative actions. As the description of this call and the overview of the funded projects act as a bridge between RPOs and RFOs experiences with collaborative practices, they are discussed first.

Some of the previously encountered themes which will be discussed in these case studies are:

- Funding as a leverage for gender equality change
- Collaborating with:
 - public bodies
 - academic partners
 - civil society and feminist organisation
- Promoting intersectionality

The Inclusion Matters call

Website: epsrc.ukri.org/funding/edi-at-epsrc/inclusion-matters/

This call by the Engineering and Physical Science Research Council (EPSRC) of 2018 funded a total of 11 projects throughout the United Kingdom. The call aimed to promote long-term cultural change regarding diversity, inclusion, and gender equality in the context of engineering and physical science.

The call announced up to £5 million in funding for proposals lasting up to 24 months, with no limit in dimension of the proposal. The funding was to be awarded to UK universities or groups of universities.

EPSRC organized two workshops to enable the participants "to discuss challenges that might be addressed through applications to the call, participate in a questions and answers session with EPSRC staff, and explore

⁵⁵ In this section, only the Science Foundation Ireland experience has a dedicated sheet because it was part of the one-on-one structured interviews presented in the methodology. The other two experiences were identified through desk-based research and the participation to the SUPERA project webinar on the matter.

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any potential synergies across institution” ([EPSRC, 2017](#)). The projects were expected to “research, innovate, and embed”: research had to be collaborative, engaging with diverse stakeholders; innovation was directed towards trying new methods for institutional change; and results could be embedded in already existing efforts towards inclusive change. Impact had to be ensured beyond the immediate institution involved, therefore actions for collaboration, dissemination, and awareness-raising were required for the obtainment of the grants.

The awarded projects are highly collaborative and include universities and a variety of project partners including learned societies and the private sector.

While only the Women and Spin Outs project has been examined in detail in this report, the following selected projects are to be considered interesting practices for RPOs as well. These projects can be useful as examples for research institutions concerned with cultural change towards more inclusive physical science and technology beyond (exclusively) gender equality matters. For this reason, the link to the website of each project has been provided, together with the short introduction which can be found in the [ESPCR call's website](#).

GE projects ⁵⁶ funded through the “Inclusion matters” call (EPSRC)		
Queen's University of Belfast	Inclusion Really Does Matter: Improving Reactions to Gender Equality Initiatives Amongst Academics in Engineering and Physical Sciences	link
<p>Programme Director Dr Ioana Latu: “Although gender equality initiatives (GEIs) exist in EPS Schools across the UK, progress is painfully slow. Our vision is that in order to change EPS diversity and inclusion culture sustainably and rapidly, we need to understand academics’ potentially negative or indifferent attitudes towards GEIs. To address this challenge, we will first conduct research to understand how attitudes towards GEIs can be improved. In a second phase, based on this evidence-based knowledge, we will build and test training tools aimed at improving the reception of GEIs. These tools will be designed both for the general EPS academic population (Virtual Reality toolkits, multimedia tools, apps) and for Athena SWAN committees. We will ensure broad impact by sharing our empirical findings and trainings tools nationally, across EPS departments, and internationally with the scientific community.”</p>		
University of Glasgow	VisNET: Virtual in situ networking to reinvent the rules of international collaborations and reduce gender differences in academic careers	link
<p>Programme Director Dr Caroline Gauchotte-Lindsay: “VisNET (virtual in situ networking), led by the University of Glasgow, aims to understand and fundamentally transform the mechanisms of networking and collaboration in academia. Focusing on the dominant leak in the academic pipeline, the post-doctoral researcher to lecturer transition, we seek to remove the disadvantage women experience in building their international reputation, an important measure of academic esteem. Ultimately, our outcomes will help to redress the under-representation of women in STEM academia by establishing equality of opportunity when competing for research funding and academic promotion. [...] The growth in technologies enabling remote working offers us an exciting opportunity to redefine networking practices by making them less reliant on frequent travel. Working with the Universities of Edinburgh and Strathclyde and multinational companies including Microsoft, Nokia and Thales, we will develop, integrate and advocate for new strategies that remove gender bias and allow women to influence the new ‘rules’, thus challenging the persistence of ‘male networks’.”</p>		
University of Strathclyde	STEM Equals	link
<p>Programme Director Professor Rebecca J Lunn: “Through an intersectional lens, the project will examine working cultures within higher education and industry, including systemic inequalities faced by women and LGBT staff in STEM disciplines. [...] The STEM Equals project aims to develop initiatives that will improve equality and diversity for female and LGBT staff across science and engineering. Project activities include the introduction of free flexible crèche facilities for staff to attend key research meetings whilst on-leave, the delivery of workshops with key industry partners to disseminate successful activities and share best practice, and the setting up of public and private social media platforms for women and for LGBT staff within the University. [...] The STEM Equals project also aims to deliver a fresh approach to University management, decades-old practice within UK Universities has led to a severe lack of senior women. [...] Research on the STEM Equals Project will ‘peel-back’ over time the CVs of volunteer</p>		

⁵⁶ Only the funded projects with a clear focus on gender equality have been included. The Women and Spinouts project by the Oxford Brookes University has already been widely discussed in this report.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

senior female academics from across the UK, to define excellence at each stage in their career, and hence to develop alternative promotion criteria, more appropriate to academics that have had periods of leave or part-time working.”

GE projects funded through the “Inclusion matters” call (EPSRC)

Durham University **Northern Power: Making Engineering and Physical Sciences Research a Domain for All in the North of England** [link](#)

PI Professor Claire Warwick: “Engineering and physical sciences contribute hundreds of billions of pounds to the UK economy each year. Yet, women, disabled people, LGBT+, and people from Black and Minority Ethnic backgrounds are poorly represented across the sector. Research reveals that women engineers and physical scientists are underrepresented in all grades, but especially in senior academic posts. [...] Unequal opportunities, paucity of role models from under-represented groups, and a lack of understanding among senior leaders as to the barriers these groups face are among a number of factors that cause, compound, and sustain this problem. Durham University, along with eight other Universities and six industrial organisations, are embarking on a new and exciting research project to tackle this issue in the North of England.”

University of Lincoln **Advanced Strategic Platform for Inclusive Research Environments (ASPIRE)** [link](#)

Programme Director Professor Belinda J Colston: “To build a more inclusive research environment, we need a step-change in our approach to equality, diversity and inclusion (ED&I). Our focus needs to shift towards long-term behavioural and culture change, and away from blunt staff statistics (eg numbers of female professors) and performance metrics. ASPIRE offers an innovative, evidence-based approach to deepen our efforts in improving ED&I. It will provide a web-based toolkit to harness best practice across the sector, enable measurement and monitoring of the implementation of inclusion initiatives across institutions, link implementation with markers of culture change and provide recommendations for scaling across the sector. It will develop a new and more comprehensive impact framework to extend simple metrics-based evaluation and measure genuine and meaningful changes in ED&I attitude and behaviour. Through extensive partnership, working and drawing on experiences across both the research and non-research communities, ASPIRE will accelerate sector-wide implementation of effective ED&I practice.”

University of Birmingham **Challenging Different Forms of Bias in Physical Sciences and Engineering Research** [Link](#)

Programme Director Professor Jon Rowe: “Female academics in STEM subjects, and those from minority groups, often struggle to progress in their careers. However, the underlying causes of this are not fully understood, and attempts to address the problem have had limited success. We will conduct experiments on how the quality and value of an academic’s work are assessed in promotion processes and the Research Excellence Framework (REF), to pin down where the sources of bias arise. [...] We will trial some innovative interventions such as ‘reverse mentoring’ (for example, getting a junior black woman to coach a senior male professor), and establishing ‘ghostbusters’ – empowering academics to challenge senior-level decisions, with appropriate backing and support. [...] We will share best practice between our partner organisations, and look forward to working with the NHS trust, which has similar career progression issues. We will roll out the lessons learned via our national networks; develop training programmes; and feed into the equality and diversity agenda for the upcoming REF.”

University of Bath **Reimagining Recruitment** [Link](#)

Programme Director Dr Tim Rogers: “The vision of our proposal is to begin a process of culture change, by giving scientists the opportunity to undo damaging stereotypes and learn the benefits of working as part of a more diverse team. To achieve this, we will run a programme of innovative ‘incubator’ events - academic research workshops in which senior academics work alongside early-career scientists, in an accessible and inclusive environment to tackle cutting-edge research problems. At the same time, we will conduct an interlinked programme of psychology research into the experiences of early-career researchers in STEM subjects and the efficacy of alternative recruitment strategies in academia. This will enable the development and communication of evidence-based policy to drive cultural change in science and technology higher education and more widely.”

Table 3 Collaborative projects for cultural change towards gender equality funded by the “Inclusion Matters” call

Gender Equality actions for Research Funding Organisations

Science Foundation Ireland⁵⁷ – Ireland

Overview

In Ireland there was an important legal case which represented the starting point of the national dialogue on gender equality. An academic reported being discriminated against for being a woman and not getting a promotion. After this case was upheld, the Higher Educational Authority started a review process with an expert panel, by collecting data from each institution and best practice internationally. The results of this review process was the first national action plan, in which funding would be dependent on obtaining the Athena SWAN certification and in which very specific criteria were given to funders including the need to adopt a Gender Equality Plan. The SFI - like the other Irish funders - has a GEP which goes from 2016 till 2020.

In the GEP, specific targets were set also internally at the SFI level. In particular, the GEP has a specific KPI on the % of female award holders in the institution's portfolio. They started with 24% and now they are at 28% with the goal (KPI) of reaching 30% by the end of 2020.

SFI has meetings with the other funders and the HEA in order to align the different policies on gender equality and to move towards intersectionality. The working group is adopting a leading agency approach: a member of the group will design a policy and the others will look at it and decide if and how to implement it. For instance, last year SFI implemented the maternity leave for PhD students, and now other funders nationally will look at implementing this. SFI carries out meetings with research offices, working with them explaining what they are doing and getting feedback. They are also starting to incentivize institutions to adopt the Dora principles (for instance, last year they implemented a Dora compliant narrative style CV to move towards recognizing more types of achievements). They are at the beginning of the process, but SFI is discussing with institutions about how Dora might change the way they are doing promotions and hiring people internally. SFI has also adapted the template of resume for researchers that the Royal Society has elaborated, and is recommending other institutions to also adopt the Dora principles. In this way *"instead of just looking at research outputs in the sense of publications, and grants we moved to the assessment of researchers into their contributions to society and the economy, their contributions to individuals and collaborations and their contributions to the research community in a broader sense"* explains Rochelle Fritch,

Website
sfi.ie

Interviewee
Rochelle Fritch

Main stakeholders and external actors

- Ireland-based RPOs
- Ireland-based and international RFOs
- Higher Educational Authority
- ForGEN CoP
Community of Practice

⁵⁷ It should be noted that in this section on SFI's experience some observations and reflections derive from its lead role in the FORGEN CoP rather than SFI's own positions.

Key takeaways from the interview

• *Funders play a critical role in addressing gender equality in the R&I landscape as equal opportunities in research are linked to success rates and participation in research funding.*

• *Research Funding Organisations Gender Equality Plans primary focus on increasing gender equality/balance in their funded portfolio of awards and the gender dimension in research content.*

• *A national approach, liaising with national stakeholders, enhances the impact of gender equality plans in RFOs.*

Research Policy Scientific Programme Manager. SFI does not currently have any data about the effects of Covid on their research community, therefore they have been working with the different research offices and with the vice presidents of research innovation on the effects of Covid on equality, diversity, inclusion within the institutions. They are supposed to launch a survey to all the researchers in Ireland.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

The SFI's GEP has three pillars:

- I pillar: improving the number of women funded within the SFI portfolio and providing support to funded researchers
- II pillar: education and public engagement
- III pillar: gender and research content

At the moment, the GEP does not deal with gender equality *within the organisation itself* (i.e. n° women in leadership), there is not a specific strategy. Therefore, the SFI now in the process of revising the GEP.

The national action plan uses a limited language, it does not provide indications on what RFOs should include in their GEPs, therefore RFOs are not expected to embed gender equality in their own organisation. The focus, for RFOs, arguably should stay on whose research is funded and the presence of gender dimension in content, as highlighted in the aims and objectives of RFOs embedding gender equality promoted by the European Commission. However, *“without embedding gender equality in the leadership and decision making you'll always have resistances”*, reflected Fritch, who also lamented a lack of open data on the actual levels gender equality in research funding organisations internationally.

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

SFI is not working with stakeholders for designing their gender equality plan. As a funding organisation, SFI requires institutions to adopt GEPs and supports them with pointing out available resources, such as those related to the Athena SWAN process. There is not a template of a GEP for funders, since funders have different needs compared to RPOs. For this reason, SFI is leading the Funding Organisations for Gender Equality (FORGEN) CoP, an international Community of Practice (CoP) supported by the Horizon 2020 project ACT. Through the CoP, they are exchanging ideas and good practices about what do they need for themselves as RFOs to promote and enhance gender equality.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

As previously stated, the main difficulty shortcoming of the SFI GEP is the lack of provisions for internal change, which are not expected by law but which are growingly considered as important. The lack of templates, and comparative information, for RPOs gender equality change, is also an obstacle to the development of a more complete GEP.

TeRRItoria (Horizon 2020 project) Region of Central Macedonia

Region of Central Macedonia

Overview

The Region of Central Macedonia developed its GEP in the frame of the *TeRRItoria* project (Horizon2020), whose aim was to position regions and local authorities as places for science governance, education, public engagement ethics and open access. The project embedded the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (*RRI*) to enable local and regional governance actors to deal with the challenges brought by globalisation. The Region of Centra Macedonia was the only partner to adopt a GEP as measure to trigger institutional change. To develop the GEP, a living lab methodology was employed to explore the existing situation, to design the plan and to test and evaluate the proposed methods. *“The gender equality plan also includes an informative and indicative guide on monitoring indicators and gender-sensitive evaluation criteria and evaluative questions”* as it is explained on TeRRItoria website.

An intersectional approach was implemented, since apart from gender, the discussions involved also discrimination on culture-related reasons, sexual orientation and disability. *“Facing these issues will create an inclusive environment where all groups will feel safe. It is crucial to focus not only on women’s issues, but on everybody’s issues”*.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

A Gender Equality Committee, under the Human Resources department, was created to ensure the GEP sustainability also after the end of the project. The Committee work was expected to be completely dedicated to the implementation of the GEP.

The Department created an open dialogue with the national body General Secretariat for Family Policy and Gender Equality.

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

Around 30-35 stakeholders’ representatives of about 10-15 institutions (universities, industrial actors, representatives of NGOs/CSOs) participated in the process of GEP’s design. The main advantage of involving different stakeholders in the process consisted in the rich variety of ideas and experiences that they shared. The interviewees reported that the presence of universities that had already an internal GEP, was particularly helpful since they shared their experiences and difficulties. In other cases, stakeholders were in the process of developing their own GEPs. All stakeholders participated actively.

Website

<https://territoriaproject.eu/central-macedonia-regions-gender-equality-plan/>

Interviewees

Eleni Pappa

Kallitsa Pantazzi

Main stakeholders and external actors

30-35 stakeholders belonging to about 10-15 universities, industries, civil society organizations and NGOs involved in the GEP’s design

Key takeaways from the interview

- The advantage of the involvement of different stakeholders relied on the mutual learning and sharing of ideas and experiences.
- An intersectional perspective was adopted in order to create an inclusive environment where all groups feel safe.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Because of the Covid19 pandemic, all activities took place online and online tools were used. This fostered the participation of stakeholders living in other cities.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

Overall, the GEP's design process ran smoothly and the collaboration with stakeholders was not problematic. However, some misalignments took place; in particular, they were related to the language used and its discrimination potential.

It is worth to highlight that there was not gender balance in the collaboration, because the majority of participants were women, as *“men think that gender equality is a women's issue, so they leave women to talk about it alone”*.

Website

<https://www.vinnova.se/en>

Interviewee

Sophia Ivarsson

Main stakeholders and external actors

Academia, gender researchers, gender and diversity experts working in civil society or NGOs and public sector

Key takeaways from the interview

- being an RFO, it is possible to actually influence the system
- having a norm-critical approach means looking for intersectional and innovative project that question the understanding and definitions of innovation itself

Norm Critical Innovation - Vinnova

Vinnova: Sweden's Innovation Agency

Overview

The Norm Critical Innovation programme was born in 2001, along with Vinnova's creation, since working on gender equality was part of its mission as a RFO. At the beginning, the program was more about launching calls targeting existing partnership to encourage them working with gender equality internally. Then the focus slightly changed to actual innovation processes questioning the understanding and definitions of innovation and the mission of funding innovation itself. Together with this change, also a more intersectional approach came to life. In 2015 the government asked them to mainstream gender in the whole Vinnova's core process, by submitting an Action Plan and report progresses. They started to launch the programme "Norm Critical Innovation" which after 2019 was integrated in the other strategic programmes, so no more ad hoc calls were launched. Within the Norm Critical Innovation Programme, around 150 specific innovation projects were financed.

Positioning the action within an internal change process

In the beginning of the project the labs were called "Gender Labs", but then since they were willing to have a more intersectional approach the name was changed into "Norm-critical Labs". However, the theme of intersectionality was seen as something too "academic" and there were some resistances. With the project developing and results showing, the approach changed and the opening to intersectionality was implemented. Setting up and managing a funding scheme on these issues and with an intersectional approach is in itself a notable internal change measure for a Research Funding Organization.

Features and added value of the multi-stakeholder collaboration

All the projects financed by the Norm Critical Innovation Programme implied a multi-stakeholder collaboration. At least two stakeholders coming from academia, civil society organizations, private sector and public sector collaborated in such projects. In particular, the interviewee observed at the beginning of the programme a very high representation of stakeholders from academia, civil society and public sector, but a very low participation of the private sector. However, in the last years the participation of the private sector increased, and it is now around the 30%.

As concerns Vinnova's programmes, the collaboration with external stakeholders is mainly in terms of providing support to organizations on how to integrate gender in innovation. Indeed, stakeholders are willing to gain a better gender balance and intersectional approach.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Internal and external evaluators are involved in the evaluation of the programmes of Gender in Innovation.

Also, in Vinnova's gender and diversity programme many women and feminist organizations received funding.

The interviewee also explained that the multi-stakeholder collaboration triggered internal change. Indeed, the work done with gender mainstreaming and Norm Critical Innovation were perceived internally as leading examples of how to achieve internal change. She reported seeing a link between internal change and collaboration with external ecosystem. Being a funding agency, Vinnova can push stakeholders in the wanted direction.

Obstacles, misalignments, and shortcomings

Some misalignments emerged from the multi-stakeholder involvement. In particular, feminist and intersectional organizations perceived that being *feminist and/or intersectional* was enough to obtain fundings, missing that it was fundamental to work on innovation as well, even redefining its terms, and this caused tensions. This manifested for example in cases when applicants did not receive funding and the evaluation letter mentioned that they should advance in their work with gender equality in innovation or the project team was not balanced.

Finally, some tensions involved the media, which showed resistances and criticisms towards the decisions of the public sector to evolve part of tax money to gender inclusive and intersectional projects ("*public sector and tax money should not go to these stupid kind of things*"). In any case,

\ Vinnova did not let these critics stop it to proceed with its work.

supera

Supporting the Promotion of Equality
in Research and Academia

The Regional Authority of Sardinia's experience

Speaker: Tara Marini

Website: <https://www.superaproject.eu/tag/ras/>

During the SUPERA webinar, Tara Marini described the experience of the Regional Authority of Sardinia (RAS) in developing their GEP. The input for the creation of their GEP was the regional law for research and innovation, the **regional law 7 of 2007** which allocated 180 million euros over 12 years for the development of human capital, internationalization and rationalization of the regional research system, and funding for basic and applied research. Yet, the regional law made no reference to gender issues.

Why a GEP: 34% projects submitted and funded by RAS are by women, 66% by men. This is similar to the male/female ratio of researchers in Sardinia.

Why a system of alliances: It provides larger basis of consensus; it ensures more awareness; it is key for effectiveness of the GEP; it permits the GEP to be spread as a good practice; it enables technical collaboration with other actors; it gives opportunities for the GEP development through international exchanges; it creates many “guardians” for the effectiveness of the GEP, as it makes the institution responsible in front of many actors. The system of alliances is developed on **three levels**:

The first is the **Regional Programming Centre** level, with internal stakeholders and two gender hubs. It also involves a feminist journalism organisation, research centres, the University of Cagliari, the local commission for equal opportunities, and other institutional actors. The activities carried out by the core SUPERA Team - composed by Massimo Carboni, Simona Corongiu, Antonio Mura and Tara Marini- at this level are the drafting of the GEP, making reference to the GEP in all official documents, constant awareness-raising through formal and informal meetings.

The second level is that of the whole regional administration, which involves other funding offices in the region. The activities at this level are the inclusion of the GEP principles in the regional development plan; interaction with the counsellor and commission Equal opportunities; offering training to other branches; interaction with the agencies involved in the call for tenders.

The **third level is that outside of the regional administration**, which involves external stakeholders, such as the evaluation group for the Regional Law 7; the regional research council; the SUPERA project's consortium; the authorities managing the ERDF (European Regional development funds); regional authorities for equal opportunities.

Hints and suggestions from this experience:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

- develop shared goals in the alliance, find common grounds and interests and use them as a glue;
- carry out continuous communication in all phases of the project, keep the interest high;
- informal dialogue is as important as the formal;
- give value to the diversity, both in the team and in the stakeholders;
- give the highest empowerment to each member, give the chance to make the difference;
- give always feedback to allies – if you can't accept a suggestion, say why;
- share activities and responsibilities;
- give visibility and recognition to the members of the alliance;
- don't be limited to what was planned, consider windows of opportunity;
- formal documents open doors, pave the way, and create the culture for change.

3.4 Concluding remarks

This chapter has presented a selection of good practices and examples of collaborative actions for gender equality and institutional change. Moreover, it has reported the experiences and opinions of numerous change actors with diverse roles: from researchers/scientists, to project managers, to consultants for gender equality.

Overall, the experts interviewed throughout this chapter have reported that the adoption of collaborative practices for gender equality has numerous positive effects for RPOs and RFOs: among many others, it has a capacity building effect, it raises awareness within and beyond the implementing institutions, it provides legitimation and leverage for change, and potentially multiplies the actions' positive effects for change within the whole innovation ecosystems.

Potential obstacles and resistances were also explored, both within and outside the implementing institutions, and the case studies presented examples of viable strategies to overcome such difficulties. Such impediments and hindrances included internal resistances to change, but also reluctance towards sharing the institutions' shortcomings regarding gender equality; differences between the stakeholders' organisational cultures, but also the fear of losing talented researchers and scientists to the competition of the private sector.

Researchers and scientists have been reported to be among the most dynamic actors in institutional change actions. Nonetheless, it is a holistic approach that involves *all* relevant internal actors, and engages with external *throughout* the gender equality plans' life cycle, that has been considered a promising practice.

Particular attention has been given to the role of feminist organisations as representatives of civil society which can contribute to gender equality collaborative practices. While some potential obstacles were identified (such as an "activist" engagement style when more nuanced and diplomatic approaches may be more valuable), the experts have also found that feminist organisations may bring valuable critical perspectives, support, and help in integrating an intersectional perspective. The latter, even if difficult to implement, was considered very important to take into account, and its presence was analysed in all the identified good practices.

Starting from the H2020 priorities for gender equality in research, this chapter described a series of collaborative actions which can be integrated in institutional change processes, together with the possible external actors to involve, and integrated them with the experiences and suggestions of the interviewees.

Finally, this chapter has examined a collection of good practices that has explored in a contextualized way many of the ideas proposed throughout this report. Moreover, the representatives of the good practices have shared suggestions and strategies for overcoming obstacles and further advices for implementing institutions.

While this chapter has served as a collection of experiences and good practices from experts and institutions throughout Europe, the next chapter will focus on the CALIPER partners' analysis of their own national and regional ecosystems and the first attempt to identify suitable strategic partners to involve in the CALIPER R&I Hubs. The Hubs themselves will rely on the outcomes and inputs of this chapter, together with the previous one, to frame and design GEPs' strategies that maximize collaboration with a variety of external stakeholders to promote and achieve internal change for gender equality.

4 External assessment

4.1 External assessment methodology at CALIPER partner organizations

As reported in D1.1 “Internal and external assessment methodologies and guidelines”, the external assessment was aimed at investigating each RPO/RFO external conditions such as the legal and cultural framework and the existing local/ national innovation ecosystems in each partnering country and identifying where gender imbalances occur, why they are created and by which factors they are influenced.

A quadruple helix approach was adopted, by involving stakeholders belonging to the following sectors:

- Academia and universities
- Industry and business
- Government & public sector
- Civil society

The first step of the analysis consisted, for each partner, in defining the **national legal and policy framework** and in particular:

- the existence of any specific national (and/or regional) policies on gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation;
- how the frameworks define the relationship between gender equality and quality/excellence in
 - research and/or in education;
- in case there are no specific frameworks, if broader national and/or regional policies on Research, Innovation, and Higher education include any measures on gender equality.

For exploring the national (and regional) policy frameworks two methods were proposed: a desk research/policy analysis and interviews with relevant stakeholders (complementary in case the desk research did not produce enough information). Most of the partners collected all the needed information through the desk research, while only 2 partners proceeded with interviews (STU BA and UEFISCDI). The list and the description of the relevant indicators (qualitative) in order to conduct the analysis was provided by Smart Venice through D1.1.

The second step of the assessment focused on the **National and Regional Innovation Ecosystems**. A **context analysis** through a dedicated desk research eventually complemented with interviews with internal stakeholders was implemented by the partners. The aim of the context analysis was to have a clear picture of the challenges faced by each organization in its own innovation ecosystem from a gender perspective. Indeed, the analysis was related to the identification of gaps and challenges related to gender inequalities at different levels (across education, scientific research and knowledge production, transfer to market of research outputs) within innovation ecosystems. Also in this case the list and description, as well as the potential sources of indicators (both qualitative and quantitative) were provided by Smart Venice in D1.1.

Besides the context analysis a **mapping** was conducted by partners in order to identify existing and potential synergies with external stakeholders, through the following methods:

- a focus group with internal stakeholders⁵⁸;
- a survey for external stakeholders;
- a Social Network Analysis (SNA).

Both the focus group and the survey had the purpose of exploring the existing collaborations with external stakeholders from a gender perspective, as well identifying actions already undertaken by stakeholders in order to overcome gender inequalities, potential synergies and risks from further collaborations on gender issues. The questions for both tools were proposed by Smart Venice in D1.1.

Focus group was expected to involve from 4 to 8 internal stakeholders, which would have helped in identifying the external stakeholders to include in the SNA and to involve in the R&I Hubs. The focus group was meant to happen face-to-face, however, due to the Covid-19 outbreak and the limitations imposed by the different countries in order to contrast the spread of the virus, in many cases it took place online.

The online survey, instead, targeted 12-15 external stakeholders per partner and consisted of around 10 questions.

Finally, a **SNA** was conducted by each partner with the aim at providing a broad view of national/regional/local networking activities that took place around the RPOs or RFOs through external projects or joint initiatives. It helped spotlighting gender gaps within every partner's institutions in the leadership of external interactions and identifying how frequently gender issues are taken into account in the external stakeholders' interactions. RPOs were asked to focus on collaborations on STEM, in order to narrow the analysis down.

The result of the SNA consists in visual maps spotlighting the collaborations in place per each RPO/RFO with stakeholders belonging to the following categories:

- academia & universities
- industry & business
- government & public sector
- civil society
- schools
- others

Per each category a map is created showing those collaborations having female leaderships (from the side of the RPO/RFO) and those focusing and/or taking into account gender issues. KUMU⁵⁹ was used as tool in order to conduct the SNA.

The specific process followed by partners in order to carry out the SNA is detailed in each partner's external assessment analysis.

The results of the external assessment was reported by partners using the template in Annex V.

⁵⁸ Suggested internal stakeholders to involve were: the President and/or vice president(s) research and/or innovation, professors leading researchers/coordinators of clusters or centres or subject areas with a high density of regional cooperation, the Head of administration and heads of research support office and technology transfer office, the Head of continuing professional development/continuing education office, the Head of start-up support service.

⁵⁹ <https://kumu.io/>

To enhance the legibility of this report, the following table works as an interactive index.

To read the report of one CALIPER partner in particular, click on its name.

CODE	FULL NAME	COUNTRY
UZG	University of Zagreb Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing	Croatia
STU BA	Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava Faculty of Materials Science and Technology	Slovakia
ULB	Université libre de Bruxelles	Belgium
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	Greece
YASAR	University of Yasar	Turkey
IRB	Institute for Research in Biomedicine	Spain
UNILE	University of Salento	Italy
SRNSFG	Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia	Georgia
UEFISCDI	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding	Romania

Table 4_Interactive index of CALIPER partners' external assessments

4.2 External assessment of UZG

4.2.1 The Croatian national legal and policy framework

Overall strategic gender equality policies at national level

In Croatia, in the Article 14 of the national Act on Gender Equality⁶⁰ it is stated that the **RPOs are obliged to work on gender balance**, but they have the freedom to define and monitor their own gender equality policies. In the same act there is an obligation for public administration bodies being mainly owned by the state, to have quotas and legal persons to facilitate the adaptation of gender equality plans. Furthermore, in Article 3 it is stated that educational institutions and research performing organizations are obliged to conduct educational programs about gender equality for staff members. Furthermore, institutions are required to promote gender equality and elimination of inequalities, stereotypes and prejudices in the education process at all levels.

The Report on the Implementation of National Policy for Gender Equality 2011 - 2015⁶¹ shows that most of the measures regarding gender sensitive education and equal opportunities on the market were implemented. But, for example, there are hardly any results on gender equality in ICT sector. There is no national policy for gender equality at the moment, however, in the Report for 2019 of the Ombudsperson for Gender Equality⁶² it is stated that the Government of Croatia plans to adopt a new national plan for gender equality for the period 2021 – 2027.

The National Anti-discrimination Plan for 2017 – 2022⁶³ is still ongoing. The objectives are the protection against discrimination, the promotion of rights to equal treatment in Croatia and raising awareness about the importance of knowing and exercising these rights.

A Committee for Gender Equality is in place at the Croatian Parliament. In 2004 the National Office for Gender Equality was established by the Government of Croatia. The office monitors the enforcement of the Gender Equality Act and other regulations regarding gender equality since 2011.

Existence of specific mechanisms to promote the under- represented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation at national or regional level

At the moment there are no mechanisms in place in Croatia to promote gender equality in Higher Education, but there were some attempts. The ERA Implementation Plan for Croatia 2016 - 2020⁶⁴ states as one of the priorities, gender equality and gender mainstreaming policy in research. However, the measures introduced were only those concerning female entrepreneurship development. Indeed, the Strategy of Female Entrepreneurship Development in Croatia, 2014 – 2020⁶⁵ includes different measures for the promotion of women in entrepreneurship.

⁶⁰ Act on Gender Equality (2008) Official Gazette, No. 82/08,69/17

<https://ravnopravnost.gov.hr/UserDocImages//dokumenti/Zakoni/2018//Act%20on%20Gender%20Equality%20ENG.pdf>

⁶¹ Governmental Office for Gender Equality. (2015). Report on National Policy for Gender Equality 2011 – 2015.

<https://ravnopravnost.gov.hr/UserDocImages//dokumenti/Izvje%C5%A1%C4%87a%20URS/2017//Izvje%C5%A1%C4%87e%20o%20provedbi%20Nacionalne%20politike%20za%20ravnopravnost%20spolova%202011.-%202015.%20%20u%20razdoblju%20od%202014.%20do%202015.pdf>

⁶² Ombudsperson for Gender Equality. (2019). Report 2019.

https://www.prs.hr/attachments/article/2894/IZVJESCE_O_RADU_ZA_2019_Pravobraniteljice_za_ravnopravnost_spolova.pdf

⁶³ Office for Human Rights and Minority Rights. (2017.) National Anti-discrimination Plan 2017 – 2022.

<https://pravamanjina.gov.hr/UserDocImages/dokumenti/Nacionalni%20plan%20za%20borbu%20protiv%20diskriminacije%20za%20razdoblje%20od%202017.%20do%202022.pdf>

⁶⁴ Ministry of Science and Education. (2016.) ERA Roadmap – Implementation Plan for Croatia 2016 – 2020.

<https://mzo.gov.hr/UserDocImages/dokumenti/Znanost/ElstrazivackiProstor/Plan%20implementacije%20Republike%20Hrvatske%20za%20razdoblje%202016.%20-%202020.pdf>

⁶⁵ Government of the Republic of Croatia. (2013). Strategy of Women Entrepreneurship Development in the Republic of Croatia 2014 – 2020.

<https://ravnopravnost.gov.hr/UserDocImages//dokumenti//Strategy%20of%20Women%20Entrepreneurship%20Development%20in%20the%20Republic%20of%20Croatia%202014%20-%202020.pdf>

In the Report on the Implementation of National Policy for Gender Equality for the period 2011 – 2015⁶⁶ it was stated that the part of the Measure 3.3 „Achieve gender balance in selecting the field of education in secondary schools and in higher education“ regarding the promotion of gender equality in STEM fields and scholarships were not put in place at all.

Existence of national policies on implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees

The National Policy for Gender Equality 2011 - 2015⁶⁷ has adopted 11 measures on equality in political and public decision-making processes, including the implementation of quotas in political and public decision-making bodies. They are based on Article 12 of the Gender Equality Act which prescribes the quota of 40% of the underrepresented gender in political and public decision-making bodies, election lists, local, regional and national governmental bodies.

The Ombudsperson for Gender Equality for Croatia conducted, in the period 2013 – 2015, an EU project called “*Dismantling the Glass Labyrinth – Equal Opportunity Access to Economic Decision-making in Croatia*”. A part of the project was about conducting a research on the representation of women and men in management positions in business entities in Croatia⁶⁸. In the ERA Progress Report for Croatia of 2018⁶⁹, it was stated that representation of women in research is high, but there is still a glass ceiling on their scientific career advancement.

Existence of national legislation promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment

In Croatia, the Anti-discrimination Act⁷⁰ is in force since 2009. It follows the legislation in place at the European Union level. The Labor Act of Croatia⁷¹ contains the Article 4 which is about “Protection of Pregnant Employees, Parents and Adoptive Parents”. The National Anti-discrimination Plan for 2017 – 2022⁷², instead, includes, as one of the main priorities, the measure of promoting equal opportunities in the area of labor and employment.

In the report of the Ombudsperson for Gender Equality for 2019⁷³, it is stated that most of the discrimination complaints are related to work, employment and social security (46%).

Existing policies at national level for reducing unequal gender division of labor related to housework and family care

In the National Act on Maternity and Parental Benefits⁷⁴, the rights regarding parental leave, part-time contracts, breastfeeding breaks and financial support are prescribed. Parental leave is paid, transferable

⁶⁶ Governmental Office for Gender Equality. (2015). Report on National Policy for Gender Equality 2011 – 2015.

<https://ravnapravnost.gov.hr/UserDocsImages//dokumenti/lzvje%20C5%A1%C4%87a%20URS/2017//lzvje%20C5%A1%C4%87e%20o%20provedbi%20Nacionalne%20politike%20za%20ravnapravnost%20spolova%202011.-%202015.%20%20u%20razdoblju%20od%202014.%20do%202015.pdf>

⁶⁷ See reference n. 66

⁶⁸ Ombudsperson for Gender Equality. (2016). Research on the representation of women and men in management positions in business entities in the Republic of Croatia.

http://staklenilabirint.prs.hr/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/PRSRH_Izvjesce_muskarci-zene500_web.pdf

⁶⁹ European Commission. (2019). ERA Progress Report 2018 – country profile Croatia.

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/era/era-2018_country_profile_hr.pdf

⁷⁰ Anti-discrimination Act (2009), Official Gazette, No. 85/08.

<https://ravnapravnost.gov.hr/UserDocsImages//dokumenti/Zakoni//The%20Anti-discrimination%20Act.pdf>

⁷¹ Labour Act. (2009). Official Gazette, No. 149/09.

<https://ravnapravnost.gov.hr/UserDocsImages//dokumenti/Zakoni//Labour%20Act.pdf>

⁷² Office for Human Rights and Minority Rights. (2017.) National Anti-discrimination Plan 2017 – 2022.

<https://pravamanjina.gov.hr/UserDocsImages/dokumenti/Nacionalni%20plan%20za%20borbu%20protiv%20diskriminacije%20za%20razdoblje%20od%202017.%20do%202022.pdf>

⁷³ Ombudsperson for Gender Equality. (2019). Report 2019.

https://www.prs.hr/attachments/article/2894/IZVJESCE_O_RADU_ZA_2019_Pravobraniteljice_za_ravnapravnost_spolova.pdf

⁷⁴ Act on Maternity and Parental Benefits. (2008). Official Gazette, No. 85/08, 110/08, and 34/11.

http://www.hzzo-net.hr/dload/zakoni/06_procisceni.pdf

between parents or guardians and there is flexibility in the use of parental leave. Fathers are encouraged to take a parental leave by getting two months extra.

Concerning the Labour Act⁷⁵, it contains articles about the protection of pregnant women, parents and adoptive parents, their working hours and leaves.

This issue is also addressed in The National Policy for Gender Equality 2011 – 2015 (Measure 2.3.1)⁷⁶. The Report on the Implementation of The National Policy for Gender Equality 2011 – 2015⁷⁷ describes the promotional activities that were carried out in order to encourage the equal distribution of household and family affairs as well as equal sharing of parental responsibility for childcare, including the promotion of the usage of parental leave by fathers.

Existing framework conditions regarding childcare facilities

According to the Barcelona Objectives Report for 2018⁷⁸, the percentages of children using childcare facilities in Croatia in 2016 were the following: 15,7% of children under 3 years old and 51,8% of children over 3 years old. The European goals are 33% and 90% respectively. There are big differences between the regions across the country. For instance, availability of childcare facilities is improving in the city of Zagreb (where UNIZG-FER is located). The data for the city of Zagreb in 2016 are: 40% of children under 3 years old of age and 83% of children over 3 years old are using childcare facilities.

Employment conditions at university and research organization

The National Act on Science and Higher Education, 2003⁷⁹ regulates the employment conditions at public universities and research performing organizations. The Act foresees a fixed number of years to access the following stage in a scientific career. According to Article 42 of the Act, for scientific positions (assistant professor, associate professor and full professors), the employment contract is of permanent type, but there is the obligation of re-election in a fixed number of years. Associate positions (doctoral and postdoctoral researchers) are not permanent, they have fixed term contracts. Article 45 of the Act prescribes the possibility of postponement of the end of contract, in case of fixed-term contracts, and the postponement of the election deadline in career progression, in the case of parental leave, longer sick leave, public service or other significant reason. In the case of employment contracts of associates in projects funded by the Croatian Science Foundation, there is no possibility of postponement, not even in the case of project leaders.

Share of precarious contracts on the overall employment positions in Higher Education in Croatia in the year 2018 is of 3.97% for female researchers and 4.92% for male researchers⁸⁰.

Existence of national programs which promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research

In the Report on the Implementation of the National Policy for Gender Equality 2011 – 2015⁸¹, it is reported that the planned measure n. 7.3.3 “*Support and funding scientific research on gender issues*” was not implemented. The new strategy for 2020 – 2024 is expected.

⁷⁵ Labor Act. (2009). Official Gazette, No. 149/09.

<https://ravnopravnost.gov.hr/UserDocsImages//dokumenti/Zakoni/Labour%20Act.pdf>

⁷⁶ Governmental Office for Gender Equality. (2015). National Policy for Gender Equality 2011 – 2015.

<https://ravnopravnost.gov.hr/UserDocsImages//arhiva/images/pdf//National%20Policy%20for%20Gender%20Equality%202011-2015.pdf>

⁷⁷ See reference n. 66

⁷⁸ European Commission. (2018). Barcelona objectives report.

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/bcn_objectives-report2018_web_en.pdf

⁷⁹ Act on Science and Higher Education (2003), Official Gazette, No. 123/2003.

<https://www.zakon.hr/z/320/Zakon-o-znanstvenoj-djelatnosti-i-visokom-obrazovanju>

⁸⁰ European Commission. (2019). She Figures 2018 https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/she-figures-2018_en

⁸¹ See reference n. 66

National/ policies and legal frameworks on sexual/gender harassment in the workplace

The Anti-discrimination Act⁸² describes forms of discrimination, states the prohibition of discrimination, provides institutional framework and penalty provisions.

The Labour Act⁸³ prescribes the obligation of the employer to protect the dignity of employees regarding discrimination and harassment. In particular, the employer has to nominate a Commissioner for the protection of the dignity of workers in the institution among the employees. The Act also presents the mechanism for reporting to the Commissioner.

Every university in Croatia has its own the Code of Ethics⁸⁴, in which harassment, discrimination and other forms of unethical behaviour between staff and students are declared as inappropriate and prohibited. Universities and faculties have Ethics Committees for reporting unethical violations of the Code of Ethics.

Funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality at national and regional level

No funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality exist at national and regional level.

⁸² See reference n. 70

⁸³ See reference n. 71

⁸⁴ University of Zagreb. (2007). Code of Ethics.

https://www.hrstud.unizg.hr/images/50014335/Eticki_kodeks-1.pdf

4.2.2 The innovation ecosystem context analysis at UZG

The following table presents the results of the context analysis conducted by UZG in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Area	Indicator	Results
Talents and workforce education and acquisition	High School and Higher Education students in STEM by gender, at regional and national levels	<p>STEM High School students (1st gr., 2018/2019)⁸⁵</p> <p>■ males ■ females</p>
		<p>STEM Higher Education students (1st year, 2018/2019)⁸⁶</p> <p>■ males ■ females</p>
	Researchers in STEM by gender in R&I, at national and regional levels	<p>STEM researchers in 2018⁸⁷</p> <p>■ males ■ females</p>
	Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender	Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender

⁸⁵ Croatian Bureau of Statistics. (2018). High Schools and dormitories, end of school year 2017. /2018. and beginning of school year 2018. /2019. (SR 1643)

https://www.dzs.hr/Hrv_Eng/publication/2019/SI-1643.pdf

⁸⁶ Croatian Bureau of Statistics. (2018). Students enrolled on Professional and University Study, Winter Semester of 2018/2019 Academic Year. (FR 8.1.7)

https://www.dzs.hr/Hrv_Eng/publication/2019/08-01-07_01_2019.html

⁸⁷ Croatian Bureau of Statistics. (2020). Research and Development 2018. (SR 1667)

https://www.dzs.hr/Hrv_Eng/publication/2020/SI-1667.pdf

		<p>Data available for 2014⁸⁸, 2015⁸⁹, 2016⁹⁰, 2017⁹¹, 2018⁹²</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Year</th> <th>Males (%)</th> <th>Females (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>2014</td> <td>59.20%</td> <td>40.80%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2015</td> <td>59.06%</td> <td>40.94%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2016</td> <td>60.57%</td> <td>39.43%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2017</td> <td>61.03%</td> <td>38.97%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2018</td> <td>60.07%</td> <td>39.93%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Year	Males (%)	Females (%)	2014	59.20%	40.80%	2015	59.06%	40.94%	2016	60.57%	39.43%	2017	61.03%	38.97%	2018	60.07%	39.93%
Year	Males (%)	Females (%)																		
2014	59.20%	40.80%																		
2015	59.06%	40.94%																		
2016	60.57%	39.43%																		
2017	61.03%	38.97%																		
2018	60.07%	39.93%																		
Leadership	Patents registrations by gender	<p>Patent registration teams⁹³</p> <p>One woman: 6.67%; All women team: 0.83%; Team with at least 60% women: 2.08%</p> <p>Mixed team: 4.17%; Team with at least 60% men: 2.92%; All men team: 16.68%; One man: 66.65%</p>																		
	Founders and leaders of innovative enterprises and start-ups by gender	<p>Data 2013⁹⁴ : TEA⁹⁵ males/TEA females = 2.24 (EU 1.86); TEA (Males): 11.47%; TEA (females): 5.11%</p> <p>Data 2018⁹⁶: TEA males/TEA females = 1.7 (EU 1.8); TEA (Males): 12.1%; TEA (females): 7.1%</p>																		

⁸⁸ Croatian Bureau of Statistics. (2016). Research and Development 2014. (SR 1572) https://www.dzs.hr/Hrv_Eng/publication/2016/SI-1572.pdf

⁸⁹ Croatian Bureau of Statistics. (2017). Research and Development 2015. (SR 1601) https://www.dzs.hr/Hrv_Eng/publication/2017/SI-1601.pdf

⁹⁰ Croatian Bureau of Statistics. (2018). Research and Development 2016. (SR 1623) https://www.dzs.hr/Hrv_Eng/publication/2018/SI-1623.pdf

⁹¹ Croatian Bureau of Statistics. (2019). Research and Development 2017. (SR 1646) https://www.dzs.hr/Hrv_Eng/publication/2019/SI-1646.pdf

⁹² *ibid*

⁹³ European Commission. (2019). She Figures 2018 https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/she-figures-2018_en

⁹⁴ Singer, S., Šarlija, N., Pfeifer, S., Oberman Peterka, S. (2019). What makes Croatia (non)entrepreneurial country? GEM Croatia 2018. CEPOR, Zagreb. <http://www.cepor.hr/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/GEM2018zaweb.pdf>

⁹⁵ Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity (TEA) Rate: Percentage of 18-64 population who are either a nascent entrepreneur or owner-manager of a new business <https://www.gemconsortium.org/wiki/1154>

⁹⁶ *ibid*.

Knowledge and tech production issues	Level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension	The total percentage of Croatia's publications having a sex or gender dimension in their research content for the period 2013 – 2017 is of 2.94 %. ⁹⁷ (The average at EU-28 level is of 1.79%) Concerning the percentages by fields, they are the followings: natural sciences 1.02%, engineering & computing 0.27%, medical sciences 5.88%, agricultural science 2.54%, social sciences 5.38% and humanities & arts 3.98%. (She Figures 2018)
	Level of consideration of the gender dimension in product/service development	No information are available with reference to this indicator.
Broader issues featuring the R&I 'cultures	Gender sensitiveness/family friendliness of supporting services to start up and entrepreneurship	One of the strategic goals of The Strategy of Women Entrepreneurship Development in Croatia, for the period 2014 – 2020 ⁹⁸ is the improvement of supporting services for women entrepreneurship. Croatia is one of the rare countries with this kind of strategy. The Croatian Chamber of Commerce is organizing international conferences on women in business on a regular basis. It also organizes a School for Entrepreneurship for Women in cooperation with the International Network of Businesswomen. Moreover, in Croatia, there are various non-profit organizations and associations with different programs and projects for developing and supporting women in business. In 2016, Ombudsperson for Gender Equality and Croatian Employers' Association established the electronic Database of businesswomen who are capable and qualified to assume management positions in companies.
	Perception of existing stereotypes/bias on gender and innovation/ entrepreneurship	In The Strategy of Women Entrepreneurship Development for Croatia, for the period 2014 – 2020, the following structural barriers are presented: educational choices of women decrease the possibility to start the business in technology and research, stereotypes about women in science and technology, traditional attitudes about the women's role in the society and lack of support for women with two jobs (work - life balance issues). In the research paper by Zirdum and Cvitanović (2011) ⁹⁹ the following examples of discrimination of women at work are identified: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "In Croatia today it is easier for men to get a job,, - "The best paid jobs are mostly for men,, - "The abilities of women at work are more often underestimated than the abilities of men,, <p>The National Agency for Electronic Media established the online portal „Women in Media“ with the purpose of strengthening the correct media visibility of women and reducing harmful stereotypes.</p>

Table 5_ Results of the context analysis conducted by UZG

⁹⁷ European Commission. (2019). She Figures 2018. https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/she-figures-2018_en

⁹⁸ Government of the Republic of Croatia. (2013). Strategy of Women Entrepreneurship Development in the Republic of Croatia 2014.-2020.

<https://ravnopravnost.gov.hr/UserDocsImages//dokumenti/Strategy%20of%20Women%20Entrepreneurship%20Development%20in%20the%20Republic%20of%20Croatia%202014%20-%202020.pdf>

⁹⁹ Zirdum, G., Cvitanović, V. (2017). Barriers and Opportunities for Developing Women's Entrepreneurship in the Republic of Croatia, *Obrazovanje za poduzetništvo - E4E*, 7 (2), 205-222. <https://hrcaj.srce.hr/191725>

4.2.3 UZG Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA

Results of the focus group with internal stakeholders

As far as the **focus group** is concerned the most relevant insights are reported below. 5 internal stakeholders (2 males and 3 females) took part in the session, 3 professors and 2 heads of administrative offices, all of them having strong connections with the ecosystem of the institution.

Concerning the current **existing or prospective collaborations on broader areas** beside gender equality, participants reported that UNIZG-FER has a wide network of existing partners and collaborations through different areas of interest. In particular, a fully developed scientific and professional network of collaboration with industry and technical institutes exists. Indeed, in recent years, the university made a big effort to deepen a cooperation on employment processes with companies in the fields of IT, telecommunication, electrical engineering and energetics through Career Center and activities such as Job Fair or Career Speed Dating. Also, UNIZG-FER follows the trends on the market and has strong connections with the industry and collaborates on promotional STEM activities with schools, NGOs, faculties and other universities. Finally, participants stressed that the cooperation with media, social media and promotional activities has been developed for one year, since the Public Relations Office was established in 2019.

The group then focused on the ways in which gender inequalities represent a **challenge** for external stakeholders. Participants reported that all educational STEM institutions in Croatia face the same issues regarding how to attract more female students to STEM and in their opinion gender prejudices and gender bias in jobs should be addressed in the early stage of the education process (e.g. elementary school). The lack of females is spread through the whole STEM industry, especially at the top leading position. Women are mostly employed as project managers in companies because of their developed soft skills, such as better organization and administration skills, while men usually work as software developers. This is also due to a false perception of the different jobs related to STEM, which are seen as no stimulating, creative. This leads girls to opt for different studies. Also participants reported how female students are in general not inclined to initiate start-ups and need much more encouragement than man. The reasons should be investigated in order to tackle them. Finally, participants pointed out how there is the risk to become unequal in the fight for equality, therefore instead of imposing quotas they would opt for raising awareness actions with the use of examples, role models.

About the **actions that external stakeholders put in place on gender equality**, participants reported that some big companies already have gender policies and pay attention to it. In particular, several IT firms are already participating in some campaigns regarding women in STEM. They use successful female employees as role models in their promotional activities. Participants were aware of two colleagues of the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Naval Architecture (UNIZ-FSB) at University of Zagreb taking part in raising awareness activities in schools.

With reference to **complementarities and synergies** with their own institution and the impact for internal institutional change, participants identified the followings:

- Inclusion of gender equality in the existing promotional activities in schools, for instance with the organization of dedicate lectures in high schools about girls in STEM;
- Connection with the faculty UNIZG-FSB regarding some promotional campaign for girls;
- Work with media on changing the public perception of UNIG-FER as a male faculty and changing the idea that STEM occupations are for men exclusively;

- Organization of events about gender equality with companies collaborating with the University Career Center, for instance, during the Job Fair, workshops about gender equality and challenges in STEM can be organized as well as open discussions on the issue, open a blog, etc.;
- Collaboration with companies for tailoring new jobs which can be satisfying for students who want to find a job with a “meaning”;
- Organization of workshops for elementary school teachers about gender sensitive teaching and prejudices in education systems;
- Inclusion of projects more appealing for girls in the presentation of departments at Open Day of UNIZG-FER;
- Improve the communication through the website by including role models;
- Promote STEM-projects with a social impact and soft skills in STEM jobs in order to attract more girls.

No **overlapping/competitive actions** were identified, while risks about the lack of human and other resources as well as the lack of interest of the stakeholders were pointed out.

Results of the survey to external stakeholders

The survey was submitted by 13 external stakeholders, 4 private companies, 3 faculties, 3 associations (NGOs), 2 schools and a public institution, dealing with a wide range of activities: education, research, IT services, promotion of women, sustainable development.

Concerning the **types of collaboration** such external stakeholders have in place with UNIZG-FER the main ones are the followings:

- Project and teaching cooperation;
- Organization of lectures;
- Participation to Job Fairs;
- Agreements for the employment of students in internships;
- Participation to workshops;
- General support to activities (in case of NGOs).

The survey tackled the same topics addressed during the focus group.

External stakeholders were asked to explain how **gender inequalities challenge their own organizations**. Faculties and schools reported that a few number of female students decide to enroll in STEM faculties or high schools, females seem not to be interested in such subjects. Within UNIZG faculties, some of them are balanced from a gender perspective, others not, but until now some of them did not consider it as a significant problem. A big challenge was raised by a school, which reported that female teachers are constantly exposed to attacks by parents, especially men, who investigate about the personal life of teachers and ask whether they plan to have children soon.

Most companies (3 out of 4) reported having a small number of female employees covering technical positions, which is also reflected in the share of women applying for internships and jobs. About NGOs, gender inequalities do not appear to be present internally, the same with the public institution filling the survey.

With reference to the **potential benefits** of addressing the challenges, faculties stressed that removing gender inequalities would benefit both men and women, as well as the faculty itself, since it would allow the selection of the most valuable people regardless of gender. Schools reported as potential benefits a more positive work climate for teachers and an incentive for girls to choose a STEM career and participate in projects, competitions and extra activities. Companies and NGOs pointed out that having heterogeneous teams and communities is beneficial for companies and for the society as a whole. Gender equality also opens

new opportunities for future generations both in terms of living and working. According to the public institution, benefits are related on raising awareness about the measures needed in order to improve the status and the opportunities for vulnerable groups in the society.

About **actions and measures** that the external stakeholders undertook to address gender inequalities, only one faculty reported undertaking measures such as: research and dissemination of results of the research on gender equality, promotion of role models, mentoring, many women appointed to the position of leaders of faculties, heads of laboratories, services and centers, promotion of successful female alumni etc. Schools celebrate the “Ada Lovelace Day” and participate in projects (Erasmus+ and national calls) on the topic. A company reported celebrating the “Women in STEM month” and participating in the Ladies in Business Conference, while another one declared having a number of measures related to gender equality in the Code of Business Ethics. Another company reported being constantly committed in promoting gender equality but without explaining with which measures. To be noticed that a company highlighted that women employees are treated equally as male ones and that they have leaderships positions, while another one stated that the percentage of women in the company reflects the percentage of the market therefore, they don’t think they have an issue about gender equality. NGOs explained paying attention on the language used and participating in the projects on gender equality. The public institution, instead, tackles the issue by implementing projects related to vulnerable groups in the society.

About **potential measures** to be adopted to tackle gender inequalities, 2 out of 3 faculties reported that they are not thinking about measures to adopt. 2 out of 4 companies are willing to keep on implementing actions. One NGO reported having actions planned while another one being willing to cooperate with the university for this purpose. The public institution is planning further actions in lifelong learning initiatives and increasing digital literacy.

The following questions explored which **form of cooperation** stakeholders envisaged with UNIG-FER in order to overcome gender equality. Faculties indicated joint projects and research on the topic as form of cooperation but they reported being open to other forms. Schools indicated the adoption of role models but also workshops, lectures and study visits. NGOs are open to any form of formal and informal cooperation also with specific actions towards students to raise their awareness about gender equality. Companies suggested to start joint conversations in order to find common issues/topics and exchange experiences on how to encourage girls to join a STEM career and motivate them to stay. The public institution would instead be available in implementing a cooperation based on the preparation and implementation of trainings related to the topic.

Talking specifically about joint actions, faculties mentioned the promotion of female role models, research activities and mentoring. Schools envisaged the partnership in projects and the promotion of role models and training for female students, but they reported being open for other actions. Only one company indicated possible actions consisting in promoting technological capabilities and good practices. The public institution mentioned actions about cooperation in the preparation and organization of education, the presentation of results and the participation in research.

No overlapping or competitive actions were identified.

Finally, **potential risks** of the cooperation were addressed. The only ones that were identified were the followings:

- Costs of the activities (by a company)
- Difficulty to identify common needs/issues (by a company)
- Difficulty to implement measures due to the small dimensions of the organization (by a NGO)

All the other stakeholders did not identify any risks but also benefits from the cooperation.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Results of the SNA

The data on collaborations with external stakeholders were collected from the Management of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing of University of Zagreb (UNIZG-FER). In particular, the data come from a database which is regularly filled by the project leaders once they start a new collaboration. It is important to notice that the ones appearing in the following maps are only collaborations with stakeholders from Croatia since the focus of the mapping, as explained in the methodology part, in paragraph 4.1, is the national and regional ecosystem, while, in general, at UNIZG-FER, most of the collaborations are with foreign universities. Special collaborations with civil society organizations and schools are managed directly by the Management of the institution.

Overall, **160 external stakeholders** were included in the mapping. The majority of collaborations are with “academia & universities” stakeholders (84 out of 160 stakeholders, representing the 52%), followed by “industry & business” stakeholders (35 out of 160, representing the 22%), “schools” (21 out of 160, representing the 13%), “civil society” stakeholders (16 out of 160, representing the 10%) and “government & public sector” stakeholders (4 out of 160, representing the 2,5%). The most important partners from “academia & universities” are the faculties of Croatian universities specialized in scientific fields of electrical engineering, engineering and computer science, while the most important partners of the “industry & business” sector are companies providing power and energy related services.

About the **intensity** of collaborations with external stakeholders, most of them (81 out of 141, representing the 57%) are “one-time” collaborations. Among “one-time” collaborations, 4 are with “government & public sector”, 11 with “civil society” stakeholders, 19 with “industry & business” stakeholders, 21 with schools and 27 are with “academia & universities” stakeholders.

Concerning the **topic** of the collaborations, most of them (74 out of 141, representing the 52%) are about “scientific research”, 32 about “transfer to market”, 24 about “education”, 9 about “science communication” and 2 are “raising awareness”.

In total, **39 collaborations (24%) are led by women** in UNIZG-FER, 21 of them concern collaborations with schools (54%), while 15 regards projects in place with “academia & universities” stakeholders (38%) and 3 with “industry & business” stakeholders (8%).

The overall number of female researchers involved in collaborations is unknown since that data is not available. Concerning the collaborations focusing or taking into account gender, it is worth to mention that the institutional database does not collect this type of data. However, through the analysis of the descriptions of the projects in place with all the 160 stakeholders, it is possible to conclude that none of the collaborations are focusing on gender or taking gender into account. Also, it is a general opinion that STEM research projects hardly focus on gender, therefore they are not asked to report on gender related data.

The following pictures represent the results of the SNA conducted by UNIZG-FER according to the kind of stakeholders. Therefore, 5 different maps are displayed, one for each category of stakeholders: “academia & university”, “industry & business”, “government & public sector”, “civil society” and “school”.

Per each map it is possible to identify the different departments of UNIZG-FER involved in the collaborations with the different external stakeholders (the nodes with a small green circle), the collaborations having female leaderships (the yellow nodes). As already mentioned, no collaborations focusing or taking into account gender were registered.

Figure 5_UNIZG-FER collaborations with "Academia & university" stakeholders

Figure 6_UNIZG-FER collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders

Figure 7_UNIZG-FER collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders

Figure 8_UNIZG-FER collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 9_UNIZG-FER collaborations with schools

4.2.4 Final remarks on the external assessment of UZG

The Croatian national law foresees a series of provisions aimed at promoting gender equality. The most relevant act in this sense is the national **Act on Gender Equality**, which states that RPOs are obliged to work on gender balance. Even though a **national policy for gender equality does not exist** yet, many measures regarding gender sensitive education and equal opportunities have been put in place. Gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research were set as one of the priorities by the ERA Implementation Plan for Croatia 2016 - 2020. Among the adopted measures, worth to mentioned are the ones targeting **political and decision-making processes**, which prescribe the quota of 40% of the underrepresented gender in local, regional and national bodies. Measures regarding parental leaves, part-time contracts and breastfeeding breaks are foreseen in the national legislation. The availability of childcare facilities is not homogeneously spread through the country. So far, **no specific measures for supporting and funding scientific research on gender issues have been implemented**. However, a new strategy on Gender Equality is expected for the period 2020 – 2024 which will provide with measures on this aspect.

From the analysis of the innovation ecosystems (paragraph 4.2.2) it is possible to observe a great **discrepancy between the number of male and female STEM students** both at high schools and higher education, while the evolution of the employment rate in R&I shows a decrease in the employment of females from 2014 to 2018. Also the data regarding patent registrations, founders and leaders of start-ups show a sensible gender gap. Quite low is also the share of Croatia's publications integrating a sex or gender dimension in their research. A positive trend is the one related to the recent improvement of **services to support women entrepreneurship**.

The analysis was implemented by the **mapping of external stakeholders** through a focus group and a survey and the SNA. According to the activities conducted, UNIZG-FER has a wide network of partners and collaborations in STEM, especially with industrial and technical institutes, related to education and research activities as well to project cooperation. External stakeholders face a lack of female students and employees, especially at the top leading positions. This is due to a biased perception of STEM jobs mainly by girls, leading to a need of implementing awareness raising actions (e.g. events, campaigns, workshops, etc.) involving role

models. Only a few external stakeholders already implemented some measures for contrasting gender inequalities, however, the ones involved through the survey expressed being willing to cooperate with UNIZG-FER on the matter, through joint projects and research on the topic, the organization of workshops, training, lectures aimed at raising awareness.

160 stakeholders were included in the SNA, most of them belonging to the “academia & universities” sector. Almost the 25% of the collaborations have a female leadership, but notably, the vast majority of those are with Schools, while no information could be collected with reference of collaborations taking into account and/or focusing on gender issues, even though, it is possible to assume that the collaboration with one of the “civil society” stakeholders, “Women in Engineering – WiE”, deals with gender issues. The lack of information is due by the fact that the dimension of gender is not monitored for what concerns STEM research projects. Also, according to the analysis provided by the UNIZG-FER researchers none of the STEM projects identified mentions gender in its description.

4.3 External assessment of STU BA

4.3.1 The Slovakian national legal and policy framework

Overall strategic gender equality policies at national level

The Slovak legislation does not specifically address the area of Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation.

Gender equality is addressed within Act no. 365/2004 Coll. on *“Equal Treatment in Certain Areas and Protection against Discrimination, and on amending and supplementing certain other laws as amended (Antidiscrimination Act)”*¹⁰⁰, which regulates the application of the equal treatment principle and provides legal protection measures in the case the principle is violated. The law states: *“Adherence to the principle of equal treatment consists in the prohibition of discrimination on of the sex, religion or belief, race, nationality or ethnic group, disability, age, sexual orientation, marital status and family status, colour, language, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, gender or other status, or because of the reporting of crime or other anti-social activity”*. *“Adherence to the principle of equal treatment also consists in accepting measures to protect against discrimination”*.

The principle of equal treatment in labour relations and similar legal relations is addressed in Act no. 311/2001 Coll. - Labour Code, which in Art. 6 states: *“Women and men have the right to equal treatment regarding access to employment, remuneration and career growth, vocational training and working conditions. Pregnant women, mothers up to the end of the ninth month after childbirth and breastfeeding women are provided with working conditions that protect their biological condition in connection to pregnancy, childbirth, childcare after childbirth and their special relationship with the child after childbirth. Women and men are provided with working conditions that enable them to perform a social function in the upbringing and care of children”*.

There is also the *“National Strategy for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic for 2014-2019”*¹⁰¹, approved by the Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic (2019a) (MPSVR) and approved by the Slovak Government. One of its strategic areas and priorities is the number 3 on *“Education, science and research”*, whose aim is improve the application of gender equality in education, science and research and the s Objectives are: 3.1 To improve the level of knowledge in the field of women's human rights and gender equality by ensuring continuing and wide-ranging education within lifelong learning; 3.2 Eliminate negative gender stereotypes in education; 3.3 Create an environment and effective mechanisms for the implementation of gender equality in the fields of science, research and higher education; 3.4 To deepen knowledge of existing forms of inequality between women and men by strengthening research in this area and gender statistics.

The Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic submitted also the *“Action Plan for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic for 2014-2019”*¹⁰², approved by the Ministry itself and the Government of the Slovak Republic. Education is defined in 3th area: *“Improving the application of gender equality in education, science and research”*, with the objective number 3: To improve the application of gender equality in education, science and research and sub-objective and in particular 3.3: To create an environment and

¹⁰⁰ Act no. 365/2004 Coll. on Equal Treatment in Certain Areas and Protection against Discrimination, and on amending and supplementing certain other laws as amended (Antidiscrimination Act) (Zákon č. 365/2004 Z. z. Zákon o rovnakom zaobchádzaní v niektorých oblastiach a o ochrane pred diskrimináciou a o zmene a doplnení niektorých zákonov (antidiskriminačný zákon) <https://www.slov-lex.sk/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/2004/365/20160102>

¹⁰¹ Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic. (2014a). National Strategy for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic for 2014-2019” (Celoštátna stratégia rodovej rovnosti v Slovenskej republike na roky 2014-2019). <https://www.gender.gov.sk/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Strategia-RR.pdf>

¹⁰² https://www.tsk.sk/buxus/docs/Akcny_plan_rodovej_rovnosti_v_Slovenskej_republike_na_roky_2014-2019.pdf

effective mechanisms for the implementation of gender equality in the field of science, research and higher education. Tasks have been set as follows:

- Task n. 32: Encourage universities and research organizations to adopt and strengthen equality strategies in their organizations, including measures to work-life balance (responsible MPSVR in cooperation with The Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic (MŠVVaŠ)).
- Task n. 33: To support an increase of women representation in management positions and decision-making positions in institutions of science, research and higher education (responsible MŠVVaŠ)

The "National Strategy for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic" and the "Action Plan for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic" have not yet been approved for the next period.

Existence of specific mechanisms to promote the under-represented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation at national or regional level

There is no national legislation, but the targets for increasing the number of women in Higher and/or Scientific Research & Innovation are stated in:

- the "National Strategy for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic for 2014-2019"¹⁰³;
- the "Action Plan for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic for 2014-2019"¹⁰⁴.

However, specific support mechanisms are not but according to our findings there is no specific support mechanism.

Existence of national policies on implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees

There is no national legislation on such matters. As already mentioned above, in the Slovak Republic there is a "National Strategy for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic for 2014-2019". In the Strategic area and interest number 2 called "Participation in decision-making in public and economic life", the goals are set as follows:

- Objective 2: Reducing gender differences in the participation of women and men in decision-making positions.
- Operational objectives:
 1. To increase the representation of women in decision-making positions in political life, including their motivation and opportunities to candidate and participate;
 2. Promote and support the women's entrepreneurship by creating systemic measures, including the work-life balance;
 3. Increase the representation of women in economic decision-making positions.

Within the "Action Plan of Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic for the Years 2014-2019", and its Objective n. 2 "To reduce gender differences in the participation of women and men in decision-making positions", goals and tasks are partially the followings:

1. To increase the representation of women in decision-making positions in political life, including their motivation and opportunities to candidate and participate:

¹⁰³ Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic. (2014a). National Strategy for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic for 2014-2019" (Celoštátna stratégia rodovej rovnosti v Slovenskej republike na roky 2014-2019). <https://www.gender.gov.sk/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Strategia-RR.pdf>

¹⁰⁴ Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic. (2014b). Action Plan for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic for 2014-2019. (Akčný plán rodovej rovnosti v Slovenskej republike na roky 2014-2019)

- To set as a long-term goal of the policy the increase of women's representation and initiate a society-wide and professional discussion on increasing the participation of women in the policy.
 - To introduce temporary compensatory measures in accordance with the ADZ and Article 4 CEDAW as part of the necessary strategy for the accelerate achievement of real equality between women and men.
 - To motivate political parties to adopt targets to increase women's representation.
2. To support and promote women's entrepreneurship by creating systemic measures, including the work-life balance:
 - To create and implement programs aimed at supporting women's entrepreneurship.
 - To support the networking of businesswomen and cooperation with the state administration.
 3. To increase the representation of women in economic decision-making positions:
 - At the level of companies, professional unions and social partners to sequentially initiate self-regulatory measures to increase gender diversity in governing bodies with set goals and periods;
 - To carry out research on the obstacles that women face in their career grow.
 - To carry out awareness-raising and information activities on the topic of women's representation in decision-making.

Worth to mention is the competition “Employer friendly to the family, gender equality and equal opportunities”¹⁰⁵, which is organized by the Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic and its aim is to increase awareness and sensitivity on the issues of work-life balance and support for the employment of women in top positions. At the same time, it is an motivation for employers to create measures that are friendly to the families of employees, but also to gender equality and equal opportunities, and thus offer examples of good practice.

Existence of national legislation promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment

There are several laws in the Slovak Republic concerning equality and anti-discrimination. In particular:

- Constitution of the Slovak Republic No. 460/1992 Coll¹⁰⁶
- Act no. 365/2004 Coll. on “Equal Treatment in Certain Areas and Protection against Discrimination, and on amending and supplementing certain other laws as amended (Antidiscrimination Act)”¹⁰⁷
- Act no. 311/2001 Coll. Labour Code¹⁰⁸
- Act no. 5/2004 Coll. Act on Employment Services and on amending to certain acts¹⁰⁹

Existing policies at national level for reducing unequal gender division of labor related to housework and family care

In order to support a more balanced division of responsibilities for the family households and a greater involvement of fathers in childcare, the paternity leave was successfully introduced in the Slovak Republic. In particular, the Labour Code acknowledges to both women and male employees the right to maternity and parental leave. However, women and men cannot jointly receive the maternity leave (to take care of the

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.gender.gov.sk/aktivity/zamestnavatel-ustretovy-k-rodine-a-rodovej-rovnosti/>
<https://www.nadaciapontis.sk/projekty/via-bona-slovakia/zamestnavatel-ustretovy-k-rodine-k-rodovej-rovnosti-a-rovnosti-prilezitosti-via-bona-slovakia/>

¹⁰⁶ Constitution of the Slovak Republic No. 460/1992 Coll (Ústavný zákon č. 460/1992 Z. z. Ústava Slovenskej republiky) <https://www.slov-lex.sk/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/1992/460/20190701>

¹⁰⁷ *ibid.*

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.slov-lex.sk/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/2001/311/20200730>

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.slov-lex.sk/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/2004/5/20200929>

same child). After the end of maternity leave, the parent is entitled to receive parental allowance (maximum till the child is 3 years old or 6 years old in case the child who has a long-term health issue).

Existing framework conditions regarding childcare facilities

Childcare is provided in:

- the child's family environment;
- environments specifically dedicated to childcare,
- the family environment of the personal entity providing childcare.

Kindergartens are a typical example of a childcare facility in the Slovak Republic. The problem with kindergartens is their insufficient capacity. Due to the lack of capacity in kindergartens, many municipalities and cities are forced to give preference to some children and reject others¹¹⁰. Another issues is related to the placement of children with health and social disadvantages in kindergarten. The legislation allows kindergartens to refuse the admission of a child with a disability, in case the kindergarten does not have suitable personnel, space, materials and other conditions. As a result, there is up to 40% of children with disabilities in Slovakia who do not attend kindergarten and parents have to take care of them¹¹¹. In general, there is an insufficient coverage of kindergartens or special social service facilities for disabled children, therefore the care usually remains in the hands of the mothers, who are therefore limited or need to leave their job.

In September 2020, STU was the first university in Slovakia opening a private kindergarten called STUBAčik¹¹², meant to be used by STU employees' and students' children.

Employment conditions at university and research organization

In Slovakia, university job positions are connected with the fulfilment of the accreditation conditions of the study programs of the university. Accreditation conditions are approved by the Ministry of Education of the Slovak Republic. The list of accredited study programs is kept in the register of study programs. Entries in the register of study programs are made by universities, the Slovak Accreditation Agency for Higher Education, and the Ministry of Education, Science, Research, and Sports of the Slovak Republic. The register also records decisions of the Minister made on the basis of previous legal regulations of the Accreditation Commission. The enrolment of student programs depends on the creation of job positions for which potential employees apply through a selection procedure (tender). The job positions are divided into the position of teacher (assistant professor, associate professor, or professor), whose subject of work performance is the pedagogical area as well as research activities, and the position of researcher, whose main subject of performance is active research. In the case of scientific research staff, the selection procedure (tender) is not mandatory. Career progression (growth) is related to the achievement of a set criteria by the candidate. As far as the employment contracts are concerned, the problem is related to permanent contracts, since, often, a space for the employees' development and fulfilment of tasks / duties / criteria for their career academic development is not provided. In the case of a university teacher and researcher, the advantage in terms of work-life balance consists in the number of holidays which is of 45 days.

¹¹⁰ MESA10. (2018). Few kindergartens, many obstacles on the way to them. (Málo materských škôl, veľa prekážok na ceste k nim). Tlačová správa <https://todorozum.sk/aktualita/210-malo-materskych-skol-vela-prekazok-na-ceste-k-nim/>

¹¹¹ BANKY,sk. (2018). In Slovakia, we have few kindergartens and many obstacles on the way to them, experts agree. (Na Slovensku máme málo škôlok a veľa prekážok na ceste k nim, zhodujú sa odborníci) <https://banky.sk/na-slovensku-mame-malo-skolok-a-vela-prekazok-na-ceste-k-nim-zhoduju-sa-odbornici/>

¹¹² https://www.stuba.sk/sk/fakulty/ine-pracoviska/mataska-skolka-stubacik.html?page_id=13400

Existence of national programs which promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research

The reference document is the "National Strategy for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic for 2014-2019", which as already mentioned above, in Objective 3 reports: "To improve the application of gender equality in education, science and research" and in particular at point n. 3.4 "To deepen knowledge of existing forms of inequality between women and men by strengthening research in this area and gender statistics".

National/ policies and legal frameworks on sexual/gender harassment in the workplace

The reference document is the Act No. 365/2004 Coll. on "Equal Treatment in Certain Areas and Protection against Discrimination, and on amending and supplementing certain other laws as amended (Antidiscrimination Act)"¹¹³. According to the Act, observance of the equal treatment principle also consists in the adoption of measures to protect against discriminations¹¹⁴.

Also Act no. 311/2001 Coll. Labour Code¹¹⁵ is applicable, which is the basic legislative norm of employment in Slovakia. The main principle enshrined in this legal norm is that natural persons have the right to work and to a free choice of employment, to fair and satisfactory working conditions, and to protection against arbitrary dismissal in accordance with the principle of equal treatment established by a special law in the field of employment relations: "*Equal Treatment in Certain Areas and on Protection against Discrimination and on the Amendment of Certain Acts*" (Anti-Discrimination Act). All workers should enjoy these rights, without any restriction or discrimination on grounds of sex, marital or family status, sexual orientation, race, colour, language, age, adverse health condition or disability, genetic characteristics, creed, religion, political or another opinion, trade union activity, national or social origin, nationality or ethnic group, property, gender or another status, unless the difference in treatment is justified by the nature of the activities pursued in the employment or the circumstances in which those activities are pursued, if that reason constitutes actual and a decisive requirement for employment, provided that the aim is legitimate and the requirement is proportionate.

Women and men have the right to equal treatment as regards access to employment, pay, and promotion, vocational training, and working conditions. Pregnant women, mothers up to the end of the ninth month after childbirth, and breastfeeding women are provided with specific working conditions.

Funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality at national and regional level

The main founding source is represented by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF / ERDF). However, at the time this report is elaborated, no opportunities/calls were identified focusing or taking into account gender equality.

However, other opportunities/calls targeting gender equality coming from other sources were identified. In particular, projects about this issue are addressed under dedicated calls of the Operational Program Human Resources¹¹⁶, within the Priority Axis 3 "Employment"¹¹⁷, such as:

¹¹³ <https://www.slov-lex.sk/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/2004/365/20160102>

¹¹⁴ Discrimination is considered as direct discrimination, indirect discrimination, harassment, sexual harassment and unjustified punishment; discrimination is also seen as instruction to discriminate and incitement to discrimination.

¹¹⁵ Act no. 311/2001 Coll. - Labor Code (Zákon č. 311/2001 Z. z. Zákonník práce) <https://www.slov-lex.sk/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/2001/311/20200404>

¹¹⁶ Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic. (2019a). Operational Program Human Resources (Operačný program Ľudské zdroje). Vyzvanie OP ĽZ NP 2019/3.2.1/02 – Rodová rovnosť na pracovisku. <https://www.employment.gov.sk/files/slovensky/esf/op-ludske-zdroje/vyzvania-2019/vyzvanie-rodova-rovnost-pracovisku.pdf>

¹¹⁷ Investment priority 3.2: "Equality between men and women in all areas, including access to employment, career progress (development, grow), work-life balance and the promotion of equal income for equal work".

Specific objective 3.2.1: "By improving conditions for work-life balance increase the employment of people with parental responsibilities, especially women".

- National projects on the prevention and elimination of gender discrimination
- Call “Advice and education in the field of prevention and elimination of discrimination II”
- Call “Promoting the reconciliation of family and professional life”

4.3.2 The innovation ecosystem context analysis at STU BA

The following table presents the results of the context analysis conducted by STU BA in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Area	Indicator	Results
Talents and workforce education and acquisition	High School and Higher Education students in STEM by gender, at regional and national levels	<p>STEM Higher Education students (year 2019)¹¹⁸</p> <p>■ males ■ females</p>
	Researchers in STEM by gender in R&I, at national and regional levels	<p>STEM researchers in 2018¹¹⁹:</p> <p>■ males ■ females</p>

¹¹⁸ Higher education institutions by group fields of study – universities. The term STEM is not clearly defined in the Slovak Republic, and therefore, the groups of disciplines were used are: 1 Sciences 2, 3 Technical sciences and theory. Source: the Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic, 2020 <http://datacube.statistics.sk/#!/lang/en>

¹¹⁹ Only researches are included (excluding technicians and equivalent staff, support staff). The term STEM is not clearly defined in the Slovak Republic, and therefore, the scientific fields of Natural sciences and Technical sciences were used.

Source: the Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic, 2020 <http://datacube.statistics.sk/#!/lang/en>

	Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender	<p>Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender (2014-2018) ¹²⁰</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Year</th> <th>Males (%)</th> <th>Females (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>2014</td> <td>57.51%</td> <td>42.49%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2015</td> <td>57.81%</td> <td>42.19%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2016</td> <td>58.76%</td> <td>41.24%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2017</td> <td>58.43%</td> <td>41.57%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2018</td> <td>59.21%</td> <td>40.79%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Evolution of employment rate in STEM by gender (2016-2018) ¹²¹</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Year</th> <th>Males (%)</th> <th>Females (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>2016</td> <td>69.29%</td> <td>30.71%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2017</td> <td>68.53%</td> <td>31.47%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2018</td> <td>69.12%</td> <td>30.88%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Year	Males (%)	Females (%)	2014	57.51%	42.49%	2015	57.81%	42.19%	2016	58.76%	41.24%	2017	58.43%	41.57%	2018	59.21%	40.79%	Year	Males (%)	Females (%)	2016	69.29%	30.71%	2017	68.53%	31.47%	2018	69.12%	30.88%
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2018	69.12%	30.88%																														
Leadership	Patents registrations by gender	<p>Patent registration teams</p> <p>Industrial Property Office of the Slovak Republic does not have statistics on patents by gender.</p>																														

¹²⁰ Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic, 2020 <http://datacube.statistics.sk/#!/lang/en>

¹²¹ *ibid.*

	Founders and leaders of innovative enterprises and start-ups by gender	<p style="text-align: center;">Founders and leaders of start-ups by gender. Data of 2016¹²²:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Number of start-ups in 2016: 253¹²³</p>
Knowledge and tech production issues	Level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension	<p>Several projects funded by the Scientific Grant of the Agency of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Slovak Republic and the Slovak Academy of Sciences (3 out of 1250 funded in 2020) are being worked out at universities¹²⁴. In particular, such projects concern:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - „Gender perspectives in political sciences in Slovakia (Faculty of Social and Economic Sciences, Comenius“ University) - „Financial position of the household sector in relation to gender-sensitive budgeting and social inequality“ (Faculty of Economics, EU) - „The gender aspect of mathematical anxiety regarding children of lower classes at schools“ (Faculty of Education, Comenius University). - The Slovak Research and Development Agency financially supports the following projects: - „An approach to gender integration in the research ecosystem through synergies between research“ (PEDAL Consulting, s.r.o.) - „Towards a healthy life of research institutions via the implementation of Gender Equality Plans“ (Alexandra Dubček University in Trenčín) - „Gender Equality Standards for AHMSSBL institutions throughout Europe“ (Faculty of Arts, Comenius University)¹²⁵ <p>An important research activity in relation to gender equality takes place at the Faculty of Philosophy, Comenius University in Bratislava, where since 2001, a Center for Gender Equality exists. This center follows a ten-year tradition of similarly oriented pedagogical and research activities carried out at the Department of Philosophy, Faculty of Arts, Comenius University in cooperation with experts from other disciplines (Comenius University, 2020). Other higher education and research institutes in Slovakia offering courses in the field of</p>

¹²² Steigertahl, L. & Mauer, R. (2018). EU STARTUP MONITOR. 2018 REPORT. <http://startupmonitor.eu/EU-Startup-Monitor-2018-Report-WEB.pdf>

¹²³ Slovak Business Agency. (2018). Analýza start-upov na Slovensku. Strategická časť. http://www.sbagency.sk/sites/default/files/5_analyza_start-upov_na_slovensku.pdf

¹²⁴ Source: Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic. 2020. Rozpis dotácií na nové a pokračujúce projekty VEGA na rok 2020. <https://www.minedu.sk/rozpis-dotacii-na-nove-a-pokracujuce-projekty-vega-na-rok-2020/>

¹²⁵ Slovak Research and Development Agency. (2020). Databáza financovaných projektov. https://www.apvv.sk/databaza-financovanych-projektov.html?select_index=281&order_by=project_demander_foreign-desc

		gender studies are the Faculty of Education and the Faculty of Social and Economic Sciences, Comenius University in Bratislava, and the Faculty of Arts of the University of Prešov. In the academic year 2013/2014, the Faculty of Arts, Pavel Jozef Šafárik University in Košice opened a Gender studies and Culture Bachelor's degree (Glosár rodovej terminológie, 2017 ¹²⁶).
	Level of consideration of the gender dimension in product/service development	The only sector which was found to design products with consideration of the differences between men and women, was the one related to safety clothes and footwear for workers and ergonomics (i.e. personal protective equipment are available in enterprises – gloves sizes, shoe sizes, masks, goggles). In certain businesses, the ergonomics of the workplace are applied to correspond to the anthropometric conditions of people/employees based on their gender (author's own knowledge and experience in teaching the subject of Ergonomics and in research activities regarding Ergonomics) ¹²⁷ .
Broader issues featuring the R&I 'cultures	Gender sensitiveness/family friendliness of supporting services to start up and entrepreneurship	<p>According to a survey conducted in 2017¹²⁸, both women and men agreed on negatively perceiving the support given by the local and national government in terms of entrepreneurship, while as concerns the access to the market no differences are pointed out. Start-up help provided by banks and other investors is well perceived by women, whereas men consider it as insufficient. 4 out of 10 female entrepreneurs reported that they did not receive any sort of assistance when starting up a business. Sources of the little help obtained were mainly coming from their partners. Parents and other family members are also an important source of assistance. Standard forms of assistance (specialized institutions, NGOs, mentors) were used only minimally by female entrepreneurs. Only the 10% of businesswomen have completed entrepreneurial professional courses or training. If they did get training, it was mainly focused on the subjects of the business and accounting.</p> <p>When starting up a business, female entrepreneurs reported encountering mainly obstacles regarding social isolation and access to finance. One out of 5 women also encountered issues of credibility. Based on the survey, it was found that men in the business environment perceive that women bring a significant degree of „emotion“ to the business, which make them feel obstacles in a more intense way. Businesswomen did not consider cultural and social attitudes to be a significant obstacle in their start-ups, despite their negative evaluation rankings. The obstacles perceived at most by women are the tax and levy burden, business legislation, and the overall unfavorable economic situation. Access to finance is not a significant hurdle for Slovak female entrepreneurs. To ease the facilitation of their businesses, women entrepreneurs would most commonly request for an increase in clarity and less frequent changes in business legislation, together with a reduction in taxes and tax burden. Thus, businesswomen, in particular, would generally prefer widespread beneficial conditions rather than selective supporting instruments. Men entrepreneurs require a similar support.</p> <p>Around the 75% of both men and women entrepreneurs claimed they did not have sufficient financial resources at the start of their businesses. Despite that, most of them did not perceive any negative consequence of such shortcoming. Even if they did, it most often regarded a slowdown in the pace of business development and growth. In relation to access to finance in start-ups, women entrepreneurs would welcome more assistance and expert advice regarding the initial business stages (especially financial), planning,</p>

¹²⁶ Glosár rodovej terminológie. (Glossary of Gender Terminology) (2017). Rodové štúdiá. (Gender studies). <http://glosar.aspekt.sk/default.aspx?smi=1&ami=1&vid=176>

¹²⁷ <https://www.employment.gov.sk/sk/praca-zamestnanost/bezpecnost-ochrana-zdravia-pri-praci/>

¹²⁸ A. Pilková (26 - Pilková, A. et al. (2017). Inkluzivita podnikania na Slovensku: stav a vývojové tendencie. Bratislava. Univerzita Komenského v Bratislave, Fakulta managementu: KARTPRINT

		<p>business plan elaboration, as well as with administrative application processing. An analysis of parents' entrepreneurship and the potential success of students in their parents' businesses shows that parents tend to involve more boys than girls in their enterprises¹²⁹.</p> <p>The following projects aiming to support women's entrepreneurship were implemented in Slovakia:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the CrossEUWBA project¹³⁰ (Enhancing the cross-sector emergence of new women business angels across Europe), co-financed by the EU. The project aims to support entrepreneurial women and to facilitate the financing of women's entrepreneurship with the help of business angels (primarily, but not exclusively, women), and thus contribute to promoting private investment in entrepreneurship in Europe. - the SUPPORT OF WOMEN'S BUSINESSES IN SLOVAKIA project¹³¹. - the Women Entrepreneurship Forum project¹³², in which Sloval female entrepreneurs have the opportunity to innovate and improve their business environments under the supervision of well-founded mentors from the USA.
	<p>Perception of existing stereotypes/bias on gender and innovation/ entrepreneurship</p>	<p>With regards to balancing and reconciling family and work life, significant shortcomings and barriers still occur in the Slovak Republic. The most frequently introduced and used measure to reconcile work and family is the adoption of flexible working hours; other measures are largely absent. Due to persistent stereotypes, to a large extent, women in Slovakia remain responsible for childcare or for taking care of other family members. Compared with their growing business role in the world, women need to face a double burden. Many women provide care for their elderly family members without the adequate facilities or services at their disposal¹³³. In Slovakia, a division into typical female (restaurants, hotels, education, recreational services, fashion, etc) and typical male businesses still dominates¹³⁴.</p> <p>Active as well as passive innovation gets manifested mainly in male entrepreneurs, such as the use of modern technologies¹³⁵. Stereotypes about women lacking of entrepreneurial skills, such as self-confidence, managerial skills, assertiveness, and willingness to take risks still prevail, while men are considered better in leading and managing companies (Pilková et al., 2017, Slovak Academy of Sciences, 2018¹³⁶).</p>

Table 6_ Results of the context analysis conducted by STU BA

¹²⁹ Pilková, A. et al. (2017). Inkluzivita podnikania na Slovensku: stav a vývojové tendencie. Bratislava. Univerzita Komenského v Bratislave, Fakulta managementu: KARTPRINT. ISBN 978-80-223-4442-5. <http://www.cem-uk.sk/uni-magazin/publikovali/inkluzivita-podnikania-na-slovensku-stav-a-vyvojove-tendencie/?IDe=47088&IDcheck=6c7b200f446aee176f105e03654ec46f>

¹³⁰ Slovak Business Agency. (2020a). Výzva na zapojenie sa do medzinárodného projektu CrossEUWBA. http://www.sbagency.sk/vyzva-na-zapojenie-sa-do-medzinarodneho-projektu-crosseuwbawba#Xzr_HOgzZPZ

¹³¹ Slovak Business Agency. (2020b). Podpora podnikania žien na Slovensku. <http://www.sbagency.sk/podpora-podnikania-zien-na-slovensku>

¹³² Ambasadorka. (2014). WEF <http://www.ambasadorka.sk/realizovane-projekty/wef/>

¹³³ Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic. (2014a). National Strategy for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic for 2014-2019" (Celoštátna stratégia rodovej rovnosti v Slovenskej republike na roky 2014-2019). <https://www.gender.gov.sk/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Strategia-RR.pdf>

¹³⁴ Pilková, A. et al. (2017). Inkluzivita podnikania na Slovensku: stav a vývojové tendencie. Bratislava. Univerzita Komenského v Bratislave, Fakulta managementu: KARTPRINT. ISBN 978-80-223-4442-5. <http://www.cem-uk.sk/uni-magazin/publikovali/inkluzivita-podnikania-na-slovensku-stav-a-vyvojove-tendencie/?IDe=47088&IDcheck=6c7b200f446aee176f105e03654ec46f>

¹³⁵ Pilková, A. et al., (2016). Komerčné, sociálne a inkluzívne podnikanie na Slovensku. Bratislava. Univerzita Komenského v Bratislave, Fakulta managementu: KARTPRINT. ISBN 978-80-223-4230-8. https://www.fm.uniba.sk/fileadmin/fm/Veda/projekty/GEM_2015_kniha.pdf

¹³⁶ Slovak Academy of Sciences. (2018). Na Slovensku stále prevláda tradičný rodový stereotyp. https://www.sav.sk/index.php?doc=services-news&source_no=20&news_no=7464/7464

4.3.3 STU BA Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA

Results of the focus group with internal stakeholders

At STU BA, the **focus group** took place in Trnava on the 28th September 2020 and involved 6 internal stakeholders (2 males and 4 females), covering the following positions: researchers, technology transfer managers and mid-level managers.

About the existing or prospective collaborations on broader areas with stakeholders, participants reported that within the MTF STU, cooperation take place at two levels: at the faculty level and at the overall institute level. A concrete example of collaboration is represented by the MTF STU Industrial Council¹³⁷, which mission is a deeper connection of the faculty with the industrial enterprises and the creation of a platform for joint solutions of strategic cooperation between academia and industry, by involving major companies and organizations of the Trnava Self-governing region (TTSK).

Generally speaking, cooperation is based, on the professional side, on providing teaching and consultation to students in professional practice and final theses. At the level of participation and joint solution of projects, instead, collaboration focuses on the creation of various professional and advisory boards and bodies, as well as teaching activities.

About the ways gender inequalities are perceived as a **challenge for the external stakeholders**, participants reported that gender inequality, generally speaking, is not perceived as an issue in Slovakia. However, the Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic reports the existence of gender inequalities on the basis of the periodic evaluation of the average wages in the industrial sector divided per gender. In addition, gender inequalities are starting to be perceived at the level of large corporations, where the topic is faced. Such issue is also starting to be added to other values of intellectual capital within enterprises and other institutions in other spheres of the national economy. There is undeniable potential in the growth of values and awareness by companies, which can have benefits in terms of human values and quality of life for the whole society. According to participants, the issue of gender equality should be addressed from the initial stages of the educational process and thus become taken into consideration in everyday life.

Concerning **actions** put in place to address gender equality, participants reported that according to their knowledge, stakeholders are aware of the issue and have identified the need to address it, as well as the willingness to engage in the change process. Participants explained that STU BA will involve stakeholders in in research activities and data collection connected to the CALIPER project, inviting them to cooperate, participate in workshops etc. Also, it was highlighted that some companies do not perceive having a problem with gender inequalities. However, they expressed the interest in taking a new perspective and motivation to improve the quality of their internal environment, and improving their own image outside.

About **complementarities and synergies** with STU BA, participants pointed out that being gender equality not directly addressed within the internal culture of external stakeholders, it is difficult to create new synergies with them around this area.

With reference of **risks** related to collaboration, participants see as a risk the current situation featured by the **COVID-19** spread, since the virus has reassessed the priorities for stakeholders, which are primarily focused on maintaining their market position and their employees. It is not possible to predict when the situation will be back to normal and stakeholders will be able to focus again on gender in their internal processes.

¹³⁷ https://www.mtf.stuba.sk/sk/diani-na-mtf/aktuality/zasadnutie-novokreenej-priemyselnej-rady-mtf-stu.html?page_id=15153

During the focus group participants identified the followings as external stakeholders to involve in the R&I Hubs:

- TTSK Trnava - Trnava Self- governing region
- Mesto Trnava – City Trnava
- SPU Nitra – Slovak University of Agriculture Nitra
- UKF Nitra – Constantine The Philosopher University in Nitra
- FPEDAS Zilina - University of Zilina, Faculty of Operation and Economics of Transport and
- SAV – Slovak Academy of Science
- FPT TNUNI Puchov - Faculty of Industrial Technologies in Púchov
- FGERG - EIT Raw materials Hub - EIT RawMaterials Hub – Regional Center Kosice
- FVT Presov TU Kosice - ACULTY OF MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGIES
- of the Technical University of Košice with the seat in Prešov
- UCM - University of Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Trnava
- UGaK - Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastre Authority of the Slovak Republic
- VÚB Leasing
- Ministerstvo práce a soc.vecí a rodiny - The Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic

Results of the survey to external stakeholders

STU BA submitted the survey to 23 external stakeholders, 16 of them participated. Overall 20 responses we collected (some stakeholders filled the survey more than once). STU BA also conducted 7 interviews with representatives of companies and of a regional public institution posing the same questions of the survey. The answers provided during the interviews will be jointly analysed with the results of the survey.

Concerning the kind of stakeholders participating 9 were universities/faculties, 5 companies and 3 public institutions.

About the kind of **collaborations already in place** with MTF STU, universities/faculties reported that they are mainly related to:

- Pedagogical activities
- Participation of teachers in commissions for state final examinations, dissertations or qualifications
- Inauguration proceedings
- Publications
- Participation in scientific conferences
- Projects related to gender equality or other projects within H2020
- Exchange of experiences

Collaborations with companies instead refer to consultation and education projects (for instance related to students' Bachelor's and Master's theses), organization of the summer children's camp within the "Automobile Academy"¹³⁸. A company are part of the Industrial Innovative Cluster¹³⁹. Some companies did not report any collaborations in place.

One of the two public entities involved has in place a collaboration related to environmental analysis, another reported having a cooperation on pedagogical activities, participation in domestic and international conferences and in projects, while the other did not report any.

¹³⁸ <https://ajakademia.sk/>

¹³⁹ <https://www.industryinnovationcluster.sk/>; <https://www.zapsr.sk/>

About the way gender equality represents a **challenge** for their own organizations, some universities/faculties reported that at their institution gender equality is a priority and it is respected, both in management positions and other job positions (professors and administrative staff), since both genders are represented and there is no difference in salary conditions. Others claim that at the university (not faculty) level there is a big issue in terms of gender discrimination (especially from the female employees side) and the challenge is represented by the fact that there is resistance among the university staff in the promotion of this agenda, since people feel that “there are no gender issues” at the university, so it is not necessary to address the topic. Some universities report the need of keeping on addressing gender equality also in the evaluation procedures of students and staff in order to take the performance and the achievements into consideration and not the gender and guarantee equal opportunities for women at all levels of work and in their social and private life. In addition some universities pointed out the need of raising the involvement of women in scientific research. Companies, in general, reported not having issues regarding gender equality since they have both men and women covering all roles, also at managerial level. The same was reported by one of the public institution, while another claimed the challenge is related to the equality of work performance.

Concerning **potential benefits** in solving the mentioned challenges, universities/faculties reported that addressing gender equality / inequality in the workplace always means improving working conditions for both women and men and increasing the work (academic) culture. Other benefits identified are the following:

- To have a more balance representation of men and women in leading positions helps in having a different approach to management, to “softer” the communication and take more into account employed mothers needs
- A more balanced view about current issues
- Diverse working teams work better
- The same level of recognition in terms of performances
- More success in technical projects
- A more just environment ensure that everyone, regardless of gender, can engage in the activities they prefer
- A higher rate of women increases the attractiveness of studying STEM subjects by women
- Equal salaries.

Companies, instead, reported as benefits a better setting of responsibilities and tasks of employees and a better coordination of the work, as well as a greater use of the potential of women and men in the work activities. Others again stressed not having problem related to gender equality. One of the three public institutions instead identified a more consistency between performance and evaluation as benefit, while another one reported that gender equality in job positions leads to the application of the principle of equal treatment of individuals in all the different spheres: wages, social benefits, etc.

Moving to the **actions/measures** already in place in order to overcome gender inequalities, some universities/faculties reported not having dedicated measures already in place at the university level, but having implemented gender fair processes at the faculty level. Other still reported not having measures in place but being willing to introduce some (for instance a “code of ethics”). An university explained that thanks to the acquisition of the HR Excellence in Research label, the University also has the task of creating a Gender Action Plan. In order to support the plan, they set up a Working Group, which was however suspended due to the Coronavirus crisis. They are planning to organize focus groups, an online survey and then draft an action plan for a university-wide debate, with the aim of having the GAP by 2021. Another university implemented a gender equality plan containing various types of activities thanks to an international project and is leading the “My TOP Scientist Competition”. Other respondents reported not being aware of any measures. No ad hoc measures were reported by companies filling the survey, with some of them stressing they do not need any measure. One of the two public institutions answered having specific measures but did not explicit which kind of measures, while another one reported having implemented the “Smart Region TTSK project” which also deals with human resources management for improving the principle of gender equality.

About **potential actions/measures** to adopt, some universities/faculties explained being willing to take measures to ensure gender equality, for instance to be incorporated in internal documents, others reported not feeling the need of implementing further measures since gender equality is already present within their own organizations or internal formal documents fighting gender inequalities already exist. Others just reported not being aware of it. Some companies would keep on with the existing measures or implement additional activities, others feel there is no need to apply any measures since men and women already have the same rights and conditions about performance in their work. Only one public institution answered to this question by mentioning as possible activities the improvement of the management of quality processes which take into account the expertise of the individual and foster the development of human resources on the basis of the acquired professional experiences, skills and knowledges.

Concerning the stakeholders interest in continuing to **cooperate with MTS STU** in order to overcome gender inequalities, universities/faculties would continue cooperating on the topic through publications, sharing of experiences, mutual cooperation on other projects and research in gender mainstreaming, training for young students and researchers, organization of events, join forces in order to put pressure at the Senate level but also at the Ministry of Education and grant agencies level about the importance to address the topic. Companies did not provide any relevant feedback on this aspect. While one of the public institutions explained being interested especially in the area of research, development and innovation.

Concerning the possible **risks** coming from the collaboration, all universities/faculties and companies reported not being aware of any, while of the public institutions involved, one mentioned as risk the difference between vision and practice and another one reported investments risks, managerial risks, organizational risks and technical risks.

Results of the SNA

The mapping of external stakeholders for the SNA took place at the premises of the Faculty of Materials Science and Technology in Trnava (MTF STU BA), which is directly involved in the CALIPER project as part of the Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava. STU BA is one of the largest universities in Slovakia and consists of seven faculties (including MTF STU BA) and another university, therefore creating an extremely large number of working relationships and cooperation.

The applied procedure consisted of a desk research by using the Academic Information System (AIS), which contains the information required for the SNAs. The system gather the information about the activities of two departments: the Department of Knowledge Management (at the level of national cooperation) and the Department of International Cooperation. The activities of the departments are ongoing and new information is added based on their findings and availability. In this system, information is recorded with the forms of contractual cooperation, solved projects, project work teams, solution time, etc. The second phase of the process consisted in finding out web pages of stakeholders in order to gather additional information. As final step, interviews were conducted with some institutions.

Overall **33 external stakeholders** were included in the mapping. The majority of collaborations are with “academia & universities” stakeholders (20, representing the 61%), followed by “industry & business” stakeholders (6, representing the 18%), “government & public sector” stakeholders (6, representing the 18%) and “civil society” stakeholders (1, representing the 3%). The form of cooperation takes various forms. The primary approach to cooperation with universities is cooperation at the level of teaching in the form of mutual exchange of pedagogical or research staff and their participation in final state exams, final theses, as well as the performance of guest lectures. The second form of cooperation is the participation in projects within interdepartmental teams.

It is worth to mention that National projects are funded by two kinds of funds. The first one is represented by the national grant agencies operated by the Ministry of Education of the Slovak Republic. The second

source are the industrial enterprises, which fund universities in order to conduct dedicated research over a specific topic („transfer of knowledge“).

About the **intensity** of collaborations with external stakeholders, most of them (22 out of 33, representing the 67%) are “solid” collaborations (more than 3 projects), 9 are “one time” collaborations and 2 “frequent” collaborations. Among “solid” collaborations, 13 are with “academia & universities” stakeholders, 5 with “government & public sector” stakeholders, 2 with “industry & business” stakeholders and 1 with the “civil society”.

Concerning the **topic** of the collaborations, many of them (12 out of 33, representing the 36%) are about “education”, 10 about “scientific research”, 5 about “science communication”, 4 are about “raising awareness” and 2 about “transfer to market”.

Overall, **24 collaborations are led by women** (representing 72% of the total) on the side of MTF STU BA. Such collaborations mainly concern the implementation of specific research projects.

The majority of the collaborations led by women (13 out of 24, 54%) are collaborations with “academia & universities” stakeholders, 6 with “industry & business” stakeholders (25%), 4 with “government & public sector” stakeholders (17%), and 1 with “civil society” (4%). It is worth to point out that the **all collaborations with “industry & business” stakeholders are led by women** (6 out of 6).

No project until 2020 focused on the content of gender equality. Gender equality is only taken into account in one project¹⁴⁰ related to the involvement of girls between 12 and 15 years old into STEM subjects and their enrollment in STEM school.

The following pictures represent the results of the SNA conducted by the Faculty of Materials Science and Technology in Trnava (MTF STU BA) according to the kind of stakeholders. Therefore, 4 different maps are displayed, one for each category of stakeholders: “academia & university”, “industry & business”, “government & public sector” and “civil society”. No collaborations with schools were included.

Per each map it is possible to identify the collaborations having female leaderships (the yellow nodes). As already mentioned, no collaborations focusing or taking into account gender were registered.

¹⁴⁰ The JUNIOR Automobile Academy <https://ajakademia.sk/>

Figure 10_MTF STU BA collaborations with "Academia & University" stakeholders

Figure 11_MTF STU BA collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders

Figure 12_MTF STU BA collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders

Figure 13_MTF STU BA collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

4.3.4 Final remarks on the external assessment of STU BA

In the Slovak Republic, the principle of equal treatment and the prohibition of discrimination based on sex, gender or other status are addressed at national level. **Women and men have the right to equal treatment as regards access to employment, pay, and promotion, vocational training, and working conditions.** However, **no specific provisions are foreseen for what concerns the area of Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation.** The improvement of the application of gender equality in education, science and research is anyway a priority for the Slovakian government and it is states in the national strategies and action plans in which objectives such as the increase of representation of women in decision-making positions and the promotion and support of women's entrepreneurship are pursued.

Pregnant women, mothers up to the end of the ninth month after childbirth, and breastfeeding women are provided with working conditions that protect their biological condition in connection with pregnancy, childbirth, childcare after childbirth, and their special relationship with the child after childbirth. In order to support a more balanced division of responsibilities for the family households and a greater involvement of fathers in childcare, the paternity leave was introduced, while in terms of childcare facilities, a lack of capacity of kindergartens is registered, generating negative effects in terms of equality. In general, **measures for balancing and reconciling family and work life are considered as not sufficient, since significant shortcomings and barriers still occur in the Slovak Republic.** Indeed, due to persistent stereotypes (e.g. lack of entrepreneurial skills, such as self-confidence, managerial skills, assertiveness, and willingness to take risks), women in Slovakia remain responsible for childcare or for taking care of other family members. As far as female entrepreneurship is concerned, many obstacles are faced by women and the support provided by the local and national government is perceived as insufficient, also in terms of financial sources.

Concerning the collected data, a great imbalance is visible concerning both STEM higher education students and researchers (the female share is around the 30% in both cases). Also, the evolution of employment rate in R&I even if higher than the EU average, is not very encouraging, and registers a decrease of the female share in the 2014-2018 time frame (from the 42,49% to 40,79%). Female funders of start-ups are a minority with respect to males (23,50%). **The integration of gender as a scientific research dimension** only happens at the moment through dedicated projects funded at national level and research activities, but **an overall strategy is still missing.**

Concerning the analysis of the collaborations in place with external stakeholders, at STU BA collaborations take place at two levels: at the faculty level and at the overall institute level.

About the ways gender inequalities are perceived as a **challenge for the external stakeholders**, it resulted that many stakeholders do not perceive gender inequalities as an issue in Slovakia. Different is the approach of other universities which, instead, claim that gender inequalities are a priority for their own organizations and they are visible both at the structural side and in the involvement of female students. Some of them reported **resistances** from the internal staff in addressing the issue. Only a couple of stakeholders reported having implemented some measures (GEPs). Stakeholders are willing to keep the cooperation with STU BA on the topic through publications, sharing of experiences, mutual cooperation on other projects and research in gender mainstreaming, training for young students and researchers, organization of events, as well as joint collaboration for involving the Ministry of Education and grant agencies.

The SNA resulted with the identification of 33 external stakeholders, the majority of them belonging to the "academia & universities" sector. Overall, the majority of **collaborations are led by women (24)** on the side of MTF STU BA, and the totality of those with industry/business sectors. Such collaborations mainly concern the implementation of projects. No collaborations focusing or taking into account gender were identified.

4.4 External assessment of ULB

4.4.1 The Belgian national legal and policy framework

Overall strategic gender equality policies at national level

In Belgium, there are different laws promoting gender equality at federal and regional level. In particular:

- Law n. 2007002011 of the 12th January 2007¹⁴¹ aimed at monitoring the implementation of the resolutions of the World Conference on Women held in Beijing in September 1995 and integrating the gender dimension into all federal policies; in particular, the integration of the gender dimension into all policies, measures, budget preparations or actions, with a focus on avoiding or correcting possible inequalities between women and men. For this purpose, at the beginning of a new legislature, the new government shall present the strategic objectives it intends to achieve during the legislature for all the pursued policies.
- Order of the Walloon Government of the 10th July 2003 establishing a Walloon Council for Equality between Men and Women.
- Circular of the 17th June 2013 on “Research and prosecution policy on discrimination and hate crimes (including discrimination based on sex)”. In the Circular it appears that: the legislation on discrimination and hate crimes is not always clear in practice and is not always correctly applied; collaboration between the public prosecutor's office, the police and/or the social inspection services can be improved; collaboration with institutional stakeholders must be developed, first and foremost with the CEOOR and the IEFH; judgments and statistical data are not always transmitted to institutional stakeholders; the recording of discrimination and hate crimes must be improved.
- Decree n. 2008204573 of the 6th November 2008¹⁴² on the “Fight against certain forms of discrimination, including discrimination between women and men in the economy, employment and professional training “.

Existence of specific mechanisms to promote the under- represented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation at national or regional level

The following provisions/initiatives can be mentioned:

¹⁴¹ Law n° 2007002011 of 12 January 2007 «Loi visant au contrôle de l'application des résolutions de la conférence mondiale sur les femmes réunie à Pékin en septembre 1995 et intégrant la dimension du genre dans l'ensemble des politiques fédérales» (Published 13 February 2007).

¹⁴² Decree n°2008204573 on 6 November 2008 «Décret relatif à la lutte contre certaines formes de discrimination, en ce compris la discrimination, entre les femmes et les hommes en matière d'économie, d'emploi et de formation professionnelle (1)» (Published 19 December 2008).

- Royal Decree n. 2003027712 of the 27th February 1990¹⁴³ on measures for the promotion of equal opportunities between men and women in the public services.
- Royal Decree of the 29th June 1983¹⁴⁴ on equal treatment between men and women as regards access to vocational training in educational establishments. It does not concern university studies but vocational training (e.g. economic conversion/reorientation).
- Royal Decree of the 15th February 1980¹⁴⁵ establishing an Education Commission to guarantee the equal roles of men and women in society. The Commission's mission is to give opinions, carry out studies or propose legal or regulatory measures in all matters directly or indirectly concerning the equalization of opportunities for boys and girls in all study directions and at all levels of education.
- Order n. 2002/838bis of the College of the French Community Commission of the Brussels-Capital Region of 27 May 2004 on the protection against violence and moral or sexual harassment at work for teaching and related staff and for staff of psycho-medico-social centres.
- Actiris¹⁴⁶ has a "diversity" label¹⁴⁷ and can help companies to set up an anti-discrimination plan.
- As part of its commitment to gender equality, the Board of Directors of the F.R.S.-FNRS (Le Fonds de la Recherche Scientifique)¹⁴⁸ recently decided that the Fund would financially participate in the AcademiaNet project "The Portal of Excellent Women Academics", a web portal edited under the aegis of the SNF Switzerland and which consists in an online database containing the profiles of high-level women researchers from all scientific disciplines¹⁴⁹.
- International Day of Women and Girls in Science (FNRS)¹⁵⁰
- The "Guidelines for integrity in scientific research" provided by FNRS¹⁵¹. Examples of breaches of the scientific integrity are: deliberately omitting the names of project collaborators who have made essential contributions to the project; mentioning, without his/her agreement, a person as a co-author regardless of their contribution to the project.

Existence of national policies on implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees

The existing policies for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees are:

¹⁴³ Royal decree n°2003027712 on 27 February 1990 « Arrêté royal portant des mesures en vue de la promotion de l'égalité de chances entre les hommes et les femmes dans les services publics »

¹⁴⁴ Royal decree on 29 June 1983 « Arrêté royal du 29 juin 1983 relatif à l'égalité de traitement entre les hommes et les femmes en ce qui concerne l'accès à la formation professionnelle dispensée dans les établissements d'enseignement, pris en exécution des articles 124 et 125 de la loi du 4 août 1978 de réorientation économique. » (Published 29 August 1983).

¹⁴⁵ Royal decree on 15 February 1980 « Arrêté royal 15 février 1980 portant création d'une Commission de l'enseignement pour la garantie de l'égalité des rôles des hommes et des femmes dans la société » (Published 26 February 1980).

¹⁴⁶ Actiris is the Brussels Regional Job Agency.

¹⁴⁷ see the list of companies that have been awarded this label <https://www.actiris.brussels/fr/employeurs/label-diversite/>

¹⁴⁸ <https://www.frs-fnrs.be/fr/>

¹⁴⁹ According to the FNRS Gender equality report of 2018, promoting gender equality requires the implementation of a diverse range of actions and measures, including actions aimed at improving the visibility of women researchers.

¹⁵⁰ <https://www.frs-fnrs.be/en/prix-mecenats/grants/l-oreal-unesco-for-women-in-science>

¹⁵¹ FNRS (2020), Directives relatives à l'intégrité dans la recherche scientifique, Fonds de la Recherche Scientifique – FNRS.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

- Royal Decree n. 2012002027 on the 2nd of June 2012, which amended the Royal Decree of the 2nd October 1937 on the status of public servants. Also, laws promoting gender equality in federal and regional advisory bodies exist. Indeed, at the beginning of 2012, in the federal public services and public programming services, only the 13% of managers and the 27% of staff appointed in classes A3, A4 and A5 were women, showing a great inequality. The decree gradually introduced a two-thirds quota per public service belonging to the federal administrative civil service.
- Law of the 28th July 2011 aimed at guaranteeing the presence of women on the boards of directors of autonomous public companies, listed companies and the National Lottery. It introduces, for all board members, a quota of at least one third of members of the least well represented sex (within six years for very large companies, eight years for small and medium-sized enterprises-SMEs and without delay for public companies). In the event of non-compliance with these provisions, penalties are provided.
- Law of the 24th May 1994¹⁵² to promote a balanced distribution of men and women on the lists of candidates for elections.
- Decree of the Walloon Government of the 9th January 2014 intended to promote a balanced representation of women and men on the boards of directors of private bodies approved by the Walloon Region.
- According to the IEFH 's report "Femmes au sommet – Recommandations" ("Women at the top")¹⁵³, *"Nobody likes quotas, but nobody can deny their immediate effect. In this sense, quotas are considered as the most effective way to fix under-representation and the measures offering sufficient guarantees of results. The progress made over the past decades in women's political representation would not have been possible without a quota system according to IEFH. Therefore, it seems obvious that the introduction of quotas should be considered also in other areas, especially where progress in gender equality is insufficient or even non-existent [...] We have received many requests to update this brochure. This proves that this information is important for many people directly or indirectly affected by the policy. It is therefore strongly recommended to systematically and regularly update these data. Figures on the presence of women on boards of directors and in company management require considerable research work. In order to enable their systematic monitoring, the data should be reported in a different way. These statistics could be published annually by the National Bank"*.
- Recommendations of the IEFH "Establishing a guaranteed presence of women in the decision-making bodies of commercial companies and public enterprises"¹⁵⁴ about which quota or how many. According to the recommendations, a representation of at least 30% is the sociological threshold that seems to be the consensus in order to set in motion an irreversible equality dynamic. The Institute for the Equality of Women and Men believes that it is up to the legislator to determine the modalities, in consultation with the partners concerned and taking into account their progress.

¹⁵² Law on 24 May 1994 «Loi du 24 mai 1994 visant à promouvoir une répartition équilibrée des hommes et des femmes sur les listes de candidatures aux élections» (Published 1 July 1994).

¹⁵³ IEFH (2020), Femmes au sommet – Recommandations, Institut pour l'égalité des hommes et des femmes. https://igvm-iefh.belgium.be/fr/avis_et_recommandations/femmes_au_sommet

¹⁵⁴ IEFH (2011), Instauration d'une présence garantie de femmes au sein des organes de décision des sociétés commerciales et des entreprises publiques, Institut pour l'égalité des hommes et des femmes.

Existence of national legislation promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment

The provisions to take into consideration are the followings:

- Law n° 2007002098 of the 10th May 2007 "Law to combat certain forms of discrimination"¹⁵⁵. It refers to discrimination based on age, sexual orientation, civil status, birth, wealth, religious or philosophical conviction, political conviction, language, current or future state of health, disability, physical or genetic characteristic, social origin but not explicitly on gender. The law protects a person when he or she files a complaint about discrimination in the workplace (protection against unfair dismissal for example) and defines sanctions and penalties against harassers and people who discriminate. In case of harassment, it is the harasser who must prove that he/she is not harassing.
- Law n° 2007002098 of the 10th May 2007 "Law to combat discrimination between women and men"¹⁵⁶. It refers to discrimination on the basis of gender.
- Act of the 22nd May 2014. It amended the Act of the 10th May 2007 about discrimination between women and men, with the purpose of extending the protection to gender identity and gender expression.
- Law n° 2012204357 of the 22nd April 2012¹⁵⁷ to fight the pay gap between men and women. Every two years, the employer of a company employing on average at least fifty workers has to carry out a detailed analysis of the pay structure within the company to determine whether the company pursues a gender-neutral pay policy and, if not, to achieve this in consultation with the staff delegation.

Existing policies at national level for reducing unequal gender division of labor related to housework and family care

National policies are included in:

- Law of the 10th May 2007 "Law to combat discrimination between women and men"¹⁵⁸. It mentions maternity, paternity, co-maternity (for lesbian couples) and the term "head of family" and "dependant". A direct distinction based on pregnancy, childbirth and maternity is assimilated to a direct distinction based on sex. The Act was amended by the Law n° 2014000613 of the 22nd May 2014¹⁵⁹ and the n. 2020020361 of the 4th February 2020¹⁶⁰.
- Royal Decree of 20 July 1971¹⁶¹ instituting compensation and maternity insurance for self-employed workers and assisting spouses.
- Collective Labour Agreement No. 64 of 29 April 1997 of the National Labour Council¹⁶² establishing a right to parental leave: both the father and the mother may make use of this right. The same applies to adoptive fathers and mothers.

There is a lot of discussion going on about legal provisions for part-time work, parental leave, but no measures to better share the parental burden exist.

¹⁵⁵ Law n°2007002099 on 10 May 2007 « Loi tendant à lutter contre certaines formes de <discrimination> » (Published 30 May 2007).

¹⁵⁶ Law n° 2007002098 on 10 May 2007 «Loi tendant à lutter contre la discrimination entre les femmes et les hommes » (Published 30 May 2007).

¹⁵⁷ Law n° 2012204357 on 22 April 2012 « Loi visant à lutter contre l'écart salarial entre hommes et femmes (1)» (Published 28 August 2012).

¹⁵⁸ See reference n. 155

¹⁵⁹ Law n° 2014000613 on 22 May 2014 «Loi modifiant la loi du 10 mai 2007 tendant à lutter contre la <discrimination> entre les femmes et les <hommes> en vue de l'étendre à l'identité de genre et l'expression de genre » (Published 24 July 2014).

¹⁶⁰ Law n° 2020020361 on 4 February 2020 «Loi modifiant la loi du 10 mai 2007 modifiant, en ce qui concerne l'interdiction de discrimination relative à la paternité ou à la comaternité, la loi du 10 mai 2007 tendant à lutter contre la discrimination entre les femmes et les hommes (1)» (Published 28 February 2020).

¹⁶¹ Royal decree on 1 July 1971 «Arrêté royal instituant une assurance indemnités et une assurance maternité en faveur des travailleurs indépendants et des conjoints aidants.» (Published 7 August 1971).

¹⁶² Convention collective de travail n° 64 du 29 avril 1997 du Conseil national du Travail instituant un droit au congé parental.

According to the Belspo report, Belgium's policy on work-life balance was originally implemented through a system called "career break". The aim of this system is to reduce unemployment by sharing available jobs. It is designed to encourage the temporary withdrawal of women from the labour market. The Directive 2010/18/UE¹⁶³ focuses on two rights: the right to leave for at least three months to take care of a child (born or adopted) up to the age of eight, and the right to leave in cases of force majeure for urgent family reasons.

Following the IEFH's report on paternity leave¹⁶⁴, it is not only male workers in the private or public sectors who want to be involved in childcare. This equally applies to the self-employed fathers. However, in case self-employed fathers take paternity leave after the birth of a baby, they do not receive any benefits and therefore suffer a pay loss. Unemployed fathers are not entitled to paternity leave either, unlike pregnant women looking for work, who are entitled to maternity leave. Also, unemployed persons may have problems in attending an interview, selection or recruitment tests, in the days following the birth of a child. A change in the mentioned rules, for instance recognising paternity leave for all fathers, would improve the involvement of fathers in childcare and permit a better sharing of tasks between mothers and fathers.

The Institute for the Equality of Women and Men recommends prohibiting direct and indirect discrimination (i.e. less favourable treatment) based on family responsibilities. Greater protection for workers with family responsibilities would enable Belgium to comply with ILO Convention n. 156 and to fill certain gaps in the fight against discrimination, particularly with regard to responsibilities towards other family members. This initiative would help to remove certain obstacles to the balance between family life and work and to change mentalities towards greater equality. Indeed, the Institute regularly receives reports of people who encounter difficulties in their work because of their family responsibilities. Examples include the dismissal of a female worker shortly after she had applied for part-time work, in order to care for her seriously ill mother, or the difficulties encountered by a man who no longer can work overtime in order to pick up his children after school. The Institute recommends that a new criterion protecting against discrimination in relation to family responsibilities should be incorporated into Belgian legislation. The Act of the 10th May 2007 already prohibits discrimination based on the "protected criteria" of sex, pregnancy, childbirth, maternity, sex reassignment and gender identity.

Existing framework conditions regarding childcare facilities

According to the Belspo report, in Belgium, at the beginning of the 1970s, it was decided to devote part of the bonuses coming from the family allowance budget as subsidy for the costs of childcare for the workers' children. This measure was aimed at reducing inequalities on the labour market, of which mothers were the main victims.

Employment conditions at university and research organization

According to the European Charter for Researchers - The Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers (FNRS, 2005):

- Funders or employers of researchers should be responsible, as recruiters, for providing researchers with selection and recruitment procedures that are open, transparent and internationally comparable.

¹⁶³ Directive 2010/18/UE du Conseil portant application de l'accord-cadre révisé sur le congé parental conclu par BUSINESSSEUROPE, l'UEAPME, le CEEP et la CES et abrogeant la directive 96/34/CE

¹⁶⁴ IEHF (2020), ongé de paternité en Belgique : l'expérience des travailleurs - Recommandations, Institut pour l'égalité des hommes et des femmes.

- Employers and/or funders of researchers shall not discriminate between researchers on grounds of sex, age, ethnic, national or social origin, religion or belief, sexual orientation, language, disability, political opinion, social or economic status.
- Employers and/or funders should aim to achieve a representative gender balance at all levels of staff, including at the level of thesis/internship supervisors and managers. This balance should be achieved through a policy of equal opportunities at the time of recruitment and at later career stages, but should not override quality and competence criteria. In order to ensure equal treatment, selection and evaluation committees should reflect an adequate gender balance (See SEC (2005) 260, Women and Science: Excellence and Innovation - Gender Equality in Science).
- Employers and/or funders should ensure that entry and admission standards for researchers are clearly specified, particularly at the beginning of their careers, and should also facilitate access for disadvantaged groups or researchers returning to a research career, including teachers (at any level) returning to a research career. Employers and/or funders should adhere to the principles set out in the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers when appointing or recruiting researchers.
- Selection committees should bring together diverse expertise and skills, reflect an adequate gender balance and, where necessary and possible, include members from different sectors (public and private) and disciplines, including from other countries, and with appropriate experience to assess the candidate. As far as possible, a wide range of selection practices should be used, such as evaluation by external experts and face-to-face interviews. Selection committee members should be properly trained.

Existence of national programs which promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research

No programs of this kind exist.

National policies and legal frameworks on sexual/gender harassment in the workplace

National provisions on sexual/gender harassment in the workplace are:

- The Law 2007002098, of the 10th May 2007 "Act to combat discrimination between women and men in the workplace". In the event of harassment, it is the harasser who must prove that he/she was not harassing.
- Order 2002/838bis of the College of the French Community Commission of the Brussels-Capital Region of the 27th May 2004 on protection against violence and moral or sexual harassment at work for teachers and similar staff and for staff of psycho-medico-social centers.

Funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality at national and regional level

Worth to mention is the "Germaine Tillion" call¹⁶⁵ (no gender-specific), which is the Walloon call for social innovation, which funds innovative actions which contribute to the development of new approaches, skills, and the adaptation of employment and training systems. Topics may cover the following areas: work organisation, corporate governance, adjustments to the productive processes, new production channels, new ways of working (teleworking, entrepreneurial design, etc.) and end-of-career management.

¹⁶⁵ <https://recherche-technologie.wallonie.be/fr/menu/acteurs-institutionnels/service-public-de-wallonie-services-en-charge-de-la-recherche-et-des-technologies/departement-de-la-recherche-et-du-developpement-technologique/direction-des-programmes-de-recherche/programmes-clotures/les-programmes-mobilisateurs/l-appel-germaine-tillion/germaine-tillion-appel.html>

4.4.2 The innovation ecosystem context analysis at ULB

The following table presents the results of the context analysis conducted by ULB in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Area	Indicator	Results
Talents and workforce education and acquisition	High School and Higher Education students in STEM by gender, at regional and national levels	<p>STEM students in FWB¹⁶⁶ (2015/2016)¹⁶⁷</p> <p>34% 66%</p> <p>■ males ■ females</p>
	High School and Higher Education students in STEM by gender, at regional and national levels	<p>STEM students in the Flanders (2019/2020)¹⁶⁸</p> <p>37% 63%</p> <p>■ males ■ females</p>
	Researchers in STEM by gender in R&I, at national and regional levels	<p>STEM researchers in Belgium in 2015¹⁶⁹:</p> <p>34% 66%</p> <p>■ males ■ females</p>

¹⁶⁶ Wallonia-Brussels Federation (FWB)

¹⁶⁷ Statistics of 2015-2016 of the CREF <http://www.cref.be/annuaire/2016/>

¹⁶⁸ Statistics from 2019-2020 of the Flanders region <https://www.vlaanderen.be/publicaties/hoger-onderwijs-in-cijfers>

¹⁶⁹ Eurostat data for 2015 https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/R_%26_D_personnel#Researchers

	Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender	<p style="text-align: center;">Evolution of the Employment rate in the ICT sector in Belgium. Data 2013-2017¹⁷⁰:</p> <table border="1" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Year</th> <th>Males (%)</th> <th>Females (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>2013</td> <td>84.50%</td> <td>15.50%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2014</td> <td>84.82%</td> <td>15.18%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2015</td> <td>84.85%</td> <td>15.15%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2016</td> <td>85.92%</td> <td>14.08%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2017</td> <td>82.84%</td> <td>18.16%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Year	Males (%)	Females (%)	2013	84.50%	15.50%	2014	84.82%	15.18%	2015	84.85%	15.15%	2016	85.92%	14.08%	2017	82.84%	18.16%
Year	Males (%)	Females (%)																		
2013	84.50%	15.50%																		
2014	84.82%	15.18%																		
2015	84.85%	15.15%																		
2016	85.92%	14.08%																		
2017	82.84%	18.16%																		
Leadership	Patents registrations by gender	<p>Patent registrations in 2016: 159.087</p> <p>According to She Figures 2018, the women to men ratio of inventorships in Belgium for the period 2013-2016 was of 0.16, showing a strong under-representation of women as inventors¹⁷¹.</p>																		
	Founders and leaders of innovative enterprises and start-ups by gender	<p>Data of self-employed men/women in 2017¹⁷²:</p> <p>Males: 17,4%; Females: 10,7%</p>																		
Knowledge and tech production issues	Level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension	<p>The FNRS, in its 2020 guide for applicants, still does not stress the importance of having a gender dimension in a research proposals that have (significant) impacts on males and females. Indeed, there is no place in application forms asking the applicants if their research will have a gender dimension or not and if yes, how they intend to deal with it (as for instance with ethics).</p> <p>The same applies for ULB in its grant applications for ARC projects, mobility grants, etc.</p>																		

¹⁷⁰ Figures for TIC sector 2013-2017 in Belgium <https://statbel.fgov.be/fr/nouvelles/chiffres-en-image-les-specialistes-des-tic-sur-le-marche-belge-du-travail>

The percentage of male and female researchers among the overall R&D personnel in the business enterprise sector, in 2015, in Belgium, was roughly the same: 60% for women, 61% for men (SHE Figures 2018, p. 50).

¹⁷¹ She Figures 2018, page 167

¹⁷² Statbel (2018) Chiffres clés. Aperçu statistique de la Belgique https://statbel.fgov.be/sites/default/files/files/documents/FR_kerncijfers_2018_web1a.pdf. Data only concern self-employed people not founders or leaders of innovative enterprises and start-ups.

		<p>On the website of the Wallonia government, while searching for “dimension genre”, only a page appears¹⁷³ saying that applications for a financial support for sports infrastructures have to take gender into account. Nothing else appears about gender as a scientific research dimension.</p> <p>Even on the websites of the Brussels region and the Flanders region, nothing is indicated with reference to the “dimension genre”.</p>
	Level of consideration of the gender dimension in product/service development	No information is available with reference to this indicator.
Broader issues featuring the R&I ‘cultures	Gender sensitiveness/family friendliness of supporting services to start up and entrepreneurship	No information is available with reference to this indicator.
	Perception of existing stereotypes/bias on gender and innovation/entrepreneurship	No information is available with reference to this indicator.

Table 7_ Results of the context analysis conducted by ULB

¹⁷³ <https://www.wallonie.be/fr/actualites/reforme-du-subsidionnement-des-infrastructures-sportives>

4.4.3 ULB Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA

Results of the focus group with internal stakeholders

The focus group took place online on the 28th of September 2020. Three internal stakeholders took part in the activity (2 male and one female), namely the head of the Technology Transfer Office, the President of the Valorisation Committee and the Vice-rector of Research and Valorisation¹⁷⁴.

Researchers adapted the questions proposed in the methodology according to the participants specific expertise, but without changing the scope of the activity.

Before analysing the inputs provided to the participants to the different questions posed, it is important to highlight that the answers given mainly focused on the internal analysis rather than on the external one. This is due by the fact that according to the focus group's participants, **gender is not taken into account by external stakeholders**. Participants reported that on their opinion gender inequalities are not perceived as a challenge by external stakeholders and were not aware of any actions taken. As a result, very few information are provided about how gender equality is perceived by external stakeholders and participants spontaneously focused on the internal situation within ULB.

Participants agreed on the existence of gender inequalities within STEM faculties: there are fewer female students, teachers and researchers in STEM faculties as well as fewer female researcher involved in entrepreneurship actions (e.g. spin-off, patents). They perceive these inequalities as a result of a broad process of socialisation, cultural schemes as well as previous study choices (e.g. at the secondary school). However, they mitigated the consequences of gender inequalities in spin-offs and entrepreneurial actions, since in their opinion such spin-offs and entrepreneurial actions are not very much valued in an academic career and, on the contrary, represent an alternative to the academic career itself. Publications remain the most important success factor for an academic career and for this purpose, international cooperation is more important than industrial cooperation. Participants stated that in their opinion the gender dimension is not taken into account at the STEM faculties, gender is not considered a relevant issue in collaborations, like the topic and the competences. According to them, the main benefit of gender equality in STEM would be that research activities would reflect the composition and the real needs of the society. In order to fulfil this, also other dimensions should be taken into account.

Concerning the **actions** put in place, the Head of the Technology Office mentioned a few projects in the frame of the Polytech: the project "Yes She Can", which aims at informing secondary school students about the STEM careers, and "Women in Tech", a regional initiative aiming at promoting women in science and technology sectors. At the institutional level, the "Children University" project enrolls professors of all faculties, including STEM faculties, who make academic teaching accessible to children. It is not focused on gender but it plays a part in making STEM studies more attractive to all.

No specific actions seem to exist at the researchers' level, even though they agreed that the main level to act upon is the secondary schools one, through dedicated communication campaigns involving role-models. Also a greater involvement of women in selection committees would produce benefits.

In general, overcoming gender inequalities would result in a better reflection of the society features and needs in the research activities.

Some of the participants reported being interested in actively participating in the Research and Innovation Hub.

¹⁷⁴ Another person was supposed to take part in the focus group but finally did not participate.

About **risks** from collaborations, participants identified only risk related to the greater involvement of women in the selection committees, which consists in overloading women with requests of joining committees.

Results of the survey to external stakeholders

The researchers of ULB adapted the survey questions in order to customize them to the 4 different kind of stakeholders involved. The survey was sent not only to current external stakeholders but also to potential ones. The questions included in the survey are listed in Annex VI.

11 external stakeholders answered the survey: 4 public bodies, 3 no-profit associations, 1 professional federation, 1 company, 1 university and 1 RFO. The public bodies mainly deal with the digital sector, employment and diversity in companies, financing research, development and innovation. The no-profit associations, instead, deal with ICT, gender in STEM and gender studies in general. The professional federation represents and supports the technology industry in Belgium, while the private company works on the vaccine research and development.

Concerning the **actions/measures to promote gender quality** within the participating institutions, 9 out of 11 stakeholders reported having measures in place, only two public bodies reported not having any. About the type of actions, the company representative mentioned that inclusion and diversity is part of their corporate strategy and many initiatives take place about internal and external communication, awareness raising, work-life balance. The no-profit associations integrate gender equality in all their activities with actions ranging from networking, inclusive communication, meetings with the ministerial cabinet on the topic, gender related projects, etc. Also the professional federation included measures such as the obligation of mixed panels and the promotion of the topic in internal communication. Two of the public bodies reported adopting the following measures: quantitative analysis, analysis of recruitment, personnel management, internal and external communication processes, adoption of gender balance measures in decision-making, measures for structural change over/under-representation of women/men in RDI domains and sectors, monitoring gender balance in project teams, gender-sensitive funding modalities, etc. The university reported having actions plans with dedicated actions about gender, while the RFO put in place several measures to reduce gender inequalities, such as:

- The composition of the scientific commissions aims as much as possible at a balance between men and women;
- Gender equality is taken into account within the internal procedures for the selection of remote experts;
- Raising awareness take place at the beginning of SC meetings of potential gender bias;
- Publications of gender statistics through the CReF¹⁷⁵;
- Participation in the European She figures survey;
- Application of fixed scales guaranteeing equal salaries for men and women with equal functions and seniority;
- Extension of the grant in case of maternity leave;
- Participation in the network of "gender contact persons" (GCP);
- Annual report on the state of gender equality and inter-institutional report in collaboration with the 6 FWB Universities;
- Participation in the "Women & Science Committee" and in the working groups of this Committee;
- Addition of the field-descriptor "IDR-32 Gender Studies";

¹⁷⁵ <http://www.cref.be/>

- Financial support of the contact group "Gender: from theories to research strategies";
- Participation in the ERA-Net GENDER-NET project and in the ERA-Net Cofund GENDER-NET Plus project;
- Member of Academia-Net;
- Creation and hosting of an Observatory of Research and Scientific Careers which includes the study of gender equality among its priorities.

The survey also explored the **problems and risks** encountered when implementing the actions. The most relevant that were pointed out are:

- Lack of interest by employees (especially for the company);
- Resistance to change by the management;
- Lack of funding/means (especially in the case of the associations and the professional federation and public bodies);
- Lack of awareness and expertise/knowledge in the field;
- Lack of time.

Regarding the **benefits** of implementing the measures, the following ones were mentioned:

- Improvement of the well-being, of the working conditions and of the reputation of the company/institution also from the side of potential new employees, who choose to work for an entity having certain values;
- More political "power" (for no-profit associations);
- Change in people mentality;
- Improvement of internal processes;
- A gender-oriented analysis in RDI contributes to promoting scientific discoveries, improving experimental efficiency and enabling social equality.

No actions/measures are considered to be taken by those stakeholders not having current measures in place at the moment.

The survey also explored existing collaborations between ULB and the stakeholders. With 7 stakeholders collaborations were already in place and concerned:

- Donations & grants, support and sponsorships for scientific meetings;
- ULB's participation in the Board of Directors of the association;
- Support to ULB's diversity plan;
- Involvement of ULB's PhD students and trainees;
- Research projects;
- Funding.

Only in 4 cases the collaboration with ULB included actions on gender equality. This is the case of actions about raising awareness activities, the common participation in the Women and Science Committee and in the FWB network of Gender Contact Persons and the support to the ULB Diversity Plan.

9 stakeholders would be interested in a collaboration with ULB for the promotion of gender equality in STEM and in particular, through the following possible joint actions:

- Joint awareness raising campaigns also targeting youngsters (by using role models);
- Exchange of good practices (for instance about recruitment, gender stereotypes in professions, etc.);
- Dedicated meeting on the topic with non-academics.

Results of the SNA

The data for conducting the SNA were retrieved through the involvement of the Technology Transfer Office of ULB. In particular, the data asked were about the collaborations in place at the STEM faculties in the last three years. The ULB researchers faced several problems in the gathering of data:

- Data were received later than expected. Researchers had to remind several times to the Technology Transfer Office about the data which were received only at the end of September, consequently delaying their analysis.
- The data received were elaborated/adapted in order to be used for the analysis and then to be included in KUMU
- Some collaborations with industries are confidential. Therefore, some collaborations do not appear in the map.
- The content of collaborations is confidential. Therefore, it is not possible to know whether they take gender into account or not.
- Researchers had no access to internal collaborations as well as to the departments involved in the collaborations. Therefore, only the involved faculties appear in the analysis.
- Given that the data were organized by leader of the collaboration and not by partner, this means that several collaboration leaders are involved with a same stakeholder. Therefore, it was not possible to define the gender of the collaboration leader. Researchers adapted the methodology by encoding “male” when the majority of the collaboration leaders were male and “female” when the majority of the collaboration leaders were female, and “Male/female” when the number of male and female collaboration leaders coincides.

Summing up, the data enabled researchers to have information about the partners each STEM faculty is involved with, which sector stakeholders belong to, and the gender of the majority of researchers collaborating with each partner. No information are available about whether collaborations take gender into account.

Overall **183 external stakeholders** were included in the mapping. The main stakeholders are the ones belonging to the “industry & business” sector (88, representing the 48%), followed by “government & public sector” stakeholders (46, representing the 25%), “civil society” stakeholders (25, representing the 14%) and “academia & universities” stakeholders (22, representing the 12%).

Two hypothesis can be made to explain the prevalence of collaborations with “industry & business” stakeholders:

1. The topic of the projects. However, data of the topic are not available, so this hypothesis cannot be confirmed.
2. The fact that “industry & business” stakeholders are involved both as funders and as research partners. They are therefore included in more collaborations.

Concerning the importance of “government & public sector” stakeholders, it can be explained by the fact that they include the major funding agencies and some research centres are public, which make public stakeholders more diverse.

About the **intensity** of collaborations with external stakeholders, almost half of them are “one time” collaborations (105 out of 222, representing the 47%), while 50 are “frequent” collaborations and 67 “solid”. About “one time collaborations”, the great majority (66) are with the “industry & business” sector.

No information about the **topic** of the collaborations was available, as already mentioned above.

With reference of the gender of the collaboration leaders, **only 20 collaborations (11%) are led by a team mainly composed by female researchers**. However, this does not reflect the number of female researchers involved in collaborations because research teams involve many researchers. 9 collaborations are instead led by an equal number of male and female researchers. As previously indicated, the low number of female researchers is partly due to a methodology gap, which leads to a bias, reducing the visibility of female collaboration leaders. However, it is undeniable that, overall, there is a lower number of female researchers compared to the male one.

Taking only female collaboration leaders into account, 8 stakeholders belong to “civil society” sector (40%), 6 to “government & public sector” (30%), 6 to “industry and business”, and none to “academia and universities” (30%).

Also data about collaborations focusing on gender or taking gender into account are not available, due to the above mentioned impossibility of gathering data about the topic of the collaborations. The absence of such type of data was also confirmed during the focus group carried out by ULB researchers, since participants reported that no data related to gender are available concerning collaborations. They also confirmed that research projects hardly focus on gender.

The following pictures represent the results of the SNA conducted by ULB according to the kind of stakeholders. Therefore, 4 different maps are displayed, one for each category of stakeholders: “academia & university”, “industry & business”, “government & public sector”, “civil society”. No collaborations with “schools” were reported. Per each map it is possible to identify the faculty of ULB involved in the collaborations (i.e. the “Faculté des Sciences” and the “Ecole polytechnique de Bruxelles” (the nodes with a small green circle), the collaborations having a predominant female leadership (the yellow nodes). As already mentioned, no collaborations focusing or taking into account gender were registered.

Figure 14_ULB collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholder

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 165_ ULB collaborations with "Academia & university" stakeholders

Figure 16_ ULB collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders

Figure 15_ ULB collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

4.4.4 Final remarks on the external assessment of ULB

The analysis conducted by ULB reveals that in Belgium, **there are different laws promoting gender equality both at federal and regional level**. Such provisions tackle the integration of the gender dimension in all policies, measures and actions, the gender based violence and the discriminations between women and men in the economy, employment and professional training.

Specific policies also promote the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees both in public and private bodies, and include quotas.

National policies are also in place concerning **work-life balance** (e.g. maternity, paternity and paternal leave), however, a lack of homogeneity can be seen in the application of the paternity leave since it is not applicable for self-employed (or unemployed) men. The Institute for the Equality of Women and Men recommends the **improvement of the existing policies against discrimination in relation to family responsibilities**.

As far as employment conditions at university and research organizations are concerned, specific provisions are included in the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers, they consist in: open and transparent recruitment procedures, prohibition of discrimination, achievement of gender balance at all staff levels and even within selection committees.

Data collected show **a great imbalance as concerns STEM students**, both in the Wallonia-Brussels Federation and in the Flanders, where respectively the 34% and the 37% of STEM students are female. The same applies for STEM researchers (34%). Looking at the **evolution of employment rate in ICT, the difference between males and females is very visible, with a slightly positive trend** (from the 15,50% of women in the 2013 to the 18,16% in 2017). Also in terms of patent registration there is a strong under-representation of women.

The level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension is not monitored since in application forms applicants are not asked about the gender dimension of their proposals. And this applies for the main funding entities, as well as for ULB itself.

Concerning the analysis of the collaborations in place with external stakeholders, ULB counts of a variety of collaborations with universities, ICT companies, NGOs and public government bodies. According to the results of the focus group, no relevant findings emerged as concerns the way in which gender is taken into account by external stakeholder. However, the survey provided with relevant information. Indeed, **external stakeholders appear to be familiar with gender equality issues and most of the participating stakeholders have already implemented different actions** concerning internal and external communication, awareness raising initiatives, gender related projects, dedicated analysis, gender balance measures in decision-making. Particularly interesting are the measures adopted by the RFO taking part in the survey (e.g. gender balance in the composition of scientific commissions, gender balance in the selection of experts, equal salaries policies, extension of the grant in case of maternity leave, etc.). About the existing collaboration with ULB, in 4 cases they included actions on gender equality, in the form of raising awareness activities and the common participation to committees and networks. In general, stakeholders reported as being willing to further collaborate on gender equality and the main kind of joint actions that were envisioned were joint awareness campaigns, exchange of good practices and dedicated meetings.

183 stakeholders were included in the SNA, most of them belonging to the “industry & business” sector. **only 20 collaborations are led by a team mainly composed by female researchers**, while 9 collaborations are instead led by an equal number of male and female researchers. Data about collaborations focusing on gender or taking gender into account were not available

4.5 External assessment of NTUA

4.5.1 The Greek national legal and policy framework

NTUA researchers carried out the analysis on the Greek national legal and policy framework mainly through a desk research, whose findings were complemented by a few inputs coming from the interviews conducted in the frame of the internal assessment.

Overall strategic gender equality policies at national level

After becoming part of the EU Member states (1981), the Greek Government started launching legislative procedures and policies to promote gender equality. This happened not only in response to the legislative reforms within the EU and the obligations stemming from the memberships of Greece but also because of the contribution of dynamic feminist and women's organisations within a general climate of euphoria and political activity which marked the 1980s¹⁷⁶.

A landmark in the evolution of gender equality legislation was the Family Law reform of 1983. It constituted a very advanced, for the Greek context, piece of legislation and was one of the most 'woman-friendly' ones in the EC. The new Law emphasised the social protection of the family (Davaki, 2013).

Recently, the Greek Strategy for Gender Equality 2016-2020 (GSGE)¹⁷⁷ was issued, based on the UN sustainable development goal (SDG) n. 5 "gender equality". The main aim of the document is to include the gender dimension in all the policies set by government bodies as well as to set specific measures to prevent, eliminate and treat gender inequalities.

Furthermore, the Law 4606/2019 on "Promoting Substantive Gender Equality, Preventing and Combating Gender-Based Violence - Provisions for Granting Citizenship -Provisions for Elections of Local Authorities- Other Provisions"¹⁷⁸ determines the content of Equality Plans and the private and public bodies liable to their submission.

Finally, Law 4589/2019 includes an article that foresees the establishment of Committees for Gender Equality (CGE) in all Greek universities¹⁷⁹. These committees are established with the role of an advisory body in order to assist the university administration in its efforts to promote gender equality. One of the main responsibilities of the CGEs is to develop Action Plans to promote substantive equality in the educational, research and administrative structures of higher education institutions¹⁸⁰.

Existence of specific mechanisms to promote the under- represented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation at national or regional level

Every Greek university falls under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of National Education and Religious Affairs. All the University Rules of Procedure (Official Government Gazette, 2000) are based on Article 16 of the Constitution of Greece, which declares that "All Greeks are entitled to free education at all levels at State educational institutions. The State shall provide financial assistance to those who are liable to it, as well as to

¹⁷⁶ Davaki K. (2013). The policy on gender equality in Greece. DIRECTORATE-GENERALE FOR INTERNAL POLICIES, Policy Department C, Citizen's rights and constitutional affairs. Retrieved from http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/note/JOIN/2013/493028/IPOL-FEMM_NT%282013%29493028_EN.pdf

¹⁷⁷ GSGE - General Secretariat on Gender Equality, Ministry of Internal Affairs, 2017. National Strategy Plan on Gender Equality 2016-2020.

¹⁷⁸ Official Government Gazette, 2019. Law 4604/2019 FEK A 50/26-03-2019 on Promoting Substantive Gender Equality, Preventing and Combating Gender-Based Violence - Provisions for Granting Citizenship -Provisions for Elections of Local Authorities- Other Provisions

¹⁷⁹ Official Government Gazette, 2019^o. Law 4589/2019 FEK A' 13/29-01-2019 Synergies of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Agricultural University of Athens, University of Thessaly, University of Applied Sciences of Thessaly and other provisions.

¹⁸⁰ Anagnostou D. Avlona R. – N., 2019. The European Union and gender equality in research and higher education: A view from Greece. Hellenic Foundation for European and Foreign Policy (ELIAMEP).

*students in need of assistance or special protection, in accordance to their abilities*¹⁸¹. The aforementioned is combined with Article 4 which states that “*Greek men and women have equal rights and equal obligations*” (Hellenic Parliament, 2008). However, there are no specific mechanisms in place promoting the underrepresented gender in Higher education. Such mechanisms would be beneficiary both for promoting girls in STEM but also for promoting boys in Humanitarian sciences.

Overall, Greek women seem to perform quite well in education compared to men. In 2010 and for the age group 30-34, tertiary educational attainment was 31.4% for women (25.7% for men)¹⁸². However, more recent studies have switched their attention from researching whether women proceed with their education to what kind of studies they pursue. It appears that women select the less rewarding subjects of Humanities and Social Sciences, as opposed to Engineering, Science and Medicine that men chose¹⁸³. In this direction there are some actions through KETHI (Research Centre for Gender Equality)¹⁸⁴ and several EU funded projects empowering women to pursue the more regarding in terms of earnings, such as Engineering, Science and Medicine.

Existence of national policies on implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees

Law 4386/2016 on “Regulations on research and other provisions”¹⁸⁵ recognizes the need to achieve greater gender balance in the composition of leadership/decision making positions and established a specific **gender quota**. In particular, the Law foresees that regarding evaluation and selection committees and advisory bodies in the field of research, technology and innovation, each gender should be represented by at least 1/3 of the committee members (i.e. at least 33% women and 33% men), “as long as the candidates have the necessary qualifications as required by each position” (Official Government Gazette, 2016).

Furthermore, the Greek Strategy for Gender Equality 2016-2020 also promotes the adoption and increase of quotas in members of advisory boards or other collective bodies¹⁸⁶.

Existence of national legislation promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment

There are several laws and measures in place that aim at establishing equality in employment and have a positive impact towards achieving non-discrimination. The first equal pay policy that was established in the new Constitution of 1975 declares that “All employees, regardless of their gender or other discrimination have the right to an equal pay for work of equal value”¹⁸⁷.

Additionally, policies on salaries are further established through laws of the Hellenic Parliament and Official Bulletins of the Ministry of Finance. Particularly, regarding permanent teaching and research staff their pay is determined according to Law 4472/2017¹⁸⁸ and to the Official Bulletin 2/52259/DEP/17-7-2017 (Ministry of Finance, 2017)¹⁸⁹. Regarding permanent administrative staff, their salary is established according to Law 4354/2015¹⁹⁰ and its respective explanatory Official Bulletin 2/1015/DEP/5-1-2016 (Official Government

¹⁸¹ Official Government Gazette, 2000. Issue No 1098/5-9-2000 Approval of the NTUA internal rules of procedure.

¹⁸² European Commission, *Education and Training Monitor*, 2012, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union

¹⁸³ Livanos, I., Pouliakas K. (2012). "Educational segregation and the gender wage gap in Greece." *Journal of Economic Studies* 39(5): 554-575.

¹⁸⁴ To know more about KETHI visit <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/structures/greece/research-center-gender-equality-kethi>

¹⁸⁵ Official Government Gazette, 2016. Issue No 4386/2016 on Regulations on research and other provisions

¹⁸⁶ GSGE - General Secretariat on Gender Equality, Ministry of Internal Affairs, 2017. National Strategy Plan on Gender Equality 2016-2020.

¹⁸⁷ Giannakourou M., Soumeli E., 2002. Equality of pay between men and women in collective negotiations. Research Center for Gender Equality

¹⁸⁸ Official Government Gazette, 2017. Law 4472/2017 FEK A' 74/19-5-2017 on Pension provisions and amendments regarding provisions of Law 4387/2016, measures on the implementation of budgetary targets and reforms, social support measures, labour arrangements, medium term budgetary strategy plan 2018-2021 and other provisions.

¹⁸⁹ Ministry of Finance, 2017. Official Bulletin 2/52259/DEP/17-07-2017 Administration of guidelines on the implementation of the provisions of part ST' of the Law 4472/2017 (A' 74).

¹⁹⁰ Official Government Gazette, 2015. Law 4354/2015 FEK 176/A/16-12-2015 on Management of non-performing loans, salary arrangements and other urgent provisions for the implementation of fiscal and budgetary targets and structural reforms agreement.

Gazette, 2016). For all the above categories **salaries are defined regardless gender** and they are only differentiated according to educational criteria and years of work experience.

Gender sensitive budgeting is foreseen in Law 4604/2019¹⁹¹: the law states that the gender dimension must be reflected in budget planning and the accompanying activities of legal entities belonging to the General Government, where universities belong. Furthermore, the Law determines that the institutions shall send, through the Ministry of Education, to the General Secretariat for Gender Equality (GSGE), a report that includes the gender dimension.

In 2015, GSGE elaborated the first version of the “Guide of using non-sexist language in administrative documents”, which was further updated to its final version in 2018¹⁹². According to the National Strategy Plan on Gender Equality (GSGE, 2017) various educational and training activities on the practical implementation of the above mentioned guide have already taken place, while the National Strategy further urges for the organisation of more similar activities. As these activities are being organized and implemented by E.K.D.A.A. (the *National Centre for Public Administration and Local Government*), anyone working in the Public Administration or Local Government can attend such activities. The Guide also contains comments, instructions, recommendations, advice and specific suggestions for the use of non-sexist language, in order to promote and apply gender equality in administrative documents with the goal of informing and sensitising on the gender equality topic.

Law 3896/2010¹⁹³ states the principle of equal treatment of men and women in terms of access to employment, vocational training and development, working conditions and other relevant provisions. This also applies to **integrating the gender dimension in all aspects of academia** into the curricula of universities.

Moreover, the Greek Strategy for Gender Equality (GSGE) calls for the integration of **gender courses** in academic, research institutions, as well as in higher education military institutions and relevant teacher training institutions. The main goal is to promote gender equality, remove gender stereotypes, enhance equal access and participation in decision making centres and provide equal opportunities for hierarchy advancement (GSGE, 2017). Additionally, Law 4604/19¹⁹⁴ in article 17 “Promoting gender equality through education and learning” refers to higher education institutions and states that those must ensure the promotion of gender equality at all levels and processes of academic life in accordance with Law 4589/2019 which establishes **Gender Equality Committees**¹⁹⁵.

From interviews conducted for the internal assessment, it results that the state’s policy for public administration is followed by all public Institutions, including ECE-NTUA. Particularly Laws 4009/11 and 4386/16 deal with the promotions of Faculty members, while the Official Government Gazette Issue 99/01-05-2002 sets the promotion criteria for Teaching and Research Laboratory Staff and Technical Staff.

Existing policies at national level for reducing unequal gender division of labour related to housework and family care

There are several policies in place for **parental leave** and **career breaks** that work towards gender equality. They are listed below:

¹⁹¹ Official Government Gazette, 2019. Law 4604/2019 FEK A 50/26-03-2019 on Promoting Substantive Gender Equality, Preventing and Combating Gender-Based Violence - Provisions for Granting Citizenship -Provisions for Elections of Local Authorities- Other Provisions

¹⁹² GSGE - General Secretariat on Gender Equality, Ministry of Internal Affairs, 2018. Guide of using nonsexist language in administrative documents.

¹⁹³ Official Government Gazette 207, Vol. I of 8 December 2010. Law 3896/2010 concerning equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in work.

¹⁹⁴ Official Government Gazette, 2019. Law 4604/2019 FEK A 50/26-03-2019 on Promoting Substantive Gender Equality, Preventing and Combating Gender-Based Violence - Provisions for Granting Citizenship -Provisions for Elections of Local Authorities- Other Provisions

¹⁹⁵ Official Government Gazette, 2019a. Law 4589/2019 FEK A' 13/29-01-2019 Synergies of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Agricultural University of Athens, Univeristy of Thessaly, Univeristy of Applied Sciences of Thessaly and other provisions.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

- **Maternity leave** (pregnancy – postpartum): the duration for the permanent staff is 5 months, with an extension of 2 months for more than 3 children¹⁹⁶. For non-permanent staff (fixed-term contracts), the maternity leave duration is of 17 weeks¹⁹⁷.
- **Special maternity protection benefit:** this measure follows the regular maternity leave and has a duration up to 6 months (EC, 2019).
- **Paternal leave** for working fathers (permanent and non-permanent staff), they have the right for a 2-day paternal leave within the first year of the child’s birth (Karamesini et al., 2016).
Parental leave referring to non-permanent staff, is when one of the two parents, after the maternity leave, is entitled to reduced working hours for 30 months (reduced working hours by 1 hour) or 18 months (2 less working hours in the first 12 months and 1 less hour in the remaining 6 months) following childbirth or adoption (EC, 2019). Regarding permanent staff, they are entitled to reduced working hours until the child turns 4 years old. In 1999, a revision of the civil service code gave the opportunity to permanent staff to undertake a parental leave of 9 consecutive months, instead of the reduced working hours. In 2007 a new revision offered the opportunity of a paternal leave also in case the mother is not permanent staff and cannot make use of this benefit. This revision was also extended to staff with fixed – term contracts and gave them the right for 3,75 months of consecutive parental leave (Karamesini et al., 2016).
- **Special Leave of Absence:** according to Law 4604/2019 female employees who undergo medically assisted reproduction, are granted leave of seven (7) fully paid working days, based on a medical certificate by the attending doctor and the director of the medically assisted reproduction unit (Official Government Gazette, 2019).
- **Child school care leave:** for permanent staff 4 days leave per year is predicted for the child’s school care supervision. These 4 days regard one child, while for two or more children one more day is added. For non-permanent staff a 4-day leave is also predicted for each child-pupil up to 16 years old (Karamesini et al., 2016).
- **Parental leave for children with disabilities or other illnesses:** permanent staff is entitled to reduced working hours in the case of a child with disabilities, 22 days leave per year in the case of a child that needs regular treatment (i.e. blood transfusion) or a child with severe mental disabilities (Karamesini et al., 2016). Permanent and non-permanent staff (fixed term) are also entitled to various unpaid leaves.
- Concerning **career breaks**, they are allowed and established by law both for the permanent administration personnel, as well as the academic personnel. Administrative personnel can be granted an unpaid leave for up to five (5) years. Also paid leaves for educational reasons (Postgraduate studies, PhD’s etc.) are foreseen. All long-term leaves need to be approved by the Staff Council. The same stands for academic personnel, for which career breaks due to research or other reasons are also granted. Career breaks due to care related issues are not taken under consideration in the recruitment/interview phase.
- Regarding non-permanent personnel and contracted researchers, career breaks are mostly up to agreements that the employee has with their supervisor(s). Due to the nature and in some cases flexibility of their work terms, career breaks are somewhat eligible for negotiation. From the interviews conducted for the internal assessment, it resulted that career breaks are allowed for a period of up to 5 years (unpaid leave). The Official Government Gazette Issue 189/29-9-09 defines

¹⁹⁶ Karamesini M., Skompa M., Chatzivarnava E., 2016. Literature review and policies analysis regarding work-life balance. Research Center for Gender Equality, Center for Gender Studies Panteion University, Federation of Attica & Piraeus Industries, EEA Grants, General Secretariat for Research & Technology

¹⁹⁷ EC - European Commission, 2019. Greece – Maternity/Paternity Benefits at: <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1112&langId=el&intPageId=4561> (Accessed April 2019).

what the Teaching and Research Laboratory Staff and the Technical Staff are eligible to, in terms of leaves.

Existing framework conditions regarding childcare facilities

There are no existing framework conditions referring to childcare facilities, it is up to each organisation or company to provide such services to their employees. Some organisations have established in-house childcare facilities for their employees, others (mainly in the private sector) may provide the employees with some form of extra financial support dedicated to childcare

Employment conditions at university and research organization

There are no specific gender sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring in university and research organizations in Greece. The promotion/tenure process and criteria are set by the Ministry of Education. The Ministry announces vacancy notices describing the full requirements of qualifications and experience needed and all eligible candidates have the right to submit their papers. Candidates are assessed regarding qualifications and experience and the gender dimension is not considered. As regards permanent researchers, their promotion criteria and procedures are established by the Presidential Decrees 117 & 118 - Official Bulletin 99/01-05-2002. The promotion criteria and processes for permanent academic personnel are established according to Laws 4009/2011 and 4386/2016.

Existence of national programs which promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research

According to the National Strategy Plan on Gender Equality (GSGE, 2017) various educational and training activities on the practical implementation of the guide have already taken place, while the plan encourages organisations to participate in activities that boost the integration of gender in research. As these activities are being organised and implemented by E.K.D.A.A., anyone working in the Public Administration or Local Government can attend.

According to the knowledge of the respondents of the internal assessment interviews, there are no national programs integrating gender in the content of scientific research. However, at EU level the gender dimension is included in the project proposals, even though gender is not a key pillar of the research activities.

National/ policies and legal frameworks on sexual/gender harassment in the workplace

Law 3896/2010¹⁹⁸ addresses the issue of sexual/gender harassment in the workplace. Specifically, the law refers at providing equal opportunities and treating equally both women and men regarding matters of work and employment.

At the same time, the law allows for an independent authority and particularly the Greek Ombudsman to monitor whether the law applies. The Ombudsman examines all the cases after the first court hearing. The law allows the employee that was harassed to claim monetary compensation and demand both administrative and criminal cases in violation of the principle of equal treatment.

Moreover, the Greek Strategy for Gender Equality 2016-2020 further promotes activities regarding the information and sensitisation of the academic and research society on issues like gender inequalities, violence, harassment, sexism, and stereotypes. Additionally, the strategy refers to the establishment of an office, within the organisational structure of the Ministry of Education and of higher education institutions, for the monitoring of the application and promotion of gender equality. This Office will also have the

¹⁹⁸ Official Government Gazette, 207, Vol. I of 8 December 2010. Law 3896/2010 concerning equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in work.

responsibility of filing complaints in cases of gender discriminatory treatment, as well as the care for the effective dealing of sexual harassment (GSGE, 2017).

Funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality at national and regional level

Gender sensitive budgeting is foreseen in Law 4604/2019 (Official Government Gazette, 2019). According to the law, the gender dimension must be reflected in budget planning and the accompanying activities of legal entities belonging to the General Government, such as NTUA. Furthermore, the Law determines that these institutions shall send a **report**, to the General Secretariat for Gender Equality (GSGE) through the Ministry of Education. This report will include data on the achievement of the institutions' objectives in terms of gender equality, as well as their plans for the coming year. Moreover, the report should be sent one month after the planning and approval of the budget. Each institution shall provide training for the staff involved in the budget and activities planning. The training is supported by GSGE, the Research Centre for Gender Equality (KETHI) and the National Centre for Public Administration and Local Government (E.K.D.D.A.). The content, methods, duration, process of training, the means of cooperation among the competent bodies as well as any other relevant issue may be determined by a decision of the Minister of Interior and Administrative Reconstruction (Official Government Gazette, 2019). Currently there are no other funding schemes available.

4.5.2 The innovation ecosystem context analysis at NTUA

The following table presents the results of the context analysis conducted by NTUA in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Area	Indicator	Results						
Talents and workforce education and acquisition	High School and Higher Education students in STEM by gender, at regional and national levels	<p>STEM High Schools students (2018)¹⁹⁹</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>males</td> <td>68%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>females</td> <td>32%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gender	Percentage	males	68%	females	32%
	Gender	Percentage						
males	68%							
females	32%							
	Researchers in STEM by gender in R&I, at national and regional levels	<p>STEM researchers in 2018²⁰⁰:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>males</td> <td>62%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>females</td> <td>38%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gender	Percentage	males	62%	females	38%
Gender	Percentage							
males	62%							
females	38%							
		<p>STEM Higher education students (2017)</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>males</td> <td>68.40%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>females</td> <td>31.60%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gender	Percentage	males	68.40%	females	31.60%
Gender	Percentage							
males	68.40%							
females	31.60%							

¹⁹⁹ Hellenic Statistical Authority. ELSTAT. Statistics.gr. (2020). Retrieved from <https://www.statistics.gr/en/home>

²⁰⁰ She figures 2018 (2019).European Commission, Retrieved from <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9540ffa1-4478-11e9-a8ed-01aa75ed71a1>

	<p>Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Evolution of employment rate in R&I, period 2011 - 2017²⁰¹:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="891 209 1984 647"> <caption>Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Year</th> <th>Males (%)</th> <th>Females (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>2011</td> <td>63.29%</td> <td>36.71%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2013</td> <td>60.62%</td> <td>39.38%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2015</td> <td>62.00%</td> <td>38.00%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2017</td> <td>62.18%</td> <td>37.82%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Year	Males (%)	Females (%)	2011	63.29%	36.71%	2013	60.62%	39.38%	2015	62.00%	38.00%	2017	62.18%	37.82%
Year	Males (%)	Females (%)															
2011	63.29%	36.71%															
2013	60.62%	39.38%															
2015	62.00%	38.00%															
2017	62.18%	37.82%															
<p>Leadership</p>	<p>Patents registrations by gender</p>	<p>Patent registration teams²⁰² One woman: 4.6%; All women team: 0.5%; Team with at least 60% women: 1.5%</p>															
	<p>Founders and leaders of innovative enterprises and start-ups by gender</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Founders and leaders of start-ups by gender. Data of 2018²⁰³:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1317 852 1547 1126"> <caption>Founders and leaders of start-ups by gender. Data of 2018</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Percentage (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Males</td> <td>82.90%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Females</td> <td>14.60%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gender	Percentage (%)	Males	82.90%	Females	14.60%									
Gender	Percentage (%)																
Males	82.90%																
Females	14.60%																

²⁰¹ Eurostat "Total R&D personnel and researchers by sectors of performance, sex and fields of science" https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/RD_P_PERSSCI_custom_239538/default/table?lang=en

²⁰² European Commission. (2019). She Figures 2018, p. 171, figure 7.12 https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/she-figures-2018_en Gender is not recorded in the statistics of the Hellenic Industrial Property Organisation, nor the European Patent Office statistics.

²⁰³ Startup founders in Europe by gender 2018 | Statista. (2018). Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/880086/startups-founders-in-european-countries-by-gender/>.

Knowledge and tech production issues	Level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension	<p>There are no official data available on the level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension. As a general comment, reflecting on the interviews conducted, the gender dimension is not fully integrated as a scientific research dimension. It widely depends on the broader topic. For instance, in pharmaceutical studies or medical searches gender is integrated.</p> <p>According to SHE Figures 2018, the percentages of publications with a sex or gender dimension in various fields (from 2013 to 2017), are the followings: natural sciences 0,84%, engineering & technology 0.21%, medical sciences 4,65%, agricultural science 2.02%, social sciences 2.66% and humanities & arts 2.62%. (She Figures 2018)²⁰⁴.</p>
	Level of consideration of the gender dimension in product/service development	<p>The level of the gender dimension in product or service development in Greece is not clear. No relevant documents (articles, studies, books, online sources, etc.) were identified.</p> <p>According to the interviews conducted for the internal assessment, gender seems only taken into account when considered absolutely necessary²⁰⁵. It must be noted that the interviewees and School stakeholders do not have significant experience with product design for the general public.</p>
Broader issues featuring the R&I 'cultures	Gender sensitiveness/family friendliness of supporting services to start up and entrepreneurship	<p>There are several (private sector) consulting or support services for start-ups and entrepreneurship, but their attitudes towards gender and family aspects is unclear. A brief research on the websites of known incubators in Greece (http://startupnation.gr/category/incubators) shows that there is no mention of the gender or family aspects in entrepreneurship.</p> <p>In the 2018 She figures report, Greece stands out as having the most striking differences in favour of men in R&D in all sectors, as the proportion of men working as researchers exceeded the one of women by 13.7%. In 2018, a study carried out by Statista (2018)²⁰⁶ identified the gender distribution of start-up founders in European countries. In Greece, 82.9% were male and 14.6% female. This distribution is aligned to the female to male ratio in the rest of the European countries. At the same time, Eurostat (2020)²⁰⁷ reports the rate of women scientists and engineers in all EU countries. In Greece, 39% of scientists and engineers are women, which is only 2% less than the overall percentage of women scientists and engineers across Europe.</p> <p>In their book, Gender, Research and Innovation in Greece, Kampouri et al. (2015)²⁰⁸ studied whether the professional and personal life of women and men working in research is balanced, and whether in Greece there are any studies about that. They reviewed existing studies and performed their own small-scale research through a survey and found out that the situation widely depends on the scientific institution where the respondents work. An emerging aspect is that women tend to better investigate which are their rights and possibilities in terms of work-life balance, while men seem usually not familiar with such a topic and rarely use paternity leaves.</p>

²⁰⁴ European Commission. (2019). She Figures 2018, p. 177, table 7.20

https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/she-figures-2018_en

²⁰⁵ It is worth to note that interviewees and School stakeholders do not have significant experience with product design for the general public.

²⁰⁶ See reference n. 203

²⁰⁷ Women in science and technology. Ec.europa.eu. | Eurostat (2020). Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/EDN-20200210-2>

²⁰⁸ Kampouri N., Papadaki K., Hatzopoulos P. (2015). Gender, Research and Innovation in Greece. Institution of technology and research. ISBN 978-618- 80725 -5-8

	<p>Perception of existing stereotypes/bias on gender and innovation/ entrepreneurship</p>	<p>The European Start-up ecosystem stated that across Europe 8.5 out of 10 start-ups are founded by men²⁰⁹. The issue has not been widely explored yet, however some reasons for the absence of women in entrepreneurship have been identified. Some studies have shown that attracting investors is more difficult for female founders. What is more, looking at demographic statistics, women with tertiary education give birth on average when they are 31 years old, and this may lead to the conclusion that they chose family instead of an entrepreneurial career. Finally, another reason is connected to the features that normally a successful start-up founder should have: decisiveness, resilience, and confidence, traits that have been traditionally associated with masculinity, also due to the lack of women as role models. The European patent office²¹⁰ reports that among 8,777,596 patent applications, the 92.21% come from male applicants and 7.79% female applicants.</p> <p>Specifically, for Greece, Pappas et al. (2018)²¹¹, investigated the impact of ICT on women’s employability and career perspectives in managerial positions since, according to their research, women feel underrepresented in the digital era. According to them there is an increasing demand for skilled workers in ICT, however women are under-represented. This is due to the fact that despite the existence of encouraging initiatives, there are wider structural inequalities embedded in the Greek culture.</p> <p>Finally, Kakouris A. et al. (2017)²¹² examined the “gender gap” in entrepreneurship in Greece and found out that entrepreneurial orientation between genders appeared similar, indicating that the way that females tend to start businesses does not vary from the way men do. They also found that gender differences in entrepreneurial tries can be attributed to the general concept of the role of the entrepreneur that is part of the Greek culture.</p>
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Table 8_ Results of the context analysis conducted by NTUA

²⁰⁹ Promoting Enterprise News Portal, (2016), European Commission | Ec.europa.eu. Retrieved from <https://blogs.ec.europa.eu/promotingenterprise/female-entrepreneurship-when-8-5-out-of-10-startups-are-founded-by-men/>

²¹⁰ European patent office (2020). EPO - Home. Epo.org. Retrieved from <https://www.epo.org/>

Hellenic Statistical Authority. ELSTAT. Statistics.gr. (2020). Retrieved from <https://www.statistics.gr/en/home>

²¹¹ Pappas, M.A.; Drigas, A.S.; Papagerasimou, Y.; Dimitriou, H.; Katsanou, N.; Papakonstantinou, S.; Karabatzaki, Z. Female Entrepreneurship and Employability in the Digital Era: The Case of Greece. J. Open Innov. Technol. Mark. Complex. 2018, 4, 15.

²¹² Kakouris, Alexandros & Apostolopoulos, Nikolaos & Dermatis, Zacharias & Komninos, Dimitrios & Liargovas, Panagiotis. (2017). Exploring the gender gap in Entrepreneurial efficacy and intention in Greece.

4.5.3 NTUA Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA

Results of the focus group with internal stakeholders

As far as the **focus group** is concerned the most relevant insights are reported below. The focus group was conducted online on the 19th of June 2020. In total 10 internal stakeholders participated (5 males and 5 females) among which 5 senior researchers, 2 academic and research personnel, 1 technical employee, and 2 people of the administration, all of them having strong connections with the ecosystem of the university.

After an initial brainstorming session, the group started discussing about the current **existing or prospective collaborations on broader areas** beside gender equality: participants reported that in NTUA there are various existing partnerships in place with other ICT experts or NGOs and public government bodies. Several of those have been established during previous partnerships in European funded research projects. In other cases, collaborations came from alumni of the ECE-NTUA, who established new contacts between the university and external stakeholders. Finally, the focus group participants provided information about people they had already collaborated with in the public or private sector.

The group was then asked to focus on the ways in which gender inequalities represent a **challenge** for external stakeholders. They agreed that the external stakeholders within their networks take into account the gender dimension. This is evident from their posts in social media and their newsletters about dedicated events they organise. One example concerns the case of *Cosmote*, which is one of the key telecommunication providers in Greece, an organisation which ECE_NTUA often works with and where many alumni are currently employed. In fact, Cosmote has a dedicated event empowering woman in managerial positions.

When it comes to the challenges that organisations may face, the group identified the issue of “gender washing” and pointed out that they should take gender into account not only for promoting their own institutions and “washing” their own images through dedicated campaign against gender discrimination but they should adopt gender equality within their core activities.

About the **actions** that external stakeholders put in place on gender equality, participants could not immediately recall any particular action. However, they stressed that they have a strong network and can bring the CALIPER group in contact with the relevant stakeholders.

With reference to **complementarities and synergies** with NTUA and the impact for internal institutional change, the focus group participants believe that there are many ways to cooperate with the existing stakeholders, or reach out to new ones, when it comes to gender equality. The issue of visibility arose: they stated that organizing events aimed at empowering women in STEM with the participation of role models (i.e. professional women who have been STEM alumni in NTUA) could, on one side, really help young students to follow STEM subjects, and, on the other, raise awareness on the issue of gender equality at an institutional level. Useful activities which could be fostered are trainings, even though they reported that trainings as joint activities do not necessarily make a difference. Another joint activity which could be promoted is the involvement of STEM alumni in events at university where they can talk to students about their own experience.

No **overlapping/competitive actions** were identified.

According to participants, the only **risk** which could derive from collaboration is the so-called “gender fatigue”, that may be caused if a lot of events on this topic take place and if it is given too much attention to the issue all of a sudden.

Results of the survey to external stakeholders

The survey was submitted by 8 external stakeholders, 3 private companies, 3 associations (NGOs), and 2 Universities (departments), dealing with a variety of activities/business: IT, scientific data collection and dissemination, industrial management and technology, gender studies, energy and sustainability in buildings, telecommunication, innovative communications and synergy platform, and digital marketing.

Not all external stakeholders have already a collaboration in place with ECE_NTUA (the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering). From the stakeholders that submitted the survey the **types of existing collaborations**, included:

- Programmes on energy management and ICT applications;
- Networking;
- Cooperation through internships for the School's students;
- Cooperation in H2020 projects.

External stakeholders were asked to explain how **gender inequalities challenge their own organizations**. As far as Universities are concerned, one of them reported that no gender challenges are observed due to their policy of equality in terms of gender, origin, and diversity. The other university reported that challenges mainly regard the professional development (recruitment, advancement, glass ceiling), the lower wages of public employees, the under-representation of women in specific scientific field (i.e. STEM subjects) and administrative areas (i.e. governing bodies), with no exception for work-life balance issues.

In general, both NGOs and companies reported having gender balance in terms of staff, however, two stakeholders recognised the prevalence of men in senior or higher positions. Moreover, 2 companies out of 3, claimed that there are not enough women in STEM professions, probably linked to the gender stereotypes deeply ingrained in the society which make these working environments strongly male-dominated.

One of the NGOs reported that a challenge for their organization is drawing the attention on the crucial role that the private sector can play in achieving SDG 5 (Gender Equality) as well as on the Women's Empowerment Principles (WEPEs).

With reference to the **potential benefits** of addressing the gender equality challenges, faculties stressed that removing gender inequalities would improve the professional environment, guaranteeing equal participation, better science and a contribution to social justice (which could produce a spill over effects in society), as well as produce better working and living conditions and improve students education.

Companies stated that achieving gender balance in their team would help having an ideal working environment where everyone participates, acts, and interacts. In this perspective a diverse team opens new horizons in innovation, increase employees and team performance.

A relevant number of **actions and measures** were undertaken from the external stakeholders to address gender inequalities. One University declared having started informing 1st year students of their policy on equality and supporting them through mentoring programs. The other University recently established an equality committee at the university level, and a specific 'Gender Laboratory'. They activated networks with researchers and other bodies to enhance research and dissemination of information on gender issues. Also, they opened a kindergarten (in one of the two campuses of the University) and programs of activities for children.

Significant actions were also taken by two of the companies. Indeed, one of them started a group (called "women @") in which the participants, in addition to their professional roles, undertake actions on gender equality and more (Diversity, Equity, Inclusion). Such actions mainly concern trainings & networking events for women and informative actions (i.e. for International Women's Day) to the general public.

The other company's measures are summarized here:

- During the recruitment process, they ensure to have a diverse pool of candidates to fill positions, as well as a common evaluation system for all and non-discriminatory remuneration.
- They allow men and women to use the parental leave without discrimination based on gender. Already about 300 male employees of their company have used it.
- They systematically invest in actions to develop digital skills and educate young people, such as the production of a film called Robogirl, which aims to familiarize both boys and girls with STEM, and the strategic partnership with the WRO Hellas organization for educational robotics.
- Implicit bias digital training is provided for all top management.
- Since 2010, they have set the goal of women covering 30% of the decision-making positions, in middle and upper level management. In 2019 the percentage achieved was 31%.
- Women represent the 39% of the total staff and hold 30% of decision-making positions. In addition, they account for 43% of new hires in the company.

Among the participating NGOs, only one provided a list of actions, such as the organisation of some workshops like the coding workshops of the program "Girls Coding - Digital Coding: Workshops for digital coding skills " and the "Workshops for Digital Coding skills targeted to female school students in Greece". They also take part to actions in collaboration with female institutions such as EDEGE, Women's Associations etc. Moreover, the institution has taken measures in accordance with the EU Gender Equality Index for their organization.

About **potential measures** to be adopted to tackle gender inequalities, one university would like to promote equality issues through workshops and events, as well as through modules in courses, while an NGO would like to implement new business models toward the achievement of SDG5 (gender equality).

Concerning potential **complementarities and synergies** with NTUA in order to overcome gender inequalities, companies indicated the possibility of having more female job applicants directly from the School of ECE, as well as the opportunity of developing actions, such as talks or discussion groups in the environment of the School, with the support of executives from the company, in order to inform and raise the awareness of students on issues related to gender equality and their professional coexistence. Another possible synergy mentioned by companies is the organisation of trainings/seminars for students.

Faculties mentioned the joint organisation of workshops or events, and the activation of networking and collaboration in research and dissemination. Interdisciplinarity is indeed crucial for starting up dynamic collaborations and synergies: the integration of sociological knowledge and IT studies can help understanding and interpreting technological and engineering issues, and the challenges related to the construction and use of computers and applications.

One of the NGOs underlines the possibility of developing actions and cooperation in the field of "Women and technology", as well as of continuing actions about "Digital Coding skills" targeting female students in Greece.

They do not identify any **overlapping/competitive actions** with the ECE-NTUA ones.

Finally, **potential risks** of the cooperation were addressed. Not many risks were identified, the ones reported were mainly related to external conditions, like the institution readiness to major unforeseen events, such as health-related threats (i.e. recent pandemic), security, natural disasters, funding difficulties and ongoing changes in the institutional development framework of organizations. A company mentioned the risk of the inappropriate use of their logo. The other stakeholders did not identify any risks from the cooperation.

Results of the SNA

The data for the SNA were collected through a two-step process. During the first step, information was gathered from the interviews during the internal analysis. In particular, academics and representatives of the top and medium level management of the School were interviewed and asked about existing collaborations. Collaborations were investigated also with the Head of the Career and Liaison office, the Professional Practice Office, as well as other established structures directly connected with ECE-NTUA. The information gathered during the first step led to the second step consisting of a desk-based research.

During the desk-based research, the research team conducted a study on the online available information at the ECE Research Laboratories, regarding the research projects they participate in, their stakeholders etc. The same process took place at the ICCS (Institute of Communication and Computer Systems), as well as at the Professional Practice Office. According to the projects identified, all stakeholders in Greece were listed and recorded in the SNA file.

All the partnerships listed in the SNA are crucial for the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (ECE-NTUA) for its activities as a leading research and academic institution. Some of the partnerships are solid and represent an integral part of the School's operations. The four most crucial collaborations are:

- with the National Technical University of Athens, as an umbrella organisation for all engineering schools and includes University-level decision-making bodies;
- with the NTUA professional practice office, which is the link between NTUA and the market;
- with the career liaison office offering guidance and consultation to students of all levels;
- with the ICCS as there is a strong collaboration in terms of research and knowledge transfer.

Overall, **89 external stakeholders** were included in the mapping. The most frequent collaborations are with "industry & business" stakeholders (49 out of 89 stakeholders, representing the 55%). The rest of the collaborations are almost equally split among "academia & universities" stakeholders (16, representing the 18%), "civil society" stakeholders (15, representing the 17%), and "government & public sector" stakeholders (9, representing the 10%).

About the **intensity** of collaborations, many of them (40 out of 97, representing the 41%) are "solid". This can be explained by considering that ECE is one of the oldest and most active engineering universities in Greece with a strong network. 34 (representing 35%) are "frequent" collaborations. This means that even though those collaborations happen often, either they are not yet based on a solid ground or they are not continuously in place. Among «solid» collaborations, 21 are with "industry & business" stakeholders, 10 with "civil society" stakeholders, 6 with "academia & universities" stakeholders and 3 with "government & public sector".

23 collaborations (representing the 24%) are "one time" and most of them are new collaborations.

Concerning the **topic** of the collaborations most of the "solid" collaborations (23 out of 40) are about "transfer to market", while 7 are about "raising awareness", 6 about "scientific research", 3 about "education" and 1 about "science communication".

In total, **40 collaborations are led by (only) 6 women** (45%). Two of them are the Heads of the Career and Liaison office and of the Professional Practice Office, which are both female and in charge of several connections. In particular, 32 of such collaborations (80%) are with "industry & business" stakeholders, while 6 are with the civil society (15%), 1 with "academia & universities" stakeholders (2,5%) and "government & public sector" stakeholders (2,5%). Therefore, women lead the majority of collaborations with the industry and business sector, while they are a minority in the remaining categories, this seems to point at a gender

gap to be further explored at the academic staff level. It should be noticed that these data do not reflect the real number of female researchers involved in collaborations (not as leaders), which are more.

It is worth to mention that there are several female researchers leading projects at the School level, however this is not being reflected in the current SNA. Indeed, a professor (usually male) is normally indicated as the “project coordinator”, while the project itself is typically managed by a senior researcher or a group of researchers, many of which are women.

Concerning the number of collaborations **taking into account or focusing on gender issues**, only 11 (out of 97) focus on gender issues, while 9 take into account gender. Among those collaborations, 6 of them are with “civil society” stakeholders, 5 with “industry & business” stakeholders and only 1 with a university.

Within the research activities of the School the gender aspect is generally overlooked. However, among specific actions focusing and/or taking into account gender, there are mainly the ones led by the Career and Liaison Office, which is also in charge of empowering the female presence in STEM. These actions concern activities such as:

- Dissemination and raising awareness activities, synergies with organizations or companies that advocate women in STEM (e.g. career liaison office);
- Co-organization of workshops and seminars on (gender) equality issues (e.g. career liaison office);
- Scholarships and internships for female students (various organizations, both private and public, that provide intern scholarships for female students in STEM communicate with the career and liaison office which further disseminates them to the interested parties);
- Research and joint research activities (e.g. collaboration and communication with University of Crete).

It is important to note that the collaborations reported in the SNA are not all the existing collaborations of the ECE. Indeed, some research laboratories/teams could not provide the information required since they do not have such information available. In other cases, laboratories/teams did not have updated information to provide, meaning that some more recent projects may have not been reported. Also, no centralised repository of the existing collaborations/stakeholders exists, meaning that information has to be collected by each laboratory/team. All these factors made it difficult to get access to the required data, also considering COVID-19 restrictions at the time of the external assessment.

The following pictures represent the results of the SNA conducted by NTUA according to the kind of stakeholders. Therefore, 4 different maps are displayed, one for each category of stakeholders: “academia & university”, “industry & business”, “government & public sector” and “civil society”.

Per each map it is possible to identify the different departments²¹³ of NTUA involved in the collaborations with the different external stakeholders (the nodes with a small green circle), the collaborations having female leaderships (the yellow nodes) and the collaborations focusing or considering gender (the connections in red).

²¹³ The School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems, the Professional Practice Office, the Career and Liaison office.

Figure 17_ECE-NTUA collaborations with "Academia & universities" stakeholders

Figure 18_ECE-NTUA collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders

Figure 20_ECE-NTUA collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders

Figure 21_ECE-NTUA collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

4.5.4 Final remarks on the external assessment of NTUA

The equality between men and women is stated in the Greek Constitution. After becoming part of the EU Member states (1981), the Greek Government started launching legislative procedures and policies to promote gender equality, like the Family Law reform of 1983 and the more recent Greek Strategy for Gender Equality 2016-2020 (GSGE) and Law 4606/2019 providing the content of Equality Plans as well as provisions related to **gender sensitive budgeting**. With Law 4589/2019 instead the establishment of a Committee for Gender Equality in each university was foreseen. The law also states that **higher education institutions must ensure the promotion of gender equality at all levels and processes of academic life**. However, **no specific mechanisms for promoting the underrepresented gender in Higher education are in place yet**.

Gender quotas in decision-making bodies are established by the law 4386/2016, which explicitly foresees for evaluation and selection committees and advisory bodies in the field of research, technology and innovation, that **each gender should be represented by at least 1/3 of the committee members**.

Dedicated provisions are set for promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment (i.e. salaries policies, access to employment, vocational training and working conditions). Several policies also exist concerning parental leave and career breaks, while no framework conditions about childcare facilities are in place.

The issue of sexual/gender harassment in the workplace is addressed by a dedicated law²¹⁴, however the Greek Strategy for Gender Equality 2016-2020 further promotes **activities regarding the information and sensitisation of the academic and research society on issues like gender inequalities, violence, harassment, sexism, and stereotypes**.

Data about STEM High School and Higher Education students show that **less than 1/3 of STEM students are female**. The share of female STEM researchers is a bit more positive (38%), while the evolution of the employment rate in R&D from 2011 to 2017, does not show any relevant progress in the mentioned period, since the female share only increased of about 1% (from 36.71% to 37.82%). Lacking is also the presence of women in patent registration teams. Also on the side of founder and leaders of start-ups, the percentage of women is very low (14.60%). Studies explain the gender gap in entrepreneurship as a result of the Greek culture related to the role of women.

The level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension is not monitored and no documents were identified exploring the integration of gender in product or service development.

Concerning the analysis of the collaborations in place with external stakeholders, according to the focus group and the survey results, NTUA has various partnerships in place with universities, ICT companies, NGOs and public government bodies. **Gender inequalities are only partially perceived by the stakeholders** involved in the survey, some of them, indeed, reported not facing this kind of challenges. Others explained that challenges are mainly related to the female professional development (and thus affecting the recruitment and advancement processes), the lower wages of public employees, the under-representation of women in specific scientific field (i.e. STEM subjects) as well as in higher positions. Many benefits from solving gender inequalities were identified: improving the professional environment, guaranteeing equal participation, better science and contributing to social justice, as well as producing better working and living conditions. About actions already put in place, worth to mention are the establishment of equality committees and “gender laboratories”, the inclusion of quotas in decision making bodies, and the adoption of specific measures for fostering work-life balance (i.e. the start of a kindergarten in an university campus,

²¹⁴ Law 3896/2010, Official Government Gazette, 207, Vol. I of 8 December 2010. Law 3896/2010 concerning equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in work.

improvement of the parental leave). Concerning complementarities and synergies with NTUA, raise awareness activities such as workshops, talks, trainings, seminars were mentioned.

89 stakeholders were included in the SNA, most of them belonging to the “industry & business” sector. Almost the 50% of the collaborations have a female leadership, even though they refer to only 6 women, who oversee the majority of collaborations with the industry sector. 11 collaborations focus on gender issues, most of them with “civil society” stakeholders.

4.6 External assessment of YASAR

4.6.1 The Turkish national legal and policy framework

Overall strategic gender equality policies at national level

Specific legal texts/acts relevant to the field of gender equality policies in higher education do not exist. Gender equality is addressed within a broader concept of anti-discrimination and equality in various laws and acts. Crucial in this sense are the article 10 and the article 42 of the Turkish Constitution²¹⁵. They regulate the equality before law and the right to free education for all citizens and guarantee equal access to education for both men and women.

The law on higher education²¹⁶ (law n. 2547), which aims to define the goals and principles of higher education, only includes a clause on gender in its disciplinary and penal procedures. The clause foresees a stop in the progression or a penalty consisting in multiple deductions in salary, in case of discriminatory acts based on mother language, race, color, gender, political opinion, belief, religion and sect.

No other legal texts related to higher education, such as the Law on Higher Education Personnel, the Law on Supporting Research, Development and Design Activities, Regulation for Upgrading and Appointment to Faculty Membership and the Law on Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey, include any reference or provision with reference to gender equality.

In 2015, the Council of Higher Education (CoHE) in Turkey prepared and published a «Gender Mainstreaming» strategy and stance document²¹⁷, which was later withdrew by the CoHE itself in 2019. The document was prepared based on the CEDAW, the equality article of the Turkish Constitution, the İstanbul Convention and the General Assembly Decision of Council of Higher Education. The purpose of the document was to guarantee gender equality provisions in higher education institutions. The document called for the development of compulsory or elective courses on gender equality, the organization of seminars and events to increase the awareness of academics, administrative staff and students, the set of measures to fight against sexual harassment in academia and the establishment of centers focusing on women's studies/gender studies. The document is said to be in revision and expected to be distributed to higher education institutions.

In 2019, The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TÜBİTAK) has published its policy principles for increasing the participation of women researchers in its processes²¹⁸. According to these principles, TÜBİTAK embraces gender balance in research, encourages female researchers to apply to R&D and innovation support mechanisms and promotes the publication of special calls for female researchers.

Although there are pieces of legislation for equality and institutional efforts to include a gender dimension in higher education, the lack of a national action plan for gender equality in academia and higher education, the lack of institutionalization of the gender studies, the lack of structured and collaborative research studies and the lack of data might be listed as the major problems in this area.

Existence of specific mechanisms to promote the under- represented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation at national or regional level

There are “gender” monitoring bodies at the national level, and they include:

²¹⁵ https://global.tbmm.gov.tr/docs/constitution_en.pdf

²¹⁶ <http://www.lawsturkey.com/law/the-law-of-higher-education-2547>

²¹⁷ http://www.ktu.edu.tr/dosyalar/kadinarastirmalari_e950b.pdf

²¹⁸ <https://www.tubitak.gov.tr/en/news/policy-principles-for-increasing-the-participation-of-women-researchers-in-tubitak-processes-are>

- 98 Research and Application Centers for Gender Equality at the Turkish Universities (YÖK, 2020²¹⁹).
- Monitory body – Institutional level;
- Council of Higher Education;
- Ministry of Family and Social Policies.

These initiatives and policies are supported also by some projects coordinated by the Ministry of Family, Labor and Social Policies, such as “Engineer Girls of Turkey Project (2016-2020)”, “Mom’s Job, My Future Project (2013-2019)”, “the Young Ideas, Powerful Women Project (2012-2015)”, “Gender Parity Task Force of Turkey” (which was transformed into “Equality at Work Platform”) (2012-2015), “Women Labour Force Profile in Turkey and the Revision of Statistics from a Gender Equality Perspective (2014-2015)”, “the Project on Promotion of Women’s Access to Economic Opportunities (2012-2017)”, “Painter Forewomen Project (2016-2017)”, “UN Joint Programme on the Protection and Promotion of Women’s Human Rights: Gender Responsive Budgeting (2012-2015)”.

The Directorate on The Status of Women also supervises some other projects on gender equality.

Furthermore, in 2015 there was a workshop hosted for academics all over Turkey on Gender Sensitive Higher Education, which was launched by the Council of Higher Education of Turkey. A committee was set up after the workshop to provide guidance and support in the applications of gender equality activities in Universities across Turkey. The Council also published a position paper²²⁰ to all University Administrations with guidelines for promoting gender equality activities in three key sections such as implementing measures to combat sexual harassment in campus and provisions for obligatory or optional courses on gender studies and promoting the Centers of Gender and Women Studies.

Existence of national policies on implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees

According to the “Global Gender Gap Report 2020”²²¹ prepared by the World Economic Forum, Turkey scores 3.63 (7 being the highest score) in advancement of women to leadership roles. The report also includes information on female leadership in firms. Indeed, according to the findings, female leadership in companies constitutes the 13.40% in the whole Turkey. The rate falls even below when it comes to female ownership of firms and female top management, with only a 3.9%.

Female employment is a priority area for national strategic documents such as the National Development Plan, the National Employment Strategy or other action plans. In particular, in the National Development Plan for 2019-2023²²², there is a strategic objective about carrying out awareness raising and encouraging activities to ensure further involvement of women in the management and decision-making bodies both in the public and private sector.

References to quotas for women in management positions can be found in the “Official Communiqué on Determination and Implementation of Corporate Governance Principles” of the Capital Markets Board²²³. The communique calls for at least one female board member in public companies. The aforementioned principle is not mandatory and the “Apply, Explain If You Don't Apply” principle applies. However, the Women's Empowerment Strategy document and action plan of the Ministry for Family, Labour and Social

²¹⁹ <https://kadincalismalari.yok.gov.tr/Sayfalar/DuyuruDetay.aspx?did=11>

²²⁰ www.haberler.com, 2016

²²¹ http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GGGR_2020.pdf

²²² <https://www.sbb.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/OnbirinciKalkinmaPlani.pdf>

²²³ <https://spk.gov.tr/Duyuru/Goster/20120211/0>

Services questions the effectiveness of this principle and argues that not including a sanction for the violation of such principle cannot provide the expected effect²²⁴.

When analysing the low number of women in leadership position it is necessary to understand the reasons that prevent women from reaching such positions, which are mainly of two kinds:

- religious and cultural perceptions of the family role of women in society;
- many institutions and companies do not have policies in place allowing the advancement of women to leadership positions.

Existence of national legislation promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment

There are several pieces of legislation promoting gender equality and non-discrimination in employment.

The major piece of law governing employment is the Turkish Labor Law 4857²²⁵ which states that:

- employers can not discriminate either directly or indirectly against an employee in the conditions, execution and termination of the employment contracts on the grounds of gender or pregnancy;
- wages should be equal and gender, marital status and family obligations, pregnancy and childbirth will not be valid reasons for termination of an employment contract;
- if the worker is sexually harassed by the employer, another worker or by a third party and if the worker reports this situation to the employer but the necessary precautions are not taken, the worker has the right to terminate the work contract immediately;
- paid and unpaid maternity leave and nursing leave periods are granted to female employees. Paid maternity leave is sixteen weeks in total, eight weeks before confinement and eight weeks after confinement. In case of multiple pregnancy, an extra two week period are added to the eight weeks before confinement. The female employee shall be granted paid leaves for periodic examinations during her pregnancy. If the female employee wishes it, she can benefit of an unpaid leave of up to six months after the expiry of the sixteen weeks, or, in the case of multiple pregnancy, after the expiry of the eighteen weeks indicated above. This period shall not be considered in determining the employee's one year of service for entitlement to annual leave with pay. Female employees are allowed to benefit of one and a half hour of nursing leave per day, in order to enable them to feed their children below the age of one. The employee can decide when and how to use this leave. The length of the nursing leave are considered as part of the daily working time.

Other provisions on gender equality and non-discrimination include:

- The Prime Ministry Circular No. 2004/7 on "Acting in Accordance with the Principle of Equality in Staff Recruitment", published in the official gazette on 22nd January 2004²²⁶.
- "The Regulation on the Employment Conditions of Pregnant or Breastfeeding Women, and Breastfeeding Rooms and Child Care Homes" published in the official gazette on 16th August 2013²²⁷.
- "The Regulation on the Night Shift Employment Conditions of Female Employees" published in the official gazette on 24th July 2013.

²²⁴ <https://www.ailevecalisma.gov.tr/ksgm/ulusal-eylem-planlari/kadinin-guclenmesi-strateji-belgesi-ve-eylem-planlari-2018-2023/>

²²⁵ Dated 22/05/2003, numbered 8423 <https://www.mevzuat.gov.tr/mevzuat?MevzuatNo=4857&MevzuatTur=1&MevzuatTertip=5>

²²⁶ <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2004/01/20040122.htm#11>

²²⁷ <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2013/08/20130816-8.htm>

- “The Regulation Amending the Regulation on Heavy and Dangerous Occupations” dated 8th February 2013, which excluded a list of jobs from the category of heavy and dangerous jobs and enabled female employment in these areas.
- The Prime Ministry Circular No. 2010/14 on “Increasing Women’s Employment and Promotion of Equality in Opportunities” published in the official gazette on 25th May 2010.
- Article 26 of the Trade Unions and Collective Labor Agreement Law No. 6356, published in the official gazette on 7th November 2012, which urges organizations to comply with the principle of equality and discrimination prohibitions among their members in benefiting from the activities of unions and confederations. Organizations observe gender equality in their activities.

Existing policies at national level for reducing unequal gender division of labor related to housework and family care

The fundamental national policy regarding labour and employment is the national 5-year Development Plan. According to the 11th 5-year Development Plan for the period 2019-2023, empowering women in the labour market is a priority. In order to increase the participation of women in the labour market, measures such as increased childcare services, flexibility in employment forms are included. The plan calls for practices that harmonize work and family life.

The Ministry for Family, Social Security and Labor is the leading executive body for ensuring equal opportunities in employment and working conditions. The Ministry works in cooperation with other organizations to promote gender equality.

The National Employment Strategy²²⁸ calls for development of policies for equal opportunities in employment for groups which face difficulties in the labour market. The strategy points out that women are not represented enough in labour market due to lack of education, gender-based division of labour and lack of work-life balance mechanisms. Furthermore, the strategy stresses that gender based division of labor is observed based on sectors as well as occupations.

The data of the Turkish Statistic Institute²²⁹ on professions selected according to gender show that women constitute a very small part of these professions among senior civil servants, judges and ambassadors, and the big difference between men and women continues over the years.

Existing framework conditions regarding childcare facilities

The conditions for childcare facilities are regulated by “The Regulation on the Employment Conditions of Pregnant or Breastfeeding Women, and Breastfeeding Rooms and Child Care Homes” published in the official gazette on the 16th August 2013²³⁰.

Some of the selected measures of the regulation regarding childcare facilities are detailed below:

- *“Regardless of their age and marital status, in workplaces with 100-150 female employees, it is obligatory for the employer to establish a breastfeeding room that meets the conditions specified in Annex-IV, separate from the workplaces and at a maximum distance of 250 meters from the workplace”.*

²²⁸ <http://www.uis.gov.tr/media/1437/uis2014-2023.pdf>

²²⁹ <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Kategori/GetKategori?p=istihdam-issizlik-ve-ucuret-108&dil=1>

²³⁰ <https://www.mevzuat.gov.tr/mevzuat?MevzuatNo=18728&MevzuatTur=7&MevzuatTertip=5>

- *“Regardless of their age and marital status, in workplaces with more than 150 female employees, the employer must establish childcare facilities for children aged 0-6 years. The qualifications and duties of the managers, health personnel and other personnel who will work in the rooms and dormitories are as regulated by this legislation”.*
- *“Necessary foods, breakfasts and meals are to be provided in facilities according to the needs of the children. Opinion of the workplace doctor is to be taken in the regulation of food lists and complementary nutrition.”*
- *“In child-care facilities, pre-school education is to be provided to children to ensure their psychosocial development”.*

Employment conditions at university and research organization

Employment conditions are governed by the Higher Education Law²³¹, the Turkish Labour Law²³² (No: 4857) and internal procedures and regulations on appointment and promotions of academic staff at each higher education institution.

Female researchers benefit from social rights pertaining to the Turkish labour law in terms of maternity leave, breastfeeding leave and the possibility of part-time working opportunities. These provide flexible criteria for career progression during major life events like childbirth or care work for relatives. Academics can move institutionally without losing social or tenure rights.

Existence of national programs which promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research

TÜBİTAK (The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey) is the main scientific body which aims at promoting science and technology and spreading basic and applied academic research in Turkey. TÜBİTAK also provides research funding and scholarships for researchers. The following are the TUBITAK’s funding programmes for higher education institutions:

- 1000 - Support Program for Increasing Research and Development Potential of Universities
- 1001 - Scientific and Technological Research Projects Support Program
- 1002 - Quick Support Program
- 1003 - Priority Areas R&D Projects Support Program
- 1004 - Center of Excellence Support Program
- 1005 - National New Ideas and Products Research Support Program
- 1007- Public Institutions Research and Development Projects Support Program
- 3001 - Preliminary R&D Projects Support Program
- 3501 - Career Development Program

Furthermore, the Turkish Council of Higher Education (YÖK) provides scholarships to researchers and funding to higher education institutions. The following are the main funding opportunities of YÖK:

- YÖK Doctoral Scholarship
- YÖK Support Scholarship
- Project Based International Exchange Program
- International Research Scholarships

Unfortunately, none of the above programmes of TÜBİTAK or YÖK promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research. Also, the analysis of the implementation principles of the above funding

²³¹ <http://www.lawsturkey.com/law/the-law-of-higher-education-2547>

²³² <https://www.mevzuat.gov.tr/mevzuat?MevzuatNo=4857&MevzuatTur=1&MevzuatTertip=5>

programmes showed that gender is not as a criterion embedded in the evaluation processes to access those grants and resources.

However, as a positive note, on the 24th December 2019 TÜBİTAK announced the ‘Policy Principles for Increasing the Participation of Women Researchers in TÜBİTAK Processes’²³³, which aims to ensure and maintain the balance between male and female researchers in the field of R&D and innovation. The principles are the following:

1. *“Within the scope of R&D and innovation support programs, taking into account scientific excellence and/or research quality, TÜBİTAK adopts a balance regarding the participation of female and male researchers in the governance mechanisms established for decision-making (group executive boards and advisory boards), project evaluation and monitoring processes, and prioritizes increasing the ratio of female researchers in a way to ensure balance when deemed necessary”.*
2. *“TÜBİTAK promotes the inclusion of facilitating measures needed by researchers for their young children in the R&D and innovation support mechanisms legislation, in order to encourage female researchers to apply to R&D and innovation support mechanisms”.*
3. *“It encourages the inclusion of female researchers and/or scholars in the project teams formed within the scope of R&D and innovation projects supported by TÜBİTAK”.*
4. *“It encourages the publication of special calls for female researchers in the field of technology-based entrepreneurship”.*
5. *“Within the scope of R&D and innovation support programs and in the activities it conducts through R&D centers and institutes, TÜBİTAK regularly monitors the balance of female and male researchers through statistics”.*
6. *“TÜBİTAK pays attention at ensuring the balance of female and male researchers among researchers employed at research centers and institutes, taking care that the research quality is ensured”.*
7. *“It carries out awareness activities regarding the facilities provided and the importance given to female researchers in the activities carried out by TUBITAK in the field of R&D and innovation”.*

National/ policies and legal frameworks on sexual/gender harassment in the workplace

Sexual harassment is described as a crime in the Turkish Criminal Law²³⁴. According to article 105 *“A person who abuses another person for sexual purposes is sentenced to imprisonment from three months to two years, or to a judicial fine. If the crime is committed by taking advantage of the convenience of working in the same workplace (paragraph c) the penalty to be given is increased by half. If, due to this act, the victim had to leave her/his job, family leave or the school, the imprisonment to be imposed cannot be less than one year.”*

Furthermore, there are some provisions regarding sexual harassment in the Labour Law (No.4857). Articles n. 24 and 25 give the employee the right to terminate the employment contract immediately without having to take into account some specific notice periods in the following situations regarding sexual harassment:

- In the event that the employer sexually harassed the employee;
- In case the employee is subjected to sexual harassment at the workplace by another worker or third parties and the necessary precautions are not taken despite notifying the employer of this situation.

However, there is no specific regulation regarding the actions to be taken by the employer to prevent sexual harassment or other forms of diversity related harassment in the workplace.

²³³ <https://www.tubitak.gov.tr/tr/haber/tubitak-sureclerinde-kadin-arastirmacilarin-katiliminin-artirilmasina-yonelik-politika-ilkeleri>

²³⁴ Article n. 105 of Law n. 5237.

Funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality at national and regional level

Turkey is not eligible for the ERDF funding, but there are many other national and international funding programmes focusing on gender, equality or empowerment of women. However, there are no specific programmes where gender in scientific research is promoted and funded.

The following are some examples of the funding programmes focusing on gender issues:

- EU Funded Programmes:
 - Promoting Decent Future of Work Approach With A Focus of Gender Equality (EuropeAid/167108/ID/ACT/TR)
 - Strengthening Capacity of National and Local NGOs on Combating Violence Against Women Grant Scheme (EuropeAid/133168/M/ACT/TR)
 - Promoting Women's Employment (PWE) Grant Scheme (EuropeAid/128148/D/ACT/TR)
 - Promotion and Protection Of Women's Rights (CFCU/TR0501.02/A1)
 - Grant Scheme for Increasing School Attendance Rates Especially for Girls (EuropeAid / 133687/M/ACT/TR)
 - Family Support Centres Fund (funded by the Ministry of Family and Social Policies)

4.6.2 The innovation ecosystem context analysis at YASAR

The following table presents the results of the context analysis conducted by YASAR in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Area	Indicator	Results												
Talents and workforce education and acquisition	High School and Higher Education students in STEM by gender, at regional and national levels	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>STEM High school students (2018/2019)²³⁵</p> <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>males</td><td>55.2%</td></tr> <tr><td>females</td><td>44.8%</td></tr> </table> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>STEM Higher education students (2018/2019)</p> <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>males</td><td>71.8%</td></tr> <tr><td>females</td><td>28.1%</td></tr> </table> </div> </div>	Gender	Percentage	males	55.2%	females	44.8%	Gender	Percentage	males	71.8%	females	28.1%
	Gender	Percentage												
	males	55.2%												
females	44.8%													
Gender	Percentage													
males	71.8%													
females	28.1%													
Researchers in STEM by gender in R&I, at national and regional levels	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p>STEM researchers in Turkey in 2020²³⁶:</p> <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>males</td><td>55.17%</td></tr> <tr><td>females</td><td>44.83%</td></tr> </table> </div>	Gender	Percentage	males	55.17%	females	44.83%							
Gender	Percentage													
males	55.17%													
females	44.83%													
Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender	Data not available													
Leadership	Patents registrations by gender	<p>Patent registrations in 2019: 1740²³⁷</p> <p>No data available regarding the gender</p>												

²³⁵ Ministry of National Education yearly statistics (2018-2019), https://sgb.meb.gov.tr/www/icerik_goruntule.php?KNO=361

²³⁶ <https://istatistik.yok.gov.tr/>

²³⁷ Turkpatent, 2020

	Founders and leaders of innovative enterprises and start-ups by gender	<p style="text-align: center;">Gender distribution of Startup Founders in Turkey 2018²³⁸:</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Gender distribution of Startup Founders in Turkey 2018</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Males</td> <td>81.00%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Females</td> <td>19.00%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	81.00%	Females	19.00%
Gender	Percentage							
Males	81.00%							
Females	19.00%							
Knowledge and tech production issues	Level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension	TÜBİTAK (The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey) is the main scientific body which aims at promoting science and technology and spreading basic and applied academic research in Turkey. TÜBİTAK also provides research funding and scholarships for researchers. The analysis of the TÜBİTAK's regulations on funding shows that there is no specific arrangements or measures to promote the integration of gender as a scientific dimension in research. Furthermore, the analysis of other national documents and regulations shows that there is no specific policy aimed at integrating gender in research at both national or regional level.						
	Level of consideration of the gender dimension in product/service development	While there are several academic articles regarding the gendering of the certain products, there are no specific requirements or standards in terms of gender-sensitive product or service production. Furthermore, there are no information available regarding the level of integration of gender dimension in product/service development in Turkey.						
Broader issues featuring the R&I 'cultures	Gender sensitiveness/family friendliness of supporting services to start up and entrepreneurship	<p>In Turkey, increasing women's employment appeared for the first time in the political agenda in the 1990's. From that period on, the topic started to be included in the Development Plans. Increasing women's employment and supporting female entrepreneurship gained momentum after Turkey gained the candidate status at the 1999 Helsinki Summit of the European Union. Since then, many initiatives, projects and funding mechanisms to support female entrepreneurship were developed. Some of the main mechanisms are listed below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KOSGEB Funds: KOSGEB (Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises Development and Support Administration) is the main body responsible for providing training and funding for the entrepreneurs in Turkey. The KOSGEB regulation regarding support programmes shows that there are some articles mentioning additional financial support for female entrepreneurs (article 7 of the 'Traditional Entrepreneur Support Program' and 'Advanced Entrepreneur Support Program'). Furthermore, according to recent news shared in the KOSGEB website, a special protocol between KOSGEB and DOĞTAŞ (a furniture production company) to support female entrepreneurship and employment was signed. According to it, 100 female entrepreneurs will be supported by both KOSGEB and DOĞTAŞ. - Social Assistance and Solidarity Foundation: it is an institution that provides financial support to low income people to start small businesses. The female applicants are prioritized in support decisions. 						

²³⁸ <http://startupmonitor.eu/EU-Startup-Monitor-2018-Report-WEB.pdf>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Credit Guarantee Fund (KGF): it acts as a guarantor for SMEs and non-SME enterprises that cannot get credit due to insufficient warranty. KGF supports SMEs and non-SMEs' access to finance. KGF also helps women entrepreneurs get the loan they need. The maturity of the loans provided by KGF is offered to women entrepreneurs with a 2-year grace period and a 5-year maturity. - The Women Entrepreneurs Association of Turkey (KAGIDER): it is a non-governmental organization aimed at strengthening women entrepreneurs not only economically but also socially and politically. KAGIDER provides training, counselling and mentorship activities to empowering women economically and strengthening women entrepreneurs. - Turkey Grameen Microfinance Program (TGMP): it is Turkey's first and only microfinance institution. TGMP provides financial services to women living in poverty. TGMP aims to support low-income families, providing appropriate financial services to women and encouraging them to make their own income-generating activities, economic and financial means to improve their social status and to create a sustainable living conditions.
	Perception of existing stereotypes/bias on gender and innovation/entrepreneurship	<p>Turkey is ranked 45th among 77 countries in The Global Entrepreneurship and Development Institute's (GEDI) Female Entrepreneurship Index 2015. According to the mentioned GEDI report Turkey is one of the countries that shows the biggest entrepreneurship gender inequalities. There are growing literature on female entrepreneurship in Turkey. In the literature, the problems faced by women entrepreneurs in Turkey were generally categorized under three headings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Problems faced at the business establishment stage; - Problems faced after the establishment of the business; - Existing structural problems. <p>About the main issues/barriers/challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in Turkey, the following ones are the main ones reported in the literature and reports:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Domestic responsibilities of women (such as burden of child, home and family care); - The socio-economic status of women (mainly low-income, home-based activities); - Traditional beliefs and pressure of the society; - Lack of education, training, knowledge and experience; - Lack of savings to establish their own business and difficulties in accessing financial resources. <p>In terms of gender stereotypes and media representation, literature shows that the existing social role of women is reinforced through advertisements and TV shows. However, there are growing number of media initiatives (social media posts, viral videos, etc.), especially during the week of March 8th (World Women's Day), which try to break gender stereotypes²³⁹.</p>

Table 9_ Results of the context analysis conducted by YASAR

²³⁹ Examples of initiatives: I can do both venture and career! <https://www.hurriyet.com.tr/yazarlar/dilek-dayinlarli/girisim-de-yaparim-kariyer-de-40563458>

I can have both baby and career! <https://pazarlamasyon.com/cocuk-da-yaparim-kariyer-de/>

Success has no gender https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PGQjMaasdU4&feature=emb_title

Let's break glass ceilings together! https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D8mesupTeTE&feature=emb_title

I am a Woman! https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OhXODo8BYhA&feature=emb_title

Celebrate your Power! https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XxDkvQBwWk&feature=emb_title

Fly for your Dreams! https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fH93Spf0e-o&feature=emb_title

Know us like this! https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tYh9aCW_Dyl&feature=emb_title

Examples of Viral Twits: <https://sosyalmedya.co/8-mart-dunya-kadinlar-gununde-markalardan-dikkat-ceken-paylasimlar/>

4.6.3 YASAR Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA

Results of the focus group with internal stakeholders

YASAR's researchers conducted the **focus group** on the 23rd September 2020 involving 9 internal stakeholders (3 males and 9 females) among mid-level managers, project experts in technology transfer, employees of the international office and the EU research center.

Concerning the **existing or prospective collaborations with external stakeholders** on broader areas, participants reported that Yasar University collaborates with a wide range of stakeholders: from other universities and education agencies, to public institutions such as ministries, TÜBİTAK (The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey), KOSGEB (Small and Medium Enterprises Development Organization of Turkey), but also NGOs, youth organizations and companies. While collaborations with public institutions, development agencies and other universities happen with the top management of such institutions, the ones with the business sector normally involve more "technical" people. In general, participants do not see any issue with reference to gender inequalities with universities, but they reported how in public bodies (like the Turkish Patent and Trademark Office), project teams and managers are usually male, while more women can be seen in collaborations with private stakeholders (companies and NGOs), especially for those collaborations concerning migration, project management, intercultural learning, youth, entrepreneurship and gender. A participants also stated that in some cases there might be even some imbalance regarding remuneration policies between men and women. Female participants reported that they experienced some difficulties as women in the African and Middle East markets due to cultural differences.

Concerning the ways in which gender inequalities **challenge** external stakeholders, in general participants stated that challenges are related to inequalities in salaries, gender balance in management positions, inequalities about women getting married and having children. However, they stressed how it depends on the specific field. For instance, in the university's Incubation Center, the difference between female and male entrepreneurs is quite big, teams tend to prefer male candidates since women are considered fragile and not patient. Also in educational agencies, there is a predominance of male employees, because partners prefer dealing with men in crucial phases of a partnership since they believe they are ones that can decide. About international offices, instead, women are the majority since "marketing" is considered a more suitable field for them, the same for EU offices, because gender equality is a priority for EU projects, therefore in such environments people are very much aware of the topic. Participants agreed that removing gender inequalities would benefit all collaborations with stakeholders.

About **actions** that external stakeholders put in place, this also depends on the specific field. Positive discriminations are made at International offices of universities in order to attract more female students. Concerning the EU projects office, the representative reported that their stakeholders, which are mainly other HEIs, youth organizations and NGOs have adopted measures to ensure gender equality, such as the implementation of quotas and other GE policies and practices.

Regarding **complementarities or synergies** with Yasar universities, experts mentioned the development of specific projects. For instance, they recalled the project in place with the Women Entrepreneurship cooperative and the first co-working space in Izmir founded by women. Other activities can be related to providing case studies to women who want to become entrepreneurs and encouraging them to apply for funds and manage projects. Another form of synergy would concern the involvement of policy makers, in order to have more resources for further supporting women.

Results of the survey to external stakeholders

The survey was submitted by 17 external stakeholders, 8 civil society organizations, 3 universities, 2 private companies, 2 public bodies, 1 foundation and 1 international organization. Stakeholders deal with a variety of activities/business:

- Media (companies)
- EU and social projects and funding (public bodies)
- Women rights and gender equality (universities and civil society organizations)
- Migration, refugees, integration issues (civil society organizations)
- Education, research, culture and art (universities and the foundation)
- Sustainable development, agriculture, economy (civil society organizations)
- Youth and mobility (civil society organizations)
- Health (civil society organizations)

The kind of collaborations in place with the Yasar University mainly concerns:

- EU funded projects
- Technical, research and educational cooperation
- Organization of seminars and events
- Trainings

Concerning the ways in which gender inequalities represent a **challenge** for the external stakeholders, almost half of the participants in the survey reported that gender inequalities do not represent a challenge for their own institution, since there is gender balance at all levels, and gender inequalities is an issue that women mainly experience outside their working place or that features other stakeholders the single institutions collaborate with. Universities reported that the challenge of gender inequalities is nestled in the culture of the country and well visible in the male-dominated structure of the administrative levels of public institutions (including universities). They claimed that there are some clear disadvantages for females in academic life compared to men. For female academics, obligations such as home and children make it difficult for them to participate in academic meetings and prevent them from taking part in administrative positions. Rectors and vice rectors are mostly men. Concerning students, gender inequalities differ in terms of departments. Science and engineering faculties are predominately male. The prejudice that women cannot be as successful as men in engineering and science fields influences a lot women choices. Interesting insights are provided by NOGs. One of them reported that since they work with refugees, their primary target are women and children. Women can be exposed to physical and sexual violence. Most of them do not work and do not have opportunities for socializing outside their own families, and this does not facilitate their participation to the activities organized by the NGO. Other civil society organizations stressed the important role of governmental institutions in setting policies in the area of gender, in order to raise the awareness on the issue and help the work of NGOs and academic institutions to be more effective.

As far as the potential **benefits** in solving gender inequalities challenges are concerned, the following ones were raised:

- More women in higher positions;
- More equal and peaceful work environments;
- Increase of the productivity, performance and efficiency;
- New perspectives, projects and collaborations;
- A more balanced and inclusive management approach;
- A healthier society structure and a more democratic university;
- Increased participation of women in social and economic life with consequent positive effects on the economic well-being of the country and social welfare of individuals.

About **measures** taken by the external stakeholders to tackle gender inequalities, companies reported paying attention in order to avoid gender discrimination in salary, working hours and work division and adopting the WEP's principles²⁴⁰. 2 out of 3 universities did not report any measures, while the other explained having a dedicated unit for sexual violence and harassment. Civil society organizations instead have many measures in place, for instance one of them reported having undertaken the Global Compact Women's Empowerment Turkey Izmir Platform's executive tasks; another one explained being member of associations and partner in relevant projects such as the Business Against Domestic Violence Project, in partnership with UNFPA and Sabancı University, for which they conduct studies about gender equality and domestic violence; another NGO explained having a team working on an action plan over the issue of gender based violence; another one provides training to youngsters on the topic; again a NGO reported guaranteeing gender balance in the volunteering teams, while another one organizes meetings at women's own houses in order to foster their participation. Public institutions reported paying attention to gender equality in the recruitment process as well as in the implementation of projects and other activities.

Regarding any **potential planned action**, only NGOs reported having planned any. The most interesting are the increase the number of women in the board and the development of a business model for women.

Concerning **additional collaborations or synergies** with Yasar University, the most relevant that were highlighted are the following ones:

- The development of jointly projects on the topic of gender equality;
- The organization of awareness events, meetings, lectures;
- Professional experience transfer;
- The organization of training programs on gender equality;
- Foster gender equality within university-industry collaborations;
- Jointly research activities/studies focusing on gender equality.

About **overlapping and competitive** areas, an university reported that often gender equality is seen as an abstract concept, while people need to see the practical benefits of it in order to take it seriously. Therefore, projects need to focus not only in studies but also in concrete outputs in order to strengthen the cooperation. Only an NGO identified the one of training as a possible competitive area. Another NGO reported that the principles of Yasar university and the NGO's values on the topic of GE overlap and this is positive also in terms of developing more effective and sustainable activities/projects, on the basis that the cooperation between an HE institution and NGO can create complementing rather than competing areas. Finally, another NGO explained that there should not be any competition as a result of the collaboration between institutions, but the overlapping of priority areas should be the main starting point for the cooperation itself.

Regarding **risks and obstacles** in the cooperation process, only a few were reported and are the followings:

²⁴⁰ <https://www.weeps.org/about>

- Gender equality is a sensitive topic in Turkey and this can be an obstacle and reduce the effectiveness of the collaboration;
- There is the risk that gender equality topics are brought only at academic and theoretical level, therefore an innovative approach should be adopted;
- Different political views on gender equality can be an obstacle, as well as the perspective of the political power;
- The difference between the factors that motivate academics working in the public and in the private sectors.

Results of the SNA

Regarding of the process followed by Yasar researchers, first of all it is important to highlight that the SNA excel was prepared according to the information provided by Knowledge Technology Transfer Office (responsible for local and national research and development projects funded by local or national funding organizations), the Project Support Office (responsible for research projects funded by Yaşar University using the institution's own funds) and the European Union Research and Application Center (responsible for all international and EU funded projects and collaborations). The EU Center coordinated the data collection process and compiled all the information on the excel to make it ready for uploading to Kumu system.

It is important to specify that collaborations tracked through the SNA represent only a part of the whole collaboration structure of the University. Indeed, the analysis only includes funded project partnerships while excludes collaborations that do not have local partners. Spontaneous cooperations and consultancies are not included in this analysis as it is difficult to trace them and document the nature and the scope of the collaborations.

Overall **39 external stakeholders** were included in the mapping. Many collaborations are with “civil society” stakeholders (16 out of 39 stakeholders, representing the 41%), followed by “industry & business” stakeholders (11, representing the 28%), “government & public sector” stakeholders (8, representing the 20,5%), “academy ad universities” stakeholders (3, representing the 7,7%) and “school” (1, representing the 2,6%). Among the listed collaborations, the most relevant are the ones with non-governmental organizations, governmental organizations and other research institutions, which represent the main group of stakeholders Yaşar University collaborates with in the frame of various projects.

About the **intensity** of collaborations with external stakeholders, most of them (29 out of 40, representing the 72,5%) are “one time” collaborations. Among “one time” collaborations, 11 are with “civil society” stakeholders, 10 with “industry & business” stakeholders, 4 are with the “government & public sector”, 3 are with “academia & universities” stakeholders and 1 with “schools”. Then, 10 (representing the 25%) are “frequent” collaborations and only 1 (representing the 2,5%) is a “solid” collaboration.

Concerning the **topic** of the collaborations, many of them (17 out of 40, representing the 42,5%) are about “scientific research”, followed by “education” (16 out of 40, representing the 40%), while 3 collaborations are about “transfer to market” and 4 about “science communication”.

Yasar University has effectively engaged in EU funded projects regarding gender equality. Gender is extremely relevant to the strategic objectives of the institution since it creates the opportunity for transferring good practices and encouraging local as well as international collaboration.

In total, **28 collaborations are led by women** at Yaşar University (72%). 13 of them concern collaborations with “civil society” stakeholders (46%) most of them from the Department of Science Culture, 8 with

“industry and business stakeholders” (29%), 5 with “government and public sector” stakeholders (18%), while 2 regard projects in place with “academia & universities” stakeholders (7%).

Concerning collaborations taking into account or focusing on **gender issues**, only 8 out of 40 (representing 20%) have such feature. The projects focusing on gender issues include projects in the frame of the European Researchers’ Night programme, the Erasmus+ programme and a service provision for the local women entrepreneurship cooperative. One of the four main themes of the ERN Project of the university was “science unites genders” and a series of activities and workshops were implemented to foster scientific curiosity of especially young girls. Partners of the project included four public bodies and a youth NGO. The Erasmus+ strategic partnership Project “Gender Perspective in EU Mobility Program” aimed at mainstreaming gender issues in EU Mobility Programs and increasing the visibility of gender issues in youth organizations. For this Project, the university collaborated with four youth organizations. University also provided technical expertise to the local women entrepreneurship cooperative in another collaborative Project.

All the mentioned projects take gender into account through their themes, objectives, activities, outputs and results.

The following pictures represent the results of the SNA conducted by YASAR according to the kind of stakeholders. Therefore, 5 different maps are displayed, one for each category of stakeholders: “academia & university”, “industry & business”, “government & public sector”, “civil society” and “schools”.

Per each map it is possible to identify the different departments of YASAR involved in the collaborations with the different external stakeholders (the nodes with a small green circle), the collaborations having female leaderships (the yellow nodes) and the collaborations focusing or considering gender (the connections in red).

Figure 19_Yasar collaborations with "Academia & universities" stakeholders

Figure 20_Yasar collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders

Figure 21_Yasar collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders

Figure 22_Yasar collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders

Figure 23_Yasar collaborations with "Schools"

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

4.6.4 Final remarks on the external assessment of YASAR

In Turkey specific legal texts/acts relevant to the field of gender equality policies in higher education do not exist. Gender equality is addressed within a broader concept of anti-discrimination and equality in various laws and acts included the Turkish Constitution. In 2015 a “Gender Mainstreaming” strategy was prepared by the Council of Higher Education. The strategy, which is under revision and is expected to be distributed to education institutions is aimed at guaranteeing gender equality provisions in higher education institutions. Dedicated policies of increasing the women’s participation in research were recently adopted by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey. Therefore, although there are pieces of legislation for equality and institutional efforts to include a gender dimension in higher education, the main issues in the area are: the lack of a national action plan for gender equality in academia and higher education, the lack of institutionalization of the gender studies, the lack of structured and collaborative research studies and the lack of data.

Female employment is a priority area for national strategic documents and dedicated provisions (even if not mandatory) exist in terms of quotas in management positions. However, female leadership in companies constitutes only the 13.40% in the whole Turkey. The rate falls even below when it comes to female ownership of firms and female top management, with only a 3.9%. Two are the main reasons identified that prevent women from reaching management positions: **religious and cultural perception of the family role of women** and lack of policies allowing the advancement of women by institutions and companies.

In order to increase the participation of women in the labour market, measures such as increased childcare services and flexibility in employment forms are foreseen. Also the maternity leave is regulated, while the paternity leave does not apply. Interesting provisions are foreseen with regards to childcare facilities (e.g. breastfeeding rooms in workplaces, childcare facilities for children 0-6 years old in big companies and possibility of part-time work).

An ad hoc legislation is foreseen as concerns sexual harassment, even though there is no specific regulation regarding the actions to be taken by the employer to prevent sexual harassment or other forms of diversity related harassment in the workplace.

Data collected regarding STEM students show that the share of female STEM students is higher than the male one as concern High School but then it dramatically decreases in Higher Education (from the 55,2% to the 28,18%). A lighter imbalance persists also about STEM researchers. Particularly low is also the share of women among founders and leaders of start-ups (19%).

No regulations are in place in terms of promoting the integration of gender as a scientific dimension in research both at national and regional level, neither any requirements or standards exist in terms of gender-sensitive product or service production.

Concerning the analysis of the collaborations in place with external stakeholders, YASAR collaborates with a wide range of stakeholders: from other universities, to public institutions, NGOs, youth organizations and companies. Even though many of the stakeholders involved in the survey reported that gender inequalities do not represent a challenge for them, from the survey and the focus groups it emerged that **gender inequalities are more visible in the projects’ team compositions, especially in case of public entities, in management positions and in salaries.** As far as actions already undertaken by stakeholder in order to fight gender inequalities are concerned, the implementation of quotas, such as measures for avoiding gender pay-gaps, discriminations in working hours and work division were reported by some of them. Many stated having adopted measures specifically addressing the issue of sexual harassment and GBV. Among the potential further synergies with YASAR on the topic, the main one that were identified by the internal and external

stakeholders were the development of joint projects on gender equality, the organization of raising awareness events and trainings and the involvement of policy makers. Indeed, being gender equality a very sensitive and controversial topic in Turkey, at political level, no involving policy makers might result in scarce results of the actions carried out.

As far as the SNA is concerned, 39 stakeholders were tracked, many of them belonging to the “civil society” sector. The analysis only included funded projects partnerships, among which EU funded projects regarding gender equality are counted. This explains the high number of collaborations led by women (28 out of 39). Concerning collaborations taking into account or focusing on **gender issues**, only 8 have such feature.

4.7 External assessment of IRB

4.7.1 The Spanish national legal and policy framework

Overall strategic gender equality policies at national level

Relevant legal acts in the field of gender equality can be identified both at national and regional level.

At the **national level** the followings can be mentioned:

- The Spanish Constitution (Constitución Española) and in particular, articles 9.2 and 14.
 - o Art 9.2: “It is incumbent upon the public authorities to promote conditions which ensure that the freedom and equality of individuals and of the groups to which they belong may be real and effective, to remove the obstacles which prevent or hinder their full enjoyment, and to facilitate the participation of all citizens in political, economic, cultural and social life”.
 - o Art. 14: “Spaniards are equal before the law and may not in any way be discriminated against on account of birth, race, sex, religion, opinion or any other personal or social condition or circumstance”.
- LOIMH 3/2007²⁴¹ about the equality between women and men, which at art. 64 establishes that the AGE²⁴² and its dependent organisms must implement a Gender Equality Plan;
- RDL 6/2019²⁴³ about the equality between women and men in employment;
- Ley 14/2011²⁴⁴, which specifically states the inclusion of the gender dimension in research;
- LO 1/2004²⁴⁵ about measures against gender violence, which at art. 6 states that educational administrations have to eliminate sexist stereotypes from educational materials;
- Collective labour agreement in the office sectors²⁴⁶;
- RDL 5/2015, which forces public universities to elaborate and implement an action plan.

More recently, in October 2020, two crucial Royal Decrees were published in the frame of gender issues and gender equality plans. In particular:

- Real Decreto ley 901/2020 regulating the content of equality plans and their registration;
- Real Decreto 902/2020 stating the principle of transparent remuneration and obligation of equal remuneration of equal value work.

Concerning the **Regional level** (Catalonia), the following provisions apply:

- Estatut d'autonomia de Catalunya (2006);
- L 17/2015²⁴⁷ about equality between man and women;
- L 11/2014²⁴⁸ which guarantees the rights of LGBTI people.

Special provisions are foreseen as concerns companies. Indeed, LOIMH 3/2007, at art. 45 states that companies with 250 employees or more have to implement a GEP. Also RDL 6/2019: the companies with 50 employees or more have to implement a GEP.

²⁴¹ LOIMH 3/2007: Ley Orgánica 3/2007, de 22 de Marzo para la igualdad efectiva de mujeres y hombres (transposed from the European Union Directives 2002/73/CE, 2004/113/CE and 97/80/CE of the European Council).

²⁴² The AGE (Administración General del Estado, General State Administration) is a public organization and it is the instrument through which the Government develops and implements its public policies or provides services.

²⁴³ RDL 6/2019: Real Decreto-ley 6/2019 de 1 de marzo, de medidas urgentes para garantía de la igualdad de trato y de oportunidades entre mujeres y hombres en el empleo y la ocupación.

²⁴⁴ Ley 14/2011: Ley de la Ciencia, la Tecnología y la Innovación.

²⁴⁵ LO 1/2004: Ley Orgánica 1/2004, de 28 de diciembre, de Medidas de Protección Integral contra la Violencia de Género

²⁴⁶ Organizational agreement: Convenio colectivo del trabajo del sector de oficinas y despachos de Cat 2019-21 (Cod. 79000375011994).

²⁴⁷ Llei 17/2015 del 21 de juliol d'igualtat efectiva de dones i homes, transposed from the Spanish LO 3/2007 and the European Union Directives 2002/73/CE, 2004/113/CE and the European Union Directives 2002/73/CE, 2004/113/CE and 97/80/CE of the European Council.

²⁴⁸ Llei 11/2014 per a garantir els drets LGBTI i per erradicar l'homofòbia, la bifòbia i la transfòbia.

A Register of Companies Equality Plans is created, as part of the Registries of collective labour agreements and agreements dependent on the General Directorate of Labour of the Ministry of Labour, Migration and Social Security and the Labour Authorities of the Autonomous Communities.

Both national and regional provisions encourages gender mainstreaming and the integration of the gender dimension in research.

Existence of specific mechanisms to promote the under- represented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation at national or regional level

At national level, Law 14/2011 applies, which establishes the basic organization of science and technology in Spain and defines a main instrument for strategic planning: “The National Plan for Scientific Research and Technological Development”.

The law aims to:

- Define a stable and merit-based career system capable of retaining and attracting talent and facilitating the mobility of researchers;
- Promote innovation and knowledge transfer to the business sector and society;
- Create a State Research Agency that will guarantee greater efficiency and effectiveness of public spending on R&D.

With special reference to the implementation of the gender perspective the law states that:

- *“The composition of the bodies, councils and committees regulated in this law, as well as the evaluation and selection bodies of the Spanish System of Science, Technology and Innovation, will conform to the principles of composition and balanced presence between women and men established by the LOIMH 3/2007”.*
- *“The Spanish Strategy for Science and Technology and the Spanish National Plan for Scientific and Technological Research and Innovation will promote the incorporation of the gender perspective as a transversal category in research and technology, so that its relevance is considered in all aspects of the process, including the definition of the priorities of the scientific-technical research, the research problems, the theoretical and explanatory frameworks, the methods, the collection and interpretation of data, the conclusions, the applications and the technological developments, and the proposals for future studies. These documents will also promote gender and women's studies, as well as concrete measures to stimulate and recognize the presence and role of women in research teams”.*
- *“The Information System on Science, Technology and Innovation will collect, process and disseminate data disaggregated by gender and will include presence and productivity indicators”.*
- *“The procedures for the selection and evaluation of research staff at the service of the public universities and the public research bodies of the General State Administration, and the procedures for granting fellowships, financed projects and subsidies by the research funding agents will establish mechanisms to eliminate gender biases, which will include, whenever possible, the introduction of confidential evaluation processes. These processes must assume that the reviewer does not know the personal details of the person being evaluated, in order to eliminate any discrimination based on birth, race, sex, religion or any other personal or social condition or circumstance”.*
- *“The Spanish Innovation Strategy and the State Innovation Plan will promote the incorporation of the gender perspective as a transversal category in all aspects of its development”.*
- *“Public Research Bodies will adopt Equality Plans within a maximum period of two years after the publication of this law (2011) and these will be monitored annually. These plans must include incentive measures for those centres that improve gender indicators in the corresponding annual monitoring”.*

Also, the RDL 2/2015, at art. 17.4 specifies that: *“Without prejudice to the provisions of the preceding paragraphs, collective negotiations may establish positive actions and measures to promote women's access to all professions.*

To this extent, it may establish reservations and preferences in the conditions of employment so that, under equal conditions of suitability, persons of the least represented sex in the professional group in question have a preference for being employed.

In the same way, collective bargaining may establish such measures in the conditions of professional classification, promotion and training, so that, under equal conditions of suitability, preference is given to persons of the under-represented sex to favour their access to the professional group or position. of work in question”.

Existence of national policies on implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees

Law 14/2011 applies also with reference to the promotion of underrepresented gender in management positions and committees. Indeed, it states that *“The composition of bodies, councils and committees regulated in this law, as well as the evaluation and selection bodies of the Spanish System of Science, Technology and Innovation, will be adjusted to the principles of composition and balanced presence between women and men established by the LOIMH 3/2007”*. According to art. 16 of LOIMH 3/2007, *“The Public Powers shall endeavour to comply with the principle of balanced presence of women and men in the appointments and designations of the positions of responsibility that correspond to them”*. Also LO 4/2007, at art. 13 establishes that *“The electoral norms regulated in the statutes of the universities must favor the balanced presence of women and men in the collegiate organs (social councils, governing council, cloister, boards of schools and faculty, and department councils)”*.

Existence of national legislation promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment

At national level the following regulations applies: RDL 2/2015; LOIMH 3/2007 and RDL 6/2019.

Article 5 of LOIMH 3/2007²⁴⁹ about *“Equal treatment and opportunities in access to employment, training and in professional promotion, and in working conditions”* establishes the principle of equal conditions and opportunities between women and men in the field of private and public employment. Such principle will be guaranteed in the access to employment (including self-employment), professional training and professional promotion, working conditions, remuneration and dismissal. It will also be applied in the affiliation and participation to trade unions and business organizations, or in any organization whose members exercise a specific profession, including the benefits granted by them.

Article 6, instead, explicitly deals with discrimination based on gender: *“Direct discrimination by gender is considered when a person has been or could be treated, based on his sex, less favourably than another in a comparable situation”*. While, *“Indirect discrimination on grounds of sex is considered to be the situation in which an apparently neutral provision, criteria or practice places persons of one sex at a particular disadvantage with respect to persons of the other sex, unless said provision, criterion or practice can be objectively justified in attention to a legitimate purpose and that the means to achieve said purpose are necessary and adequate. In any case, any order to discriminate, directly or indirectly, based on sex is considered discriminatory”*.

At the regional level, L 17/2015, art. 32 on the about the *“Promotion of equal treatment and opportunities for women and men in the workplace”* applies.

²⁴⁹ Ley Orgánica 3/2007, de 22 de marzo, para la igualdad efectiva de mujeres y hombres.

Existing policies at national level for reducing unequal gender division of labour related to housework and family care

Existing policies concern:

- Maternal leave²⁵⁰ which lasts 16 weeks from the birth, adoption or tutelage. The first 6 weeks are mandatory and then they can be transferred to the other parent (if any) or enjoyed part time, discontinuously within the 12 months after the birth. About economic conditions, maternal leave covers the 100% of the salary.
- Paternal leave²⁵¹ which initially lasted 13 days than it was increased to 4 weeks in 2017, to 8 weeks in 2019²⁵², 12 weeks in 2020 and it will reach 16 weeks in 2021.
- Paternal and maternal leaves can be extended if the newborn has been hospitalized or the birth has been premature.
- Breastfeeding leave²⁵³, the workers have the right of one hour of absence from work, which can be divided in two, for the care of the infant until he/she is nine months old. A three-month extension may be given if requested by both parents. This agreement implies that one of the parents charges the hour that is reduced by the INSS (social security) and the salary remains at 100%, and the other parent will have the hour reduction. This figure is called “prestaciones por corresponsabilidad en el cuidado del lactante” (benefits for co-responsibility in infant care).

Existing framework conditions regarding childcare facilities

In Spain there is no obligation to attend school before the age of 6. Therefore, there are no legislation regarding childcare facilities. Primary education (6-12 years), instead, is compulsory, all children are obliged to enrol.

Childcare facilities are divided per age range:

- 0-3 years: Public childcare facilities, whose cost is partially subsidized by the city council. These facilities have very high standards of quality (qualified staff, very cozy premises, etc). Nevertheless, the public offer does not cover all the needs.
- 3-6 years: Kindergarten. Public schools, 100% subsidized by the Regional Government.
- 6-12: Primary Schools. Public schools, 100% subsidized by the Regional Government
- 12-16: Secondary Schools. Public schools, 100% subsidized by the Regional Government.

Concerning data, the Barcelona target has not been reached yet for children from 3 to mandatory school-going age. In 2016, children aged 0-3 years old attending formal childcare or education were the 40%, while children 3-6 years old, the 95,2%.

Employment conditions at university and research organization

In Spain there are 82 universities (50 of which are public and 32 are private). Several laws, some at national level, some at a regional level, regulate universities.

The main laws/regulations at National level can be distinguished between Science and universities regulations, public service regulations and labour regulations.

Science and universities regulation:

²⁵⁰ Regulated by RDL 2/2015; LOIMH 3/2007, RDL 6/2019, RDL 295/2009.

²⁵¹ Introduced by LOIMH 3/2007.

²⁵² The RDL 6/2019 change term used for the paternal and maternal leave into “Child Birth Permission”, which is considered more inclusive and gender neutral.

²⁵³ LOIMH/2007

- The Universities code²⁵⁴ which gathers all the legal and regulatory standards on the matter of higher education. This Code is constantly updated, including all the regulations that may affect current legislation on this topic. The University Code comprises 12 sections:
 1. Spanish Constitution
 2. Organic Law on Universities
 3. Higher Education
 - i. Access to Higher Education
 - ii. Academic Ordering: Teaching and Degrees
 - iii. Specialized university education with access to regulated professions
 4. Students
 5. Teaching and Research Staff
 6. Higher Education Institutes
 7. Research
 8. University Councils
 9. Organization in the Higher Education fields
 10. Disciplinary Regime
 11. University Centres of Defence and Civil Guard
 12. Higher Education in the Autonomous Communities
- L 14/2011 which establishes the scientific track and regulates the general employment conditions for PhD Students, Postdocs and senior researchers.
- Real Decreto 103/2019²⁵⁵, which regulates the employment conditions of pre-doctoral researchers.
- Real Decreto 1313/2007 and Real Decreto 1313/2007 which foresee the requirements and regulations governing competitive access to lecturer positions in university teaching bodies.
- Real Decreto 1086/1989 regulating the salaries of lecturers/professors.
- Real Decreto 1052/2002, that regulates the procedure for obtaining the evaluation and certification for candidates who wish to apply for teaching and research staff positions at universities. The certification is granted by the National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation.
- Real Decreto 989/2008 about hiring of collaborating professors (which is considered as an exceptional case).

Public service regulations:

- Public function code²⁵⁶.
- Real Decreto Legislativo 5/2015²⁵⁷ regulating employment conditions of all public employees. It establishes the basis of the statutory regime of civil servants as well as applicable rules.
- General State Budget Laws.
- L 53/1984 about incompatibilities of staff in service for the public administration. It establishes that civil servants cannot hold more than one employment contract except in the case that that the public service calls for it. The exercise of those private activities that do not jeopardise the proper performance of the duties or endanger their impartiality or independence as public servants are allowed as well.

Labour Regulations:

²⁵⁴ <https://boe.es/legislacion/codigos/codigo.php?id=133&modo=1¬a=0>

²⁵⁵ "Estatuto del personal investigador predoctoral en formación".

²⁵⁶ https://boe.es/legislacion/codigos/codigo.php?id=003_Codigo_de_la_Funcion_Publica&modo=1

²⁵⁷ Real Decreto Legislativo 5/2015, de 30 de octubre, por el que se aprueba el texto refundido de la Ley del Estatuto Básico del Empleado Público.

- Each research organization has an agreement in force. For instance has the “*Convenio colectivo de trabajo del sector de oficinas y despachos de Cataluña para los años 2019-2021 (código de convenio núm. 79000375011994)*”.
- RDL 2/2015²⁵⁸, general frame that applies to all workers.
- Real Decreto 8/2015²⁵⁹ about social security law.
- Real Decreto Legislativo 5/2000²⁶⁰, about infractions of the social order.
- Llei Orgànica 11/1985²⁶¹, about trade union freedom/rights.

At Catalan level, the main laws that regulate the employment conditions are:

- Llei 1/2003 “Catalan Universities Law”.
- Reial decret 1313/2007 that regulates the access to a university professor position.
- Resolució TRE/309/2006 that regulates the inscription and publication of the collective agreement of the teaching and research personnel of Catalan public universities.
- Reial decret 1086/1989 which regulates the salaries of the universities professors.
- Public function code²⁶².
- Decret 1/1997 “Catalonia Decree of the Civil Service”.
- Llei 21/1987 about incompatibilities of staff in service for the public administration.

Also, the Government of Catalonia implemented CERCA, the current research centre system. All the centres in the CERCA system are organised according to a governance and operational model that ensures they are efficient and flexibly managed, can attract and promote talent, have able managers and function according to strategic planning.

In the latest year Catalan Research institutes are making efforts to develop a sectoral research agreement in order to develop a better and unified framework, including working conditions.

Existence of national programs which promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research

At National level LOIMH 3/2007 applies and in particular article 25 about “Equality in the field of higher education”, which states that “In the field of higher education, public administrations in the exercise of their respective competences will promote teaching and research on the meaning and scope of equality between women and men”.

At the Regional level, L 17/2015 applies. The Law states:

²⁵⁸ Real Decreto Legislativo 2/2015, de 23 de octubre, por el que se aprueba el texto refundido de la Ley del Estatuto de los Trabajadores.

²⁵⁹ Real Decreto 8/2015, de 30 d’octubre, pel que s’aprova el text refós de la seguretat social.

²⁶⁰ Real Decret Legislatiu 5/2000, de 4 d’agost, pel que s’aprova el text refós de la llei d’infraccions i sancions de l’ordre social.

²⁶¹ Llei Orgànica 11/1985, de 2 d’agost, de “llibertat sindical”.

²⁶² https://boe.es/legislacion/codigos/codigo.php?id=124_Codigo_de_la_Funcion_Publica_Normativa_Autonomica&modo=1

- The promotion of gender perspective in a transversal way and studies on the contribution of women throughout history in all fields of knowledge and in academic and research activities has to be included in the curriculum of undergraduate and postgraduate programs. The submission of applications for accreditation of undergraduate and postgraduate courses must be accompanied by a report detailing, where applicable, how the gender perspective has been incorporated into the curriculum or, if not, of the planned improvement plan to make it possible.
- The non-sexist and androcentric use of language in all its communications.
- The training in co-education of people who carry out teaching tasks, especially those who study teaching or education sciences and, where applicable, in undergraduate, postgraduate, master's and doctoral studies aimed at training teachers, professors and educators.

Also, in order to achieve the goal of effective equality of women and men in the field of university and research, universities must:

- Promote the work of women researchers and their participation in research groups and to make their contributions visible in the scientific and technical fields.
- Guarantee the training of their staff in matters of gender and women's perspective in each of the academic disciplines.
- Create specific modules or courses on gender and women's perspectives in each of the academic disciplines.

There are no programs to promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research at national level. The Spanish Ministry of Science has a “Woman in Science Unit” which is the organ to promote gender perspective in scientific, innovation and technology, but in fact it does not have a specific program.

National/ policies and legal frameworks on sexual/gender harassment in the workplace

At National level LOIMH 3/2007 applies and in particular article 48 about “*Specific measures to prevent sexual harassment and harassment based on sex at work*”. According to it “*Companies must promote working conditions that prevent sexual harassment and harassment on the basis of sex and arbitrate specific procedures for their prevention and to channel the complaints or claims that may be made by those who have been subject of this matter.*

For this purpose, measures may be established that must be negotiated with the workers' representatives, such as the preparation and dissemination of codes of good practices, the carrying out of information campaigns or training actions.

The workers' representatives must contribute to preventing sexual harassment and harassment on the grounds of sex at work by sensitizing workers to it and informing the management of the company about the conduct or behaviours of that they had knowledge and that they could promote it”.

At the Regional Level, article 33 of L 17/2015 about “*Prevention of sexual harassment and harassment based on sex in workplaces*” applies and states that “*Companies must adopt specific measures, negotiated with the legal working representative, to prevent sexual harassment and harassment based on sex, as well as promote working conditions that prevent this type of harassment.*

Companies must arbitrate specific procedures to respond to complaints or claims that may be made by those who have been subjected to harassment.

Employee representatives must actively contribute to the prevention of sexual harassment and harassment for reasons of sex, sensitizing workers and informing the company management of the behaviors detected that may lead to it.

Sexual harassment and harassment based on sex at work are considered direct discrimination based on sex, without prejudice to their classification as a crime”.

Funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality at national and regional level

No funding opportunities were identified.

4.7.2 The innovation ecosystem context analysis at IRB

The following table presents the results of the context analysis conducted by IRB in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Area	Indicator	Results						
Talents and workforce education and acquisition	High School and Higher Education students in STEM by gender, at regional and national levels	STEM High school students at regional level (2019)²⁶³ <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Males</td><td>46.50%</td></tr> <tr><td>Females</td><td>53.50%</td></tr> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	46.50%	Females	53.50%
		Gender	Percentage					
		Males	46.50%					
		Females	53.50%					
STEM High school students at national level (2019) <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Males</td><td>47.80%</td></tr> <tr><td>Females</td><td>52.20%</td></tr> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	47.80%	Females	52.20%		
Gender	Percentage							
Males	47.80%							
Females	52.20%							
STEM Higher education students at regional level - engineering (2019)²⁶⁴ <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Males</td><td>24.97%</td></tr> <tr><td>Females</td><td>75.06%</td></tr> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	24.97%	Females	75.06%		
Gender	Percentage							
Males	24.97%							
Females	75.06%							
STEM Higher education students at regional level - health (2019) <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Males</td><td>72.91%</td></tr> <tr><td>Females</td><td>27.09%</td></tr> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	72.91%	Females	27.09%		
Gender	Percentage							
Males	72.91%							
Females	27.09%							
		STEM Higher education students at regional level - science (2019) <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Males</td><td>51.50%</td></tr> <tr><td>Females</td><td>48.05%</td></tr> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	51.50%	Females	48.05%
Gender	Percentage							
Males	51.50%							
Females	48.05%							

²⁶³ Catalunya, G. d. (2020). Estadístiques. Tratto da Departament d'Educació: <http://educacio.gencat.cat/ca/departament/estadistiques/> and <http://ensenyament.gencat.cat/ca/departament/estadistiques/>

²⁶⁴ *ibid.*

		<p>STEM Higher education students at national level - engineering (2019)²⁶⁵</p> <p>51% 49%</p> <p>■ males ■ females</p>		
	<p>Researchers in STEM by gender in R&I, at national and regional levels</p>	<p>STEM researchers at regional level in 2018²⁶⁶:</p> <p>39% 61%</p> <p>■ males ■ females</p>		

²⁶⁵ *ibid.*

²⁶⁶ Dones i ciència, 2018 & Científicas en Cifras, 2018

	<p>Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Evolution of employment rate in ICT by gender (2014-2017)²⁶⁷</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Year</th> <th>Males (%)</th> <th>Females (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>2014</td> <td>59.80%</td> <td>40.20%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2015</td> <td>59.25%</td> <td>40.75%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2016</td> <td>59.39%</td> <td>40.61%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2017</td> <td>58.80%</td> <td>41.20%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Year	Males (%)	Females (%)	2014	59.80%	40.20%	2015	59.25%	40.75%	2016	59.39%	40.61%	2017	58.80%	41.20%
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<p>Leadership</p>	<p>Patents registrations by gender</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Patent registrations in 2019²⁶⁸</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Percentage (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>males</td> <td>75,6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>females</td> <td>24,4</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gender	Percentage (%)	males	75,6	females	24,4									
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²⁶⁷ Institute for women and equal opportunities, Women in Figures - Science and Technology – Employment & Oportunidades, I. d. (2018). Mujeres en Cifras - Ciencia y Tecnología - Empleo. Ministerio de Igualdad: inmujer.gob.es/MujerCifras/CienciaTecnologia/Empleo.htm

²⁶⁸ I. (2019). *World Intellectual Property Report 2019*. WIPO: https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_944_2019.pdf

	Founders and leaders of innovative enterprises and start-ups by gender	<p style="text-align: center;">Start-ups by founders' gender (2020)²⁶⁹</p> <table border="1" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Males</td> <td>82%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Females</td> <td>18%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	82%	Females	18%
Gender	Percentage							
Males	82%							
Females	18%							
Knowledge and tech production issues	Level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension	<p>Multiple institutes of gender research are spread throughout the Spanish territory. The majority of them are based at the Universities and they develop different tasks on gender research.</p> <p>Some examples:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Observatory for Equality: the Barcelona Autonomous University (UAB) among other research programmes and masters launches every year an award to the best Final Career Work (TFG) with Gender Perspective. Their objective is to raise awareness on gender equality and no discrimination, through the potentiation of the research. 2. The Alicante Institute of Gender Research develops the following lines of research: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Health and Gender - Gender, Literature and Linguistics - Development and Gender - Gender, History, Laws and Power - Education and Gender <p>They also develop PhD programmes and specific Master Programmes on gender.</p> 3. Universidad Complutense of Madrid: PhD programme in gender and feminist studies. 4. In 2016 a Spanish Academic Platform for the Gender and Feminist studies was created (EUFEM). One of its objectives is the creation of a specific area of knowledge in gender issues. 						
	Level of consideration of the gender dimension in product/service development	<p>“Gender Bias”²⁷⁰ is a service that, since 2003, provides abstracts of articles focused on evidences about differences by sex in the main health problems and specially in those problems specific of women.</p>						

²⁶⁹ Summit, S. S.-S. (2020). *Mapa del Emprendimiento 2020*. Tratto da Pymes y Autonomos: <https://www.pymesyautonomos.com/vocacion-de-empresa/mapa-emprendimiento-2020-spain-startup-startups-espanolas-alcizan-madurez>

²⁷⁰ <http://www.genderbias.net/resources.php>

		<p>Information on contents and existing processes related to the Gender Dimensions in innovation is very hard to find. However, according to the periodic report “Científicas en Cifras”²⁷¹, significant progress in embedding the gender dimension in the production of scientific knowledge has been done since 2007.</p> <p>In the absence of data, efforts have focused in collecting and analysing information, mostly unpublished, related to entrepreneurship and human resources, innovation financing programs, exchange activities and knowledge transfer and composition decision-making bodies.</p> <p>With the objective of analysing gender dimension in the content of the research calls financed by the State, new indicators have been included on "FEM - Feminist, Women's and Gender Studies". These indicators allow identifying and quantifying gender gaps, advances and setbacks which will after a processes of analysis provide the tools to create policies and new actions in favour of effective equality in the participation of women and men and in publicly funded research applications.</p>
Broader issues featuring the R&I ‘cultures	Gender sensitiveness/family friendliness of supporting services to start up and entrepreneurship	<p>Only in recent years it has become clear that women entrepreneurs can be a powerful economic resource. World Bank studies show that women entrepreneurs make significant contributions to economic growth and poverty reduction, not only in developing countries but also in already developed ones. Women entrepreneurs create new jobs for themselves and others. Besides boosting employment, women’s entrepreneurship also supports the diversification of business, stimulating innovation and diversification in management, in production and in marketing practices as well as in products and services. Women provide different solutions to management, organisational and business problems²⁷².</p> <p>In Spain, female entrepreneurship rate is increasing (from 5.6% to 6%) and the gap between men and women when it comes to entrepreneurship has decreased for the sixth consecutive year. Currently, every 10 Spanish men, 9 women start businesses (more than the European average, which is 6 women every 10 male entrepreneurs)²⁷³.</p> <p>Women entrepreneurs mostly create startups related to health, tertiary sector and robotics, Once they start their projects they run into various obstacles. For example, with a gender bias among potential investors, the OECD warns that the probability of a startup receiving funding is 10% higher in those founded entirely by men²⁷⁴.</p>
	Perception of existing stereotypes/bias on gender and innovation/ entrepreneurship	<p>The graph below represents the gender distribution of employment in companies financed by the CDTI (Spanish Center for the Technologic and Industrial Development) considering type of financing: loan (empleo préstamo) and grant (empleo subvención)²⁷⁵.</p>

²⁷¹ Ministerio de Ciencia, I. y. (2017). *Científicas en Cifras*. Unidad de Mujeres y Ciencia.

²⁷² Equality, E. I. (2020). Entrepreneurship. Retrieved from European Institute for Gender Equality: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/policy-areas/entrepreneurship>

²⁷³ Association, G. E. (2020). Global Entrepreneurship Monitor 2019-2020. London: GEM. <https://www.gemconsortium.org/file/open?fileId=50443>

²⁷⁴ Arroyo, I. R. (2019, October 2). Emprendedores Solo 1 de cada 5 emprendedores en España es una mujer. Retrieved from Retina: https://retina.elpais.com/retina/2019/10/02/talento/1569994978_745264.html

²⁷⁵ Innovacion, M. d. (2020). *Mujeres e Innovacion 2020*. Observatorio, Mujeres Ciencia y Observacion.

GRÁFICO 6.5 Distribución del empleo existente en las empresas financiadas por el CDTI según sexo y tipo de financiación, acumulado 2014-2018

Fuente: CDTI

The table below shows the distribution of women and men in the presidencies and corporate governance boards financed by the innovative business clusters, in 2018 (Blue, man; Violet women)

Distribución de mujeres y hombres en las presidencias y juntas de gobierno de las asociaciones empresariales financiadas con ayudas a Agrupaciones Empresariales Innovadoras (AEI), convocatoria 2018

	MUJERES	HOMBRES	% MUJERES	% HOMBRES	TOTAL
Presidencias de AEI	4	50	7%	93%	54
Miembros de las juntas de gobierno	92	577	14%	86%	669

Fuente: Dirección General de Industria y de la Pequeña y Mediana Empresa, Secretaría General de Industria y PYME, Ministerio de Industria, Comercio y Turismo

The following table instead shows the gender of promoters of technology companies in the CSIC (Spanish Superior Council of Scientific Research) (Blue, man; Violet, women)

	TOTAL EMPRESAS CREADAS	PROMOTORAS	PROMOTORES	% MUJERES
2012	7	13	12	52,0%
2013	10	7	13	35,0%
2014	9	8	10	44,4%
2015	12	13	16	44,8%
2016	9	6	14	30,0%
2017	5	4	1	80,0%
TOTAL	52	51	66	43,6%

Fuente: CSIC

Finally, the table below represents the gender distribution of R&D staff of companies of high and médium technology and other business sectors (Blue, men; Violet, women).

	2009			2017		
	MUJERES	HOMBRES	% MUJERES	MUJERES	HOMBRES	% MUJERES
Personal I+D AyMAT (EJC)	22.039	51.425	30%	24.665	54.899	31%
Personal I+D resto de sectores empresariales (EJC)	17.428	43.351	29%	16.603	40.936	29%
Personal investigador AyMAT (EJC)	10.661	25.478	30%	12.786	28.064	31%
Personal investigador resto de sectores empresariales (EJC)	6.940	18.037	28%	7.464	17.220	30%

Table 10_Results of the context analysis conducted by IRB

4.7.3 IRB Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA

Results of the focus group with internal stakeholders

IRB's researchers conducted the **focus group** on the 9th July 2020 involving 9 internal stakeholders (2 males and 7 females). The internal stakeholders hold the following positions: Head of Innovation Department, Public Engagement and Science Education Officer, Group Leader (Principal Investigator), internal Head of Core Faculties Department, Core Faculty Manager, Section Head Pre-Award Grants, Lab Manager, Head of the Human Resources Department, and Human Resources Generalist.

About existing **collaborations** participants in the focus group distinguished stakeholders according to different categories. For instance, for what concerns funding institutions, participants mentioned the Fundació Catalunya La Pedrera (private institution), FECYT (public/competitive funding), the Ajuntament de Barcelona (public/competitive funding). According to participants, Fundació Catalunya La Pedrera and FECYT take into account gender issues in their work. Concerning education related institutes, instead, the Escola Montserrat de Cornellà was mentioned, which collaborate with IRB in the Tandem project²⁷⁶ in which mainly women are involved (as project coordination and scientific staff). CESIRE (Centre de Recursos Pedagògics Específics de Suport a la Innovació i la Recerca Educativa), instead, provides guides and documents regards gender for institutional projects/programs. Among research institutes, companies and universities participants also mentioned the followings: FEDER²⁷⁷, Josep Carreras²⁷⁸, VHIR²⁷⁹, San Joan de Deu²⁸⁰ (collaborations in infrastructure), CRG-CNAG-BIST²⁸¹, UB/UAB²⁸², UPF²⁸³, VC, Clara Campas/Catalonio BIO²⁸⁴, Biocat²⁸⁵ and the Universidad de Santiago²⁸⁶ (which has a gender plan). Normally research centers consider gender as a priority in their work.

Regarding the ways in which gender inequalities represent a **challenge** for stakeholders, a participant reported that for instance the Fundació Catalunya La Pedrera has an important interest in all kind of gender topics, especially in vocational topics. FECYT and Ajuntament de Barcelona as public institutions, also, have gender always in their own agenda and are engaged in finding solutions to such issues. Educational institutes do not usually primarily focus on gender issues, however they are crucial institutions for promoting projects and gender initiatives. According to two participants, all institution have, in a more or less developed way, gender in their own agendas, especially research centres which according to them all are willing to adopt common plans towards gender equality.

About **actions** that stakeholders put in place, only a participant was aware of some actions put in place by some stakeholders. For instance, one of the stakeholders implemented trainings and courses, others developed dedicated projects while another one promotes female talents within the institution. The other participants did not know about any specific actions except celebration days like the International Women's day.

About **complementarities and synergies** between IRB and the external stakeholders, they observed that in some cases external stakeholders (especially founding agencies) can provide with funding while IRB can

²⁷⁶ <https://www.irbbarcelona.org/annualreport2018/en/institutional-highlights/tandem>

²⁷⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/funding/erdf/

²⁷⁸ <https://www.fcarreras.org/en>

²⁷⁹ <http://en.vhir.org/>

²⁸⁰ <https://www.sjdhospitalbarcelona.org/en>

²⁸¹ <https://www.crg.eu/> - <https://bist.eu/>

²⁸² <https://www.ub.edu/> - <https://www.uab.cat/en/>

²⁸³ <https://www.upf.edu/>

²⁸⁴ <https://www.cataloniabioht.org/>

²⁸⁵ <https://www.biocat.cat/en>

²⁸⁶ <https://www.usc.gal/en>

provide with research staff. Opening collaborations about the issue of gender equality can foster better and stronger relations among institutions and have a positive impact for the ongoing projects. A participant pointed out that a “common language” in the topic could be created as well as a common training process with a sharing of good practices.

Only a participant stated that there might be **overlapping**, but it has to be detected and used to copy “good” experiences/practices. IRB should take advantage from synergies instead of duplicating efforts.

About **risks**, two were identified: the risk of copying others project ideas and the risk that a collaboration becomes an “endogamy”, for this reason it is important to often change collaborators.

Results of the survey to external stakeholders

The survey was filled by 12 external stakeholders: 5 universities/research centers, 3 NGOs/Associations, 3 Foundations/funding organizations, 1 regional authority. They deal with a variety of activities/businesses:

- education and research (universities, research centers and the regional authority);
- inclusivity, women in STEM and cancer research (NGOs/associations);
- funding social inclusion, innovation and research programmes, fostering multidisciplinary research (foundations and funding organizations).

Concerning the **collaborations in place** with stakeholders, universities and research centers reported to have several research collaborations in place also related to the participations to projects and gender communities of practice, training actions about gender. NGOs and associations instead collaborate with IRB in the frame of round tables about inclusive and diverse working environments, research projects funded by the stakeholders and developed by IRB’s researchers, also some of the members of an association work at IRB. Foundations and funding organizations they collaborate with IRB in the frame of different programmes about the promotion of science vocations among young people (i.e. Joves i Ciència, Bojos per la ciència, Barcelona International Youth Science Challenge and Escoles Tàndem), as well as in training activities for researchers. About the regional authority, it holds the Secretary position in the Board of Trustees of IRB Barcelona and examples of collaborations with IRB are the application of a Code of Conduct, of the Research Impact Assessment and of the Data management strategy.

As far as the way in which gender inequalities represent a **challenge** for external stakeholders, universities and research centres reported facing the issue mainly at the PIs level since only a little percentage of PIs are women and at leadership level where women are underrepresented. However, the issues is not only present in the organizations’ structure but also at the level of integration of the gender dimension into training and teaching. NGOs/associations feel gender inequalities a challenge especially in terms of integration in STEM workplaces (especially for LGBTIQ+ people). Foundations and funding organizations explained that attracting girls in scientific research in their programmes is a challenge and therefore they are committed in making young scientists aware of gender inequalities. Also, they are aware of the fact that there is a lack of women (and minorities) in top management positions, as well as of a gender perspective in strategic decisions. One organization reported that gender inequality is a transversal issue affecting all society’s spheres, and it is committed to bring the issue in all its activities. The regional authority admitted that inequalities are present in its centres, since there are no female directors and a low percentage of female group leaders. Also in the Scientific advisory boards a certain degree of inequality exists.

About the **benefits** of solving the challenges, the most interesting ones that were identified are the followings:

- a more equal and diverse working environment and better working conditions for all;
- avoid loss of talents and attract new talents, reduce the leaky pipeline effect;
- avoid bias in scientific studies;
- guarantee a form of justice;
- a more diverse perspective from a strategic point of view;
- better prepare new generations of scientists aware about gender equality issues.

About **actions/measures** the organization has put in place to overcome gender inequalities, many actions were identified. Most universities and research centres reported having implemented Gender & Diversity Action Plans/GEPs for addressing gender inequalities. One of them reported having a policy regarding gender equality included an Office for Equality and Social Action, a Commission for Equality delegated from the Governing Council of the University and a Equality Gender Unit responsible for coordinating all policies arising from the decisions of the Equality Commission. Also the university has a protocol for the prevention, detection and action against situations of sexual and sexual harassment, gender identity and sexual orientation, and other sexist behaviours. Other actions concern the participation in gender related projects, the elaboration of tools, the organization of national competitions and online trainings for women entrepreneurs and for the university's staff, networking activities. Foundations and funding agencies work on:

- programmes addressing women and fostering their career advancements in science;
- having equal representation of males and females among the staff, researchers, speakers;
- dedicated calls for proposals and projects;
- Implementing instruments in the research selection process in order to avoid gender biases;
- Dedicated reports about women in STEM (e.g. "Women's Advancement and Leadership in the Biomedical Research Centres of Catalonia").

NGOs and Associations are committed in making the professional activity of women more visible and denouncing discriminatory situations. They organize meetings and seminars about the "glass ceiling" phenomenon, collaborate with national and international administrations and institutions about gender imbalances in STEM research. They take care about the evaluation process (when presenting calls) making sure that committees for evaluation are constituted by both women and men and that calls are advertised in a gender sensitive way.

The regional authority issued an Equal Opportunities and Diversity Management Plan. Its Diversity Commission prepared a pioneering protocol about evaluation processing tackling the issue of gender bias.

About potential new measures to adopt, Foundations mentioned the adoption of a GEP, while an Universities mentioned the new GEP for the period 2020-2024, where the following actions are included:

- promoting the work of women researchers and their participation in research groups and making their contributions visible;
- promoting balanced representation also in the evaluation process adopting a gender perspective to avoid any type of direct or indirect discrimination;
- promote research and transfer projects and establish incentives for research whose research focus is women, gender, diversity or intersectionality.

Concerning further **complementarities or synergies** with IRB, the following ones were identified:

- joint awareness campaigns;
- co-participation in projects;
- sharing of equality policies;
- support and provide advice to IRB about measures that can be implemented to make it a more inclusive space (NGO);
- learning process in order to understand how measures related to the selection procedures, the promotion of women careers are put in place in order to design funding programmes (for funding agencies);
- preparation of periodic research and transfer indicators disaggregated by gender;
- organization of training programmes;
- sharing of experiences and best practices;
- organization of round tables, workshops on gender discriminations and diversity.

No potential **overlapping and competitive** actions were identified.

About **risks**, the ones that were identified are the risk that projects become too big and therefore difficult to manage, the possibility that measures and policies are not actually implemented and no benefits emerge. Also the risks of workload and resistances to adopt structural changes actions were highlighted. Finally, the dispersion of the results was another risk pointed out, even though a stakeholder observed that it can be avoided if from the beginning of the collaboration a system of shared data, allowing an evolutionary study and not a fixed picture of the results of the different working indicators, is generated.

Results of the SNA

IRB Barcelona has a wide range of collaborations related to biomedical research. Regarding of the process of how stakeholders were chosen, it was structured in two phases. Initially, the “Caliper working group”, with the collaboration of the Directorate and the Equality and Diversity Committee, elaborated a list of “key” stakeholders, using, as main criteria, the Institute’s most important/frequent interactions.

As a second step and as suggested in the external assessment guidelines, a focus group was conducted gathering the opinion of IRB key members, considering different areas and working aspects of the Institute. The feedback, suggestions, and opinions collected from the focus group were analysed and then added to the final list.

Overall, **50 external stakeholders** were included in the mapping. The majority of collaborations are with “academia & universities” stakeholders (19 out of 50 stakeholders, representing the 38%), followed by “government & public sector” stakeholders (16, representing the 32%), “industry & business” stakeholders (8, representing the 16%), “civil society” stakeholders (4, representing the 8%) and “others” (3, representing the 6%). Concerning the most relevant stakeholders, they are mainly Universities, academia and research agencies (ICREA, CSIC), National and International public funding institutions such as Spanish Ministerio, Generalitat, EU and also private (competitive grants and fellowships provided by La Caixa, BBVA, la Marató TV3, to mention a few).

About the **intensity** of collaborations with external stakeholders, most of them (32 out of 57, representing the 56%) are “solid” collaborations. Among “solid” collaborations, 16 are with “academia & universities” stakeholders, 9 with “government & public sector”, 3 with “civil society” stakeholders, 2 with “industry & business” stakeholders and 2 with “others” stakeholders. Among “others”, IRB researchers included Bank Foundations and the EC recruitment portal.

Concerning the **topic** of the collaborations, most of them (38 out of 57, representing the 66,6%) are about “scientific research”, 11 about “transfer to market”, 5 about “raising awareness” and 3 about “science communication”.

The network also includes other research institutions (BIST and Parc institutions, Large facility centres) and spin-off companies or small companies that help IRB to explore potential applications of the research. Fruitful collaborations are also in place with patient associations and hospitals. Also, IRB is highly committed to communication activities aimed to reach the general public (interviews in TV and media) and young students (to spread the interest in STEM and research) through Open days’ sessions.

With respect to competitive grants and projects, only 2 out of 25 Grant Leaders (GLs) are female, and they are indicated in the SNA.

Regarding collaborations, overall, **18 are led by women (36%)**. 7 of them concern collaborations with “government and public sector” stakeholders (45%), 5 regards projects in place with “academia & universities” stakeholders (25%), 2 with “industry and business” stakeholders (10%), 2 with “civil society” stakeholders (10%) and 2 with “others” stakeholders (10%). Looking at the figures below the gap is more visible in the one related to “industry & business” stakeholders.

11 (representing the 19,3%) are the collaborations taking into account and/or focusing on gender (5 of them have a female leadership). Such collaborations are mainly with organizations which are part of BIST (Barcelona Institute of Science and Technology). IRB and the HR departments of such organizations are constantly participating in working groups with the objective of analysing gender equality plans, salary audits, work-life balance measures, etc. Among the projects with BIST centres there is the “Mothers of Science” programme, which is aimed at providing support to young mothers during their Postdoc, to support them in advancing their career and find a better work/life balance during this period of life. In addition, the IRB Barcelona is part of a community of practices called ACT LifeSciCoP from CRG (practical solutions to change institutional culture towards Gender Equality).

In a more broad and regional scope, the IRB Barcelona has constant interactions and collaborations concerning good practices exchange, mentoring programs and training actions, with the CERCA members (Agency for the Research Centres of Catalonia). Also, IRB collaborates, as far as events organization is concerned, with AMIT (Asociación de Mujeres Investigadoras y Tecnólogas/ Association of Women Researchers and Technologists) and PRISMA (Asociación para la Diversidad Afectivo-Sexual y de Género en Ciencia/ Association for Sexual-Affective and Gender Diversity in Science).

The following pictures represent the results of the SNA conducted by IRB according to the kind of stakeholders. Therefore, 5 different maps are displayed, one for each category of stakeholders: “academia & university”, “industry & business”, “government & public sector”, “civil society” and “others”.

Per each map it is possible to identify the different departments of IRB involved in the collaborations with the different external stakeholders (the nodes with a small green circle), the collaborations having female leaderships (the yellow nodes) and the collaborations focusing or considering gender (the connections in red).

Figure 24_IRB collaborations with "Academia & Universities" stakeholders

Figure 25_IRB collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders

Figure 26_IRB collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders

Figure 27_IRB collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders

Figure 28_IRB collaborations with "others" stakeholders

4.7.4 Final remarks on the external assessment of IRB

In Spain relevant acts in the field of gender equality can be identified both at national and regional level. Indeed, specific laws/regulations prescribe the equality between women and man also in employment and foresee mechanisms for fighting discriminations based on gender. Dedicated measures exist for the implementation of the gender perspective in Higher Education, such as: adoption of quotas for the composition of bodies, councils and committees, the **integration of the gender dimension in research**, the collection of data disaggregated by sex, procedures for selection and evaluation of staff and for funding with no gender bias, GEPs for public research bodies.

Ad hoc policies are also in place about work life balance (i.e. maternity and paternity leave and breastfeeding leave), while no legislation exists in terms of childcare facilities since there is no obligation of attending school before the age of 6.

A dedicated policy applies for what concerns sexual harassment at work, which specific duties from the side of the employers.

According to the data collected, a slight unbalance is visible about STEM High School students, while looking at Higher education, the unbalance is more or less clear according to the specific discipline. Indeed, while the share between male and female students is similar in disciplines like science, it is very divergent in engineering, where the share of male students is predominant (around the 75% at both national and regional level) and health where the share of female students widely exceeds the one of male students (around 72% at both levels).

The evolution of employment rate in ICT does not show a great improvement over the years taken into consideration (from the 40,20% in 2014 to the 41,20% in 2017). Quite limited is the share of females regarding patent registrations (24,40%) as well of start-ups funders (18%).

While information on contents and existing processes related to the gender dimension in innovation were not identified, according to the periodic report “Científicas en Cifras”, in Spain, significant progress in embedding the gender dimension in the production of scientific knowledge has been done since 2007.

Concerning the analysis of the collaborations in place with external stakeholders, IRB collaborates with stakeholders belonging to different categories: funding institutions, education and research institutes, NGOs and companies. According to the results of the focus group, **all IRB external stakeholders have, in a more or less developed way, gender in their own agenda**. External stakeholders reported through the survey that the issue of gender inequalities is not only present in the organizations’ structure (at top management positions) but also at the level of integration of the gender dimension into training and teaching. This constitutes a good ground for setting up a pro-active R&I Hub. Other challenges identified regarded the involvement of girls in STEM disciplines. Most of the stakeholders involved reported having implemented some measures: from the adoption of Gender & Diversity plans or other specific policies towards gender equality, to the participation into dedicated projects, the organization of trainings and events as well as dedicated measures for the evaluation processes. Regarding synergies with IRB, research collaborations, joint projects, sharing and learning process about equality policies/measures, organization of workshops, events and trainings were identified.

As far as the SNA is concerned, 50 stakeholders were tracked, many of them belonging to the “academia & universities” sector. 18 collaborations are led by women while 11 take into account and/or focus on gender. Women lead a minority of the collaborative projects with industry/business stakeholders.

4.8 External assessment of UNILE

4.8.1 The Italian national legal and policy framework

Overall strategic gender equality policies at national level

The main source of the Italian legislation is represented by the Constitution of the Italian Republic, which at article 3 states that *“All citizens shall have equal social dignity and shall be equal before the law, without distinction of gender, race, language, religion, political opinion, personal and social conditions.*

It shall be the duty of the Republic to remove those obstacles of an economic or social nature which constrain the freedom and equality of citizens, thereby impeding the full development of the human person and the effective participation of all workers in the political, economic and social organisation of the country”.

Other crucial articles of the Constitution are art. 37 about equal treatment of male and female workers: *“Women workers shall be entitled to equal rights and equal pay as men for similar jobs. Working conditions shall allow women to fulfil their essential role in the family and ensure appropriate protection for the mother and child”* and art. 51 on the promotion of equal opportunities in public offices: *“All citizens of either sex are eligible for public offices and for elective positions on equal terms, according to the conditions established by law. To this end, the Republic shall adopt specific measures to promote equal opportunities between women and men”.*

Summing up, the constitutional framework contains a set of principles that represent the basis for a further regulation of the matter also at institutional level.

Besides, other laws (ordinary laws) are worth to be mentioned as far as the promotion of equal opportunities and contrast of gender discrimination are concerned.

In particular, the Legislative Decree n. 198 of the 11th April 2006 (“Code of equal opportunities”)²⁸⁷ at art. 1 states: *“The provisions of this decree are aimed at eliminating any distinction, exclusion or limitation based on sex, which has as its consequence or purpose to compromise or prevent the recognition, enjoyment or exercise of human rights and fundamental freedoms in the political, economic, social, cultural and civil fields or in any other field.”*

However, it is important to point out that the abundance of principles and legislation is not accompanied by a substantial apparatus that guarantees its effectiveness.

According to the Code the “National Committee for the Implementation of the Principles of Equal Treatment and Equal Opportunities for Workers” (“Comitato nazionale per l'attuazione dei principi di parità di trattamento e uguaglianza di opportunità tra lavoratori e lavoratrici”) was set up by the Ministry of Labour. The aim of this body is to remove discrimination and promote equality between men and women in accessing employment, promotions and vocational trainings and working conditions. The tasks of the Committee are listed in the above mentioned “Code of equal opportunities” (art. 10.). Among them it is worth to highlight the one of formulating, by February of each year, guidelines on the promotion of equal opportunities for initiatives of the Ministry of Labour. This planning constitutes the basis for the financing of positive action programmes that should be prepared by the Ministry in the following financial year. The last financing dates back to 2015 and the total amount committed was EUR 183,550.00.

²⁸⁷ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/anteprema/codici/pariOpportunita>

It is worth to mention that members of the Committee shall not receive any kind of remuneration or reimbursement of expenses. Therefore, the work carried out by the members should be of a voluntary nature and not of a professional nature.

Existence of specific mechanisms to promote the under- represented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation at national or regional level

There are no existing mechanisms at National/Regional levels, but some positive actions in building GEPs in some Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation Institutions and Organisms.

Existence of national policies on implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees

Law n. 215, of the 23rd November 2012²⁸⁸, on “Provisions to promote the rebalancing of gender representation in local and regional councils and councils. Provisions on equal opportunities in the composition of competition commissions in public administrations”, implements the principle of equal access to elected offices at the regional and local level. The law states that in the frame of the elections of municipal councils with a population of more than 5,000 people, women and man can respectively represent more than two-thirds of the overall candidates. In municipalities with a population of more than 15,000, the non-compliance with the mentioned quota leads to the decline of the list.

For all municipalities, with a population of up to 5,000, it is still established that both sexes shall be guaranteed on the candidate lists. The consecutive law n. 56/2014²⁸⁹ stated that in Municipalities with a population of more than 3,000 inhabitants, each sex should be represented at least in the measure of 40%.

Municipalities and provinces are required to 'ensure' the presence of both sexes in non-elective councils and collegiate bodies. This also applies to the institutions, companies and corporations that are connected with the local authorities themselves.

Existence of national legislation promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment

When analysing the existence of national legislation promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment, we need to focus on different concepts:

²⁸⁸ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2012/12/11/012G0237/sg>

²⁸⁹ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2014/4/7/14G00069/sg>

- Principle of equality, which is stated by the already mentioned art. 3 of the Constitution. In particular, from the article two principles emerge: the one of equality and the one of “good sense”, elaborated by the “Constitutional Court”.
- Principle of equal treatment: according to a “good sense” principle the legislator must treat equal situations equally. Therefore, differences in regulatory treatment are not allowed unless reasonably justified by different circumstances. Being the principle of equal treatment a limitation of private autonomy, it must be expressly stated in a legislative provision.
- Principle of prohibition of discrimination: the principle of equal treatment leads to the one of prohibition of discrimination, meaning that the features listed in art. 4 of the Constitution (gender, race, language, religion, political opinion, personal and social conditions) cannot justify differentiated legislation. The prohibition of discrimination means that a person must not be harmed by belonging to a disadvantaged social group.
- Principle of equal opportunity: in 1991 the Italian legislator adopted the Law no. 125, which, in relation to the previous discipline on gender equality (L. n. 903/1977), represents the awareness of the necessity to go beyond the mere formal equality in order to promote the change in the social reality and allow women to achieve equal opportunities. The followings are the main elements characterizing the law: the introduction of positive actions as tools to achieve equal opportunities and the introduction of the distinction between “Direct discrimination” and “Indirect discrimination”. Currently the law n. 125 has converged into the “Code of the equal opportunities for men and women” (decreto legislativo n. 198, of 2006).
- Principle of “differentiated law” in order to protect specific categories of subjects from discrimination.

The already mentioned “*National Committee for the implementation of the principles of equal treatment and equal opportunities between workers and women workers*”, promotes, within the competence of the State, the removal of discrimination and any other obstacles that in fact limits equality between men and women in access to employment, promotion and vocational training, in working conditions including pay, as well as in relation to the collective supplementary pension schemes.

Worth to mention is also the Legislative Decree n. 5 of the 25th January 2010²⁹⁰, regarding the “Implementation of Directive 2006/54/EC on the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation”.

Existing policies at national level for reducing unequal gender division of labour related to housework and family care

Relevant legislations/policies are mainly meant at protecting the “working mother” and are the followings:

²⁹⁰ <https://www.camera.it/parlam/leggi/deleghe/10005dl.htm>

- Art.37.1 of the Italian Constitution: “To working women are entitled equal rights and, for comparable jobs, equal pay as men. Working conditions must allow women to fulfil their essential role in the family and ensure appropriate protection for the mother and child”. It therefore stated two different principles, the one of equal treatment for working women and men and the differentiated protection of the working mother (unequal or differentiated law).
- Legislative decree n. 151/2001²⁹¹ about measures to support maternity and paternity.
- Law n. 80/2015²⁹² on the reconciliation of care, life and work needs which has given a legal discipline that aims to overcome the differentiated protection of motherhood. It regulates the parental leave, consisting in a period of optional absence from work allowing working parents to take care of their children. Parents can use it during the first 12 years of the child’s life. The parental leave may be used by the parents for a maximum of 10 months, which may be raised to 11 months if the father is absent for at least three months. For this period, the Italian social welfare system pays an allowance equal to the 30% of the salary.

Existing framework conditions regarding childcare facilities

The main evidences of the ISTAT report “Nurseries and educational services for children”²⁹³ show the persistence of important critical issues: a structural lack in the availability of educational services for early childhood compared to the potential needs (children under 3 years of age), and a deeply irregular distribution on the national territory. The coexistence of situations of excellence in some areas and of serious shortage in others, if on the one hand can offer interesting organizational models, on the other hand strongly undermines the guarantee of equal educational opportunities where the availability and accessibility to services is severely limited. The traditional role of nursery school as a care service and support to women's work has meant that the spread of early childhood services was guided by the degree of economic development of the territories. The result is a strong heterogeneity of public and private offer in the territory, which also reflects the choices made over decades by regional and municipal governments, which created strong inequities in the opportunities for access in the South. In the southern regions, indeed, the number of places available in the public and private supplementary services does not reach on average 15% of the potential needs, against an Italian average of 24.7%. The lack of public investment and current expenditure by the municipalities is often associated with a scarcity of private services as well. The possibility of using educational services for early childhood also weighs on an economic constraint, since the cost of services is high and cannot be sustainable for families with low incomes and at risk of poverty. Paradoxically, children who should benefit of educational opportunities offered by nurseries at most, as means for fighting the risks of isolation and social exclusion, are the ones who remain excluded. The State contributions introduced by Law no. 232/2016²⁹⁴ (“nest bonus”) have given a positive impulse to the development of the system, probably contributing to the increase in demand of the use of such services. A further impulse from this point of view is expected, although not yet observable, from the subsequent enhancements of this measure that raise the payable amount on the basis of the economic situation of families.

At National level, the progressive establishment of the integrated system of education (“ZEROSEI” System²⁹⁵), initiated by Law n. 107/2015²⁹⁶ and the subsequent Legislative Decree n. 65/2017²⁹⁷, represents a significant innovation which is the basis of the many legislative acts issued and in progress by the regions in recent years.

²⁹¹ http://presidenza.governo.it/USRI/magistrature/norme/dlvo151_2001_n.pdf

²⁹² <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2015/06/24/15G00094/sg>

²⁹³ https://www.istat.it/it/files//2020/06/report-infanzia_def.pdf

²⁹⁴ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2016/12/21/16G00242/sg>

²⁹⁵ <https://www.secondowelfare.it/focus-zerosei/la-normativa-sullo-zero.html>

²⁹⁶ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2015/07/15/15G00122/sg>

²⁹⁷ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2017/05/16/17G00073/sg>

The "new" system consists of educational services for 0-3 years old children and kindergartens for 3-6 years old children, with the aim of overcoming the distinction between the two age groups.

At Regional level (Regione Puglia) some funds have been dedicated to these actions, in addition to the National ones. The allocation of the 2019 fund (16,523,339.00 euro in addition to 5,757,016.58 euro of regional co-financing) is defined in the annex of DGR 2398/2019²⁹⁸. In particular, 50% of the national quota funds infrastructure projects (renovations, requalification, new construction, etc.), while the remaining quota, the management costs of educational services and canteen contributions for state schools and private schools that are recognised by the State, which benefit from about 4.7 mln/€ of regional co-financing.

Employment conditions at university and research organization

Positive actions as a mean of achieving equal opportunities are provided in the legislative decree n. 198/2006, the Code of Equal Opportunities. The Code, indeed, establishes that Public Administrations (Universities included) have to prepare three-year **positive action plans**, aimed at ensuring the removal of obstacles which, in fact, prevent the full realization of equal opportunities between men and women. More in detail, the positive actions shall be directed at:

- the elimination of the de facto disparities in training which hamper the access to employment and career progression;
- overcoming conditions, organisations and work distribution which cause different effects in training, career and salary treatment;
- supporting the reconciliation between work and family responsibilities.

Besides the elaboration of positive actions plans, according to the Law 183/2010²⁹⁹ each public administration has to establish a "Unique guarantee committee" ("Comitato Unico di Garanzia"), which tasks are:

- to ensure, in the context of public work, gender equality and equal opportunities, eliminating all forms of psychological moral violence and direct and indirect discrimination relating to gender and age;
- to optimise the productivity of public work;
- rationalise and make the organization of the public administration efficient, also in the field of equal opportunities, discriminations and well-being of workers.

Existence of national programs which promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research

There is no national programs but each institution provides its own programme on the basis of the actual National regulation reported above.

²⁹⁸ https://www.consoziomipa.it/db_normativa/puglia/puglia_dgr_2398_2019.pdf

²⁹⁹ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2010/11/09/010G0209/sg>

National/ policies and legal frameworks on sexual/gender harassment in the workplace

The legislative decree n. 145/2005³⁰⁰ defines as discriminatory a conduct if it consists in *“undesirable behaviour carried out for sex-related reasons, having the purpose or the effect of violating the dignity of a worker and creating an intimidating, hostile, humiliating, degrading or offensive atmosphere”*.

Article 28 of the legislative decree 150/2011³⁰¹ provides with a procedural protection against discrimination.

The Legislative Decree n. 165 of the 30th March 2001³⁰² which regulates the work in public administrations provides that *“The employee victim of gender violence included in specific protection paths, duly certified by the social services of the municipality of residence, may apply for transfer to another public administration located in a municipality other than the one of residence”*.

The Law n. 107/2015³⁰³ “Reform of the national education and training system and delegation for the reorganization of existing legislation” (“Riforma del sistema nazionale di istruzione e formazione e delega per il riordino delle disposizioni legislative vigenti”), at article 1, provides that *“the three-year training plan shall ensure the implementation of the principles of equal opportunities by promoting gender equality education, the prevention of gender-based violence and all forms of discrimination in schools of all levels, in order to inform and raise awareness among students, teachers and parents on these issues”*.

Again, the already mentioned Legislative Decree n. 80/2015, at art. 24 states that *“the employee of a public or private employer included in the protection pathways related to gender violence, duly certified by the social services of the municipality of residence or by the antiviolenza centers or refuge houses shall have the right to abstain from work for reasons related to the aforementioned protection course for a maximum period of three months”*. During the period of leave, the worker is entitled to an allowance corresponding to the last salary.

Funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality at national and regional level

No funding opportunities were identified.

³⁰⁰ <https://www.camera.it/parlam/leggi/deleghe/05145dl.htm>

³⁰¹ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2011/09/21/011G0192/sg>

³⁰² <http://www.parlamento.it/parlam/leggi/deleghe/01165dl.htm>

³⁰³ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2015/07/15/15G00122/sg>

4.8.2 The innovation ecosystem context analysis at UNILE

The following table presents the results of the context analysis conducted by UNILE in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Area	Indicator	Results						
Talents and workforce education and acquisition	High School and Higher Education students in STEM by gender, at regional and national levels	STEM Higher education students at national level (2019)³⁰⁴ <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Males</td><td>35,6 %</td></tr> <tr><td>Females</td><td>64,40 %</td></tr> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	35,6 %	Females	64,40 %
		Gender	Percentage					
		Males	35,6 %					
		Females	64,40 %					
		STEM Higher education students at UNILE (2019) <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Males</td><td>73,2 %</td></tr> <tr><td>Females</td><td>26,8 %</td></tr> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	73,2 %	Females	26,8 %
		Gender	Percentage					
Males	73,2 %							
Females	26,8 %							
STEM Higher education students at UNIBA & Polytechnic (2019) <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Males</td><td>34,1 %</td></tr> <tr><td>Females</td><td>65,9 %</td></tr> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	34,1 %	Females	65,9 %		
Gender	Percentage							
Males	34,1 %							
Females	65,9 %							
Engineering students at national level (2019) <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Males</td><td>26,8 %</td></tr> <tr><td>Females</td><td>73,2 %</td></tr> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	26,8 %	Females	73,2 %		
Gender	Percentage							
Males	26,8 %							
Females	73,2 %							
Engineering students at UNILE level (2019) <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Males</td><td>29,3 %</td></tr> <tr><td>Females</td><td>70,7 %</td></tr> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	29,3 %	Females	70,7 %		
Gender	Percentage							
Males	29,3 %							
Females	70,7 %							
Engineering students at UNIBA & Polytechnic (2019) <table border="1"> <tr><th>Gender</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Males</td><td>27,8 %</td></tr> <tr><td>Females</td><td>72,2 %</td></tr> </table>	Gender	Percentage	Males	27,8 %	Females	72,2 %		
Gender	Percentage							
Males	27,8 %							
Females	72,2 %							

³⁰⁴ <https://www2.almalaurea.it/cgi-php/universita/statistiche>

	<p>Researchers in STEM by gender in R&I, at national and regional levels</p>	<p align="center">STEM researchers in public research institutes (2015-2017)³⁰⁵:</p> <p>In the Italian research system, the women employed in the research careers (not only STEM) are respectively 39.9% in Universities, 45.9 % in Public Institutions for research and 21.6% in business (CNR, 2019).</p> <div align="center"> <p>■ males ■ females</p> </div>			
		<p align="center">STEM researchers - chemical sciences</p> <div align="center"> <p>■ males ■ females</p> </div>			

³⁰⁵ Rapporto GETA 2019 CNR, https://www.cnr.it/sites/default/files/public/media/attivita/editoria/Rapporto_GETA2019.pdf

	<p>Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender</p>	<p>Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender (2015-2019)³⁰⁶</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Year</th> <th>Males (%)</th> <th>Females (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>2015</td> <td>76.86%</td> <td>23.14%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2016</td> <td>76.20%</td> <td>23.28%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2017</td> <td>78.00%</td> <td>22.00%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2018</td> <td>78.37%</td> <td>21.63%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2019</td> <td>77.22%</td> <td>22.78%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Year	Males (%)	Females (%)	2015	76.86%	23.14%	2016	76.20%	23.28%	2017	78.00%	22.00%	2018	78.37%	21.63%	2019	77.22%	22.78%
Year	Males (%)	Females (%)																		
2015	76.86%	23.14%																		
2016	76.20%	23.28%																		
2017	78.00%	22.00%																		
2018	78.37%	21.63%																		
2019	77.22%	22.78%																		
<p>Leadership</p>	<p>Patents registrations by gender</p>	<p>Patent application in Italy (1990-2016)³⁰⁷:</p> <p>Preliminary WIPO statistics reveal that in 2019 less than one fifth of inventors named in international patent applications were women. It has taken 25 years for this share to almost double, from 9.5 percent in 1995 to 18.7 percent in 2019. While numbers are going in the right direction, at the current pace parity amongst PCT-listed inventors will only be reached in 2044.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Percentage (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Males</td> <td>88.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Females</td> <td>7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other</td> <td>11.6</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gender	Percentage (%)	Males	88.3	Females	7	Other	11.6										
Gender	Percentage (%)																			
Males	88.3																			
Females	7																			
Other	11.6																			

³⁰⁶ http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=hrst_st_nsecsex2&lang=en

³⁰⁷ https://www.wipo.int/women-and-ip/en/news/2020/news_0001.html

	Founders and leaders of innovative enterprises and start-ups by gender	Innovative startups in Italy ³⁰⁸ : Mainly female ³⁰⁹ : 13.55% (Jan-March 2019); 13.54% (Apr-June 2019) With female participation ³¹⁰ : 43.15% (Jan-March 2019); 43.15% (Apr-June 2019)
Knowledge and tech production issues	Level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension	No information available
	Level of consideration of the gender dimension in product/service development	No information available
Broader issues featuring the R&I 'cultures'	Gender sensitiveness/family friendliness of supporting services to start up and entrepreneurship	No information available.
	Perception of existing stereotypes/bias on gender and innovation/entrepreneurship	No information available.

Table 11 Results of the context analysis conducted by UNILE

³⁰⁸ startup.registroimprese.it

³⁰⁹ The share of women is over the 50%

³¹⁰ At least a women has a management position or a share of the society

4.8.3 UNILE Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA

Results of the focus group with internal stakeholders

UNILE's researchers carried out the focus group on the 5th of October 2020. 3 internal stakeholders (2 males and 1 female) participated in the focus group: the head of the ISUFI excellence school, the former Vice-Rector for Scientific and Technological innovation and Internationalization at Unisalento.

Concerning existing **collaborations** with external stakeholders, all participants reported having active collaborations with various stakeholders, related to R&D activities and job-placement for graduated students. About prospective collaborations with stakeholders, the most interesting one could be related to the themes of sustainability and circular economy, such as a cost-effective use of natural resources and the development of new technologies to address environmental issues.

About the ways in which gender inequalities represent a **challenge** for external stakeholders all participants agreed that reducing gender inequalities is not generally considered a priority by external actors. The issue is often reduced to an unbalance between males and females in some scientific and professional areas. However, two of the participants reported that the reduction of gender inequalities will bring many benefits, like the activation of new synergies, skills and competences.

With reference to the **actions** that external actors put in place, in general, participants reported not being aware of any specific actions. One of them stressed that great attention is paid in providing opportunities to young people, even though inequalities get manifested in a later stage of the academic career, due to a loss of competitiveness from the female side. However, participants reported that in their opinion, in the frame of academic research, improvements in terms of gender equality can be noticed even without the adoption of specific measures. Another participant reported being aware of the existence of a Centre of Studies called "Woman Observatory" at UNILE aimed at making research on gender roles and how they impact the family, social and political spheres.

For what concerns **complementarities or synergies** with UNILE, participants agreed synergies are positive and should be encouraged. Research activities on gender inequalities in schools were suggested as well as the possibility to give extra scores to female research teams or teams lead by a woman when applying for competitive funds. The female stakeholder reported that gender diverse work teams are more effective in research and actions should be taken to encourage more women to study and work in areas where they are currently a minority (as engineering) and suggest measures to encourage female research teams to apply for competitive funding.

No **overlapping and competitive actions** were identified.

The only **risk** that was identified was that collaborations for reducing gender inequalities could not acknowledge merit .

Results of the survey to external stakeholders

The survey was filled only by 4 external stakeholders: 2 private companies, 1 public-private consortium (high tech district) and 1 network of laboratories. Their core activities/businesses are nanomedicine, ICT, broadcast & ISM, industrial research and technology transfer.

About the kind of **collaborations** already in place with UNILE, they are mainly related to research and laboratories sharing, but with a couple of stakeholders no specific collaborations are already in place.

Concerning the ways in which gender inequalities represent a **challenge** for them, the network of laboratories reported that gender inequalities are not present in the lab. One company explained paying a lot of attention

to gender equality, while the other is committed in demonstrating that technological innovation is independent of gender. On the contrary, the district explained that they try to implement the promotion of gender equality according to the 2030 agenda, through the dissemination of knowledge, analysis activities and the sharing of good practices.

As far as the potential **benefits** in solving gender inequalities are concerned, the following ones were reported:

- better work environment and production;
- overcome gender differences and improve general culture;
- more satisfied employees;
- increase of employment rate for women and reduction of pay gaps which will as a consequence attract more women to STEM careers.

About **actions** already put in place, two stakeholders did not report any. One stakeholder explained that they did not implement any specific measure since gender equality is already embedded within the company's culture, while another one reported that since its establishment the organization have tried to implement gender equality through women's access to decent jobs as an opportunity to promote sustainable and inclusive development.

Concerning instead **potential measures** to adopt, most of stakeholders are willing to adopt new measures. One of them especially explained that their goal is to collaborate with UNILE to define an organic approach on the issue.

When asked about which **complementarities or synergies** they envisage with UNILE in order to overcome gender equality, they explained that they are willing to share ideas on the topic, as well as organize specific workshops. A stakeholder reported that, since UNILE is one of their founding members, they will implement all the policies adopted by the university.

No **overlapping or competitive actions** were envisaged, but a stakeholder explained that it is essential to strengthen the use of technologies, in particular those of information and communication, that promote the emancipation of women. Care and domestic work must be recognized and valued, women should be given equal opportunities in the political, economic and public life spheres. They emphasized that it is necessary to create laws that allow to promote gender equality and empower women and girls, at all social and economic levels.

About **risks**, the only one reported is underestimating the problem and failing to follow up with concrete actions.

Results of the SNA

The methodology followed by UNILE concerned, at first, the collection of the list all funded projects of the last three years, related to the scientific (STEM) departments: Department of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Biology and Department of Engineering. As a second step, UNILE's researchers asked to those colleagues resulting project coordinators within the mentioned three departments, to fill the excel files with details of the different stakeholders and the existing connections with such stakeholders. Finally, all the results were merged in one single file.

Overall **162 external stakeholders** were included in the mapping. When we look at the stakeholders' type, many of them are "industry & business" stakeholders (60 out of 162, representing the 37%), followed by "Schools" stakeholders (49, representing 30,2%), "academia & universities" stakeholders (38, representing the 23,4%), "governments & public sector" stakeholders (11, representing the 7%) and "civil sector" stakeholders (4, representing the 2,4%).

4.8.4 Final remarks on the external assessment of UNILE

In Italy, gender equality is established within the Constitution and a set of ordinary laws which promote equal opportunities and contrast gender discrimination. It was underlined how **the abundance of principles and legislation in the matter is not accompanied by a substantial apparatus which guarantees its effectiveness**. A dedicated Committee was established for implementing the principles of equal treatment and equal opportunities of workers, however, members of such Committee do not receive any kind of remuneration for the work carried out within the Committee and this inevitably affects the work of the Committee itself.

No mechanisms at National/Regional levels are in place for promoting the under-represented gender in Higher Education, but public Universities as all other Public Administration bodies are requested to set up dedicated bodies (CUG- Comitato Unico di Garanzia) in charge of designing and implementing triannual Positive Action Plans, to contrast discrimination and favour equal opportunities. Some positive actions in building GEPs in some Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation Institutions and Organisms can be identified.

One of the most relevant provisions is the law n. 125/1991, in which the Italian legislator shows to be aware of the necessity to go beyond the mere formal equality, in order to promote the change in the social reality and allow women to achieve equal opportunities. Indeed, it introduced “positive actions” as tools to achieve equal opportunities and the distinction between “Direct discrimination” and “Indirect discrimination”.

Some measures are in place for supporting maternity and paternity, but the more recent law on the reconciliation of care, life and work needs introduced the parental leave. About childcare facilities, a **structural lack in the availability of educational services for early childhood compared to the potential needs and a deeply irregular distribution on the national territory** are present.

Concerning the collected data, interesting insights are offered when comparing the STEM higher education students at national level and the ones at UNILE level, since in the first case females are the minority (35,6%) while in the second one the great majority (73,2%). STEM researchers as a whole are more balanced (44% women), but differences can be observed in the specific disciplines, the most unbalanced are biological sciences (with the 67% of females) and engineering (with the 29% of females). **The evolution of employment rate in R&I is quite discouraging showing a wide difference between the male and female shares and a little decreasing trend in the considered period (2015-2019)** as far as the female rate is concerned. Very low are also the percentages of patent applications by women (11,63%) and of female founders in innovative start-ups (13.55%).

About the analysis of the collaborations in place with UNILE, regarding research projects, R&D activities, job placement for students. UNILE also established spin-offs. According to the results of the focus group, **reducing gender inequalities is not generally considered a priority by external actors** and the issue is underestimated. This also appears in the outcome of the survey, also considering that no specific implemented actions were reported by stakeholders. However, there is willingness to collaborate with UNILE on the topic: the public private tech district of whom UNILE is one of the founders is ready to adopt common measures, others to cooperate in the form of research activities or organization of workshops.

Concerning the SNA, 162 stakeholders were identified, many of the belonging to the “industry & business” sector. Overall, **62 collaborations are led by women**, centralized by a few/or single staff member, and the majority of those with schools in particular. Only 4 collaborations focusing or taking into account gender issues were identified.

4.9 External assessment of SRNSFG

4.9.1 The Georgian national legal and policy framework

Overall strategic gender equality policies at national level

Georgia has taken important steps towards creating institutional mechanisms for gender equality. At present, three key national agencies are responsible for the advancement of gender equality in the country: 1) the Gender Equality Council of the Parliament, 2) the Inter-Agency Commission on Gender Equality, Violence against Women and Domestic Violence Issues, and 3) the Gender Department of the Public Defender's Office.

Adopted in 2010, the Law of Georgia on Gender Equality³¹² is one of the key legal acts regulating gender balance in higher education. It determines the state's obligation to ensure equality of women and men in all spheres of public life, including education and science. Particularly, Article 7 of the Law of Georgia on Gender Equality addresses equality in access to higher education. Article 7 states in full:

1. *"Everyone shall have the right to freely choose a profession and specialty according to their abilities. Such equality shall be ensured through equal access, without discrimination, to general, vocational and higher education"*.
2. *"The State shall ensure that equal conditions are created for men and women to acquire general, vocational and higher education in all kinds of educational establishments, and to participate in educational and scientific processes (the Law of Georgia on Gender Equality, 2010). However, it was suggested, in a report by the Gender Equality Council of Georgia and UNDP, that "Article 7 of the Gender Equality Law should be significantly expanded to include rights establishing a claim to more comprehensive aspects of gender equality in all stages of education."*³¹³

As to the Law of Georgia on Higher Education³¹⁴, it determines higher education institutions' obligation to ensure *"equal treatment irrespective of the ethnic origin, sex, social origin, and the political or religious affiliation of a person"* (Article 16(1d)).

It shall be noted that Gender Equality Law does not require employers to develop internal gender equality plans.

Existence of specific mechanisms to promote the under-represented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation at national or regional level

The management of the Georgian Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) system is regulated by the following laws: Law of Georgia on Science, Technology and their Development (1994)³¹⁵, Law of Georgia on Higher Education (2004), Law of Georgia on Innovations (2016)³¹⁶, Law of Georgia on Grants (1996)³¹⁷ and Law of Georgia on Education Quality Improvement (2010)³¹⁸.

Neither national legislation nor national action plans on gender equality contain any specific mechanisms to promote the under-represented gender in higher education or scientific research and innovation. However, the Law of Georgia on higher education highlights the importance of the prohibition of any forms of

³¹² Parliament of Georgia. Law of Georgia on Gender Equality (2010)

³¹³ Gender Equality Council of Georgia and UNDP. (2018). Gender Equality in Georgia: Barriers and Recommendations, Volume 1. Tbilisi: Parliament of Georgia. Retrieved from:

https://www.undp.org/content/dam/georgia/docs/publications/DG/UNDP_GE_DG_Gender_Equality_in_Georgia_VOL1_ENG.pdf

³¹⁴ Parliament of Georgia. Law of Georgia on Higher Education (2005).

³¹⁵ Parliament of Georgia. Law of Georgia on Science, Technology and Their Development (1994).

³¹⁶ Parliament of Georgia. Law of Georgia on Innovations (2016).

³¹⁷ Parliament of Georgia. Law of Georgia on Grants (1996).

³¹⁸ Parliament of Georgia. Law of Georgia on Education Quality Improvement (2010).

discrimination in the field of higher education, including “discrimination on any ground such as academic, ethnic, social or religious affiliation, and/or opinion, sex and other grounds” (article 3).

Existence of national policies on implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees

The national legislation emphasises the importance of the provision of equal access to public service for the citizens of Georgia. “Every citizen of Georgia shall have an equal opportunity to be employed in public service according to their skills, qualification and professional training” (Law of Georgia on Public service, article 13, 2015). The same law also specifies that “decisions on the career promotion of an officer shall be impartial and based on a fair and transparent evaluation of the officer's competence and skills to perform work, and shall aim at selecting the best candidate” (article 11). Moreover, equal treatment in the evaluation of the quality of work of men and women is guaranteed by the Law of Georgia on Gender Equality (chapter 2, article 4). The same law also obliges the Municipality bodies to develop and carry out activities to ensure detection and elimination of discrimination locally (Article 13). However, it was suggested in the abovementioned UNDP study that “Article 13 should be amended to require local self-government bodies to employ temporary special measures or affirmative action policies to foster a gender balance in staff and management positions, as well as in all advisory bodies, committees and councils.”³¹⁹

Existence of national legislation promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment

The Law of Georgia on Gender Equality determines the state’s obligation to ensure gender equality in labour relations. Article 6 specifies what shall not be allowed in labour relations:

1. harassment and/or coercion of a person with the purpose or effect of creating an intimidating, hostile, humiliating, degrading, or offensive environment;
2. any unwanted verbal, non-verbal or physical behaviour of sexual nature with the purpose or effect of violating the dignity of a person or creating an intimidating, hostile, or offensive environment.

Article 6 continues by stating that:

- *“The State shall provide equal employment opportunities for men and women”.*
- *“During recruitment and in the course of employment persons may be put in unequal conditions and/or given priority over others on the basis of sex due to the substance and specificity of work or due to specific conditions required for its performance, and also if it serves a legitimate purpose and is appropriate and necessary for achieving that purpose”.*
- *“The legislation of Georgia shall ensure the creation of favourable working conditions for pregnant women and nursing mothers which excludes their work in hard, harmful and dangerous environments, as well as at night”.*

Existing policies at national level for reducing unequal gender division of labour related to housework and family care

These issues are regulated by different laws of Georgia. First of all, the Organic law of Georgia - Labour Code of Georgia (2010)³²⁰ regulates procedures of leaves, maternity leaves, leaves for adoption of new-born children and compensation issues (articles 27, 28, 29).

In addition to this, the Law of Georgia on Gender Equality ensures gender equality in family relations. Article 10 provides a detailed description:

³¹⁹ See note 313.

³²⁰ Parliament of Georgia. Organic Law of Georgia - Labour Code of Georgia (2010).

1. In family relations, during marriage and its dissolution, men and women shall have equal personal and property rights, including the right to choose a family name, profession and occupation. Their responsibilities shall be equal as well. Discrimination or preference related to rights and duties shall not be allowed in family relations.
2. Men and women shall have equal rights in the family to independently solve issues related to participation in labour and public activities.
3. Spouses shall solve child-rearing and other family issues based on mutual agreement. Spouses shall be guaranteed and provided with equal opportunities in their occupations and child-rearing.
4. Spouses shall have equal rights and duties in household chores.
5. Spouses shall have equal rights to own, acquire, manage, enjoy, and administer property.
6. Spouses shall have equal rights to participate in recreational activities and in all aspects of cultural life.

Moreover, the Law of Georgia on Public Service (2015)³²¹ provides conditions regarding parental leaves and care of a child (Article 64(6)).

Existing framework conditions regarding childcare facilities

The law of Georgia on Early and Preschool Education³²² ensures “*universal accessibility to, and the development and quality assurance of, early and preschool education in Georgia, and the organizational structure of early and preschool education institutions*” (Article 1). The same law states that Georgian children are ensured free education at the public preschool education institutions of Georgia (Article 4(1)).

In 2019, the Code on the Rights of the Child was adopted by the Georgian Parliament with the technical support of UNICEF and Georgia renewed its commitment to the full implementation of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC 1989).

According to the external studies conducted on child-care systems in Georgia, some challenges have been identified. For example, the assessment of Georgia’s childcare system³²³, carried out by the Public Defender’s Office with the support of UNICEF Georgia and the European Union, identified some challenges. Concerns include the lack of fully qualified people caring for children and a continued shortage of other human and financial resources. However, UNICEF Georgia continued to support the Government and municipalities in their efforts to improve the quality and accessibility of pre-school education and care.

Furthermore, the World Bank published a study in 2019 about care services in Georgia³²⁴. According to it, there is a rising demand for care services in Georgia. The main findings of this study can be summarized as follows: there is a need to increase the capacity, quality, and availability of childcare and early education as complementary to home-based care and for women who need childcare support.

At the same time, there is an increased demand for formal childcare and the infrastructure capacity of public kindergartens face some challenges. The importance of quality of formal care services for potential users is also highlighted. The main challenges of the existing supply involve children-staff ratios and staff’s qualifications for childcare and the human resource component in general.

³²¹ Parliament of Georgia. Law of Georgia on Public Service (2015).

³²² Parliament of Georgia. Law of Georgia on Early and Preschool Education (2017).

³²³ UNICEF. (2020). UNICEF in Georgia Newsletter #1 (21). Retrieved from https://www.unicef.org/georgia/media/3916/file/newsletter_eng-FINAL.pdf

³²⁴ World Bank. (2019). Why should we care about care? Supply and Demand Assessment of Care Services in Georgia: A Mixed Methods Study. Retrieved from: <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/887801548269893452/pdf/133961-Final-report-Care-Services-in-Georgia-clean-01-23-19.pdf>

Employment conditions at university and research organization

The law of Georgia on science, Technology and their development (1997) Article 10 (7) specifies procedures and rules of appointment of scientific personnel and emphasizes the principles of their appointment on an open competition basis, which must comply with the principles of transparency, equality and fair competition. It is noteworthy that, according to the same law, the procedure and other requirements of the competition are determined by the director of the institution in coordination with the head of a structural unit of the institution (article 10.7).

As to the universities, according to the law of Georgia on Higher education, (2004) higher education institutions are established as legal entities under public or private law (article 9(2)) and develop the statute, approve the internal regulations of the institutions and approve common procedures for recruiting academic and assistant personnel (article 10, b, c). The same law also specifies employment conditions for academic positions and states that “an academic position may be held only on an open competition basis and procedures for a competition shall be determined by the statute of the higher education institution” (article 34 (1.3)).

Existence of national programs which promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research

Analyses of the national legislation (Law of Georgia on Science, Technology and their Development (1994), Law of Georgia on Higher Education (2004)) as well as the respective policy documents (National Action Plan of 2014-2016 for implementation of Gender equality Policy in Georgia, Unified Strategy for Education and Science (2017-2020)³²⁵ show that currently there are no national programs which integrate a gender dimension in scientific programs.

National/ policies and legal frameworks on sexual/gender harassment in the workplace

Sexual/gender harassment in the workplace is regulated by the respective laws of Georgia. First of all, the Organic Law of Georgia - Article 2(4) of the Labour Code of Georgia states that:

“Discrimination (including sexual harassment) shall be defined as the direct or indirect harassment of a person aimed at or resulting in impairing dignity of a person, and in creating an intimidating, hostile, humiliating, degrading, or abusive environment for him/her, and/or creating the circumstances for a person directly or indirectly causing their condition to deteriorate as compared to other persons in similar circumstances.”

“Sexual harassment shall be defined as a behaviour of a sexual nature towards a person, which is meant to humiliate him/her and/or causes his/her humiliation and which creates an intimidating, hostile, humiliating or offensive environment³²⁵ for him/her”.

It is worth to note that for the purposes of this Law, a behaviour of a sexual nature shall be defined as saying and/or addressing with phrases of a sexual nature, showing genitals, and/or any other non-verbal physical behaviour of a sexual nature” (Organic Law of Georgia, 2010).

In addition to this, according to the Article 6 (1b) of the Gender Equality Law “Any unwanted verbal, non-verbal or physical behaviour of sexual nature with the purpose or effect of violating the dignity of a person or creating an intimidating, hostile, or offensive environment” is not allowed in labour relations (Law of Georgia on Gender Equality, 2010).

³²⁵ National Action Plan of 2014-2016 for implementation of Gender equality Policy in Georgia (2014), retrieved from:

www.parliament.ge/ge/ajax/downloadFile/27264

Unified Strategy for Education and Science (2017-2020), retrieved from:

<http://mes.gov.ge/uploads/files/Unified%20Strategy%20of%20Education%20and%20Science%202017-2021.docx>

Funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality at national and regional level

One of the key components of the gender equality policy at the national level is the economic strengthening of women. In line with this, the Progress Report on the National Action Plan of 2014-2016 for the Implementation of Gender Equality Policy in Georgia³²⁶ singles out the programs that have been implemented to support women.

Though not designed to address gender issues directly, the state program "Produce in Georgia", created new opportunities for women. In 2015-2016, the number of applicants within the framework of the Micro and Small Entrepreneurship Promotion Program of Georgia "Produce in Georgia" amounted to 43885 people, including 16401 women, which makes 37.5% of total applicants. Within the program, 8880 people were trained, including 3200 women (36%). The number of beneficiaries of the program amounted to 4911 people, including 1935 women (40%)³²⁷.

The LEPL³²⁸ Georgia Innovation and Technology Agency (GITA) of the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia also finances innovative projects. According to the above-mentioned report, in 2016, 35% of the GITA project beneficiaries were women. In particular, for the Micro Grants Program there were 17 (20%) women among 84 beneficiaries, and since January 2017 there have been 3 women among 12 beneficiaries (25%); within the framework of the "Start-up Georgia" program: 4 (20%) female beneficiaries out of 20 high-tech idea start-ups; out of the 420 applications submitted to Industrial Laboratory, 140 (34%) were from women. Finally, there were 93 (45%) women out of 205 participants of the project "Start Business with Fab Lab"³²⁹.

³²⁶ Implementation of Gender Equality Policy in Georgia. (2017). 2016 Progress Report on National Action Plan of 2014-2016 for the Implementation of Gender Equality Policy in Georgia. Tbilisi. Retrieved from http://www.parliament.ge/en/ajax/downloadFile/72000/Gender_Equality_NAP_report_2016_ENG_Edited_Final_July_2017

³²⁷ *ibid.*

³²⁸ Legal Entity of Public Law

³²⁹ http://www.parliament.ge/en/ajax/downloadFile/72000/Gender_Equality_NAP_report_2016_ENG_Edited_Final_July_2017

4.9.2 The innovation ecosystem context analysis at SRNSFG

The following table presents the results of the context analysis conducted by SRNSFG in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Area	Indicator	Result													
Talents and workforce education and acquisition	High School and Higher Education students in STEM by gender, at regional and national levels	Male and female STEMS students (2020) ³³⁰ males: 29.47%; females: 15.58 %													
	Researchers in STEM by gender in R&I, at national and regional levels	Male and female Researchers in 2018 in Engineering and technology ³³¹ : males: 23%; females: 12 %													
	Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender	No appropriate information could be found. There is a general indicator on the ratio of female participation in the labour force, but it is only in industry and agriculture sectors.													
Leadership	Patents registrations by gender	No relevant information could be found. Neither the National Intellectual Property Center of Georgia nor the World Intellectual Property Organization provide patent registration statistics by gender.													
	Founders and leaders of innovative enterprises and start-ups by gender	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Founders of start-ups by gender in 2018³³²</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Founders of start-ups by gender in 2018</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Males</td> <td>29%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Not identified</td> <td>19%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Females</td> <td>52%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Majority ownership of companies by gender³³³</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Majority ownership of companies by gender</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Males</td> <td>19,20%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Females</td> <td>80,8%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> </div> </div>	Gender	Percentage	Males	29%	Not identified	19%	Females	52%	Gender	Percentage	Males	19,20%	Females
Gender	Percentage														
Males	29%														
Not identified	19%														
Females	52%														
Gender	Percentage														
Males	19,20%														
Females	80,8%														

³³⁰ The data represent the share of male and female STEM students on the overall number of male and female students. In particular, 15.58% represent the share of female STEM students on the overall number of female students. Source: World Economic Forum, Global Gender Gap Report 2020 http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GGGR_2020.pdf

³³¹ The data represent the share of male and female STEM researchers (engineering and technology) on the overall number of male and female researchers. In particular, 12% represent the share of female STEM researchers on the overall number of female researchers. Source: National statistics office of Georgia, Women and men in Georgia, 2019 https://www.geostat.ge/media/27546/W%26M-ENG_2019.pdf

³³² National statistics office of Georgia, Women and men in Georgia, 2019 https://www.geostat.ge/media/27546/W%26M-ENG_2019.pdf

³³³ World Economic Forum, Global Gender Gap Report 2020 http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GGGR_2020.pdf

Knowledge and tech production issues	Level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension	The analysis of the policy documents at the national level ³³⁴ shows that there are no clear and measurable policy tools aimed at the integration of gender as a scientific research dimension. Thus, efforts are needed in order to raise awareness of the importance of incorporating a gender dimension in research, set up institutional mechanisms and increase the capacity of the researchers to better adopt this approach.
	Level of consideration of the gender dimension in product/service development	<p>On a national level, there are support schemes for the development of technical and business services in order to assist enterprises to introduce and implement innovative activities in their production processes. Specifically, Georgia's Innovation and Technology Agency (GITA) and Enterprise Georgia (EG) are involved in this process. GITA provides various sets of training to increase firms' potential for business innovation. EG hosts various international product exhibitions to promote Georgian products and services on the international markets. However, the existing policy and schemes do not directly address the issue of considering a gender dimension in product/service development.</p> <p>One of the challenges identified by the SME Development Strategy of Georgia 2016-2020 is a lack of measures towards gender equality necessary to maximize the workforce potential of women and stimulate deeper involvement of women in entrepreneurial and economic activities. However, on a policy level, consideration of gender dimension in the services or products design is not addressed.</p>
Broader issues featuring the R&I 'cultures	Gender sensitiveness/family friendliness of supporting services to start up and entrepreneurship	<p>Economic empowerment of women is one of the key areas of concern in Georgia. As indicated in "SME Policy Index: Eastern Partner Countries 2020"³³⁵, Georgia has made important steps in the direction. Through its SME Development Strategy (2016-2020) and a rural development strategy (2017-2020), the Country supports female entrepreneurship. Strategies are stressing the importance of the development of specific mechanisms to stimulate deeper involvement of women in entrepreneurial and economic activities. It is mentioned that fostering female entrepreneurship is necessary to conduct gap assessments and needs analyses of women's involvement in entrepreneurial activities and then based on the results develop ad hoc approaches. Besides that, it is mentioned that it is important to establish a platform for cooperation with women in business, with the involvement of relevant stakeholders which will facilitate women's involvement in entrepreneurial activities. In terms of the institutional framework, Georgia established several public-private bodies one of which is a Sub-Council for Women's Entrepreneurship Promotion. One of its objectives is closing the gender gap in entrepreneurship³³⁶.</p> <p>It is also worth to mention that the necessity for entrepreneurial learning has been emphasized by the Unified Strategy for Education and Science (2017-2020). Specifically, the recognition of entrepreneurship as a key competence is reflected within a national curriculum (primary, secondary and upper secondary education) and addressed through respective subjects. Furthermore, the Ministry of Education, Science, Culture and Sport of Georgia also chairs an inter-agency working group on entrepreneurial learning. The function of the group is to raise awareness and ensure cross-stakeholder co-operation in lifelong entrepreneurial learning³³⁷.</p>

³³⁴ Government of Georgia, 2016. Georgia 2020 – Socio-Economic Development Strategy, Unified Strategy of Education and Science 2017-2021, National Action Plan of 2014-2016, for implementation of Gender equality Policy in Georgia.

³³⁵ OECD et al. (2020), SME Policy Index: Eastern Partner Countries 2020: Assessing the Implementation of the Small Business Act for Europe, SME Policy Index, OECD Publishing, Paris/European Union, Brussels, <https://doi.org/10.1787/8b45614b-en>

³³⁶ SME Policy Index: Eastern Partner Countries, 2020.

³³⁷ Unified Strategy of Education and Science 2017-2021.

		<p>According to the study “Georgia: small business act country profile” (2020)³³⁸ entrepreneurial skills are more developed in vocational education and training (VET), with teacher training and support materials available. There were no significant developments in entrepreneurship promotion in higher education, apart from individual cases at several universities.</p> <p>The abovementioned study points to a predominance of women-owned businesses in retail, social services, food processing and hospitality sectors, with 40% of state-support programmes. Enterprise Georgia and GITA are key providers for training for women’s start-up and growth businesses. However, women account for just 31% of start-ups. 60% of women-owned businesses are located in two (Tbilisi and Imereti) of the country’s nine, mostly rural regions.</p> <p>Additionally, it should be mentioned that the SME strategy (Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia, 2018) and its Mid Term Evaluation Georgia’s SME Development Strategy 2016-2020, (2018) feature a number of mechanisms to stimulate deeper involvement of women in entrepreneurial and economic activities. According to the midterm evaluation report, in 2016-2017, GITA was engaged in the project “Strengthening Women’s Entrepreneurship”. In the frame of this project, 200 women visited the Technopark and were introduced to the possibilities offered to women entrepreneurs. Moreover, Enterprise Georgia introduced some preferential treatments for women in the selection process for the Micro and Small Business Support programme under Produce in Georgia: <i>“in case of limited resources, when two SME businesses, one led by women and the other by men, apply for financial support and fulfil the same criteria, the women-led venture will be chosen over the men-led one. Women entrepreneurs amount to 40% of the programme’s beneficiaries in 2016- 2017”</i>³³⁹.</p> <p>Thus, despite some positive developments in this regard, undoubtedly, more effort is required to further develop targeted policies to maximize the potential of women’s entrepreneurship across the country.</p>
	<p>Perception of existing stereotypes/bias on gender and innovation/ entrepreneurship</p>	<p>Georgia has made significant progress in honoring its national and international commitments on gender equality. These commitments, inter alia, call for fostering female entrepreneurship. As it has been highlighted above, the importance of women’s economic empowerment is emphasized both in the SME Development Strategy of Georgia 2016-2020 (Priority Action 3.9: Encouragement of female entrepreneurship) and in the Rural Development Strategy of Georgia 2017-2020 (Priority Area 2. Social Conditions and Living Standards). Nevertheless, there exist several studies showing that entrenched social norms and gender stereotypes hinder women’s social and economic advancement.</p> <p>According to the publication “Mentoring for Women’s Empowerment”³⁴⁰, the main cause of women’s economic inactivity is the widespread gender stereotypes that lead to gender-based division of labour and economic opportunities. Prevailing stereotypes of the Georgian society towards women in entrepreneurship are still common and strong, especially in rural areas. A study, conducted in 2018 by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN, indicates that the social status of women in rural areas is low. This has a negative impact on women’s economic opportunities and, furthermore, on women’s access to machinery and new technologies (Gender, Agriculture and Rural Development in Georgia, 2018³⁴¹). Another</p>

³³⁸ OECD et al. (2020), "Georgia: Small Business Act country profile", in SME Policy Index: Eastern Partner Countries 2020: Assessing the Implementation of the Small Business Act for Europe, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/fcc42977-en>

³³⁹ Mid Term Evaluation Georgia’s SME Development Strategy 2016-2020, 2018.

³⁴⁰ UN WOMEN. (2020). MENTORING FOR WOMEN’S EMPOWERMENT. Guide for workplace mentoring programmes. Retrieved from <https://www2.unwomen.org/-/media/field%20office%20georgia/attachments/publications/2020/mentoring%20guide.pdf?la=en&vs=3133>

³⁴¹ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2018). Gender, agriculture and rural development in Georgia. Rome. Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/3/ca0577en/CA0577EN.pdf>

		<p>important study on the issue of existing stereotypes on gender was conducted by the Asian Development Bank³⁴², according to which, women are expected to do the majority of unpaid care work inside the home, and apart from this, there also exist gender-based occupation segregation. All of these aspects affect female entrepreneurship and employability. The same claim is supported by the article Gender Inequality and Women’s Entrepreneurship-Challenges and Opportunities³⁴³. The author argues that gender stereotyping is considered a critical factor in women’s entrepreneurship development. Specifically, in Georgia, a stereotypical view of women and men suggests that men participate in the formation of a family budget and their function is that of a “breadwinner”.</p> <p>Thus, a joint effort is needed by government and civic interest groups to raise awareness and understanding of the potential of women’s entrepreneurship for wider socio-economic development, including the promotion of role models and success stories through mass media³⁴⁴.</p>
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Table 12_Results of the context analysis conducted by SRNSFG

³⁴² Asian Development Bank. (2018). Georgia: Country Gender Assessment. Retrieved from <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/institutional-document/479186/georgia-country-gender-assessment.pdf>

³⁴³ Natsvlshvili, Ia. (2017). Gender Inequality and Women’s Entrepreneurship-Challenges and Opportunities (Case of Georgia).

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/309896441_Gender_Inequality_and_Women's_Entrepreneurship-Challenges_and_Opportunities_Case_of_Georgia

³⁴⁴ OECD et al. (2020), "Georgia: Small Business Act country profile", in SME Policy Index: Eastern Partner Countries 2020: Assessing the Implementation of the Small Business Act for Europe, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/fcc42977-en>.

4.9.3 SRNSFG Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA

Results of the focus group with internal stakeholders

SRNSFG's researchers conducted the **focus group** on the 9th of June 2020, online, involving 8 colleagues being able to provide useful and detailed information regarding the existing network and collaborations (2 males and 6 females): 1 top-level manager, 2 middle-level managers, and 5 low-level managers.

At first participants reviewed the preliminary context analysis carried out by SRNSFG researchers and then discussed the potential gaps and challenges related to gender inequalities which the innovation system faces. The preliminary analysis demonstrated the existence of multiple gender related issues. Focus group's participants were asked to prepare in advance a preliminary map of existing collaborations with external stakeholders. As a result of the focus group, 40 external stakeholders were identified.

Existing **collaborations** mainly regard science and innovation. Such collaborations include joint calls and projects, multiple workshops, webinars and joint events. Prospective collaborations are expected to be on similar issues. According to participants, SRNSFG does not have any collaborations with stakeholders regarding gender equality.

Regarding how gender inequalities represent a **challenge** for stakeholders, it must be noted that there are no proper policies regulating gender equality inside the organizations. Since the issues related to gender equality remain unsolved, the stakeholders can be interested to tackle these issues with joint efforts. Solving gender equality issues at stakeholders' organizations can help to improve the overall situation regarding gender equality and help to raise awareness about the existing problems.

About the **actions** that stakeholders put in place, focus group's participants were not aware of any of them.

About **complementarities and synergies** between SRNSFG and the external stakeholders, future joint projects, training sessions or events were envisaged. Changes in the ecosystem can accelerate the institutional change process at SRNSFG, since there can be fewer contradictions and oppositions for change from different actors.

The focus group had a positive view of the possibility of **overlapping** actions, as some programs, projects and events can cover similar topics and concertedly contribute to similar goals.

About **risks**, focus group participants recognised that there can be a lack of interest or lack of capacity and resources for conducting particular actions. Besides that, it should be kept in mind that the timeframe for the implementation of particular changes can be substantial as joint efforts can require more time.

Results of the survey to external stakeholders

17 stakeholders participated in the survey. The great majority of them (13) were universities/higher educational institutions/research institutions, while the remaining stakeholders were: 2 NGOs, 1 company and 1 public entity. Stakeholders deal with a variety of activities/business such as:

- Improve business environment (NGO);
- Educational, research, teaching activities (universities/educational institutions/research institutions and the company);
- ICT (NGO);
- Culture (the public entity).

As far as the kind of **collaborations** in place with SRNSFG, most of stakeholders are beneficiaries of SRNSFG's grants/funding for what concerns educational and research projects. In a few cases (NGOs) stakeholders and SRNSFG collaborate in the same projects. One university reported that thanks to the collaboration in place

with the foundation, they enjoy free access to international databases as well as appropriate consultations and recommendations. Another university instead explained that university representatives attend/take part in different events organized by the foundation and the university itself sometimes hosts meetings of the representatives of the foundation at the university's premises.

The majority of stakeholders stated that gender inequalities do not represent a problem for their own institutions. However, a few of them reported the following ones as the main **challenges** related to the topic:

- Lack of qualified staff;
- Lack of women engaged in technology and business enterprises;
- Cultural background;
- Lack of women in the highest academic and scientific positions;
- Maternity leaves.

About potential **benefits** in solving such challenges, stakeholders reported the followings:

- Improvement of career perspectives and conditions of work of both men and women;
- More qualified staff;
- More women involved in STEM businesses/enterprises and academic spheres and as a consequence promotion of economic and sustainable development of the Country;
- Improvement of student's academic performance;
- More man in biology field;
- Improvement of the quality of research and teaching.

Concerning the **actions** that external actors have put in place in order to overcome gender inequalities, the most relevant are the followings:

- Awareness raising activities (e.g. discussions, events, exhibitions, etc.);
- Implementations of projects aimed at fighting gender imbalances (for instance "Coding School for women" and "Profession does not have sex");
- Cooperation with UN Women;
- Promotion of female participation into research projects;
- Establishment of a Gender Equality Center within the university organizing conferences;
- Codes of ethics and codes of conduct;
- Organization of festivals dedicated to women;
- Positive discrimination actions;
- Stipulation of a memorandum of understanding with NGOs dealing with women's rights, in the frame of which consultations to the university are provided in order to implement gender mainstreaming.

About actions that stakeholders plan to adopt, one of them reported the possibility to adopt a dedicated strategy and related measures in order, while another one explained that they will support any event contributing to the improvement of research activities within the university.

As far as further **complementarities or synergies** with SRNSFG in order to overcome gender inequalities are concerned, all stakeholders expressed being willing to continue the collaborations with SRNSFG also with reference to this specific issues. From one side, stakeholders are available to learn about SRNSFG's experience regarding the introduction and implementation of specific measures overcoming gender inequalities, as well as to co-organize different initiatives (discussions, events, open lectures, seminars etc.), also involving representatives of management bodies, aimed at promoting the awareness on the topic, like group meetings with also the participation of specialists in the field, in order to gain knowledge on gender issues. Another form of synergy would be the elaboration and submission of research projects about gender

inequalities and the sharing of good experiences in academic and scientific environments. Additional actions that were envisaged are the followings:

- Development of dedicated training and courses (e.g. “women in technology”);
- Launch of educational campaigns;
- Development of co-funding mechanisms for people at their early career stages;
- Adoption of dedicated grants for female researchers;
- Dissemination of gender related research papers;
- Elaboration of recommendations – indicators of gender equality.

No overlapping/competitive actions were envisaged.

Finally, concerning the **risks**, most of stakeholders could not identify any risk at this stage. The only ones that were reported were related to the lack of human resources, lack of time and lack of resources/funding. In addition, the risk of a poor communication between participating organizations as well as the improper dissemination of the obtained results were pointed out. More generally speaking, a change in the government policy as well as the current gender norms and values could represent a barrier in the implementation of the projects.

Results of the SNA

For gathering data to conduct the SNA, representatives of low, middle and top management who could provide useful and detailed information regarding the existing network and collaborations were identified.

Necessary data were collected by sharing a dedicated file to fill. In order to validate such data, a focus group was organized. Focus group participants were asked to prepare in advance a preliminary map of existing collaborations with external stakeholders which was then summarized and discussed during the meeting. Based on the discussion, a review and analysis of the provided information was conducted.

All the relevant stakeholders were included in the list, without making a specific selection due to the fact that the number of stakeholders did not exceed 50 (the number required by the methodology).

Indeed, overall, **40 external stakeholders** were included in the mapping. The majority of collaborations are with “academia & universities” stakeholders (28 out of 40 stakeholders, representing the 70%), followed by “government & public sector” stakeholders (4, representing the 10%), “civil society” stakeholders (3 out of 40, representing the 7,5%), “industry & business” stakeholders (2, representing the 5%) and “others” (3, representing the 7,5%). Stakeholders included in “others” are for instance museums. Regarding “academia & universities”, the collaborations with such stakeholders are mainly long-terms ones and are mainly related to the participation of the stakeholders to the “Elsevier Database consortia” which is fully funded by SRNSFG. All collaborations can be considered as relevant.

About the **intensity** of collaborations, most of them (34 out of 40, representing the 85%) are “frequent” collaborations. Among “frequent” collaborations, 27 are with “academia & universities” stakeholders, 2 with “civil society” stakeholders 1 is with “government & public sector”, 1 with a “industry & business” stakeholder and 3 with “others” stakeholders. Only 5 out of 40 collaborations are “one time” collaborations and only 1 is a “solid” collaboration.

Concerning the **topic** of the collaborations, most of them (31 out of 40, representing the 77,5%) are about “scientific research”, 4 about “transfer to market”, 3 are “raising awareness” and 2 about “science communication”.

It is important to mention that the majority of the connections and projects have a female leadership. Indeed, **24 collaborations are led by women** in SRNSFG (60%). 16 of them are collaborations with “academia & universities” stakeholders (67%), 2 with “government & public sector” stakeholders (8%), 1 with “industry &

business” stakeholders (4%), 1 with “civil society” (4%) and 3 with “others”. However, there are no collaborations **focusing or taking into account gender and diversity**.

The following pictures represent the results of the SNA conducted by SRNSFG according to the kind of stakeholders. Therefore, 5 different maps are displayed, one for each category of stakeholders: “academia & university”, “industry & business”, “government & public sector”, “civil society” and “others”.

Per each map it is possible to identify the different departments of SRNSFG involved in the collaborations with the different external stakeholders (the nodes with a small green circle), the collaborations having female leaderships (the yellow nodes). As already mentioned, no collaborations focusing or taking into account gender were registered.

Figure 34_SRNSFG collaborations with "Academia & universities" stakeholders

Figure 35_SRNSFG collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders

Figure 36_SRNSFG collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders

Figure 37_SRNSFG collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders

Figure 38_SRNSFG collaborations with "others"

4.9.4 Final remarks on the external assessment of SRNSFG

Recently, **Georgia has taken important steps towards creating institutional mechanisms for gender equality** and now three key national agencies are responsible for the advancement of gender equality in the country.

The most relevant piece of legislation is the Law of Georgia on Gender Equality, which also regulates gender balance in higher education. Indeed, it determines the state's obligation to ensure equality of women and men in all spheres of public life, including education and science. However, **neither the national legislation nor national action plans on gender equality contain any specific mechanisms to promote the under-represented gender in higher education or scientific research and innovation**, even though the Law of Georgia on higher education highlights the importance of the prohibition of any forms of discrimination in the field of higher education. Either no national legislation/program are in place about the integration of the gender dimension in research.

Specific provisions exist regarding the reduction of unequal division of labour related to housework and family care: maternity leaves, parental leaves, leaves for adoption of new-born children and compensation issues. The childcare system, instead, faces some challenges like the **lack of fully qualified people caring for children and a continued shortage of other human and financial resources**, while an increased of childcare and early education as complementary to home-based care is registered.

Concerning the collected data, the ratio of females students and researchers studying or making research about STEM (on the overall number of female students/researchers) is about half of the ration of males studying or making research in the same field. Quite low is also the share of female founders of start-ups and companies owners (the 29% and the 19,20%, respectively).

On a national level, support schemes for the development of technical and business services in order to assist enterprises to introduce and implement innovative activities in their production processes exist. However, **the integration of the gender dimension in the services or products design is not addressed**.

Economic empowerment of women is one of the key areas of concern in Georgia, indeed, the country supports female entrepreneurship through specific strategies stressing the importance of the development of specific mechanisms to stimulate deeper involvement of women in entrepreneurial and economic activities. Studies highlight the predominance of women-owned businesses in retail, social services, food processing and hospitality sectors. However, **still gender stereotypes are spread leading to a gender-based division of work and economic opportunities**, since women are still expected to do the majority of unpaid care work inside the home.

About the analysis of the collaborations in place with SRNSFG, they mainly include joint calls and projects, multiple workshops, webinars and joint events, but **no collaborations are in place with specific reference to gender equality**. In addition, most of the stakeholders involved through the survey stated that gender inequalities do not represent a problem for their own institutions. Some of them already implemented some actions in order to overcome gender inequalities, like awareness raising activities, dedicated projects, establishment of Gender Equality Centres, Codes of Ethics and positive discrimination actions. About further synergies with SRNSFG in order to overcome gender inequalities, all stakeholders expressed being willing to continue the collaborations with SRNSFG also with reference to these specific issues, with actions like the co-organisation of different initiatives (discussions, events, open lectures, seminars etc.), submission of research projects, sharing good experiences in academic and scientific environments and the adoption of dedicated grants for female researchers. Concerning the SNA, 40 stakeholders were identified, the majority of them belonging to the "academia & universities" sector. Overall, **24 collaborations are led by women** in SRNSFG. However, there are no collaborations focusing or taking into account gender and diversity.

4.10 External assessment of UEFISCDI

4.10.1 The Romanian national legal and policy framework

The national legal and policy framework is the result of both a desk research and an interview conducted with a representative (female) of the University of Bucharest.

Overall strategic gender equality policies at national level

The Romanian Constitution, adopted in 2003, includes the fundamental principles of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, with provisions on equal rights and non-discrimination. In particular, article 16 provides that:

1. *“Citizens are equal before the law and public authorities, without any privilege or discrimination”.*
2. *“No one is above the law”.*
3. *“Access to public, civil, or military positions or dignities may be granted, according to the law, to persons whose citizenship is Romanian and whose domicile is in Romania. The Romanian State shall guarantee equal opportunities for men and women to occupy such positions and dignities”.*³⁴⁵

For what concerns gender equality legislation and policies, the following ones are to be mentioned:

- Ordinance No. 137/2000 of the Government on Prevention and Sanctioning Discrimination³⁴⁶. It includes provisions on direct and indirect discrimination including sex-based discrimination, victimization, harassment, discrimination on multiple grounds, the right to personal dignity, and affirmative actions. According to this Ordinance, any measure taken by public authorities in favour of a person, group, or community to support *de facto* equal opportunities is not considered discrimination.
- Law No. 202/2002 on Equal Opportunities between Women and Men³⁴⁷. This is the key legislative tool and stipulates the following areas as priorities:
 - o Equality of opportunities and treatment for women and men in the labour market;
 - o Equality of opportunities and treatment for women and men in access to education, health care, culture and information;
 - o Equality of opportunities and treatment for women and men in decision-making. The first and the last provisions relating to the labour market and to decision-making are directly relevant and appear to be supportive of the issue of an improved gender balance in the public administration, especially in decision-making positions.
- Law No. 202/2002 also has an important provision on incentive measures to foster gender equality. Article 4, paragraph E states: *“By incentive measures or positive discrimination it is understood those special measures adopted for a temporary period in order to accelerate de facto achievement of equal opportunity between women and men and which are not considered discriminatory actions (...)”*.³⁴⁸ This law also provided the legal basis for the country’s Gender Equality Mechanism, which is the ANES (National Agency for Equal Opportunities). During the restructuring of the public administration, the National Agency for Equal Opportunities between Women and Men was dissolved in July 2010 for financial reasons, together with a number of other state agencies. In the following years it was redesigned with considerably less power as a Directorate under the Ministry of Labour. Only a central

³⁴⁵ Romanian Constitution, TITLE II: Fundamental rights, freedoms and duties, CHAPTER I: Common provisions, ART 16 “Equality of rights”. Source: http://www.cdep.ro/pls/dic/site.page?den=act2_2&par1=2

³⁴⁶ Government Ordinance (GO) no. 137/2000, on the prevention and sanctioning of all forms of discrimination <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/librarydoc/romania-government-ordinance-no-137/2000-on-preventing-and-sanctioning-all-forms-of-discrimination>

³⁴⁷ Romanian Constitution - law no. 202/2002 dated 19th of April 2002 regarding gender equality <https://anes.gov.ro/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Legea-202-din-2002.pdf>

³⁴⁸ *ibid.*

structure was maintained, and the local structures were dissolved. Nowadays, ANES is the agency in charge with developing the National Strategy for Gender Equality.³⁴⁹

- Law No. 217/2003 on the Prevention and Sanctioning of Domestic Violence³⁵⁰. This law provided the legal basis for the National Agency for Family Protection, which was also dissolved for financial reasons in 2010, then merged with the National Authority for the Protection of Children, and finally redesigned as a Directorate for Children's Protection under the Ministry of Labour.

There are no positive measures to support gender equality in decision-making, even though the Constitution was drafted after important instruments/measures at international level, such as the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) in 1979 and the Beijing Platform for Action (BPFA) in 1995. Both these acts clearly state women's equal participation in decision-making as a goal and set out a range of provisions³⁵¹.

Existence of specific mechanisms to promote the under-represented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation at national or regional level

The 2018 female HDI (Human Development Index) value for Romania is 0.809 in contrast with 0.821 for males, resulting in a GDI (Gender Development Index) value of 0.986. In comparison, GDI values for the Russian Federation and Ukraine are 1.015 and 0.995 respectively³⁵². The GDI measures gender inequalities considering three basic dimensions of human development: health, education and command over economic resources.

Romania has a GII³⁵³ value of 0.316, ranking it 69 out of 162 countries in the 2018 index. In Romania, the 18.7% of parliamentary seats are held by women, and the 87.2% of adult women have reached at least a secondary level of education compared to the 93.1% of their male counterparts. Every 100,000 births, 31 women die of pregnancy related causes. Female participation in the labour market is of 45.6% compared to the 64.2% for men³⁵⁴.

In 2006, the CEDAW Committee noted the low representation of women in public life and decision-making in Romania, including in the public administration, and made the following recommendations:

- to take effective measures to accelerate and increase the representation of women in elected and appointed bodies;
- use of incentives or sanctions for fulfilment of the obligation of local and central public authorities to reach 'equitable and balanced representation of women and men' as proclaimed in the Law on Equal Opportunities Between Women and Men;
- utilize temporary special measures including establishment of benchmarks, quotas, numerical goals and timetables, to accelerate women's full and equal participation in elected and appointed bodies;

³⁴⁹ Romanian National Agency for Gender Equality – national legislation regarding gender equality

<https://anes.gov.ro/legislatie-nationala-egalitatea-de-sanse/>

³⁵⁰ Law No. 217/2003, amended by Law 25/2012 <http://www.evaw-global-database.unwomen.org/en/countries/europe/romania/2003/law-no-217-2003-on-the-preventing-and-fighting-against-family-violence>

³⁵¹ Băluță, Oana, 2011, Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment in Public Administration. Romania Case Study, United Nations Development Programme

<http://www.undp.org/content/dam/undp/library/Democratic%20Governance/Women-s%20Empowerment/RomaniaFinal%20-%20HiRes.pdf?download>

³⁵² UNDP, Human Development Report 2019, Inequalities in Human Development in the 21st Century – country profile Romania http://hdr.undp.org/sites/all/themes/hdr_theme/country-notes/ROU.pdf

³⁵³ GII: Gender Inequality Index, it reflects gender-based inequalities in three dimensions – reproductive health, empowerment, and economic activity. Reproductive health is measured by maternal mortality and adolescent birth rates; empowerment is measured by the share of parliamentary seats held by women and attainment in secondary and higher education by each gender; and economic activity is measured by the labour market participation rate for women and men. More information at <http://hdr.undp.org/en/content/gender-inequality-index-gii>

³⁵⁴ See note n. 352.

- increase efforts in offering or supporting training programmes for current and future women leaders and carry out awareness-raising campaigns about the importance of women's participation in public life and at decision-making levels, as a democratic requirement³⁵⁵.

These recommendations have only partly been implemented in Romania.

At the moment, there is no functional mechanism at national level to promote underrepresented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research.

Recent policies are actually at risk of hindering further developments in terms of Gender Equality policies for research and Higher Education in Romania: the article 7 of the National Education Law passed in 2020, has prohibited education regarding the so called "gender identity theory" and is refusing to accept the current scientific consensus which distinguishes between gender and biological sex. On the other hand it has to be noted how there is a broad consensus in the academic environment that this law should not have been approved. In fact, all major universities of Romania contested the law at the Constitutional Court asking to declare it unconstitutional. At the moment this report was finalized, the procedure was still open.

Existence of national policies on implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees

Although there is a legislative framework, and a strategy in the field of equal opportunities between women and men for the period 2018-2021³⁵⁶, the National Education Law (Law no. 1/2011 with subsequent amendments and completions) does not transpose the principle of equal opportunities. In Chapter XI, section 1, it refers to the management structures in state or private higher education institutions, but also to the obligation to respect gender quotas in the management structures. Same failure of transposing national laws in gender quotas can be seen in women's political representation³⁵⁷.

Existence of national legislation promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment

The Labour Inspectorate is responsible for monitoring that the access to the labour market happens without discrimination and that work provisions for youth and women are respected. The Inspection oversees the enforcement of Law No. 202/2002 in the field of labour relations and occupational safety and health, in both the public and private sectors. According to Law No. 202/2002 on Equal Opportunities between Women and Men, "*The Labour Inspection ensures the control of implementation of measures aiming at the observance of equal opportunities and treatment between women and men in the field of labour relations and occupational safety and health*"³⁵⁸. A recent institutional study³⁵⁹ concluded that Labour Inspection "*is the most important implementing, monitoring and control institution for equal opportunities and non-discrimination in work-relations*". Labour Inspection also has regional representation, called Work Regions Inspectorates³⁶⁰.

Existing policies at national level for reducing unequal gender division of labour related to housework and family care

Work-life balance is not a priority area for national policy makers, even if related measures and interventions are widely acknowledged as crucial for gender equality and women's empowerment. Romania has provisions of various types of leaves, but a critical gap is the lack of adequate childcare services/facilities. One aspect that should be addressed is that the current policies impacting on work-life balance are women-centred, with

³⁵⁵ Ministry of Labour - Romanian National Strategy for promoting gender equality 2018-2021

http://www.mmuncii.ro/j33/images/Documente/MMJS/Transparenta-decizionala/5003-20171026_StrategiaNat_pilonES.pdf

³⁵⁶ *ibid.*

³⁵⁷ Romanian National Agency for Gender Equality – national legislation regarding gender equality

<https://anes.gov.ro/legislatie-nationala-egalitatea-de-sanse/>

³⁵⁸ See note n. 347.

³⁵⁹ https://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/librarypage/democratic-governance/public_administration/gepa2.html

³⁶⁰ Ministry for Sustainable Development - Romania's Sustainable Development Strategy 2030, 2018, pp 43-45. <http://dezvoltaredurabila.gov.ro/web/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Romanias-Sustainable-Development-Strategy-2030.pdf>

incentives for men being only updated in latest years. The lack of incentives must be understood within the broader socio-political context, which has seen an awakening of traditional gender roles. Nowadays, the government supports a greater co-responsibility of the domestic burden, along with the increase of the participation of women in the labour market.

A positive aspect is that fathers have the right to paternity leave and that there is also the provision for parental leave, which both parents can access. The EU represented an important incentive for the national government to start focusing on gender equality. Although the financial benefits are small, the principle is important. Policies that help families to access childcare are a vital instrument for gender equality in the public administration as well. This is because they increase the women's participation in the labour market and help to mitigate gender segregation, and therefore to reduce the gender pay gap³⁶¹.

There is no coherent strategy, neither any policy, for reducing unequal gender division of labour related to housework and family care and promoting and harmonious family life. However, besides the regulated parental, maternity and paternity leaves, a network of nurseries and kindergartens exists.

Existing framework conditions regarding childcare facilities

In Romania, people who have worked for 12 months before the date of birth of their child can benefit either from:

- a leave of two years, as well as a monthly compensation equivalent to 85% of the average net income over the last 12 months. Compensation may not exceed 8,500 RON/month (about 1750 EUR/month).

The "second" parent has the right to one month of parental leave. The second parent can either:

- Request one month of leave. Compensation and leave are suspended for this month and the "first" parent will have the choice of taking an unpaid leave or coming back to work.
- Inform the Labour Inspectorate that he or she will not opt for the one month leave a minimum of 60 days prior to the baby's first birthday. The leave of the first parent and the compensation is reduced by one month in this case.

These provisions do not apply if the workers return 9 months after the birth of the child.

Maternity leave and allowance are granted to pregnant women or women who have given birth during the last 6 to 8 weeks (postpartum women), for a total of 126 calendar days.

Maternal risk leave may be granted to pregnant or postpartum women who are not on maternity leave and whose employer cannot guarantee working conditions that are free of risks for their health and/or the one of the child. Maternal risk allowance may be granted for up to 120 days before and after maternity leave on the recommendation of a family doctor or obstetrician and gynaecologist.

To receive maternity/paternity leave and allowance, parents must meet the following conditions:

- mother/father is legally resident in Romania;
- mother/father live together with the child or children for whom they are requesting the allowance;
- mother/father contributed for at least 6 months to the social insurance system during the last 12 months prior to the maternity leave.

To receive maternal risk leave, the following conditions must be met:

³⁶¹ Hurubean, Alina, 2013, Post-communist Romanian feminism and gender equality. Between stereotypes, conceptual ambiguities and thinking outside the box - *Analyze – Journal of Gender and Feminist Studies* http://www.analyze-journal.ro/library/files/numarul_1/alina_hurubean.pdf

- the mother is legally resident in Romania;
- the mother is employed and request this leave before your maternity leave or, if you are postpartum or breastfeeding, you apply for this benefit after your maternity leave ends and only if you do not request child-raising allowance for a child aged up to 2 years.

Maternity allowance is paid to the mother for 126 calendar days while she is on leave. This period is made up of 63 days of leave before the birth and 63 days after the child is born. The first 42 days of leave after the child is born are compulsory. Maternity allowance is equal to the 85% of the average monthly income earned by the mother during the last 6 months prior to maternity leave. This allowance is paid for the 126 days of maternity leave, even if the child is stillborn. It is not subjected to the income tax system, but recipients must pay a contribution of 10% to the health insurance system. Maternal risk allowance is equal to the 75% of the mother's average monthly income over the last 10 months before the benefit was requested. It is paid for a period of up to 120 days. The maternity or maternal risk allowance is paid by the employer in case of employees. Persons who are self-employed or authorized individuals must submit their application for maternity leave and allowance to their local Health Insurance Authority.

In the case of executive/managerial positions, the maternity model can act as an obstacle for women in decision-making positions. Indeed, the two or three years of parental leave have long-term consequences on women's professional experience and incomes, and also negatively impact their retirement benefits. Expectations about women's roles, a lack of gender equality in educational policies and a lack of facilities to support work-life balance do not help to overcome this model.

The lack of childcare services further increases women's social vulnerability. Employment rates of 25-49 years people with and without children are different for women and men. There is already a gender gap in the employment rate of 25-40 years old people without children, but this gap considerably increases when women have children (69.6% for women in comparison to the 83.5% for men).

Parental leave covers the first two years after the birth, but children can only be enrolled at kindergarten when they are three years old. There is therefore a gap of one year when the family is entirely responsible for childcare. Families rely on informal care by grandparents, other relatives or on baby-sitters, if income permits. The number of state-funded care facilities has dramatically decreased. The situation is even more dramatic for families living in rural areas, where there is a desperate shortage of care facilities. In terms of progress, Romania is far from meeting Barcelona targets on child coverage. There is therefore a critical gap between state supply of childcare services and demand, especially from women³⁶².

Employment conditions at university and research organization

The national law 319/2003 regarding employment in research in Romania does not address gender equality or equal opportunities³⁶³.

Existence of national programs which promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research

Romania achieved its best scores in Priority 4 (Gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research). The country's performances positioned it either above (Cluster 2) or well above (Cluster 1) the ERA average³⁶⁴.

Romania's greatest score was registered in this priority, namely for its inclusion of gender dimension in research content. Indeed, the country's score on this indicator was more than twice the level measured for

³⁶² Emergency Act no. 111 date 8th December 2010 regarding maternity leave

<https://anes.gov.ro/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/10.-OUG-Nr-111-din-2010-privind-concediul-si-indemnizatia-lunara-pentru-cresterea-copiilor.pdf>

³⁶³ European Commission. (2019). ERA Progress Report 2018 – country profile Romania.

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/30043562-34c3-11e9-8d04-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

³⁶⁴ *ibid.*

Member States overall. It also performed very well on the headline indicator, the share of women among Grade A positions in the higher education system. Finally, the country performed above both the ERA average and the EU-28 benchmark for its share of PhD female graduates³⁶⁵.

According to the RIO Report 2017 on Romania, although the share of female researchers in 2015 (46.23%) was above the EU average (33.4%)³⁶⁶, the participation of women in research was slightly higher in the social sciences and humanities field (around 52%) than in natural and agricultural sciences (around 45%)³⁶⁷. Overall, since the gender division among researchers is rather equal in Romania, no major policy developments in this respect were observed during the reference period³⁶⁸.

National/ policies and legal frameworks on sexual/gender harassment in the workplace

The reference provision is the Ordinance n. 137/2000 of the Government on “Prevention and Sanctioning Discrimination”³⁶⁹. The Ordinance includes provisions regarding direct and indirect discrimination including sex-based discrimination, victimisation, harassment, discrimination on multiple grounds, the right to personal dignity, and affirmative actions. According to this Ordinance, any measure taken by public authorities in favour of a person, group or community to support de facto equal opportunities is not considered discrimination. The Ordinance also provides the legal basis for the country’s mechanism for combating discrimination - the National Council Combating Discrimination (NCCD) - and specifies instruments for litigation, either directly petitioning the NCCD or addressing the Court of Justice. The NCCD has responsibilities in the areas of prevention, mediation, investigation, sanctioning and monitoring and is an institution under Parliamentary control. NCCD elaborates and implements public policies in the anti-discrimination field and can facilitate consultations with public authorities, NGOs, trade unions interested in combating discriminations and protecting human rights. The consultation process is important, and the gender equality expertise of NGOs and academia is a central resource for government when elaborating and implementing gender equality policies. Unless the decisions of NCCD are contested in court, sanctions with regard to discrimination cases are mandatory. On the issue of sexual harassment, Article 2, paragraph 5 of the Ordinance No. 137/2000 defines the concept of harassment. The same as Law No. 202/2002 on “Equal Opportunities between Women and Men” also defines the concept of sexual harassment in particular, stating that “*by sexual harassment it is understood any undesirable sexual-related behaviour – verbal, nonverbal or physical – which is intended to negatively affect the dignity of person and/or to create a degrading, intimidating, hostile, humiliating or offensive environment*”³⁷⁰. While there is a legislation on sexual harassment in the workplace, there are no institutional mechanisms for prevention and evaluation, as there are no mentions of sexual harassment in most of the workplaces’/universities’ ethics codes.

Funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality at national and regional level

There are no funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality at national and regional level. Most of the NGOs active in this field perform voluntary work or get funding from other kind of projects.

³⁶⁵ European Commission. (2019). She Figures 2018.

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9540ffa1-4478-11e9-a8ed-01aa75ed71a1>

³⁶⁶ Chioncel, M; del Rio, J-C, RIO Country Report 2017: Romania, EUR 29169 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324900025_RIO_Country_Report_2017_Romania_Research_and_Innovation_Observatory_country_report_series

³⁶⁷ Zamfir A., Hjalmsardóttir E. H., Research & Development through a gender lens – the case of Romania and Iceland. August 2017 HOLLISTICA – Journal of Business and Public Administration 8(2). Available at

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319618701_Research_Development_through_a_gender_lens_-_the_case_of_Romania_and_Iceland

³⁶⁸ UNDP, Human Development Report 2019, Inequalities in Human Development in the 21st Century – country profile Romania

http://hdr.undp.org/sites/all/themes/hdr_theme/country-notes/ROU.pdf

³⁶⁹ See note n. 346.

³⁷⁰ Discrimination in higher education – Research report – Iordache, 2018 <http://www.romaniacurata.ro/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/Raport-de-cercetare-Mob-univ-2.pdf>

4.10.2 The UEFISCDI national and regional innovation ecosystem

The following table presents the results of the context analysis conducted by UEFISCDI in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Area	Indicator	Results																	
Talents and workforce education and acquisition	High School and Higher Education students in STEM by gender, at regional and national levels	<p>Bachelor's or equivalent level (2018)³⁷¹: males/thousand inhabitants: 11.9; females/thousand inhabitants: 8.3</p> <p>Master's or equivalent level (2018): males/thousand inhabitants: 5.6; females/thousand inhabitants: 5.4</p> <p>Doctoral or equivalent level (2018): males/thousand inhabitants: 0.3; females/thousand inhabitants: 0.2</p>																	
	Researchers in STEM by gender in R&I, at national and regional levels	<p style="text-align: center;">STEM researchers (2018)³⁷²</p> <p style="text-align: center;">■ males ■ females</p>																	
	Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender	<p style="text-align: center;">Employment rate in R&I evolution³⁷³:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Year</th> <th>Males (%)</th> <th>Females (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>2015</td> <td>54.11%</td> <td>45.89%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2016</td> <td>54.16%</td> <td>45.84%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2017</td> <td>54.14%</td> <td>45.86%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2018</td> <td>54.90%</td> <td>45.10%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2019</td> <td>55.00%</td> <td>45.00%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Year	Males (%)	Females (%)	2015	54.11%	45.89%	2016	54.16%	45.84%	2017	54.14%	45.86%	2018	54.90%	45.10%	2019	55.00%
Year	Males (%)	Females (%)																	
2015	54.11%	45.89%																	
2016	54.16%	45.84%																	
2017	54.14%	45.86%																	
2018	54.90%	45.10%																	
2019	55.00%	45.00%																	

³⁷¹ National Institute for Statistics, Romania <https://insse.ro/cms/>

³⁷² *ibid*

³⁷³ *ibid*

Leadership	Patents registrations by gender	Patent registration teams ³⁷⁴ : One woman – 2.37%; All women team – 1.63%; Team with at least 60% women – 6.28%; Mixed team – 8.29% Team with at least 60% men – 13.93%; All men team – 26.57%; One man – 40.93%
	Founders and leaders of innovative enterprises and start-ups by gender	Data of 2018 ³⁷⁵ : 28,9 % 71,1 % ■ Males ■ Females
Knowledge and tech production issues	Level of integration of gender as a scientific research dimension	In Table 7.19 of the Report of European Commission (2019) the total percentage of the country's publications with a sex or gender dimension in their research content for the period 2013 – 2017 is 0.54 %. (EU-28: 1.79%) In Table 7.20 the percentages by fields are given: natural sciences 0.21%, engineering & computing 0.09%, medical sciences 2.72%, agricultural science 0.34%, social sciences 1.05% and humanities & arts 1.94% ³⁷⁶ .
	Level of consideration of the gender dimension in product/service development	There are no such information available.
Broader issues featuring the R&I 'cultures	Gender sensitiveness/family friendliness of supporting services to start up and entrepreneurship	In Romania, at the moment, there is no national strategy for empowering women in entrepreneurship. Instead, in the last years there have been various programs and events dedicated to support women in business.
	Perception of existing stereotypes/bias on gender and innovation/ entrepreneurship	In Romania, the main barriers in creating a strong entrepreneurial cultural among women are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stereotypes and biases regarding women in STEM; - A traditional perspective about women's role in society and in family; - Poor work-life balance for women.

Table 13_Results of the context analysis conducted by UEFISCDI

³⁷⁴ European Commission. (2019). She Figures 2018. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9540ffa1-4478-11e9-a8ed-01aa75ed71a1>

European Commission. (2019). ERA Progress Report 2018 – country profile Romania. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/30043562-34c3-11e9-8d04-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

³⁷⁵ MasterCard Index of Women Entrepreneurs, 2018 https://newsroom.mastercard.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/MIWE_2018_Final_Report.pdf

³⁷⁶ European Commission. (2019). She Figures 2018. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9540ffa1-4478-11e9-a8ed-01aa75ed71a1>

4.10.3 UEFISCDI Mapping of external stakeholders and SNA

Results of the focus group with internal stakeholders

As far as the **focus group** is concerned the most relevant insights are reported below. The focus group was conducted online due to the covid-19 limitations. Four internal stakeholders participated, all females, among which 3 experts and 1 head of department.

The focus group opened with a discussion about the current **existing or prospective collaborations on broader areas** beside gender equality: participants reported that there are various existing partnerships mostly in the higher education area with national stakeholders. Moreover, there are existing partnerships with international organizations aimed at supporting and promoting research and innovation, science education, digitalization, sustainable and smart development, energy, climate, policy recommendations, intellectual property and social impact. UEFISCDI focuses on the development of a sustainability oriented organizational culture, which includes a variety of new topics for cooperation (i.e. promoting women in science, environmental protection, and actions with social impact). They collaborate with different kind of stakeholders, ranging from public administration institutions to research institutions, higher education institutions, SME, corporations, hubs and accelerators.

The group was then asked to focus on the ways in which gender inequalities represent a **challenge** for external stakeholders. They all agreed that the main issue is that in most of the organization's contexts gender inequalities are not considered or even not perceived as such, although in their opinion the problem is real, since there are various entirely male teams and there are only a few projects in which women hold management positions.

When it comes to the **benefits** of overcoming gender inequalities, participants agreed that dealing with the issue would bring positive outcomes, like developing better policies for encouraging women in different domains, reaching gender balance in terms of accessing and promotion procedures at higher educational and RDI levels, as well as increasing the overall quality of the work.

About the **actions** that external stakeholders put in place on gender equality, participants could not recall any particular measures, apart from assuring the presence of at least one woman in the management or implementation teams.

With reference to **complementarities and synergies** with their own institution and the impact for internal institutional change, focus group participants stated that given the low awareness about this topic, a first important step would be to organize actions aimed at raising the awareness. Moreover, a participant proposed to increase the attention on the topic of women empowerment in managerial positions, through the organization of management courses to help building managerial skills. These actions would be in line with the RFO's organisational culture, which lays on the concept of sustainability and social impact.

When it comes to **overlapping/competitive actions**, participants focused on possible activities, not strictly competitive with the external stakeholders. For instance, they propose that the private sector could organize a kind of "Leaders Academy", where participants could learn and acquire skills that are important in order to become a project coordinator/manager, and where women can be selected. Other possible activities identified were:

- Creating joint projects with gender balanced teams;
- Extra points in project evaluation for female / joint teams in areas / domains where the number of female researchers / experts is low;
- Extra financing for institutions with internal gender balance practices and policies;
- Organizing workshops and events to raise awareness at stakeholders' level.

Speaking about possible **risks** which could derive from collaboration, the participants stressed the possible misinterpretation of measures implemented by the organizations involved, due to different institutional cultures. Moreover, if the partner organisations do not have a clear vision towards sustainability, there is the risk of not having a real dialogue in the advancement of the collaboration.

Results of the survey to external stakeholders

The survey was submitted by 13 external stakeholders: 3 private companies, 4 associations/NGOs, 3 Universities and 3 public institutions, dealing with a variety of activities/business: European AAL Projects, ROP (Regional Operational Programme), social enterprise acceleration and incubation, promoting civic culture and social impact, science and innovation policies, research financing, philanthropy, marketing, Higher Education, research and innovation, political sciences and transport consultancy.

Concerning the **types of collaboration** such external stakeholders have in place with UEFISCDI, they are mainly related to partnerships or collaborations in EU and national projects. With a stakeholder, a collaboration about mentorship is in place.

The survey tackled the same topics addressed during the focus group with internal stakeholders.

External stakeholders were asked to explain how gender inequalities **challenge** their own organizations. Most of the stakeholders did not perceive gender equality challenges within their own organization, while other listed some of them. They mentioned the lack of commitment toward policies for female entrepreneurship, female access to employment and career progression, and toward the gender dimension of innovation. Also sensitive communication represents a challenge for some of them, as well as the low representation of females in forums, conferences, public debates in international relations, political studies, security studies, and the general low number of female researchers with respect to male ones.

With reference to the **potential benefits** of addressing such challenges, the NGOs pointed out the improved horizontal communication and awareness this would bring in their community; universities underlined the possible wider perspectives/approaches in research; the public institution highlighted the contribution of the improved policies on the regional development, while some of the respondent companies stated the quality of their work and the internal procedures might improve in terms of work life balance.

Most of the **actions and measures** undertaken from the external stakeholders to address gender inequalities are related to the gender balanced distribution of employees and their role and "power" in internal decisions. Besides this, one of the respondents reported about the project FEMINA - Female participation in high-tech enterprises – which aims at promoting female engagement in the high-tech sectors. In this context, the implemented or planned measures consisted in the alignment of the regional practices regarding gender equality – particularly in high-tech enterprises – in the Bucharest-Ilfov Region, to a benchmarked standard agreed by all project partners. This would foster the design of some concrete measures to be introduced in the area of governance/management or of structural change of the 2014-2020 Regional Operational Programme.

On the companies' side, one of them launched *StepFWD*, a pre-acceleration program for early-stage start-ups with diverse teams: a prerequisite to participate was to have at least one female among the founders.

Universities, instead, mentioned an annual conference (FANEL - F from female), at Central European Level, in which the panels' speakers are only women specialists in areas like international relations, security studies, etc. as well as a master's degree in minority and gender policies within the Faculty of Political Science.

The following questions explored which **form of cooperation** stakeholders envisage with UEFISCDI in order to overcome gender equality. Most of the stakeholders are open to collaborate with the RFO on the issue of gender equality. The actions proposed are various: collaboration in new projects concerning women in scientific areas, promotion of raising awareness campaigns on gender equality to avoid stereotypes or harassment - in attitude, in language, etc. In addition, UEFISCDI can play an important role in the design and implementation of the policy addressed by the FEMINA project.

Participants did not identify any **overlapping/competitive actions** with UEFISCDI.

Finally, **potential risks** of the cooperation were addressed. The risk of giving more attention to women rather than to valuable researchers (even when males) emerged, as well as the one of continuing a discourse on gender inequalities without taking into consideration UEFISCDI's specificities and power relations.

Results of the SNA

UEFISCDI is the national funding agency for scientific, research and innovation fields in Romania, therefore it has many interactions with various types of stakeholders. It also contains several departments, each of them having its own area of specialization. When UEFISCDI's researchers gathered information for the SNA, they involved people directly implicated in the projects: in particular, colleagues of the "Policies for Higher Education, Science, Innovation and Entrepreneurship Department" and of the Innovation Café (an UEFISCDI initiative that reunites the quadruple helix actors around a common subject debated during each edition of the event).

Overall **84 external stakeholders** were included in the mapping. The great majority of stakeholders belong to the "industry & business" sector (44 out of 84, representing the 53%), followed by "government & public sector" stakeholders (22, representing the 26%), "Academia & Universities" stakeholders (12, representing the 14%), "civil society" stakeholders (4, represents the 5%) and "others" (2, representing the 2%). As a RFO, many representatives of the industry sector participate in calls for programs and access funds necessary to develop their businesses. Moreover, UEFISCDI and, in particular, the "Policies for Higher Education, Science, Innovation and Entrepreneurship Department", focuses on the RDI and entrepreneurship policy support and development, thus most interactions occur with the business environment made by large, small and medium companies. Innovation Café is an initiative developed by the department in order to strengthen the relations between the business and research domains, to mediate networking and collaborations. The most relevant stakeholders involved in the RDI domain are national administrative authorities (the Romanian Ministry of Education and Research; the Regional Development Agency for Bucharest-Ilfov region), universities (Politechnica University of Bucharest; West University in Timisoara), research institutes ("Horia Hulubei" National Institute for R&D in Physics and Nuclear Engineering), professional associations (ANIS - Employers' Association of the Software and Services Industry in Romania; ARIES - Romanian Association for Electronic Industry and Software) and of course, large, medium and small companies (Siveco Grup, TechHub Bucharest, Impact Hub Bucharest, GapMinder, Bitdefender, etc).

Looking from a horizontal perspective, UEFISCDI has also strong relationships with entities from the government and public sector due to the nature of its activity, as part of the national administrative & governmental system. A few institutions from the academia and the civil society sectors interact with the mentioned department, however they have strong connections with other departments from UEFISCDI.

When analyzing the **intensity of collaborations**, most connections are "one time" connections (46 out of 83, representing 55,5%), 24 are of "frequent" and only 13 are "solid" collaborations. Most of the identified stakeholders ("one time" collaborations) take part in the Innovation Café events. "Frequent" and "solid" connections are the ones with those stakeholders with which UEFISCDI shares common projects or activities,

or collaborates on daily basis (such as the Ministry of Education and Research). In general, depending on the areas of expertise, “frequent and solid” relations are the ones with stakeholders that share the same “interests” as UEFISCDI and “one time” relations are with stakeholders that belong to an “unfamiliar” field of experience.

When taking into consideration the **geographical dimension**, many collaborations are with national entities (37 out of 83, representing the 44,5%) followed by local entities (31, representing 37,3%).

Concerning the **topic** of the collaborations, the most frequent topic is “scientific research” (24 out of 83, representing almost the 29%), while 19 collaborations concern “transfer to market”, 18 “science communication”, 15 “education” and 7 “raising awareness”.

Regarding **collaborations led by women**, it is worth to mention that UEFISCDI is an organization where the number of female employees is greater than the number of male employees. And although the General Director’s position is occupied by a man, the Deputy General Director is a woman. According to the analysis, about half of the projects are led by women (41 out of 84, representing the 49%). Of these 41 collaborations, 30 are related to STEM and medical sciences (the rest being collaborations on humanities, social sciences, etc.).

Till the CALIPER project, UEFISCDI was not involved in any project with a specific focus on gender. That is why only 2 collaborations (representing the 1%) **focus on gender issues**. Such collaborations are related to 2 stakeholders that implemented gender programs: ANIS and the Romanian Ministry of Research and Education.

The following pictures represent the results of the SNA conducted by UEFISCDI according to the kind of stakeholders. Therefore, 5 different maps are displayed, one for each category of stakeholders: “academia & university”, “industry & business”, “government & public sector”, “civil society” and “others”.

Per each map it is possible to identify the different departments of UEFISCDI involved in the collaborations with the different external stakeholders (the nodes with a small green circle), the collaborations having female leaderships (the yellow nodes) and the ones focusing and/or taking into account gender issues (red lines).

Figure 39_UEFISCDI collaborations with "Academy & Universities" stakeholders

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 40_UEFISCDI collaborations with "Industry & business" stakeholders

Figure 410_UEFISCDI collaborations with "Civil society" stakeholders

Figure 421_UEFISCDI collaborations with "Government & public sector" stakeholders

Figure 43_UEFISCDI collaborations with "others"

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

4.10.4 Final remarks on the external assessment of UEFISCDI

In Romania, **principles of equal rights and non-discrimination are included in the Romanian Constitution**. Other national provisions specifically tackle sex-based discrimination, equality of opportunities and treatment for women and men in the labour market, in accessing education, health care, culture and in decision-making, even though positive measures are not foreseen. Indeed, in 2006, the CEDAW Committee pointed out that in Romania there is low representation of women in public life and decision-making and provided with some recommendations which have only partially been implemented.

At the moment, also, **there is no functional mechanism at national level to promote underrepresented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research**.

Work-life balance is not a priority area for national policy makers, even if related measures and interventions are widely acknowledged as crucial for gender equality and women's empowerment. Romania has provisions of various types of leaves (i.e. maternity, paternity and parental leaves), but **a critical gap is the lack of adequate childcare services/facilities**. In general, the lack of incentives/measures must be understood within the broader socio-political context, which has seen an awakening of traditional gender roles.

About the integration of gender in scientific research, according to the ERA Progress Report 2018³⁷⁷, **Romania achieved its best score in the priority related to the inclusion of gender in research content** and data show that the share of male and female STEM researchers is quite similar. Indeed, the share of female researchers in 2015 (46.23%) was above the EU average (33.4%), showing that **gender division among researchers is rather equal in Romania**, therefore no major policy developments in this respect were observed. The evolution of the employment rate in the considered period (2015-2019) appears linear, while still a great unbalance is visible as concerns patent registration teams and founders of start-ups. This can be commented also considering that no national strategy for empowering women in entrepreneurship is in place at the moment.

About the analysis of the collaborations in place with UEFISCDI, various existing partnerships exist mostly in the higher education area with national stakeholders. They also collaborate with public administrations, research institutions, SMEs, companies. According to the results of both the focus group and the survey, most **external stakeholders do not perceive gender equality challenges within their own organisations**, even though they recognize benefits in overcoming gender inequalities. The actions already undertaken mainly concern the balanced gender distribution of employees and the implementation of specific projects.

About potential synergies with UEFISCDI, the organisation of actions aimed at raising the awareness was pointed out as well as the collaboration in new projects concerning women in scientific areas.

Concerning the SNA, 84 stakeholders were identified, the majority of them belonging to the "industry & business" sector, which is mainly represented by both large companies and SMEs. Regarding **collaborations led by women**, it is worth to mention that UEFISCDI is an organization where the number of female employees is greater than the number of male employees. According to the analysis, about half of the projects are led by women, while only 2 collaborations focus on gender issues.

³⁷⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/30043562-34c3-11e9-8d04-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

4.11 Concluding remarks on the CALIPER partners' external assessments

From the analysis of the assessments of all the partners some common traits and trends can be identified. In general, policies on gender equality exist in all countries, indeed, all national systems ensure to women and men the right to equal treatment, even though the level of development and concrete application of such policies is different. In some cases (BE, GR, ES, IT) there are specific provisions concerning the area of Higher Education and Scientific Research & Innovation, but still the level of advancement differs. In most cases, specific provisions are related to the inclusion of gender quotas in decision-making bodies of public administrations and therefore also of public Higher Education Institutions. Rare is the adoption of specific measures for the integration of the gender dimension in research (ES).

In all countries, measures for fostering the participation of women in the labor market have been adopted, like maternity, paternity and parental leaves, while childcare facilities seem to represent an issue almost everywhere (high need and low resources).

The data collected by partners in terms of STEM students, researchers, patent registrations, innovative start-up founders, etc. show a great predominance of males, only in a few cases the share between males and females is quite similar.

Partners analysed the collaborations in place in their own regional and national innovation ecosystems, mainly through a survey, an internal focus group and the SNA. Overall, and recalling the trends highlighted in chapters 2 and 3, all partners have a wide range of collaborations in place with a variety of stakeholders, mainly other education and research institutions, RFOs, companies, public institutions and less frequently civil society organizations of the (NGOs and associations). Only some of the stakeholders involved reported having implemented gender equality measures. However, the great majority expressed the willingness of fostering collaborations with the partners in this area and would be interested in taking part in specific project on gender equality, co-organize raising awareness initiatives and trainings or design/set up joint projects.

A component of the SNA implied tracking numbers of collaborations led by women as well as the numbers of those taking into account and/or focusing on gender issues. As partners followed different processes in order to collect relevant information, the purpose of the assessment was not to result in a comparative study. However, it is interesting to point out how on average the 42% of the collaborations identified by the partners are led by women in RPOs while the share of women-led collaborative actions for RFOs is obviously higher (about 54%), not surprisingly due to higher share of female representation in their workforce. For what concerns the collaborations taking into account or focusing in gender issues, for those partners who could track them, the average share was of 14%. To be noted how in certain cases (UNILE, NTUA, YASAR) horizontal/thematic segregation could be observed with women mostly in charge of collaborations with schools or civil society organizations (presumably less resourceful type of collaborations) and with men taking the lead in more 'prestigious' or directed connected to funding synergies.

The overall picture emerging from the assessments, points at a potentially fruitful environment for developing the CALIPER R&I Hubs. Still, risks were also highlighted by respondents in terms of aligning timelines and possible lack of resources. Taking this into account, it will be important that CALIPER partners promote gender equality externally, starting by selecting a few strategic alliances with those entities which are already active on the topic, and as emerging also from Chapters 2 and 3, keeping a close and strong connection between the desired internal change in a given area of intervention, and the synergies which will be leveraged with the respective innovation ecosystems.

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Whilborg, M. & Teelken, K. (2014). *Striving for Uniformity, Hoping for Innovation and Diversification: A Critical Review concerning the Bologna Process-Providing an Overview and Reflecting on the Criticism*, *Policy Futures in Education*, 12, 8, pp. 1084-1100.

Wullum, M. (2021). *Gender in academic recruitment and selection*, in Drew, E. and S. Canavan, *The Gender-Sensitive University; A Contradiction in Terms?* The Gender-Sensitive University. pp. 28-40, Abingdon, Oxon; New York, Routledge

5.2 Websites

<https://eit.europa.eu/who-we-are/eit-glance/eit-strategy-2021-2027>

<https://heinnovate.eu/en>

<https://www.eua.eu/resources/publications/927:the-impact-of-the-covid-19-crisis-on-university-funding-in-europe.html>

www.genderedinnovations.stanford.eu

www.digitalsocial.eu

Annex I: Semi-structured interview template

Introductory questions

- 1) Please tell us about [the action], what are its goals and actions, beneficiaries, how did it originate?
- 2) How was the choice of external stakeholders made, based on what rationale/criteria?
- 3) Which funding model was applied?
- 4) Could you please summarize the results of the action and the way they were monitored/evaluated?
- 5) Was an intersectional approach to gender equality taken into account? if yes how and if not why?

Positioning the action within an internal change process

- 6) Which were the leading and participating departments/Units/offices at your institutions? did the university integrate this project into its own GEP or into an internal institutional change process? How?
- 7) Did the need for it originate from an initial internal assessment?
- 8) Was the action designed and planned collaboratively with the external stakeholders (or some of them) or did other stakeholders join at a later stage once your institution set the main features of the action?
- 9) What is/was the impact of this project on the internal change process of the university?
- 10) Did [the action] result in higher engagement towards GE from top management and/or from specific internal stakeholders at your institution?
- 11) Did it meet any particular resistances or face any criticisms? if yes, could you please elaborate on those?
- 12) Did this practice lead to diminished efforts towards internal change mechanisms?
- 13) What are the main difficulties which the university has encountered in the process? What strategies/actions were implemented to overcome them?
- 14) Based on your experience in this practice, do you think linking institutional change for gender equality in Research Organisations can benefit from synergies and collaborative actions at the ecosystems level? Under what conditions and with what limitations?

Features and added value of the multistakeholder collaboration

- 15) Which were the added values of a multi stakeholder collaboration?
- 16) Which were the roles and contributions of the different engaged organisations?
- 17) Why and how did they find such a collaborative action interesting and relevant?
- 18) Which departments/units offices were committed and participated in the action/practice?
- 19) Were any women/feminist organisations or organisations active on gender issues included in the action? If yes, with what role and if no, why?
- 20) Overall, was the multistakeholder team balanced from a gender perspective?
- 21) Did any tensions or conflicts or major misalignments emerge during the collaboration?
- 22) As far as you know, did the action/practice trigger any internal changes on gender equality or did it originate any further activities on these issues at any of the collaborating stakeholders?
- 23) Are you aware of any interesting/promising/good practice on the same line?
- 24) Any final considerations /notes from your side?

Annex II: Focus group template

Section 1 - Involving actors from external innovation ecosystem in actions related to the design and/or implementation of the GEP: potential benefits

1st round table (10 minutes)

- Could you share your experience on if and how promoting collaboration and synergies between implementing RPOs/RFOs and external stakeholders in their respective innovation ecosystems can be beneficial when working on institutional change for gender equality? Why? Please refer to concrete examples whenever possible.
- (If yes) **at which stage** of the change process the involvement of external actors can be more relevant/useful? (diagnostic phase/GEP design phase/ implementation/evaluation and monitoring)

Change process stage	Please prioritize 2 options	Comments
Assessment/diagnostic		
GEP design		
Implementation		
Evaluation and monitoring		

- **Which internal staff categories** could be more interested/ready to cooperate with external stakeholders (scientists/academics/ administrative/middle-high management)? Please comment also on which staff categories could be more resistant/problematic to involve.

Internal staff categories	Please prioritize 2 options	Comments
Scientists/academics		
Administrative staff		
HR staff		
Middle-high management		

2nd round table (15 minutes)

- Looking more closely at the 3 main priorities for gender equality in research:
 - promoting female scientific careers in STEM
 - fostering gender balance in decision making in research organisations
 - integrating a gender perspective in the content of scientific research
- Which collaborative actions with external stakeholders can positively impact on internal institutional change? and with what type of stakeholders?

GE priorities	Type of collaborative actions	Type of stakeholders (business, academia, public sector, civil society i.e. also feminist organisations)
Promoting female scientific careers in STEM		
Gender balance in decision making		
Gender in scientific research content		

- What role women/feminist organisations or organisations active on gender issues can play? Are they easily engaged? If not, why?
- How can an intersectional approach be relevant to this respect?

Section 2: Possible shortcomings, obstacles, unexpected effects, resistances, other concerns**3rd round table** (10 minutes)

- What **internal obstacles and/or resistances** at the RPOs/RFOs level could such an approach generate?
- What **other** shortcomings or unexpected effects could such an approach generate? Could they end up hindering the process of institutional change for gender equality?

Annex III: Survey template

1) Are you currently holding a grant? *

- *Yes, an ERC grant (go to question 2)*
- *Yes, another grant (go to question 3)*
- *No*

2) If you are holding an ERC grant, what type of grant are you currently holding?

- *Starting grant*
- *Consolidator grant*
- *Advanced grant*
- *Proof of concept grant*
- *Synergy grant*

3) If you are holding a different grant, what type of grant are you currently holding?

4) Which is the field/discipline of your research?*

- *Science*
- *Technology*
- *Engineering*
- *Mathematics*
- *Medicine*
- *environment*
- *humanities and creative arts*
- *economics*
- *education*
- *other - please specify*

5a) Is your research project connected to social innovation?*

- *Yes*
- *No*

5b) If yes, please shortly explain how:

6a) Does your project take gender into consideration as a dimension of scientific research?*

- *Yes*
- *No*

6b) If yes: did you take and/or are taking gender in consideration in one or more of the following steps of the research cycle? (choose all options that apply)

- *project ideation*
- *research design/ formulation of your research questions*
- *research methodologies*
- *data collection process*
- *interpretation and analysis of research results*
- *communication of scientific research results*

7a) Does your research project foresee any engagement of stakeholders other than your University/research center?*

- Yes
- No

7b) If yes, please select the kind of stakeholder engaged (choose all that apply):

- other universities/research organisations
- industry & business
- government & public sector
- civil society

7c) if yes: what roles these stakeholders play? (please choose all options that apply)

	<i>informants</i>	<i>testers or testbed providers</i>	<i>co-owners/partners/</i>	<i>dissemination/exploitation of research results</i>	<i>funders/co-funders</i>	<i>other (please specify)</i>
<i>Other universities/research organisations</i>						
<i>Industry & business</i>						
<i>Government & Public sector</i>						
<i>Civil society</i>						

7d) Is the involvement of any of the above mentioned stakeholders related to the gender equality dimension?

- Yes
- No

7e) if yes, please specify how:

8a) Does your project include any exploitation of scientific research results activities or their transfer to market?*

- Yes
- No

8b) If yes, which kind of exploitation plan or activity is envisaged?

- patenting
- creation of spin-outs
- set up of startup businesses

- transfer of research results to third parties through licences
- other - please specify:

8c) If yes, is it gender equality taken into account in any of the above mentioned components?

- Yes
- No

8d) If yes to 8c), please specify why and how:

9a) Is any scientific communication/science education/third mission activity planned as part of the research project or in connection to it? *

- Yes
- No

9b) if yes to 9a) please briefly explain how:

9c) If yes, is it gender equality taken into account in any of such activities?

- Yes
- No

9d) if yes, please shortly describe how:

10a) Are, in your opinion, any of the above-mentioned types of activities linking scientific research and innovation (potentially) affected by gender inequalities? (see questions 8 and 9) *

- Yes
- Partly
- No

10b) If you chose "yes" or "partly", please explain how and why:

10 c) if you chose "yes" or "partly", are there any possible ways your project could contribute to tackle them or mitigate inequality effects?

11a) Can you name any STEM research projects you are aware of, which also incorporate social innovation and/or having a transfer to market component, which take gender into account? *

- Yes
- No

11b) If yes, please provide us with a few information about the project(s), including title, webpage, and contacts

12) We are going to select a few respondents for further online semi-structured interviewing. In case you would be available, please provide us with an e-mail address, you may be contacted again:

Annex IV: Infographics of the results of the survey

Figure X: infographics summarising the results of the short survey for YAE researchers

[Back to the Ch.3 methodology](#)

Annex V: External assessment reporting template

Linking Research & Innovation for
Gender Equality

External assessment report

RPOs/RFOs

Reporting file

Partner: x

Document information

Grant Agreement Number	873134	Acronym	CALIPER
Full Title	The CALIPER project: Linking research and innovation for gender equality		
Topic	Swafs-09-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting research organisations to implement gender equality plans		
Funding scheme	CSA – Coordination and Support Action		
Start Date	1 st January 2020	Duration	48 months
Project URL	http://caliper-project.eu/		
Work Package	WP1 – Analysis of external and internal conditions for GEPs development and acceptance		
Beneficiary			

Document History

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1.00		Final		

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Reporting instructions

CALIPER RPOs/RFOs will follow the methodology described in D1.1 (*Internal and external assessment methodology and guidelines*) to carry out both the internal and external assessment.

This document will be used by RPOs/RFOs to report the qualitative and quantitative data they collect from the **external assessment**.

The external assessment includes the following two fields:

- National legal and policy frameworks
- National and regional Innovation ecosystems

This document provides RPOs/RFOs with the templates that you will be needed during the external assessment and the place to report the outcomes.

All RPOs/RFOs will save the files at Teamwork (folder Reporting/your organisation/internal assessment).

The reporting period starts from the date you receive D1.1 and this report and ends on 15 June 2020. RPOs and RFOs should complete the history table when producing different versions of the current file.

For the implementation of the external assessment, partners will need to involve/consult at least 12 stakeholders each.

Linked Objective/Impact	Description	WP	Deliverables	Duration	Measurement type	Target
Objective 1	Stakeholders reached for the implementation of the external assessment	1	D1.3	M1-M8	#of stakeholders	100

Table 1: KPIs set at page 128 of the GA

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Contents

1	National legal and policy frameworks	5
1.1	Data profile - Desk research/policy analysis.....	5
1.2	Interviews notes – Template	5
1.3	Data profile - Relevant stakeholder interviews.....	6
1.4	Data reporting	7
2	National and regional Innovation ecosystems	10
2.1	Data profile - Desktop research.....	10
2.2	Data reporting - Desktop research	10
2.3	Focus group reporting	12
2.4	External stakeholders mapping survey	13
2.5	External stakeholders mapping report.....	14
	ANNEX I Focus groups minutes	14
	ANNEX II Semi structural interviews notes	14

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1 National legal and policy frameworks

Instructions at D1.1 - Chapter 3.2 The National legal and policy frameworks, pages 59.

1.1 Data profile - Desk research/policy analysis

List the references (APA style preferred)

1.2 Interviews notes – Template

You may use this table structure to keep notes during the interviews. Copy this table to complete information for every interview. **Advise:** gather all the interview notes at Annex II of the current document.

National legal and policy frameworks interviews notes	
Place, date and time	
Participant (male/female)	
Notes	
<p>Overall strategic gender equality policies in place at national level</p> <p><i>The overall strategic orientation of gender equality policies in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation including the legal basis/acts relevant to the field of gender equality is an important context-related indicator to assess the awareness/commitment to gender equality at the national level. It is aimed at exploring if universities/research organizations are obliged by law to work towards gender balance and/or to implement a GE plan. The indicator also includes an understanding of how the frameworks define the relationship between gender equality and quality/excellence in research and/or in education.</i></p>	
<p>Existence of specific mechanisms to promote the under- represented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation at national or regional level</p>	
<p>Existence of national policies on implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees.</p>	
<p>Existence of national legislation promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment</p>	
<p>Existing policies at national level for reducing unequal gender division of labour related to housework and family care</p> <p><i>The indicator aims at identifying and describing measures such as parental leave (paid/non paid, transferable, eligibility criteria, flexibility, etc.) and other measures aimed at reducing unequal gender division of labour.</i></p>	
<p>Existing framework conditions regarding childcare facilities</p> <p><i>Availability and quality of formal childcare offer in the country and the city where RPO/RFO is located (potential source: data on the Barcelona Objectives by country)</i></p>	

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Employment conditions at university and research organization

It aims at exploring which are the employment conditions in each country with regard to university and research organizations more generally. In particular, it refers to the share of precarious contracts on the overall amount of employment positions, as well the grade of rigidity or flexibility of scientific career schemes which play an important role in the female career advancement. It refers to the level of mobility both between institutions and sectors, fixed or non-fixed number of years to access the following stage, but also to the existence of flexible criteria for career progression which take into consideration major life events like childbirth, care work for relatives or continuing education as well as individual performance.

Existence of national programmes which promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research

When this happens measures usually combine training programmes and funding incentives (gender as a criterion embedded in evaluation processes to access grants and resources)

National/ policies and legal frameworks on sexual/gender harassment in the workplace

We are interested to know whether there is legislation in place requiring that employers take action and set up measures to prevent and/or contrast sexual harassment or other forms of diversity related harassment

Funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality at national and regional level

Specific Indicators can be the level of integration of gender in ERDF Work Programmes at the national and regional levels, or other national programmes where gender in scientific research is promoted and funded

1.3 Data profile - Relevant stakeholder interviews

Relevant stakeholder interviews (complementary in case the desk research does not produce enough information)

If any

Total number of interviews	
Number of stakeholders (Please specify the category)	
Number of stakeholders (Please specify the category)	
Number of stakeholders (Please specify the category)	
Number of males	
Number of females	
Number of females/males who preferred not to say	

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1.4 Data reporting

RPOs/RFOs should describe the external assessment result for each indicator according to the different tool(s) used for the internal assessment (desk research, interview).

Overall strategic gender equality policies in place at national level	Tool
<i>The overall strategic orientation of gender equality policies in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation including the legal basis/acts relevant to the field of gender equality is an important context-related indicator to assess the awareness/commitment to gender equality at the national level. It is aimed at exploring if universities/research organizations are obliged by law to work towards gender balance and/or to implement a GE plan. The indicator also includes an understanding of how the frameworks define the relationship between gender equality and quality/excellence in research and/or in education.</i>	
	Desk research
	Interview (if any complementary)

Existence of specific mechanisms to promote the under- represented gender in Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation at national or regional level	Tool
	Desk research
	Interview (if any complementary)

Existence of national policies on implementation of quotas or targets for promoting the underrepresented gender in management positions and committees.	Tool
	Desk research
	Interview (if any complementary)

Existence of national legislation promoting equality and non-discrimination in employment	Tool
	Desk research

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	Interview (if any complementary)

Existing policies at national level for reducing unequal gender division of labour related to housework and family care Tool	
<i>The indicator aims at identifying and describing measures such as parental leave (paid/non paid, transferable, eligibility criteria, flexibility, etc.) and other measures aimed at reducing unequal gender division of labour.</i>	
	Desk research
	Interview (if any complementary)

Existing framework conditions regarding childcare facilities Tool	
<i>Availability and quality of formal childcare offer in the country and the city where RPO/RFO is located (potential source: data on the Barcelona Objectives by country)</i>	
	Desk research
	Interview (if any complementary)

Employment conditions at university and research organization Tool	
<i>It aims at exploring which are the employment conditions in each country with regard to university and research organizations more generally. In particular, it refers to the share of precarious contracts on the overall amount of employment positions, as well the grade of rigidity or flexibility of scientific career schemes which play an important role in the female career advancement. It refers to the level of mobility both between institutions and sectors, fixed or non-fixed number of years to access the following stage, but also to the existence of flexible criteria for career progression which take into consideration major life events like childbirth, care work for relatives or continuing education as well as individual performance.</i>	
	Desk research
	Interview (if any complementary)

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Existence of national programmes which promote the integration of gender in the content of scientific research Tool	
<i>When this happens measures usually combine training programmes and funding incentives (gender as a criterion embedded in evaluation processes to access grants and resources)</i>	
	Desk research
	Interview (if any complementary)

National/ policies and legal frameworks on sexual/gender harassment in the workplace Tool	
<i>We are interested to know whether there is legislation in place requiring that employers take action and set up measures to prevent and/or contrast sexual harassment or other forms of diversity related harassment</i>	
	Desk research
	Interview (if any complementary)

Funding opportunities for collaborative actions on gender equality at national and regional level Tool	
<i>Specific Indicators can be the level of integration of gender in ERDF Work Programmes at the national and regional levels, or other national programmes where gender in scientific research is promoted and funded</i>	
	Desk research
	Interview (if any complementary)

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2 National and regional Innovation ecosystems

2.1 Data profile - Desk research

Instructions at D1.1 - Chapter 3.3 National and Regional Innovation Ecosystems.

List here the references (APA style preferred)

2.2 Data reporting - Desk research

Instructions at D1.1 - Chapter 3.3 National and Regional Innovation Ecosystems, pages 65.

Complete the table below lists the relevant indicators for the context analysis more in detail, highlighting potential sources of information (consider that a primary source potentially valid for all RPOs/RFOs are the ERA country reports).

Area	Indicator	Further description	Result	Potential sources
Talents and workforce education and acquisition	High School and Higher Education students in STEM by gender, at regional and national levels	Low rates of enrolled students in STEM at universities often originate from gender differences in study choices at an earlier stage.	#males: #females:	Reports on national or regional education systems at policies
	Researchers in STEM by gender in R&I, at national and regional levels	The lack of women among STEM researchers is an issue both for public research and for companies investing in R&D (data are most likely available on public research only)	#males: #females:	Regional/ national statistics and studies on R&I
	Evolution of employment rate in R&I by gender	This points at employment trends in R&I in absolute terms and by gender, in the last 5 years (flexible time span)	#males: #females:	Regional/national statistics and reports on employment, or on R&I
Leadership	Patents registrations by gender	It would be more meaningful if applied to the last 3-5 years	# of patents:	Existing studies/reports on R&I and/or Patenting bodies/institutions

Broader issues featuring the R&I ‘cultures: Gender sensitiveness/family Tool friendliness of supporting services to start up and entrepreneurship

Services to start up and businesses tend to not consider gender (and other) inequalities in their service offer and this translates into offers suitable for young or middle aged white men.

Broader issues featuring the R&I ‘cultures: Perception of existing Tool stereotypes/bias on gender and innovation/ entrepreneurship

Institutional communication from players in the ecosystems and media representation reproduce gender stereotypes.

2.3 Focus group reporting

Instructions at D1.1 - Chapter 3.3 National and Regional Innovation Ecosystems, pages 68-69.

RPOs/RFOs may use the table below to describe the minutes of each focus group. Copy this table to complete information for every focus group. **Advise:** gather all the interview notes at Annex I of the current document.

Focus groups minutes	
Place	
Date and time	
Number of stakeholders	(Please specify the category)
Number of stakeholders)	(Please specify the category)
Number of stakeholders	(Please specify the category)
Number of males	
Number of females	
Minutes	

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- What is the current existing or prospective collaboration on broader areas/issues with the stakeholder (beside gender equality)?
- In what ways gender inequalities seem to represent a challenge for them? How, up to your knowledge, these challenges appear to be perceived and what potential benefits would come from solving them?
- What actions did they put in place on the matter or do they intend envisage to? If any, are there colleagues of yours who are in contact with them?
- What complementarities or synergies can be envisaged with your institution? What would be the impact and benefit for internal institutional change at our RPO/RFOs?
- What overlapping /competitive actions could be envisaged?
- What risks could derive from collaboration?

2.4 External stakeholders mapping survey

Instructions at D1.1 - Chapter 3.3 National and Regional Innovation Ecosystems, page 68-69. Partners are asked to submit a survey to at least 12 – 15 stakeholders.

The survey is anonymous and includes both closed and open-ended questions. More Instructions at D1.1 - Chapter 2.3.1.4 Survey, page 55.

The template for the Google Form of the survey is here: **Please copy this template to your personal folder to edit it – Do not edit this file, it is common for all partners. To do it, click on the three dots on the top right of the screen and then, make a copy.**

If needed, you may translate the fields on the online copy file you create.

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1WfLilpVuuZKbWa21Qv5bym4P3k2um1XR9aPbNydkw4I/edit?usp=sharing>

For the survey results, you may upload the excel file it generates at Teamwork (folder Reporting/your organisation/internal assessment).

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2.5 External stakeholders mapping report

Instructions at D1.1 - Chapter 3.3 National and Regional Innovation Ecosystems, page 68-69.

The excel file that you should fill in is the *Mapping of external stakeholders_SNA.xls*. It is a file within the same folder in the Teamwork folder.

ANNEX I Focus groups minutes

Here you may keep concentrated the minutes kept during the focus groups.

ANNEX II Semi structural interviews notes

Here you may keep concentrated the notes kept during the interviews.

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Annex VI: ULB's survey's questions

Questions for stakeholders belonging to the "Academia & university" sector

- Name of the institution/organization/company
- Type of organization (e.g. university, national or regional authority, business company, NGO, etc.)
- Main activities of your organization

Gender equality in the organization

- What is the proportion of boys and girls who take the in-depth science/mathematics courses in the third level? (e.g. M 50% - W 50%)
- Are there any actions/measures in your organization to promote gender equality in the choice of studies? Yes/No

Existing actions/measures

- What kind of actions/measures are already in place to tackle gender inequalities? (e.g. in internal or external communication, awareness-raising actions, equal pay, introduction of quotas, measures to promote the work-life balance, career promotion, training to avoid gender bias in teaching, ...)
- What are the problems/risks encountered when implementing such actions in your organization or in the schools you work with? (e.g. lack of resources, lack of awareness of the issue, lack of diagnosis of the issue, lack of training on the problem, reluctance within the organisation, ...)
- What were the benefits of implementing such actions in your organization or in the schools you work with? (e.g. improved well-being at work, performance, corporate image, commitment to social justice, ...)

Actions/measures to be implemented

- If no actions/measures are currently in place to tackle gender inequalities, is your organization considering taking such measures? Yes/no
- [If yes] Which ones? (e.g. in internal or external communication, awareness-raising actions, equal pay, introduction of quotas, measures to promote the work-life balance, career promotion, training to avoid gender bias in teaching, ...)
- What are the possible problems/risks related to the implementation of such actions in your organization or in the schools you work with? (e.g. lack of resources, lack of awareness of the issue, lack of diagnosis of the issue, lack of training on the problem, reluctance within the organisation, ...)
- What are the potential benefits of tackling gender inequalities in your organization or in the schools you work with? (e.g. improved well-being at work, performance, corporate image, commitment to social justice, ...)
- [If not] Why not? What would be the possible problems/risks related to the implementation of such actions in your organization or in the schools you work with?

Collaboration with the Université Libre de Bruxelles

- Is there already some collaborations between your organization and the Université libre de Bruxelles? Yes/No
- [If yes] What kind of collaborations already exist? (e.g. research project, career promotion, pedagogical project, dissemination of science, ..)
- Do these partnerships include actions in the area of gender policies/quality? Yes/no
- [If yes] Which ones?
- Would a collaboration with the Université Libre de Bruxelles to promote gender equality in STEM be of interest for your organization? Yes/no
- [If yes] What joint actions could be envisaged? (e.g. recruitment process, information on job vacancies, joint awareness campaigns, ...)
- As part of the CALIPER Project, ULB will set up a "Research & Innovation Hub", a pole made up of representatives of ULB's national, regional and local innovation ecosystem, including business, research, government and civil society actors. Through their participation in the hub, these actors will feed into the process of elaborating the Gender Equality Plan in the ULB STEM. The 'R&I Hub' will act at the same time as a

target and multiplier of the project communication. Does your organization wish to participate in the Research and Innovation Hub? Yes/no

- [If not] Why not? What are the possible problems/risks for your organization in setting up such a collaboration?
- Contact person in your organization (mail/phone) for the R&I Hub.

Questions for stakeholders belonging to the “Industry & business” sector

- Name of the institution/organization/company
- Type of organization (e.g. university, national or regional authority, business company, NGO, etc.)
- Main activities of your organization

Gender equality in the organization

- What is the proportion of men and women in your organization? (e.g. M 50% - W 50%)
- What is the proportion of men and women in leadership positions in your organization? (e.g. M 50% - W 50%)
- Are there any actions/measures in your organization to promote gender equality? Yes/No
- Existing actions/measures
- What kind of actions/measures are already in place to tackle gender inequalities? (e.g. in internal or external communication, awareness-raising actions, equal pay, introduction of quotas, measures to promote the work-life balance, career promotion, training to avoid gender bias in teaching, ...)
- What are the problems/risks encountered when implementing such actions in your organization? (e.g. lack of resources, lack of awareness of the issue, lack of diagnosis of the issue, lack of training on the problem, reluctance within the organisation, ...)
- What were the benefits of implementing such actions in your organization? (e.g. improved well-being at work, performance, corporate image, commitment to social justice, ...)

Actions/measures to be implemented

- If no actions/measures are currently in place to tackle gender inequalities, is your organization considering taking such measures? Yes/no
- [If yes] Which ones? (e.g. in internal or external communication, awareness-raising actions, equal pay, introduction of quotas, measures to promote the work-life balance, career promotion, training to avoid gender bias in teaching, ...)
- What are the possible problems/risks related to the implementation of such actions in your organization? (e.g. lack of resources, lack of awareness of the issue, lack of diagnosis of the issue, lack of training on the problem, reluctance within the organisation, ...)
- What are the potential benefits of tackling gender inequalities in your organization? (e.g. improved well-being at work, performance, corporate image, commitment to social justice, ...)
- [If not] Why not? What would be the possible problems/risks related to the implementation of such actions in your organization?

Collaboration with the Université Libre de Bruxelles

- Is there already some collaborations between your organization and the Université libre de Bruxelles? Yes/No
- [If yes] What kind of collaborations already exist? (e.g. research project, career promotion, pedagogical project, dissemination of science, ...)
- Do these partnerships include actions in the area of gender policies/quality? Yes/no
- [If yes] Which ones?
- Would a collaboration with the Université Libre de Bruxelles to promote gender equality in STEM be of interest for your organization? Yes/no
- [If yes] What joint actions could be envisaged? (e.g. recruitment process, information on job vacancies, joint awareness campaigns, ...)

- As part of the CALIPER Project, ULB will set up a "Research & Innovation Hub", a pole made up of representatives of ULB's national, regional and local innovation ecosystem, including business, research, government and civil society actors. Through their participation in the hub, these actors will feed into the process of elaborating the Gender Equality Plan in the ULB STEM. The 'R&I Hub' will act at the same time as a target and multiplier of the project communication. Does your organization wish to participate in the Research and Innovation Hub? Yes/no
- [If not] Why not? What are the possible problems/risks for your organization in setting up such a collaboration?
- Contact person in your organization (mail/phone) for the R&I Hub.

Questions for stakeholders belonging to the "Government & public sector" and, in particular, to Research funding institutions

- Name of the institution/organization/company
- Type of organization (e.g. university, national or regional authority, business company, NGO, etc.)
- Main activities of your organization

Gender equality in the organization

- What is the proportion of men and women whose project and/or salary is funded by your organization ? (e.g. M 50% - W 50%)
- What is the proportion of men and women in leadership positions whose project and/or salary is funded by your organization? (e.g. M 50% - W 50%)
- Are there any actions/measures in your organization to promote gender equality in research funding? Yes/No

Existing actions/measures

- What kind of actions/measures are already in place to tackle gender inequalities in research funding? (e.g. in internal or external communication, awareness-raising actions, equal pay, introduction of quotas, measures to promote the work-life balance, career promotion, training to avoid gender bias in teaching, ...)
- What are the problems/risks encountered when implementing such actions in your organization? (e.g. lack of resources, lack of awareness of the issue, lack of diagnosis of the issue, lack of training on the problem, reluctance within the organisation, ...)
- What were the benefits of implementing such actions in your organization? (e.g. improved well-being at work, performance, corporate image, commitment to social justice, ...)

Actions/measures to be implemented

- If no actions/measures are currently in place to tackle gender inequalities, is your organization considering taking such measures? Yes/no
- [If yes] Which ones? (e.g. in internal or external communication, awareness-raising actions, equal pay, introduction of quotas, measures to promote the work-life balance, career promotion, training to avoid gender bias in teaching, ...)
- What are the possible problems/risks related to the implementation of such actions in your organization? (e.g. lack of resources, lack of awareness of the issue, lack of diagnosis of the issue, lack of training on the problem, reluctance within the organisation, ...)
- What are the potential benefits of tackling gender inequalities in your organization? (e.g. improved well-being at work, performance, corporate image, commitment to social justice, ...)
- [If not] Why not? What would be the possible problems/risks related to the implementation of such actions in your organization?

Collaboration with the Université Libre de Bruxelles

- Is there already some collaborations between your organization and the Université libre de Bruxelles? Yes/No
- [If yes] What kind of collaborations already exist? (e.g. research project, career promotion, pedagogical project, dissemination of science, ..)
- Do these partnerships include actions in the area of gender policies/quality? Yes/no

- [If yes] Which ones?
- Would a collaboration with the Université Libre de Bruxelles to promote gender equality in STEM be of interest for your organization? Yes/no
- [If yes] What joint actions could be envisaged? (e.g. recruitment process, information on job vacancies, joint awareness campaigns, ...)
- As part of the CALIPER Project, ULB will set up a "Research & Innovation Hub", a pole made up of representatives of ULB's national, regional and local innovation ecosystem, including business, research, government and civil society actors. Through their participation in the hub, these actors will feed into the process of elaborating the Gender Equality Plan in the ULB STEM. The 'R&I Hub' will act at the same time as a target and multiplier of the project communication. Does your organization wish to participate in the Research and Innovation Hub? Yes/no
- [If not] Why not? What are the possible problems/risks for your organization in setting up such a collaboration?
- Contact person in your organization (mail/phone) for the R&I Hub.

Questions for stakeholders belonging to the “civil society” sector and, in particular, to Women’s and professional associations

- Name of the institution/organization/company
- Type of organization (e.g. university, national or regional authority, business company, NGO, etc.)
- Main activities of your organization

Gender equality in the organization

- What is the proportion of men and women in organizations/companies you work with? (e.g. M 50% - W 50%)
- What is the proportion of men and women in leadership positions employed in organizations/companies you work with? (e.g. M 50% - W 50%)
- Are there any actions/measures to promote gender equality in organizations/companies you work with? Yes/No

Existing actions/measures

- What kind of actions/measures are already in place to tackle gender inequalities ? (e.g. in internal or external communication, awareness-raising actions, equal pay, introduction of quotas, measures to promote the work-life balance, career promotion, training to avoid gender bias in teaching, ...)
- What are the problems/risks encountered when implementing such actions in organizations/companies you work with? (e.g. lack of resources, lack of awareness of the issue, lack of diagnosis of the issue, lack of training on the problem, reluctance within the organisation, ...)
- What were the benefits of implementing such actions in organizations/companies you work with? (e.g. improved well-being at work, performance, corporate image, commitment to social justice, ...)

Actions/measures to be implemented

- If no actions/measures are currently in place to tackle gender inequalities, is your organization considering taking such measures? Yes/no
- [If yes] Which ones ? (e.g. in internal or external communication, awareness-raising actions, equal pay, introduction of quotas, measures to promote the work-life balance, career promotion, training to avoid gender bias in teaching, ...)
- What are the possible problems/risks related to the implementation of such actions in organizations/companies you work with? (e.g. lack of resources, lack of awareness of the issue, lack of diagnosis of the issue, lack of training on the problem, reluctance within the organisation, ...)
- What are the potential benefits of tackling gender inequalities in organizations/companies you work with? (e.g. improved well-being at work, performance, corporate image, commitment to social justice, ...)
- [If not] Why not? What would be the possible problems/risks related to the implementation of such actions in organizations/companies you work with?

Collaboration with the Université Libre de Bruxelles

- Is there already some collaborations between your organization and the Université libre de Bruxelles? Yes/No
- [If yes] What kind of collaborations already exist? (e.g. research project, career promotion, pedagogical project, dissemination of science, ...)
- Do these partnerships include actions in the area of gender policies/quality? Yes/no
- [If yes] Which ones?
- Would a collaboration with the Université Libre de Bruxelles to promote gender equality in STEM be of interest for your organization? Yes/no
- [If yes] What joint actions could be envisaged ? (e.g. recruitment process, information on job vacancies, joint awareness campaigns, ...)
- As part of the CALIPER Project, ULB will set up a "Research & Innovation Hub", a pole made up of representatives of ULB's national, regional and local innovation ecosystem, including business, research, government and civil society actors. Through their participation in the hub, these actors will feed into the process of elaborating the Gender Equality Plan in the ULB STEM. The 'R&I Hub' will act at the same time as a target and multiplier of the project communication. Does your organization wish to participate in the Research and Innovation Hub? Yes/no
- [If not] Why not? What are the possible problems/risks for your organization in setting up such a collaboration?
- Contact person in your organization (mail/phone) for the R&I Hub.
- Thank you for your participation in this survey.

